

European long-term ecosystem, critical zone and socio-ecological systems research infrastructure PLUS

High resolution biodiversity data to assess environmental change

Deliverable D8.1

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Table of Contents

Executive Summary	7
Abbreviations	9
Work packages designation	9
1. Introduction	10
1.1 eLTER PLUS	10
1.2 Aim of the document	11
2. Methodology	13
2.1. High resolution biodiversity data to assess environmental change	13
2.1.1. Baixo-Sabor (PT)	14
2.1.2. Doñana (SP)	16
2.1.3. Moor House (UK)	17
2.2. Identification of suitable datasets to integrate biodiversity analysis in WAILS	21
3. Results and Discussion	22
3.1. High resolution biodiversity data to assess environmental change	22
3.1.1. Baixo-Sabor (PT)	22
3.1.2. Doñana (SP)	24
3.1.3. Moor House (UK)	29
3.2. Identification of suitable datasets to integrate biodiversity analysis in WAILS	31
3.3. Technical considerations from data legacy and practical recommendations to eLTER managers and site owners	31
4. Acknowledgements	34
5. References	34
6. Appendices	38
6.1. Appendix A	38
6.2. Appendix B	54
6.3. Appendix C	134
6.4. Appendix D	168
6.5. Appendix E	184
6.6. Appendix F	191

List of Figures

Figure 1 - The core concept of eLTER PLUS. (Source: https://elter-ri.eu/elter-plus)	10
Figure 2 - Structure of deliverable D8.1. The site-based research on biodiversity change according to three scientific cases selected (Baixo-Sabor, Doñana and Moor House), including a workflow of data analysis for the scientific case of Moor House as a direct contribution to WP10.	11
Figure 3 - Location of the eLTER Site of Sabor (Portugal). Source: DEIMS-SDR.....	15
Figure 4 - Location of the eLTER Site of Doñana (Spain). Source: DEIMS-SDR	17
Figure 5 - Location of the eLTER Site of Moor House (United Kingdom). Source: DEIMS-SDR	18
Figure 6 - Workflow of data analysis for the case study ‘Biodiversity trend analysis at the site scale - Moor House UK’	19
Figure 7 - Model predicted probabilities (interaction term BA:FLOODED_AREA) of the breeding occurrence and productivity of Golden eagles (left) and Egyptian vultures (right) in relation to sampling period (Before in red; After in blue) and proportion of flooded area around breeding territory (FLOODED_AREA). Shaded zones represent variation around the mean (i.e. 95% confidence intervals).	23
Figure 8 - Temporal trends (1984-2020) of waterbird diversity (number of species per functional group), including predictions for 2040 according to the future scenarios considered (i.e. ‘Regular hydrological year’ and ‘Dry hydrological year’).	25
Figure 9 - Temporal trends (1984-2020) of waterbird abundance (number of individuals per functional group), including predictions for 2040 according to the future scenarios considered (i.e. ‘Regular hydrological year’ and ‘Dry hydrological year’).	26
Figure 10 - Location of the 24 plots used for waterbirds analysis on the Doñana eLTER Site, discriminated by sectors based on principal habitat-types.....	27
Figure 11 - Spatial projections of seasonal variation in Dabbling ducks diversity (number of species) for the ‘Regular hydrological year’ and the ‘Dry hydrological year’.....	27
Figure 12 - Spatial projections of seasonal variation in Dabbling ducks abundance (number of individuals) for the ‘Regular hydrological year’ and the ‘Dry hydrological year’.....	28
Figure 13 - Ordination plot (DCA) showing the distribution of the total number of species per plot through isolines summarising a fitted regression model (the positions of original data points used to fit the regression model correspond to plot scores in the ordination space). Distance between symbols approximates the dissimilarity of species composition measured as turnover distance in standard deviation (SD) units. Land use types are discriminated through contrasting symbols.	30
Figure 14 - Number of sites available on B2DROP (last update 1st of April 2022) presenting biodiversity (BD) data, timespan longer than 15 years, more than 10 measurements within the monitoring period and availability of supplementary abiotic data. For a detailed description of the results from ‘Identification of suitable datasets to integrate biodiversity analysis in WAALS’ see Appendix E.	31

List of Tables

Table 1 - Scientific cases addressed in Task 8.1: <i>High resolution biodiversity data to assess environmental change</i>	13
Table 2 - GLMM regression coefficients (full model) relating breeding occurrence and productivity of Golden eagles, Egyptian vultures and Griffon vultures with sampling period (BA; 2010– 2014 vs. 2015– 2021), proportion of flooded area around breeding territory (FLOODED_AREA), and an interaction term (BA:FLOODED_AREA). Model statistics (Log Likelihood, Akaike Information Criteria, Bayesian Information Criteria, Chi-square of Random effects and of Full model) are also presented.	23
Table 3 - Summary results of multiple comparisons and anomaly detection to investigate potential variations in vegetation patterns at the Moor House eLTER Site. For detailed analysis information see Appendix C.	29

List of Appendixes

Appendix A - Detailed description of the methods and results of Case study 1 – Baixo-Sabor eLTER Site - 'Evaluate changes in reproductive trends of priority conservation cliff-nesting bird species in relation to the Baixo Sabor hydropower dam installation and operation'.	38
Appendix B - Detailed description of the methods and results of Case study 2 - Doñana eLTER Site - 'Understand how changes in freshwater flow and inundation affect the diversity and abundance of waterbird communities, and predict the future suitability of Mediterranean wetlands to form critical breeding and wintering habitats'.	54
Appendix C - Detailed description of the methods and results of Case study 3 – Moor House eLTER Site - 'Identify stressors of biodiversity change by addressing biodiversity responses to environmental variation based on accompanying abiotic data (i.e. in situ measurements)'.	134
Appendix D - Data documentation, including provenance, of the workflow of data analysis for the case study 'Biodiversity trend analysis at the site scale - Moor House UK' (as a direct output to WP10).	168
Appendix E - Detailed description of the results from 'Identification of suitable datasets to integrate biodiversity analysis in WAILS'.	184
Appendix F - List of standard observations proposed by eLTER PLUS (last update January 2024).	191

Executive Summary

Common approaches to draw inferences about the impacts of natural or human-induced distresses on biodiversity must include the consideration of baseline data, and the assessment of spatial and/or temporal biodiversity trends centred about the source of the perturbation. Within the eLTER PLUS project, the primary objective of Task 8.1: *High resolution biodiversity data to assess environmental change* was to determine and prioritise the stressors promoting biodiversity change, and to identify indicators for characterising long-term biodiversity trends at the site and catchment scale. Results demonstrate the effectiveness of eLTER long-term data to: select appropriate indicators of biodiversity response (Baixo Sabor eLTER Site, Portugal); predict patterns of biodiversity change (Doñana eLTER Site, Spain); and identify stressors affecting long-term biodiversity change (Moor House eLTER Site, United Kingdom).

In the Baixo-Sabor eLTER Site (Portugal), we used cliff-nesting birds as ecological indicators of ecosystem resilience to anthropogenic changes (river damming). Generalized linear mixed models were implemented in order to relate breeding occurrence and productivity of Golden eagles, Egyptian vultures and Griffon vultures with periods of pre- and post-dam construction, across breeding territories subjected to a gradient of disturbance created by this infrastructure. We tested the general hypothesis that temporal bird reproductive trends were more favourable (i.e., more positive or less negative) in the control (breeding territories with less proportion of flooded area in the surroundings), using a procedure akin to a Before-After-Control-Impact design with multiple sites and years. Despite a stable trend in the number of Egyptian vultures' breeding pairs using the area, a decrease in breeding productivity after the dam installation (as opposed to an increasing trend towards affected areas before the dam construction) suggests a negative impact of this infrastructure in the demographic rates of this species. Our results provide evidence of changes acting at levels of biological organization other than that commonly used to evaluate biodiversity change (i.e. the community and species level). These results highlight the **need of identifying context-dependent indicators of biodiversity change in order to adequately evaluate the influence of stressors acting at the site and catchment level.**

In the Doñana eLTER Site (Spain), we used waterbirds as ecological indicators of wetlands resilience to environmental change (i.e. land use changes, flooding regime and vegetation dynamics). We developed statistical predictive models, based on generalized linear models, to infer seasonal cause-effect relationships between waterbird functional diversity/abundance and environmental predictors. Abiotic data included time series of land use characterization, and a set of inundation and Normalized Difference Vegetation Index raster files to reconstruct historical spatial and temporal patterns of marshes flooding and vegetation dynamics in the Doñana region. The statistical models created were then used to project spatial-temporal patterns of waterbird diversity and abundance for 2040, according to two scenarios considered (i.e. 'dry hydrological year' and 'regular hydrological year'). Overall, despite a solely decrease in the diversity of Large Wading birds for the Summer of the 'dry hydrological year', the results suggest declines in the abundance of waterbirds from all functional groups in all seasons of the 'dry hydrological year'. Our projections also suggest that the most affected habitats by drought events in the future will be natural marshes, with predicted decreases in diversity and abundance of waterbirds from all functional groups. Our results demonstrate the **usefulness of remote sensing data acquisition to assess a range of variables with great potential for predicting ecological patterns at the site level; the importance of combining biodiversity metrics to get a more comprehensive picture of biodiversity change in time and space; and the added value of spatial predictive modelling frameworks** as tools to support the design of conservation and management actions targeting specific areas within eLTER Sites.

In the Moor House eLTER Site (United Kingdom), we used plant community as an ecological indicator of peatland resilience to environmental changes. We investigated the potential influence of soil properties and weather conditions (*in-situ* abiotic measurements) shaping plant diversity patterns. Multiple

comparisons and anomaly detection were used to investigate the temporal variability of species richness at the site and habitat levels; multivariate analysis (Detrended Correspondence Analysis and Principal Component Analysis) were applied to assess gradients underlying variations in the floristic composition, including the potential impact of environmental data on targeted plant communities. Analyses at the habitat level enabled discriminating plant diversity patterns among main habitat types, allowing to better understand changes in plant trends within the Moor House eLTER Site. However, the lack of spatial variability in abiotic data (i.e. *in-situ* abiotic measurements were obtained at a single location within the site only) impaired our ability to understand changes in plant trends via habitat-specific modifications. In this study we show the **importance of spatial and temporal scales in biodiversity trend analysis, including the need to ensure the spatial-temporal match between biotic and abiotic data sampling** in order to address biodiversity responses at fine spatial-temporal scales.

We also provide an outline of how we evaluated the appropriateness of biodiversity data to align eLTER Sites with the requirements of WAILS (eLTER Whole System Approach), using the database provided by the project and shared through B2DROP. Despite the significant number of eLTER Sites with biodiversity and accompanying abiotic data available on B2DROP, in none of these sites were environmental data available covering all spheres described by WAILS. This made it impossible for us to select a master site for biodiversity analysis under the Whole system approach. The final part of the Deliverable is dedicated to technical considerations regarding data legacy, standard observations and practical recommendations to eLTER managers and site owners. From our general perspective, we highlight the importance of:

- 1) field monitoring protocols to process biodiversity data in a systematic, reliable and repeatable way for robust and accurate comparison purposes at the site level;
- 2) uninterrupted data collection and robust metadata information to guarantee general access to good quality data;
- 3) spatial-temporal overlap between biotic and abiotic data sampling to identify stressors affecting biodiversity at fine spatial-temporal scales;
- 4) identifying multiple-scale stressors (local versus global) to address the combined effects of multiple drivers of biodiversity change at the site and catchment level;
- 5) testing different biodiversity metrics (e.g. level of biological organization; combined metrics of biodiversity response) to identify the most appropriate indicators of biodiversity response;
- 6) remote sensing data acquisition to assess a range of variables with great potential for identifying, explaining and /or predicting ecological patterns, including selecting *in-situ* standard observations as these are available across Europe and aim for a common set of parameters;
- 7) data covering all system dimensions in order to address integrated ecosystem responses;
- 8) spatial predictive modelling frameworks as tools to support the design of conservation and management actions within eLTER Sites.

Abbreviations

B2DROP - EUDAT B2DROP Service

BACI - Before–After–Control–Impact

DCA - Detrended Correspondence analysis

DEIMS-SDR - Dynamic Ecological Information Management System - Site and dataset registry

eLTER Site - European Long-Term ecosystem, critical zone and socio-ecological systems research Site

eLTER PLUS - European long-term ecosystem, critical zone and socio-ecological systems Advanced community project, funded by H2020

eLTER PPP - European long-term ecosystem, critical zone and socio-ecological systems Preparatory Phase Project, funded by H2020

eLTSEER Platform - European Long-Term Socio-Ecological Research Platform

ESFRI - European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures

GLMMs - Generalized linear mixed models

GLMs - Generalized Linear Models

NDVI - Normalized Difference Vegetation Index

PCA - Principal Component Analysis

RI - Research Infrastructure

WAILS - Whole-system Approach for in-situ research on Life Supporting systems

WP - Work Package

Work packages designation

WP7 - NA07 Transnational Access (TA), Remote Access (RA), and Virtual Access (VA) supervision

WP8 - JRA01 eLTER Whole System Approach at site and catchment scale

WP9 - JRA02 Optimisation of the eLTER Network design at the pan-European scale

WP10 - NA08 Define core data and ICT needs and pilot data workflows

WP11 - JRA03 ICT service piloting and dissemination of data products

1. Introduction

1.1 eLTER PLUS

The eLTER PLUS represents an advanced community project aimed at boosting the development of the eLTER community towards the formal establishment of a Research Infrastructure (RI). Its primary objective is to create and distribute innovative methods for integrating research in ecosystems, the critical zone, and socio-ecology on a pan-European scale. These methods are designed to provide national and European decision-makers, natural resource managers, and land use planners with high-quality information and tools to assess the long-term effectiveness of policies.

The main goals of eLTER PLUS include conducting a performance evaluation of the emerging eLTER RI, promoting interdisciplinary research, facilitating access to eLTER research Sites and Platforms, as well as their existing and historical data and services. This endeavour encompasses various aspects such as developing the RI's standard observation framework, creating workflows, data products, and services, managing site and platform design, enhancing community and capacity building, and contributing essential input to the eLTER PPP project and the eLTER ESFRI process.

Figure 1 illustrates the central concept of eLTER PLUS. In the core, Work Packages 8 and 9 address the various system layers, ranging from the geosphere to the atmosphere, covered by eLTER Sites and Platforms.

Figure 1 - The core concept of eLTER PLUS. (Source: <https://elter-ri.eu/elter-plus>)

Four Research Challenges (RCs) are derived from these system layers: Socio-Ecological systems; Biodiversity Loss; Climate-Water-Food nexus, and Biogeochemistry control of ecosystem functions (Figure 1, WPs 8 and WP9; <https://elter-ri.eu/elter-plus>). WP8 focuses on the site scale, while WP9 operates at

catchment-to-continental scales; implementing, in total, eight illustrative thematic Case Studies (CSs) in collaboration with relevant scientific partners (i.e. High resolution biodiversity data to assess environmental change - Task 8.1; Plot scale ecosystem process understanding - Task 8.2; Water use efficiency (WUE) of ecosystems and resilience to drought - Task 8.3; Socio-ecological analyses of stakeholder-defined local and regional environmental challenges - Task 8.4; Representativeness towards pan-European biodiversity pressures and trends - Task 9.1; The Water-Climate-GHG Nexus at the pan-European scale - Task 9.2; Testing eLTER network for a pan-European terrestrial ecosystem model - Task 9.3; Assessment of the value of eLTER for European-scale environmental policy - Task 9.4). Cross-theme cooperation between WP8 and WP9 addresses the eLTER Whole System Approach (WAILS). eLTER PLUS WPs 10 and 11 translate user requirements and research outcomes across themes into tool and data product specifications and conduct piloting and implementation of services and tools. Strategic site selection is based on the existing eLTER Site pool for data and service utilization in the eight CSs. The CSs also assess and test virtual access (VA), trans-national access (TA), and remote access (RA) to the data and services provided by the sites and platforms. The eLTER ESFRI process and the eLTER PPP project receive input from a wide range of requirements. Synthesis connects all project outcomes, scientific communities, the site and platform network, as well as the ESFRI process.

1.2 Aim of the document

The primary objective of this deliverable is to summarize contributions of Task 8.1: *High resolution biodiversity data to assess environmental change*, specifically to determine and prioritise the stressors affecting short term variability and long-term changes in biodiversity, and to identify indicators for characterising long-term trends in biodiversity at the site and catchment scale. According to the project framework and task definition, Deliverable D8.1 is structured as follows (Figure 2):

Figure 2 - Structure of deliverable D8.1. The site-based research on biodiversity change according to three scientific cases selected (Baixo-Sabor, Doñana and Moor House), including a workflow of data analysis for the scientific case of Moor House as a direct contribution to WP10.

We start the deliverable by defining the scientific approach of Task 8.1, namely the criteria used to select the three scientific cases presented (section 2.1), background information and methodological approaches to analyse the data (Baixo-Sabor in section 2.1.1; Doñana in section 2.1.2 and Moor House in section 2.1.3) and discussion of the results (Baixo-Sabor in section 3.1.1; Doñana in section 3.1.2 and Moor House in section 3.1.3). A workflow of data analysis for the scientific case of Moor House (as a direct contribution to WP10) is presented in the methodology section of this case study (section 2.1.3). We also provide an outline of how we evaluated the appropriateness of biodiversity data to align eLTER Sites with the requirements of WAILS (section 'Identification of suitable datasets to integrate biodiversity analysis in WAILS'), using the database provided by the project and shared through B2DROP (sections 2.2 and 3.2). The final part of the 'Results and Discussion' is dedicated to technical considerations regarding data legacy and practical recommendations to eLTER managers and site owners (section 3.3). We expect to submit two peer-reviewed papers (one concerning to the Baixo-Sabor eLTER Site and another to the Doñana eLTER Site) during the first quarter of 2024.

2. Methodology

2.1. High resolution biodiversity data to assess environmental change

The primary objective of Task 8.1: *High resolution biodiversity data to assess environmental change* is to determine and prioritise the stressors affecting long-term changes and short-term variability in biodiversity, and identify indicators for characterising long-term trends in biodiversity at the site and catchment scale. In particular, the main goals are:

- 1) to quantify long-term trends and short term variability in biodiversity and relate both to changes in abiotic variables;
- 2) to explain trends and patterns in biodiversity, rank the stressors and identify appropriate indicators of ecosystem response;

In order to address these goals, three scientific case studies (Table 1) were selected in order to:

- Cover different ecosystem types across Europe, ranging from mountain (agro-forestry systems) to coastal ecosystems (wetlands);
- Address different sources of pressures, ranging from anthropogenic (river damming) to environmental stressors (drought events);
- Evaluate metrics of biodiversity change at different levels of organization, from population (demographic rates) to community levels (functional diversity);
- Explore sets of abiotic data coming from different sources, from remote sensing imagery to *in-situ* measurements;
- Explore different approaches to the data, from biodiversity trend analysis to predictive modelling;

Table 1 - Scientific cases addressed in Task 8.1: *High resolution biodiversity data to assess environmental change*.

	eLTER Site	Ecosystem	Environmental Stressor	Biodiversity indicator	Abiotic data	Methodology	eLTER direct outcome
1	Baixo-Sabor (PT)	Agro-forestry	Human infrastructures (river damming)	Cliff-nesting bird species (individuals occurrence and demographic rates)	Not considered	Trend analysis (GLMMs; akin BACI design)	Showcase the added value of eLTER data to select appropriate indicators of biodiversity response
2	Doñana (SP)	Wetland	Land use and climate (drought events)	Waterbirds (functional diversity and abundance of individuals)	Cartography (Land use) and remote sensing (NDVI and inundation)	Predictive modelling (GLMs)	Showcase the added value of eLTER data to predict patterns of biodiversity change
3	Moor House (UK)	Peatland	Climate (soil chemistry and weather patterns)	Vegetation (species richness and community structure)	In-situ measurements (soil and weather)	Trend analysis (multiple comparisons; anomaly detection; DCA; PCA)	Showcase the added value of eLTER data to identify stressors affecting long-term biodiversity changes

Overall, the scientific cases developed aimed to:

1. Evaluate changes in reproductive trends of priority conservation cliff-nesting bird species in relation to the Baixo Sabor hydropower dam installation and operation. In this study we aim to test metrics of biodiversity change at different levels of organization in order to showcase the added value of eLTER data to select appropriate indicators of biodiversity response.
2. Understand how changes in freshwater flow and inundation affect the diversity and abundance of waterbird communities, and predict the future suitability of Mediterranean wetlands to form critical breeding and wintering habitats. In this study we aim to test a spatial-temporal modelling approach in order to showcase the added value of eLTER data to predict patterns of biodiversity change.
3. Identify stressors of biodiversity change by addressing biodiversity responses to environmental variation based on accompanying abiotic data (i.e. *in-situ* measurements). In this study we attempt to explain biodiversity patterns based on abiotic *in-situ* measurements in order to showcase the added value of eLTER data to identify stressors affecting biodiversity change.

2.1.1. Baixo-Sabor (PT)

Background

As the largest renewable source of energy worldwide, hydropower has been presented as a silver-lining solution to supply the growing energy demand of human population, as well as reducing greenhouse gas emissions for a low-carbon climate-resilient future (IEA, 2021). However, hydropower has a large environmental footprint, and the ecological costs of hydroelectric dams are still underestimated or neglected. This is especially true in vertebrate groups, where the impact of dams are counterintuitive due to the large heterogeneity of observed responses (ranging from negative to positive) (Bohada-Murillo et al., 2021). For example, dams can positively affect several fish species, favouring those species capable of rapidly adapting to the novel conditions (Cooper et al., 2017), but have negative effects on mammals and birds that lose their breeding territories due to flooding (Nilsson and Dynesius, 1994). In this study, we intend to use cliff-nesting birds as ecological indicators of ecosystem resilience to anthropogenic changes (river damming), using the Baixo-Sabor eLTER Site as a case study.

Study site

The Sabor LTSER Platform is situated in the north-eastern part of Portugal, as depicted in Figure 3. It is located within the Trás-os-Montes region, encompassing the watershed of the Sabor River, which spans an area of 3868 square kilometres and ultimately flows into the Douro River. The platform covers both the lower reaches of the Sabor River and the catchment areas of its tributaries, totalling 1590 square kilometres. Notably, a portion of this area was submerged in 2015 due to the construction of the Baixo Sabor Hydroelectric Infrastructure reservoir. Research conducted at this site primarily revolves around enhancing our comprehension of the long-term impacts of river damming on freshwater and nearby terrestrial ecosystems. Additionally, the research explores how these effects interplay with various socio-economic and environmental drivers, ranging from local factors like changes in land use to global-scale influences such as climate change and biological invasions. The topography of LTSER-Sabor varies, with elevation ranging from 100 meters at the mouth of the Sabor River to 1100 meters in the Hills of Bornes and Nogueira. The climate predominantly exhibits Mediterranean characteristics with some continental influence. Annual rainfall varies from approximately 500 mm to 1000 mm, and the mean annual temperature ranges between roughly 10°C and 16°C. Regarding land cover, the region is dominated by

several key elements, including Mediterranean oak forests and shrublands, pine plantations, olive groves, other permanent crops, and arable cropland and pastures, accounting for over 80% of the landscape. Much of the LTSER-Sabor area falls within the Rede Natura 2000 network, specifically within the Special Protection Area (SPA) of the Rivers Sabor and Maçãs, which is designated under the European Directive 79/409/EEC (Birds Directive), and the Sites of Community Importance (SCI) of the Rivers Sabor and Maçãs and of Morais, classified under Directive 92/43/EEC (Habitats Directive). The SPA designation for Rivers Sabor and Maçãs primarily results from the presence of various raptors, including several breeding pairs of species like the golden eagle (*Aquila chrysaetos*), Bonelli's eagle (*Hieraetus fasciatus*), and Egyptian vulture (*Neophron percnopterus*). Meanwhile, the classification of Rivers Sabor and Maçãs and of Morais as SCIs is due to the abundance of diverse habitats and species of conservation importance. Notably, the region is home to the wolf (*Canis lupus*). The LTSER Sabor Platform largely falls within the territories of the municipalities of Torre de Moncorvo, Alfândega da Fé, Macedo de Cavaleiros, and Moncorvo. Human population density in these areas is relatively low, ranging from 12 to 22 inhabitants per square kilometre. Furthermore, there has been a notable decline in population, exceeding 25% to over 50% since 1960. Over recent decades, there has been a trend of population concentration in the main urban centres. Agriculture plays a significant role in the local economy, but there is a pervasive trend of agricultural abandonment due to population declines and an aging demographic. (Source: <https://deims.org/45722713-80e3-4387-a47b-82c97a6ef62b>, website accessed on 9th August 2023).

Figure 3 - Location of the eLTER Site of Sabor (Portugal). Source: DEIMS-SDR

Data analysis

In the Baixo-Sabor eLTER Site (Portugal), we used cliff-nesting birds as ecological indicators of ecosystem resilience to anthropogenic changes (river damming). Generalized linear mixed models were implemented in order to relate breeding occurrence and productivity of Golden eagles, Egyptian vultures and Griffon vultures with periods of pre- and post-dam construction, across breeding territories subjected to a gradient of disturbance created by this infrastructure. We tested the general hypothesis that temporal bird reproductive trends were more favourable (i.e., more positive or less negative) in the control (breeding territories with less proportion of flooded area in the surroundings), using a procedure akin to a Before-

After-Control-Impact design with multiple sites and years. For a detailed description of the methodology and results of this research case study see Appendix A.

2.1.2. Doñana (SP)

Background

The services that wetlands provide, such as carbon storage, water purification, biodiversity conservation, food production, nutrient fixation, and flood prevention, make wetlands significantly valuable across the globe (Zedler and Kercher, 2005; Almeida et al., 2020). However, environmental challenges as climate and land use changes are severely threatening Doñana's ecosystems. In particular, global warming and direct anthropogenic impacts, such as water extraction, affect water budgets in wetlands increasing wetland salinities and isolation, and decreasing water depths and hydroperiods, which are of paramount importance for local biodiversity (Ramírez et al., 2018).

One of the most important areas for waterbirds across Europe (and across the Mediterranean region) is the Doñana National Park, which holds a range of natural, restored, and artificial wetlands that benefit birds (Rendón et al., 2008; Sebastián-González and Green, 2014; 2016). Among the most important animal communities in wetlands are waterbirds, which sustain various ecological functions such as nutrient cycling, dispersal of propagules, ecosystem engineering, and biological control (Green and Elmerberg, 2014; Almeida et al., 2020). Therefore, waterbirds can be important indicators of wetland functions, acting as 'flagship community' to support management strategies for wetland conservation especially under the current context of environmental change (Dudgeon et al., 2007; Green et al., 2017; Ramírez et al., 2018). In this study, we intend to use waterbirds as an ecological indicator of wetlands resilience to environmental change (land use, flooding regime and vegetation dynamics), using the Doñana eLTER Site as a case study.

Study site

Established in 1968, Doñana National Park, covering an area of 537 square kilometres, boasts multiple prestigious conservation designations. It is recognized as a UNESCO Biosphere Reserve, a Ramsar Site, and a Natural World Heritage Site. The park is renowned for hosting the largest wetland in Western Europe, a complex network of marshlands spanning 270 square kilometres, phreatic lagoons, a 25-kilometer-long dune ecosystem with its accompanying shoreline, and representative terrestrial plant communities characteristic of the Mediterranean region. Doñana plays a pivotal role as both a crucial stopover site for Palearctic birds during their migration to Africa and a vital overwintering habitat for waterfowl. The Doñana LTSE Platform, illustrated in Figure 4, encompasses not only the protected area itself but also the surrounding territories, spanning a vast 2,736 square kilometres. These surroundings comprise a diverse landscape matrix, including rice fields, fisheries, irrigated crops, berry greenhouses, vineyards, olive groves, and pine afforestation areas. These features are interconnected by tributary streams that flow into the fluvial marshland, which stands as the centrepiece of Doñana. The human population residing in the vicinity of Doñana exceeds 180,000 permanent inhabitants. Within the protected land, three primary ecosystems coexist, harbouring an impressive array of biodiversity: Doñana supports more than 1,550 species of vascular plants, 900 species of arthropods, up to 400 breeding and migratory bird species, 38 mammal species, 72 species of fish and 40 species of reptiles and amphibians. This extraordinary diversity underscores the ecological significance of Doñana National Park, making it a treasure trove of biodiversity and a vital hub for scientific research and conservation efforts. (Source: <https://deims.org/bcbc866c-3f4f-47a8-bbbc-0a93df6de7b2>, website accessed on 9th August 2023).

Figure 4 - Location of the eLTER Site of Doñana (Spain). Source: DEIMS-SDR

Data analysis

In the Doñana eLTER Site (Spain), we used waterbirds as an ecological indicator of wetlands resilience to environmental change (i.e. land use changes, flooding regime and vegetation dynamics). We developed statistical predictive models, based on generalized linear models, to infer seasonal cause-effect relationships between waterbird functional diversity/abundance and environmental predictors. Abiotic data included time series of land use characterization, and a set of inundation and Normalized Difference Vegetation Index raster files to reconstruct historical spatial and temporal patterns of marshes flooding and vegetation dynamics in the Doñana region. The statistical models created were then used to project spatial-temporal patterns of waterbird diversity and abundance for 2040, according to two scenarios considered (i.e. ‘dry hydrological year’ and ‘regular hydrological year’). For a detailed description of the methodology and results of this research case study see Appendix B.

2.1.3. Moor House (UK)

Background

Ombrotrophic peatlands (bogs) are peat-forming naturally species-poor wetlands (Vitt and Belland, 1995; Warner and Asada, 2006) that are mostly viewed as resilient ecosystems with important compositional vegetation changes usually occurring over centuries to millennia (Gunnarsson et al., 2002). However, several studies have shown recent rapid and drastic compositional changes in response to human-induced disturbances (drainage, eutrophication, climate warming, land-use modifications), through their impact on water and nutrient availability (Pinceloup et al., 2020).

Above- and belowground components of terrestrial ecosystems are intimately linked by plant communities. For example, temporal variability in rainfall has been linked to changes in species composition and is widely shown to influence plant diversity in peatlands (Sonesson et al., 2002). Soil chemistry is also likely to be affected by physical and chemical changes in the environment (triggered by

land use and/or climate changes) thus driving important modifications in plant diversity and composition (e.g. Roem and Berendse, 2000; Dingaan et al., 2017). In this study, we intend to investigate the potential influence of soil properties and weather conditions in shaping plant diversity patterns of peatlands, using the Moor House eLTER Site as a case study.

Study site

Moor House - Upper Teesdale is a high-altitude site situated in the northern region of England, characterized by extensive moorland and grassland ecosystems (Figure 5). This location serves as a key UK Environmental Change Network (ECN) site. It encompasses England's highest and largest terrestrial National Nature Reserve (NNR), is designated as a UNESCO Global Geopark, and holds the status of an EU Special Protection Area. The site boasts a diverse range of habitats, including exposed mountain summits, expansive blanket peatlands, upland grasslands, pastures, hay meadows, and deciduous woodlands. The site is home to grazing sheep, and it is divided into two distinct areas. The Moor House area extends from the upper reaches of the Eden Valley, encompassing Great Dun Fell (848 meters), Little Dun Fell, and Knock Fell, extending all the way to the River Tees. The geological composition of this area consists of alternating layers of limestone, sandstone, and shale, with intrusions of dolerite from the Great Whin Sill. The eastern side of this region, with its gentle slopes, is covered by poorly-drained glacial till, which has given rise to the formation of blanket bogs with peat layers ranging from 1 to 3 meters in depth. The dominant vegetation in these areas includes *Eriophorum* (cotton grass), *Calluna vulgaris* (heather), and various species of Sphagnum moss. On the western side of the site, soils and vegetation exhibit greater variability. The Upper Teesdale area within the reserve is especially notable for its unique communities of arctic-alpine plants and other flora and fauna. Starting from Cow Green Reservoir, it stretches southward to the summit of Mickle Fell (788 meters) and eastward along the course of the Tees River to the remarkable High Force waterfall. Much like the Moor House area, the geology, soils, and vegetation in this region share similarities. However, 'sugar limestone' soils and moist riverside soils create favourable conditions for a variety of rare plant species to thrive. (Source: <https://deims.org/bf78c96f-0763-4b31-b1a6-6eccef19edd1>, website accessed on 21st October 2022).

Figure 5 - Location of the eLTER Site of Moor House (United Kingdom). Source: DEIMS-SDR

Data analysis

In the Moor House eLTER Site (United Kingdom), we used plant community as an ecological indicator of peatland resilience to environmental changes. We investigated the potential influence of soil properties and weather conditions (*in-situ* abiotic measurements) shaping plant diversity patterns. Multiple comparisons and anomaly detection were used to investigate the temporal variability of species richness at the site and habitat levels; multivariate analysis (Detrended Correspondence Analysis and Principal Component Analysis) were applied to assess gradients underlying variations in the floristic composition, including the potential impact of environmental data on targeted plant communities. For a detailed description of the methodology and results of this research case study see Appendix C.

Workflow of data analysis

This section describe the working steps of the case study 'Biodiversity trend analysis at the eLTER Site of Moor House', using a list of prioritised workflow elements required by eLTER PLUS WP10:

1. Workflow documentation and persistent identification

Figure 6 - Workflow of data analysis for the case study 'Biodiversity trend analysis at the site scale - Moor House UK'.

2. Data retrieval (access to data, e.g. API)

The biodiversity dataset used in this study includes vegetation sampling (plant species list and relative abundance) obtained from the UK Environmental Change Network (via B2DROP folder). Abiotic datasets include *in-situ* abiotic measurements of soil chemistry and meteorological data obtained from ECN (downloaded from http://data.ecn.ac.uk/request_form.asp in June 2022) (Figure 6A).

3. data format harmonisation and transformation (including check of data formats)

All datasets (Biodiversity and Abiotic) have been received as csv files (Figure 6A).

4. Variable harmonisation (semantic) as the basis for further check of the data

Plant species names in the original dataset were harmonized via data cleaning and abbreviation procedures (Figure 6B).

5. Quality control and outlier detection (variable / site level and across site / variable level - tipping points and change point detection / are site data comparable)

Samples in which the quality of the data have been affected during sampling were removed from the database (Figure 6B).

6. Data fusion

Not applicable

7. Unit transformation

Vegetation raw data (plant species list and abundance data) were transformed into biodiversity metrics (i.e. species abundance per plot per year; species presence/absence per plot per year) (Figure 6C).

8. Spatial aggregation and harmonisation - this includes methods and protocols and the observation design

Analyses were performed at two spatial scales (i.e. site level and habitat level). In order to identify changes in vegetation communities at the habitat level, the available classification of plots in terms of Land use/Land cover type was used (Figure 6C and 6D).

9. Temporal aggregation and harmonisation

Since vegetation data correspond to annual measurements, abiotic variables (measured at finer temporal scales) were aggregated as annual values. The annual average of abiotic variables was calculated based on the average of their trimestral values. This procedure included the verification of data quality in terms of intra-annual availability of abiotic *in-situ* measurements (i.e. trimester per year) (Figure 6C and 6D).

10. Gap filling

Not applicable

11. Data documentation including provenance

Accompanying descriptive information is shown in Appendix D.

12. Data ingestion, data storage and persistent identification

Not applicable

2.2. Identification of suitable datasets to integrate biodiversity analysis in WAILS

Screening of high-resolution biodiversity data (both spatial and temporal) to identify potential sites to work in WAILS focused on the database provided by the project and shared through B2DROP (EUDAT B2DROP - developed by WP7). The following criteria, considered to reflect good quality data to analyse long-term biodiversity trends (Haase et al., 2018), were defined: availability of datasets with timespan longer than 15 years, more than 10 measurements within the monitoring period available, and availability of supplementary abiotic data. Existing biodiversity data shared on B2DROP was analysed by eLTER Site, country, presence/absence of biodiversity data, biodiversity indicators surveyed, timespan, number of sampled years and availability of supplementary abiotic data.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. High resolution biodiversity data to assess environmental change

Common approaches to draw inferences about the impacts of natural or human-induced pressures on biodiversity include the consideration of baseline data, and the assessment of spatial and/or temporal biodiversity trends centred about the source of disturbance (e.g. Márquez-Ferrando et al., 2014; Santana et al., 2014; Cooper et al., 2017). In this deliverable we showcase the usefulness of eLTER data in generating empirical evidence to identify human and environmental impacts influencing biodiversity at different levels of organization and spatial scales. For this, the prioritization of stressors and identification of the most appropriate indicators of biodiversity response was an essential step to formulate the research questions and conduct the analyses at the site and catchment level.

3.1.1. Baixo-Sabor (PT)

The primary source of perturbation at the Baixo-Sabor eLTER Site has been associated with the hydroelectric power dam installation and operation, leading the focus of investigation in this site towards the effects of river damming on freshwater and adjacent terrestrial ecosystems. To address this, our research question was directed to understand whether this anthropogenic stressor may have a direct influence on cliff-nesting bird species, and what could be the most suitable metrics to capture its potential effect.

Statistical results suggest a significant positive relationship between Griffon vultures' breeding occurrence and productivity and the period after the dam installation (i.e. operation phase) (marked in yellow, Table 2). However, the lack of a significant interaction between the before/after periods and the proportion of flooded area around breeding territories does not seem to indicate a direct relationship between the observed patterns and the influence of the dam. On the other hand, for Golden eagles and Egyptian vultures, a significant interaction between these two factors (at both 2km and 5km spatial scales) suggest a potential effect of this infrastructure in the breeding productivity of these species (marked in blue, Table 2). In particular, for Golden eagles, the positive interaction between the before/after periods and the proportion of flooded area around breeding territories suggest that, despite a decrease in breeding productivity towards areas more affected by the dam (i.e. higher proportion of flooded area), this pattern has been similar in both periods before and after the dam installation (Figure 7). These results do not support a potential negative effect of this infrastructure in the breeding productivity of this species. On the other hand, for Egyptian vultures, a decrease in breeding productivity after the dam installation (as opposed to an increasing trend towards affected areas before the dam construction) suggests a negative impact of this infrastructure in this particular species (Figure 7). Overall, our results suggest a direct negative influence of this infrastructure on the breeding productivity of Egyptian vultures, despite a stable trend in the number of breeding pairs using the area over the years (i.e. lack of a significant effect in breeding occurrence of Egyptian vultures as shown in Table 2).

Table 2 - GLMM regression coefficients (full model) relating breeding occurrence and productivity of Golden eagles, Egyptian vultures and Griffon vultures with sampling period (BA; 2010–2014 vs. 2015–2021), proportion of flooded area around breeding territory (FLOODED_AREA), and an interaction term (BA:FLOODED_AREA). Model statistics (Log Likelihood, Akaike Information Criteria, Bayesian Information Criteria, Chi-square of Random effects and of Full model) are also presented.

	Golden eagle 2km	Golden eagle 5km	Egyptian vulture 2 km	Egyptian vulture 5 km	Griffon vulture 2 km	Griffon vulture 5 km
BREEDING OCCURRENCE						
Intercept	0.44	0.69	-1.89	-1.06	-4.98	-5.21*
BA	0.08	-0.20	1.60	0.76	4.91	5.35*
FLOODED_AREA	-4.95	-12.79	27.08	24.08	23.66	50.88
BA:FLOODED_AREA	4.86	13.48	-22.03	-16.18	2.76	-4.13
Observations	90.00	90.00	73.00	73.00	90.00	90
Groups (year, territory)	11,10	11,10	11,8	11,8	11,10	11,10
Log Likelihood	-59.10	-58.30	-46.20	-46.80	-42.30	-41.70
Akaike Inf. Crit.	130.20	128.60	104.30	105.50	96.60	95.50
Bayesian Inf. Crit.	145.20	143.60	118.10	119.30	111.60	110.50
Chisq (Random effects)	1.96	2.10	3.21	3.00	0.0004672***	10.75**
Chisq (Full Model)	2.11	3.75	3.81	2.60	15.39**	16.55***
PRODUCTIVITY						
Intercept	-0.43***	-0.27***	0.10	0.20	-0.17	-0.02
BA	-0.79***	-0.98***	-0.03	-0.13	0.40*	0.23*
FLOODED_AREA	-2.85***	-8.21***	3.06	2.44	2.21	0.67
BA:FLOODED_AREA	1.18***	6.68***	-3.72***	-3.19*	-2.07	0.02
Observations	90.00	90.00	73.00	73.00	90.00	90
Groups (year, territory)	11,10	11,10	11,8	11,8	11,10	11,10
Log Likelihood	-70.6	-70	-0.1	-2.2	-4.3	-5
Akaike Inf. Crit.	153.10	152	14.2	18.4	22.5	23.9
Bayesian Inf. Crit.	168.10	167	30.3	34.4	40	41.4
Chisq (Random effects)	1.37	1.37	21.13***	20.99***	20.74***	18.92***
Chisq (Full Model)	3.31	4.40	14.57**	10.42*	5.64	4.22

Figure 7 - Model predicted probabilities (interaction term BA:FLOODED_AREA) of the breeding occurrence and productivity of Golden eagles (left) and Egyptian vultures (right) in relation to sampling period (Before in red; After in blue) and proportion of flooded area around breeding territory (FLOODED_AREA). Shaded zones represent variation around the mean (i.e. 95% confidence intervals).

These findings, in addition to provide evidence of changes acting at levels of biological organization other than that commonly used to evaluate biodiversity change (i.e. the community level), also indicate that individuals occurrence and distribution (i.e. the species level) may not always be robust indicators to evaluate disturbance effects on terrestrial wildlife. In fact, by focusing exclusively on species occurrence and/or taxonomic diversity, impact assessment may ignore changes on other important components of biodiversity response (e.g. Devictor et al., 2010; Bastos et al., 2018; Abreu et al., 2020). Therefore, inference can be greatly improved when, in addition to traditional measurements of diversity, other metrics are also addressed, i.e. using ecological information from individuals to upscale count-based field data into rate-based demographic inference (e.g. Katzner et al., 2020). These results highlight the need of identifying context-dependent indicators of biodiversity change in order to adequately evaluate the influence of stressors acting at the site and catchment level. As future steps, we suggest the integration of abiotic information, such as land use/land cover and/or prey density (available to the Baixo-Sabor eLTER Site), in order to better understand the ecological processes underlying the patterns identified in this study (e.g. habitat fragmentation and/or modification in predator–prey relationships).

3.1.2. Doñana (SP)

Our approach at the Doñana eLTER Site was based on the effects of multiple stressors affecting waterbird communities in order to predict the ecological resilience of wetlands to sustain future wintering and breeding habitats for waterbirds in the region. In this regard, the availability of long-term abiotic datasets was a key step to reconstruct historical spatial and temporal patterns of land use changes, marshes flooding and vegetation dynamics in Doñana (see Appendix B). This was fundamental to inform the statistical model and, consequently, to ensure accuracy in the prediction of waterbird responses to future environmental changes (Santos et al., 2013). Furthermore, since most of this abiotic information came from satellite data, we stress the importance of remote sensing data acquisition to assess a range of continuous remotely sensed variables with great potential for identifying, explaining and/or predicting ecological patterns at the site level (e.g. Levanoni et al., 2013; Alcaraz-Segura et al. 2017; Bastos et al., 2016a; 2018). These results also highlight the interplay between remote sensing information (i.e. from Unmanned Aerial Vehicles and satellite imagery) and *in-situ* field measurements. In fact, remote sensing data at the site scale must be always complemented with *in-situ* measurements (i.e. ground truthing assessment to verify remotely collected data) (e.g. Díaz-Delgado et al., 2016), while *in-situ* observations may be supported by remote sensing information (e.g. species detection and mapping) due to the very high resolution of UAVs products and satellite imagery available. Remote sensing products can therefore act as an important delineators of the most appropriate variables to collect in the field, thus providing valuable guidelines for the selection of standard observations at the site and catchment level.

We also highlight the added value of combining biodiversity metrics to get a more robust assessment of the ecological resilience of vulnerable ecosystems to environmental changes. For example, despite a solely decrease in the diversity of Large Wading birds for the Summer of the ‘Dry hydrological year’ when compared to the ‘Regular hydrological year’ (Figure 8), our results suggest future declines in the abundance of waterbirds from all functional groups in all seasons of the ‘Dry hydrological year’ (Figure 9). These integrated results allow to get a more comprehensive picture of waterbird community responses to future environmental scenarios, thus offering greater insight into the resilience of wetlands to extreme hydrological conditions.

Figure 8 - Temporal trends (1984-2020) of waterbird diversity (number of species per functional group), including predictions for 2040 according to the future scenarios considered (i.e. ‘Regular hydrological year’ and ‘Dry hydrological year’).

Figure 9 - Temporal trends (1984-2020) of waterbird abundance (number of individuals per functional group), including predictions for 2040 according to the future scenarios considered (i.e. 'Regular hydrological year' and 'Dry hydrological year').

Another important aspect of our approach in Doñana is its practical applicability in terms of management. In fact, the capacity to accurately predict spatial responses of ecological indicators to future environmental changes is crucial for the sustainable management of a given territory (e.g. Morinha et al., 2017). In this regard, our future projections suggest that the most affected habitat type by drought events in Doñana will be natural marshes (Figure 10), with predicted decreases in diversity and abundance of waterbirds from all functional groups considered (Figure 11 and Figure 12) as an illustrative example for Dabbling Ducks).

Figure 10 - Location of the 24 plots used for waterbirds analysis on the Doñana eLTER Site, discriminated by sectors based on principal habitat-types.

Figure 11 - Spatial projections of seasonal variation in Dabbling ducks diversity (number of species) for the 'Regular hydrological year' and the 'Dry hydrological year'.

Figure 12 - Spatial projections of seasonal variation in Dabbling ducks abundance (number of individuals) for the 'Regular hydrological year' and the 'Dry hydrological year'.

Taking these results, our modelling framework can be used to support the design of conservation and management actions, namely by testing local-specific management programs and conservation measures targeting specific areas within this site (e.g. Bastos et al., 2012). Furthermore, the integration of both local (i.e. Land use) and global stressors (i.e. flooding regimes as a proxy to extreme climatic events) influencing waterbird community responses in Doñana will allow policymakers to create holistic strategies that address multiple levels of impact, from local habitat preservation to global greenhouse gas reduction (e.g. Márquez-Ferrando et al., 2014).

Despite the limitations inherent to a first demonstration, the developed model also provides a useful starting point for the improvement of more inter-calibrated techniques (e.g. hybrid approaches), allowing the development of increasingly robust modelling frameworks to support policy makers and environmental planners. As further steps, we anticipate the integration of the statistical model conceded in this study with mechanistic approaches, such as system dynamics, in order to create hybrid models (e.g. StDM approach; Santos and Cabral, 2004) capable of providing future dynamic trends of spatially-explicit waterbird responses to socio-ecological changing scenarios (e.g. Bastos et al., 2016b). In this regard, we see great potential in merging our modelling tool for biodiversity assessment in Doñana with other themes within WP8. For example, the prediction of long-term waterbird community trends under future realistic social-economic scenarios (Task 8.4 - *Socio-ecological analyses of stakeholder-defined local and regional environmental challenges*) can support conservationist management recommendations, namely by anticipating relevant ecological consequences associated with future realistic land use changing scenarios. Also, by incorporating mechanistic components capable of translate primary productivity into availability of refugee/nesting sites (via dynamic plant-soil models in Task 8.2 - *Plot scale ecosystem process understanding*) and/or flooding area into availability of prey (via hydro-chemical catchment models in Task 8.3 - *Water use efficiency (WUE) of ecosystems and resilience to drought*), we may be able to upgrade

model results into a mechanistic understanding of the waterbird responses to modified local environmental conditions (e.g. Carvalho et al., 2013). This are considerations to take into the WAILS approach.

3.1.3. Moor House (UK)

Finally, at Moor House, our aim was to identify stressors of biodiversity change by addressing biodiversity responses to environmental variation based on accompanying abiotic data (i.e. in situ measurements). For this, temporal patterns in plant species richness were analysed at two spatial scales (i.e. site level and habitat level), discriminated by data sampled at three-years interval (45 plots) and data sampled annually (8 plots). Our findings show the importance of scale in biodiversity data analysis (Anderson, 2018). For example, results indicate high variability of plant species richness among sampling plots, both in space and time. However, such variability is particularly critical at the site-level, making it difficult to understand the mechanisms underlying temporal changes of plant diversity patterns within the site (Appendix C1). Conversely, analyses at the habitat level enabled discriminating plant diversity patterns among habitat type, allowing to better understand changes in plant trends within the Moor House eLTER Site (Appendix C1). In this regard, the frequency of sampling also proved to be critical in depicting temporal patterns of plant species richness. In fact, the detection of anomalies in time series of plant species richness proved to be useful in identifying anomaly patterns for data sampled annually (Table 3).

Table 3 - Summary results of multiple comparisons and anomaly detection to investigate potential variations in vegetation patterns at the Moor House eLTER Site. For detailed analysis information see Appendix C.

Spatial scale	Sampling strategy	Habitat type	Differences in plant species richness among years (multiple comparisons)	Anomalies in plant species richness throughout time (anomaly detection)
Site level	45 plots sampled at 3 yr interval	-	n.s	1996*
	8 plots sampled annually	-	n.s	1999
Habitat level	45 plots sampled at 3 yr interval	Semi-natural grasslands	n.s	2014*
		fen, moor or bog	n.s	2014*
		Permanent or long-term grasslands	n.s	2014*
	8 plots sampled annually	Semi-natural grasslands	n.s	1999, 2004, 2006
		fen, moor or bog	n.s	1999

absence of significant differences in plant species richness among years (n.s)

anomaly detection in plant species richness (year)

Lack of confidence interval in the response ()*

However, the lack of confidence intervals obtained for data sampled at three-years interval suggest that the low number of sampled years (7) impairs the ability of the algorithm to identify reliable anomaly patterns in this dataset (Table 3). Therefore, despite the limited number of plots, our results show the importance of continuing performing a more periodic systematic monitoring (i.e. data sampled annually), so that plant trend analyses can include robust time series of biodiversity indicators in main habitat types. From another perspective, sampling in the largest number of plots (i.e. at three years interval), in addition to confer robust spatial representativeness of habitats within the site, may also buffer possible future restrictions in long-term funding. Another important aspect of these analyses relies on inconsistencies between results obtained from different approaches to the data (i.e. multiple comparisons *versus* anomaly detection; anomaly detection at the site *versus* habitat level; Table 3). The disparities observed may denote the challenges associated with trying to quantify biodiversity shifts, particularly when they fall short of catastrophic events within such brief time frames.

We also assessed gradients underlying variations in the floristic composition and the potential impact of abiotic data (in situ measurements of soil properties and weather conditions) on targeted plant communities of Moor House. Not surprisingly, more similar plant communities tended to aggregate by land use types and/or at the plot-level when considering time (i.e. year) (Figure 13). However, the lack of spatial variability in abiotic data (i.e. *in-situ* abiotic measurements were obtained at a solely location within the site) impaired our ability to understand changes in plant trends via habitat-specific modifications. These results reinforce the idea that field monitoring protocols should (whenever possible) ensure the spatial-temporal overlap between biotic and abiotic data sampling in order to address biodiversity responses at fine spatial-temporal scales (Anderson, 2018).

Figure 13 - Ordination plot (DCA) showing the distribution of the total number of species per plot through isolines summarising a fitted regression model (the positions of original data points used to fit the regression model correspond to plot scores in the ordination space). Distance between symbols approximates the dissimilarity of species composition measured as turnover distance in standard deviation (SD) units. Land use types are discriminated through contrasting symbols.

3.2. Identification of suitable datasets to integrate biodiversity analysis in WAILS

Considering the quality criteria for long-term biotic and abiotic data to be included in WAILS (Haase et al., 2018), our results indicate the availability of biodiversity data (accompanied by abiotic information) in circa 30 eLTER Sites of the database provided by the project and shared through B2DROP (Figure 14).

Figure 14 - Number of sites available on B2DROP (last update 1st of April 2022) presenting biodiversity (BD) data, timespan longer than 15 years, more than 10 measurements within the monitoring period and availability of supplementary abiotic data. For a detailed description of the results from 'Identification of suitable datasets to integrate biodiversity analysis in WAILS' see Appendix E.

In this regard, the biggest limitation found in the use of biodiversity data to the WAILS implementation was related to the availability of thematic abiotic data. In fact, WP8 presupposes the study of interactions and feedbacks between social and biophysical systems, particularly with regard to resilience and the response of social-ecological systems to extreme events at the site and catchment scale (Mirtl et al., 2021). Although the significant number of eLTER Sites with biotic and abiotic data available, in none of these sites environmental data belong simultaneously to all the spheres covered by WAILS (Figure 14). This made it impossible for us to select a master site for biodiversity analysis under the Whole-system approach. Despite these limitations, we discuss below how biodiversity data can be integrated with other layers of the system in an illustrative case of the Doñana's potential for developing an ecosystem-based approach (see discussion of Doñana's results above).

3.3. Technical considerations from data legacy and practical recommendations to eLTER managers and site owners

DATA ACCESS: Of the three case studies presented in this deliverable, only data from Moor House was fully available on B2DROP. Data from the Baixo-Sabor eLTER Site was partially available on B2DROP (i.e. 2010-2014), so that after 2015 data was obtained directly from site manager. The full dataset from Doñana was

obtained directly from site manager. Overall, these limitations on data access reveal flaws in the centralization of eLTER data by the RI.

DATA PROCESSING: From a technical-scientific perspective, the workflow developed for the Moor House eLTER Site constitutes a useful tool for documenting the analyses and making processed data available. This product was a direct contribution from Task 8.1 to WP10.

As practical recommendations (lessons learned) to eLTER managers and site owners, we highlight:

1. The implementation of field monitoring protocols to process biodiversity data in a systematic, reliable and repeatable way for robust and accurate comparison purposes at the site level (e.g. at the Baixo-Sabor eLTER Site the monitoring protocol partially changed between the installation and operation phases of the dam); In this regard, eLTER PLUS already provided a crucial way forward towards the development of standard observations (Appendix F). These standardized measurements will allow comparisons within and across eLTER Sites, both in space and time. Nonetheless, challenges arise when the aim is to address trends at the site scale, namely due to the need of identifying site-specific indicators of biodiversity response (see point 3 and 5).
2. The importance of not interrupting data collection and ensuring the datasets informatization in order to guarantee general access to good quality data (e.g. at the Moor House eLTER Site monitoring was interrupted in 2015; at the Baixo-Sabor eLTER Site the data was only partially made available in the RI). For example, the proposed standard observation (SOBIO_017; Appendix F) will allow not only to continue assessing vegetation trends in the eLTER Site of Moor House but also comparisons across eLTER sites. Nonetheless, intra-site variability in biotic and abiotic measurements should also be addressed in order to infer trends at the site and catchment level (see also point 3).
3. The need of ensuring the spatial-temporal overlap between biotic and abiotic data sampling in order to identify stressors affecting biodiversity change at fine spatial-temporal scales (e.g. at the Moor House eLTER Site the lack of spatial variability in abiotic data impaired our ability to understand changes in plant trends via habitat-specific modifications). This is a fundamental point relating to the standard observations that has probably still to be addressed with sufficient robustness (e.g. If eLTER has as one of its aims to develop datasets to understand vegetation change through the collection of soil chemical - e.g. SOGEO_003; Appendix F - and meteorological data - e.g. SOATM_027; Appendix F), appropriate scaling of measurements is critical). In fact, tight co-location of stressor and response variables at appropriate frequencies is of course ideal, but may often be impractical/unaffordable where replication is necessary. In some cases it may be however possible to draw inferences from intensive measurements made at one point, if coupled with less intensive but more spatially extensive measurements across a wider site. In this respect, eLTER needs to think about the realistic potential of collecting abiotic variables at specific points to represent change across wider spatial scales.
4. The need for identification of multiple-scale stressors, i.e. local stressors (e.g. river damming) versus global stressors (e.g. climate change) to address the combined effect of anthropogenic and/or environmental drivers shaping biodiversity at the site and catchment level (e.g. the integration of multi-scale stressors influencing waterbird community responses in Doñana will allow policymakers to create holistic strategies that address multiple levels of impact).
5. The need to identify site-specific indicators of biodiversity response (i.e. testing of different levels of biological organization/combined metrics of biodiversity response) to correctly evaluate context-specific stressors acting at the site and catchment level (e.g. at the Sabor eLTER Site,

demographic parameters proved to be the most reliable indicators of cliff-nesting birds responses to the dam installation). In this regard, standard observations measured at the species/community level (e.g. SOBIO_018; Appendix F) may be coupled with observations at finer levels of biological organization (e.g. the population level) in order to accurately quantify biodiversity changes at the site and catchment level. Overall, we stress the value of working closely with those who best understand the particular sites and their data (including all the quirks and limitations) (e.g. the inconclusive results on the Moor House eLTER Site can be partly explained by a failure to understand the potential of the available data to address the scientific question raised).

6. The importance of remote sensing data acquisition to assess a range of variables with great potential for identifying, explaining and /or predicting ecological patterns at the site level (e.g. at the Doñana eLTER Site, the availability of long-term abiotic datasets from continuous remotely sensed variables was a key step to reconstruct historical spatial and temporal patterns of land use changes, marshes flooding and vegetation dynamics in the region). This may configure important information for standard observations selection (e.g. SOSOC_036; Appendix F), namely the targeting of remote sensing data to select *in-situ* standard observations at the site and catchment level (as these are available across Europe and aim for a common set of parameters);
7. The obtention of data covering all system dimensions in order to address ecosystem-based responses (e.g. in none of the eLTER Sites with biodiversity data available on B2DROP environmental data belong simultaneously to all spheres covered by WAILS); Adherence to the WAILS approach, although not essential to address every environmental change question, can help ensuring that most key measurements, actual or derived, are factored into the final standard observations design. Here we also stress the value of eLTER long-term co-located data available in repositories other than B2DROP, which are important with regard to potential legacy assets.
8. The added value of spatial predictive modelling frameworks as tools to support the design of conservation and management actions targeting specific areas within eLTER Sites (e.g. our modelling tool for biodiversity assessment in Doñana can be used to test waterbird responses to future local-specific management programs and conservation measures).

We conclude by highlighting broader considerations, essential for integrating biodiversity trend analysis from local to continental scales, and *vice versa*. This includes the necessity to incorporate biodiversity indicators mandated by existing legislation, such as the EU birds and habitats Directives, the Water Framework Directive, and Regulation (EU) 1143/2014 for Invasive Alien Species, to ensure standardized data collection across eLTER Sites. This standardization will allow for cross-European comparisons thus contributing to the EU's reporting efforts concerning the implementation of biodiversity-related directives. Overall, it may be important to consider the need for another round of horizon scanning (with a more applied focus than before), in order to ensure that standard observations (including their distributions within sites) will adequately tackle the most pressing and emerging environmental challenges in Europe.

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6. Appendices

6.1. Appendix A

Appendix A - Detailed description of the methods and results of Case study 1 – Baixo-Sabor eLTER Site - ‘Evaluate changes in reproductive trends of priority conservation cliff-nesting bird species in relation to the Baixo Sabor hydropower dam installation and operation’.

Methodology

BIODIVERSITY DATA

Database: Cliff-nesting bird data is structured in two phases, before and after 2015, corresponding to the Baixo-Sabor hydropower dam installation (2010-2014) and operation phases (2015-2021), respectively. For data analysis, different datasets were used:

- nest monitoring data before 2015 (EDP15_monitNinhos_evid_nid.xls) and data from complementary observations (2010-2014) (EDP18_obs_complementares_evid_nid.xls) (downloaded from <https://www.gbif.org> in November 2021; dataset available on B2DROP)
- nest monitoring data after 2015 (2015-2021; Rupicolos_2015_2021_RB.xls) (provided by João Cabral – site manager - in November 2021)

Description: Cliff-nesting bird data is characterised by data obtained from monthly surveys of cliff-nesting birds’ breeding activities and reproductive success.

Sampling strategy: Monitoring of Golden eagles, Egyptian vultures and Griffon vultures followed a two-fold approach: Installation phase (2010-2014): systematic monitoring of known existing nesting sites inside the eLTER Site boundaries (i.e. within a 5-km buffer around the lower Sabor river; Figure A1); Operation phase (2015-2021): systematic monitoring of known existing nesting sites inside and outside the eLTER Site boundaries (i.e. along the Sabor, Angueira and Mações rivers) (Figure A1). All known existing nests were visited at least once during the mating stages, incubation, post-hatching and pre-emancipation of juveniles. The nests were observed with a telescope, in order to confirm the existence of postures (i.e., adult incubating and/or eggs, chicks or juveniles in the nest) and the number of flying juveniles produced.

Note: Complementary observations refer to data obtained outside the systematic monitoring scheme between 2010 and 2014 (i.e. in transects between known existing nesting sites or while prospecting potential new nests within the study area). Records refer to flying birds (adults or juveniles) and/or evidence of potential new nesting areas (i.e. adult incubating and/or eggs, chicks or juveniles in the nest).

Figure A1 - Location of the study area within the Baixo-Sabor eLTER Site (dotted line), and outside the eLTER Site boundaries along the Sabor, Angueira and Maçãs rivers.

Data analysis

Definition of breeding territories

As wide-ranging predators/scavengers, cliff nesting birds often exhibit interannual variations in nest location within potential nesting areas (Kochert and Steenhof, 2012). Therefore, in order to quantify changes in reproductive patterns of individuals over time, breeding territories (i.e. set of nests used by the same couple among years, in the case of Golden eagles, or set of nests used by individuals of the same colony among years, in the case of the gregarious Egyptian and Griffon vulture) were identified in the study area. For this, only data of nests with confirmed evidence of reproduction were considered in the analysis, i.e. indirectly through adults' behavioural information (nesting code between 10 and 16) or directly through evidence in the nest (presence of eggs, chicks or juveniles). This allowed to identify clusters of nests spread across the study area that, based on expert knowledge (i.e. fieldwork specialists opinion), were defined as potential breeding territories for each target species. To confirm/validate this information, we analysed the spatial distribution of occupied nests over the years, and only areas with nests occupied simultaneously in the same year were assumed to be independent breeding territories (i.e. separate breeding pairs/colonies). All analysis were performed using QGIS software (QGIS Development Team, 2020).

Metrics selection

Temporal trends in breeding occurrence and breeding productivity of Golden eagles, Egyptian vultures and Griffon vultures were plotted between 2010 and 2021, in which:

Breeding occurrence = nr. of occupied breeding territories/ nr of available breeding territories

Breeding productivity = nr of flying juveniles / nr of breeding pairs

Note: Complementary observations were used to complete data from systematic observations between 2010 and 2014, namely for the estimation of n°. of occupied breeding territories and nr. of flying juveniles.

Statistical analyses

Generalized linear mixed models (GLMMs) were implemented in order to relate breeding occurrence and productivity of Golden eagles, Egyptian vultures and Griffon vultures with periods of pre- and post-dam construction, across breeding territories subjected to a gradient of disturbance created by this infrastructure. For this, the proportion of flooded area in a buffer of 2 km and 5 km around breeding territories was calculated (i.e. mean flooded area for all nests identified per breeding territory), and included in the final database as an indirect measure of the dam potential impact in the breeding activities of cliff nesting bird species. We tested the general hypothesis that temporal bird reproductive trends were more favourable (i.e., more positive or less negative) in the control (breeding territories with less proportion of flooded area in their surroundings), using a procedure akin to a BACI (Before–After–Control–Impact) design with multiple sites and years (Smith, 2006). We modelled breeding occurrence (presence/absence of confirmed nesting per breeding territory) and breeding productivity (number of flying juveniles per number of breeding pairs per breeding territory) against proportion of flooded area (control vs impact), sampling period (2010-2014 vs. 2015 vs 2021), and their interaction (Table A1). The main focus was on the interaction term, which indicated whether the trend observed was above (positive coefficient) or below (negative coefficient) that expected from the trend observed in the control.

Table A1 - Fixed component of the alternative GLMM candidate models used for model inference, and corresponding ecological effects. FLOODED_AREA = % of flooded area per breeding territory; BA = 2010-2014 versus 2015-2021.

Alternative models	Ecological effects
$H1 g1 = \beta0$	No effects (null model)
$H2 g2 = \beta0 + \beta1$ (FLOODED_AREA)	Flooded area
$H3 g3 = \beta0 + \beta1$ (BA)	Period
$H4 g4 = \beta0 + \beta1$ (FLOODED_AREA)+ $\beta2$ (BA)	Flooded area and period
$H5 g5 = \beta0 + \beta1$ (FLOODED_AREA)+ $\beta2$ (BA)+ $\beta3$ (FLOODED_AREA * BA)	Flooded area, period and interaction effects (full model)

GLMMs were used to account for lack of independence among samples, i.e. assuming breeding territories and sampling year as random effects (Pinheiro and Bates, 2000). Particularly, a binomial variance distribution (with log link function) was used to model breeding occurrence for all three target species. In the case of breeding productivity, we applied a Poisson distribution (with log link function) for Golden eagles (i.e. number of flying juveniles per breeding pair), whereas a Gamma distribution (with log link function) was fitted to assess the GLMM models supporting the Egyptian and Griffon vulture data (number of flying juveniles per number of breeding pairs). All explanatory variables were considered and the full model was selected (Burnham and Anderson, 2002). Model building was based on the information theoretic approach, and inference was based on model averaging (Burnham & Anderson 2002). For each dependent variable we calculated: (1) model probabilities (w_i) for all five candidate models (Table A1), based on AIC; (2) model average of each coefficient among models; and (3) 95% confidence intervals (CI) for each model averaged coefficient from unconditional variances (Burnham & Anderson 2002). All analysis were performed using R software (R Development Core Team, 2020).

Results

Definition of breeding territories

Only data obtained from 2015 onwards was used to identify bird breeding territories due to a more stable and complete overview of nesting areas within the study area (i.e. inside and outside the eLTER Site boundaries). Overall, we identified 10 breeding territories of Golden eagles, 8 territories of Egyptian vultures and 10 territories of Griffon vultures (Figure A2). Analyses of the spatial distribution of nests used by each species over the years are displayed in Appendix A1.

Figure A2 - Location of breeding territories of Golden eagles, Egyptian vultures and Griffon vultures in the study area between 2015 and 2021.

Cliff nesting birds temporal trends

Taking into account a significant decrease in the number of visits to nests due to fieldwork restrictions during the pandemic, data from 2020 were excluded from the analyses (Table A2).

Table A2 - Number of sampling days included in cliff-nesting birds surveys, discriminated by year.

year	Nr. of sampling days
2010	27
2011	46
2012	42
2013	53
2014	25
2015	25
2016	42
2017	37
2018	34
2019	31
2020	10
2021	31

Results show a relatively stable pattern in breeding occurrence of Golden eagles and Egyptian vultures over the years, along with an apparent reduction in breeding productivity from 2014 onwards (marked in blue, Figure A3). In the case of Griffon vultures, both breeding occurrence and productivity show a clear pattern of increase throughout time (marked in yellow, Figure A3).

Figure A3 - Temporal trends in breeding occurrence (upper panel) and breeding productivity (lower panel) of cliff-nesting bird species (Golden eagles, Egyptian vultures and Griffon vultures) between 2010 and 2021. Dots represent mean values \pm standard error (minimum and maximum) as bars.

Statistical outputs

Statistical results suggest a significant positive relationship between Griffon vultures' breeding occurrence and productivity and the period after the dam installation (i.e. operation phase) (marked in yellow, Table A3). However, the lack of a significant interaction between the before/after periods and the proportion of flooded area around breeding territories does not seem to indicate a direct relationship between the observed patterns and the influence of the dam. On the other hand, for Golden eagles and Egyptian vultures, a significant interaction between these two factors (at both 2km and 5km spatial scales) suggest a potential effect of this infrastructure in the breeding productivity of these species (marked in blue, Table A3). In particular, for Golden eagles, the positive interaction between the before/after periods and the proportion of flooded area around breeding territories suggest that, despite a decrease in breeding productivity towards areas more affected by the dam (i.e. higher proportion of flooded area), this pattern has been similar in both periods before and after the dam installation (Figure A4). These results do not support a potential negative effect of this infrastructure in the breeding productivity of this species. On the other hand, for Egyptian vultures, a decrease in breeding productivity after the dam installation (as opposed to an increasing trend towards affected areas before the dam construction) suggests a negative impact of this infrastructure in this particular species (Figure A4). Comparative results among candidate models are shown in Appendix A2. Charts of model probabilities for breeding occurrence and productivity of the three target species are shown in Appendix A3.

Table A3 - GLMM regression coefficients (full model) relating breeding occurrence and productivity of Golden eagles, Egyptian vultures and Griffon vultures with sampling period (BA; 2010–2014 vs. 2015–2021), proportion of flooded area around breeding territory (FLOODED_AREA), and an interaction term (BA:FLOODED_AREA). Model statistics (Log Likelihood, Akaike Information Criteria, Bayesian Information Criteria, Chi-square of Random effects and of Full model) are also presented.

	Golden eagle 2km	Golden eagle 5km	Egyptian vulture 2 km	Egyptian vulture 5 km	Griffon vulture 2 km	Griffon vulture 5 km
BREEDING OCCURRENCE						
Intercept	0.44	0.69	-1.89	-1.06	-4.98	-5.21*
BA	0.08	-0.20	1.60	0.76	4.91	5.35*
FLOODED_AREA	-4.95	-12.79	27.08	24.08	23.66	50.88
BA:FLOODED_AREA	4.86	13.48	-22.03	-16.18	2.76	-4.13
Observations	90.00	90.00	73.00	73.00	90.00	90
Groups (year, territory)	11,10	11,10	11,8	11,8	11,10	11,10
Log Likelihood	-59.10	-58.30	-46.20	-46.80	-42.30	-41.70
Akaike Inf. Crit.	130.20	128.60	104.30	105.50	96.60	95.50
Bayesian Inf. Crit.	145.20	143.60	118.10	119.30	111.60	110.50
Chisq (Random effects)	1.96	2.10	3.21	3.00	0.0004672***	10.75**
Chisq (Full Model)	2.11	3.75	3.81	2.60	15.39**	16.55***
PRODUCTIVITY						
Intercept	-0.43***	-0.27***	0.10	0.20	-0.17	-0.02
BA	-0.79***	-0.98***	-0.03	-0.13	0.40*	0.23*
FLOODED_AREA	-2.85***	-8.21***	3.06	2.44	2.21	0.67
BA:FLOODED_AREA	1.18***	6.68***	-3.72***	-3.19*	-2.07	0.02
Observations	90.00	90.00	73.00	73.00	90.00	90
Groups (year, territory)	11,10	11,10	11,8	11,8	11,10	11,10
Log Likelihood	-70.6	-70	-0.1	-2.2	-4.3	-5
Akaike Inf. Crit.	153.10	152	14.2	18.4	22.5	23.9
Bayesian Inf. Crit.	168.10	167	30.3	34.4	40	41.4
Chisq (Random effects)	1.37	1.37	21.13***	20.99***	20.74***	18.92***
Chisq (Full Model)	3.31	4.40	14.57**	10.42*	5.64	4.22

Figure A4 - Model predicted probabilities (interaction term BA:FLOODED_AREA) of the breeding occurrence and productivity of Golden eagles (left) and Egyptian vultures (right) in relation to sampling period (Before in red; After in blue) and proportion of flooded area around breeding territory (FLOODED_AREA). Shaded zones represent variation around the mean (i.e. 95% confidence intervals).

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Appendix A1 - Spatial distribution of occupied nests by Golden eagles, Egyptian vultures and Griffon vultures over the years (2015-2020), inside (1) and outside (2) the Baixo-Sabor eLTER Site boundaries.

Location of breeding territories of Golden eagles, Egyptian vultures and Griffon vultures in the study area between 2015 and 2021.

Appendix A2 - Comparative results among the 5 candidate models used for model inference of breeding occurrence and breeding productivity of Golden eagles, Egyptian vultures and Griffon vultures, before and after the dam installation (BA_01), using proportion of flooded area in a buffer of 2 km and 5 km around breeding territories (prp_fla_2km; prp_fla_5km).

Golden eagle

Breeding occurrence

2 km

Model selection table

	(Int)	BA_01	prp_fla_2km	BA_01:prp_fla_2km	df	logLik	AIC	delta	weight
1	3.162e-01				3	-60.170	126.3	0.00	0.407
3	4.631e-01			-2.139	4	-59.799	127.6	1.26	0.217
2	3.090e-06	0.51460			4	-59.813	127.6	1.29	0.214
4	1.686e-01	0.45030		-1.879	5	-59.533	129.1	2.73	0.104
8	4.368e-01	0.08392		-4.947	4.863 6	-59.115	130.2	3.89	0.058

Models ranked by AIC(x)

Random terms (all models):

1 | year, 1 | territorio

5 km

Model selection table

	(Int)	BA_01	prp_fla_5km	BA_01:prp_fla_5km	df	logLik	AIC	delta	weight
1	3.162e-01				3	-60.170	126.3	0.00	0.358
3	5.033e-01			-4.312	4	-59.610	127.2	0.88	0.230
2	3.090e-06	0.5146			4	-59.813	127.6	1.29	0.188
8	6.930e-01	-0.1982		-12.790	13.48 6	-58.294	128.6	2.25	0.116
4	2.200e-01	0.4316		-3.891	5	-59.367	128.7	2.39	0.108

Models ranked by AIC(x)

Random terms (all models):

1 | year, 1 | territorio

Breeding productivity

2km

Model selection table

	(Int)	BA_01	prp_fla_2km	BA_01:prp_fla_2km	df	logLik	AIC	delta	weight
2	-0.6528	-0.6509			4	-71.188	150.4	0.00	0.291
1	-1.0510				3	-72.211	150.4	0.04	0.285
4	-0.4672	-0.7292		-2.301	5	-70.591	151.2	0.81	0.195
3	-0.9435			-1.829	4	-71.819	151.6	1.26	0.155
8	-0.4281	-0.7943		-2.854	1.18 6	-70.557	153.1	2.74	0.074

Models ranked by AIC(x)

Random terms (all models):

1 | year, 1 | territorio

5 km

Model selection table

	(Int)	BA_01 prp_fla_5km	BA_01:prp_fla_5km	df	logLik	AIC	delta	weight	
2	-0.6528	-0.6509		4	-71.188	150.4	0.00	0.258	
1	-1.0510			3	-72.211	150.4	0.04	0.252	
4	-0.4221	-0.7495	-4.590	5	-70.371	150.7	0.37	0.215	
3	-0.9167		-3.686	4	-71.654	151.3	0.93	0.162	
8	-0.2731	-0.9812	-8.209	6.679	6	-70.012	152.0	1.65	0.113

Models ranked by AIC(x)

Random terms (all models):

1 | year, 1 | territorio

Egyptian vulture

Breeding occurrence

2 km

Model selection table

	(Int)	BA_01 prp_fla_2km	BA_01:prp_fla_2km	df	logLik	AIC	delta	weight	
1	-0.1029			3	-48.062	102.1	0.00	0.368	
3	-0.5327		9.494	4	-47.375	102.8	0.63	0.269	
2	-0.1344	0.0455		4	-48.058	104.1	1.99	0.136	
8	-1.8910	1.5970	27.080	-22.03	6	-46.157	104.3	2.19	0.113
4	-0.6907	0.1921	10.060		5	-47.320	104.6	2.52	0.105

Models ranked by AIC(x)

Random terms (all models):

1 | year, 1 | territorio

5 km

Model selection table

	(Int)	BA_01 prp_fla_5km	BA_01:prp_fla_5km	df	logLik	AIC	delta	weight	
1	-0.1029			3	-48.062	102.1	0.00	0.380	
3	-0.4629		12.28	4	-47.309	102.6	0.49	0.297	
2	-0.1344	0.0455		4	-48.058	104.1	1.99	0.140	
4	-0.5918	0.1665	12.77	5	-47.266	104.5	2.41	0.114	
8	-1.0580	0.7556	24.08	-16.18	6	-46.762	105.5	3.40	0.069

Models ranked by AIC(x)

Random terms (all models):

1 | year, 1 | territorio

Breeding productivity

2km

Model selection table

(Int)	BA_01	prp_fla_2km	BA_01:prp_fla_2km	df	logLik	AIC	delta	weight	
8	0.1022	-0.02549	3.0640	-3.717	7	-0.117	14.2	0.00	0.927
2	0.3243	-0.27130			5	-5.259	20.5	6.28	0.040
4	0.3136	-0.27150	0.2830		6	-5.239	22.5	8.24	0.015
1	0.1913				4	-7.403	22.8	8.57	0.013
3	0.1860		0.1339		5	-7.399	24.8	10.56	0.005

Models ranked by AIC(x)

Random terms (all models):

1 | year, 1 | territorio

5 km

Model selection table

(Int)	BA_01	prp_fla_5km	BA_01:prp_fla_5km	df	logLik	AIC	delta	weight	
8	0.2019	-0.1304	2.4380	-3.19	7	-2.194	18.4	0.00	0.616
2	0.3243	-0.2713			5	-5.259	20.5	2.13	0.212
4	0.3160	-0.2714	0.3310		6	-5.241	22.5	4.09	0.079
1	0.1913				4	-7.403	22.8	4.42	0.068
3	0.1870		0.1765		5	-7.398	24.8	6.41	0.025

Models ranked by AIC(x)

Random terms (all models):

1 | year, 1 | territorio

Griffon vultures

Breeding occurrence

2km

Model selection table

(Int)	BA_01	prp_fla_2km	BA_01:prp_fla_2km	df	logLik	AIC	delta	weight	
4	-5.1920	5.136	26.11		5	-42.318	94.6	0.00	0.436
2	-3.8530	5.005			4	-43.406	94.8	0.18	0.399
8	-4.9800	4.907	23.66	2.76	6	-42.313	96.6	1.99	0.161
1	-0.9843				3	-50.006	106.0	11.38	0.001
3	-2.1800		24.46		4	-49.115	106.2	11.59	0.001

Models ranked by AIC(x)

Random terms (all models):

1 | year, 1 | territorio

5 km

Model selection table

	(Int)	BA_01	prp_fIA_5km	BA_01:prp_fIA_5km	df	logLik	AIC	delta	weight	
4	-5.0110	5.126		47.52	5	-41.737	93.5	0.00	0.530	
2	-3.8530	5.005			4	-43.406	94.8	1.34	0.271	
8	-5.2070	5.346		50.88	-4.133	6	-41.730	95.5	1.99	0.196
3	-2.0640			45.94	4	-48.551	105.1	11.63	0.002	
1	-0.9843				3	-50.006	106.0	12.54	0.001	

Models ranked by AIC(x)

Random terms (all models):

1 | year, 1 | territorio

Breeding productivity

2 km

Model selection table

	(Int)	BA_01	prp_fIA_2km	BA_01:prp_fIA_2km	df	logLik	AIC	delta	weight	
2	-0.00183	0.2338			5	-5.088	20.2	0.00	0.451	
4	-0.01912	0.2352		0.3521	6	-5.022	22.0	1.87	0.177	
1	0.11150				4	-7.084	22.2	1.99	0.167	
8	-0.17470	0.3988		2.2100	-2.071	7	-4.264	22.5	2.35	0.139
3	0.09525			0.3427	5	-7.021	24.0	3.87	0.065	

Models ranked by AIC(x)

Random terms (all models):

1 | year, 1 | territorio

5 km

Model selection table

	(Int)	BA_01	prp_fIA_5km	BA_01:prp_fIA_5km	df	logLik	AIC	delta	weight	
2	-0.00183	0.2338			5	-5.088	20.2	0.00	0.480	
4	-0.01753	0.2350		0.6889	6	-4.974	21.9	1.77	0.198	
1	0.11150				4	-7.084	22.2	1.99	0.177	
3	0.09683			0.6709	5	-6.973	23.9	3.77	0.073	
8	-0.01691	0.2342		0.6746	0.01999	7	-4.974	23.9	3.77	0.073

Models ranked by AIC(x)

Random terms (all models):

1 | year, 1 | territorio

Appendix A3 - Model predicted probabilities (interaction term BA:FLOODED_AREA) of the breeding occurrence and productivity of Golden eagles, Egyptian vultures and Griffon vultures in relation to sampling period (Before in red; After in blue) and proportion of flooded area around breeding territory (Proportion flooded area in 2km/5km). Shaded zones represent variation around the mean (i.e. 95% confidence intervals).

6.2. Appendix B

Appendix B - Detailed description of the methods and results of Case study 2 - Doñana eLTER Site - 'Understand how changes in freshwater flow and inundation affect the diversity and abundance of waterbird communities, and predict the future suitability of Mediterranean wetlands to form critical breeding and wintering habitats'.

Methodology

BIODIVERSITY DATA

Database: Doñana_Aquatic_Birds_Aerial_Census_1973_2021 (Provided by Ricardo Díaz-Delgado – site manager - in March 2022)

Description: Data was obtained from monthly aerial surveys recording the presence and abundance of all species of waterbirds in the study area.

Sampling strategy: Depending on the census, the observers have identified flocks for one bigger plot, including several subplots. Overall, birds were quantified according to a 3-scale nested approach:

- 58 plots (smaller scale): The most detailed scale. Includes all the smallest plots for which a record can be found in the dataset. When a record starts by "NA_" or "NA_NA_" refers to a bigger plot represented by the other scales (the intermediate and broader scales, respectively).

- 24 plots (intermediate scale): It merges some of the plots from the smaller scale (58 plots) in bigger plots (i.e. the observation was made for a larger plot). When a record starts by "NA_" refers to a bigger plot represented by the broader scale (4 plots).

- 4 plots (broader scale): The broadest limits for which a record can be assigned. It merges many plots from the other scales. Observations refer to the whole area covered by this large plots.

Data period: 1973-2021

Data measurements: The flight path used in waterbird aerial surveys is about 450 kilometres long (following the same route whenever possible). In general, if a large number of birds is not observed, linear routes are carried out. Otherwise, a circular trajectory is performed so that birds take off and identification of species and estimation of flock size can be easily recorded. The flight speed oscillates between 150 and 200 km/h, depending on the direction and speed of the wind, and the flight is never less than 50 meters nor greater than 300 meters in height. The flight takes place in the morning, as soon as possible after sunrise, usually between 10 am and 1 pm, depending on weather conditions (i.e. visibility and wind). For safety reasons, censuses cannot be carried out in rain, persistent fog or strong wind. (Román and Vilà, 2014).

Data analysis

Metrics selection

Waterbird species were aggregated by functional traits, discriminated by species richness and density of individuals. Waterbird data analysis comprehended data from 1984 onwards, corresponding to a systematization of the census in terms of monitoring periodicity (i.e. months) and sampled plots across the study area (i.e. 58 plots) (Román and Vilà, 2014). We selected the intermediate sampling spatial scale (i.e. 24 plots) to relate seasonal variation of waterbirds diversity and density with habitat features (Figure B1).

Figure B1 - Location of the 24 plots used for waterbirds analysis on the Doñana eLTER Site, discriminated by sectors based on principal habitat-types.

In terms of area, the plots with greater proportion of area (across the study area) are ‘Arrozales de Puebla e Isla Mayor’ and ‘Veta de la Palma’, whereas ‘Partido’, ‘Marismas del Rocio’, ‘Lucio de la Fao’, ‘Lagunas RBD’, ‘Dehesa de Abajo’ and ‘Brazo de la Torre y Cantaritas’ are the smallest plots in the study area (Figure V2; Appendix B1).

Figure B2 - Proportion of area occupied by each plot considered in the waterbird analysis.

The following criterion was used: a) all records sampled from December to February were assumed in Winter; b) all records sampled between March and May were assumed in Spring; c) all records sampled between June and August were assumed in Summer; and d) all records sampled between September and November were assumed in Autumn. Environmental parameters (i.e. Land use, Normalized Difference Vegetation Index and flooded area) were used to investigate potential relationships between waterbird diversity/density and abiotic conditions.

Waterbird classification

Waterbird species were aggregated by habitat-related functional traits. Seven functional groups were considered, according to the criteria used by Ramírez et al. (2018): Dabbling ducks, Diving birds, Fishing birds, Large Wading birds, Raptors, Small Wading birds, and Vegetation Gleaners.

Since raptor species do not represent wetland-specific related guilds (the focus of our analysis), this group was not considered in the analysis. Furthermore, since vegetation gleaners were represented by only 2 species (Table B1), functional diversity of this functional group was not considered sufficiently representative to capture changes in wetland-related habitats, thus being discarded from the analysis. Overall, from a total of 43 species, Dabbling Ducks, Large Wading birds and Small Wading birds were the groups encompassing more diversity of species, followed by Fishing and Diving birds (Figure B3). All waterbird species, discriminated by functional groups, are listed in Table B1.

Figure B3 - Species richness (number of species) of functional groups considered in the waterbird analysis.

Table B1 - List of waterbird species, discriminated by functional group.

Functional Group	Species	Functional Group	Species
Dabbling ducks	<i>Anas acuta</i>	Large wading birds	<i>Ardea alba</i>
	<i>Anas crecca</i>		<i>Ardea cinerea</i>
	<i>Anas platyrhynchos</i>		<i>Ardeola ralloides</i>
	<i>Anatidae</i>		<i>Bubulcus/Egretta</i>
	<i>Anser anser</i>		<i>Ciconia ciconia</i>
	<i>Mareca penelope</i>		<i>Ciconia nigra</i>
	<i>Mareca strepera</i>		<i>Grus grus</i>
	<i>Marmaronetta angustirostris</i>		<i>Phoenicopterus roseus</i>
	<i>Spatula clypeata</i>		<i>Platalea leucorodia</i>
	<i>Spatula querquedula</i>		<i>Plegadis falcinellus</i>
Diving birds	<i>Tadorna tadorna</i>	Small wading birds	<i>Charadrius/Calidris</i>
	<i>Aythya ferina</i>		<i>Himantopus himantopus</i>
	<i>Aythya fuligula</i>		<i>Limosa limosa</i>
	<i>Netta rufina</i>		<i>Pluvialis apricaria</i>
	<i>Podiceps nigricollis</i>		<i>Pluvialis squatarola</i>
Fishing birds	<i>Sternula albifrons</i>		<i>Recurvirostra avosetta</i>
	<i>Chlidonias hybrida</i>		<i>Tringa nebularia</i>
	<i>Chlidonias niger</i>		<i>Tringa ochropus</i>
	<i>Chroicocephalus</i>		<i>Tringa totanus/erythropus</i>
	<i>Gelochelidon nilotica</i>		<i>Vanellus vanellus</i>
	<i>Hydrocoloeus minutus</i>	Vegetation gleaners	<i>Fulica atra</i>
	<i>Larus michaelis/fuscus</i>		<i>Porphyrio porphyrio</i>
	<i>Phalacrocorax carbo</i>		

A total of 99029 waterbird records were present in the dataset (Table B2). Of these, 21% were obtained in Autumn, 27% in Spring, 16% in Summer and 35% in Winter (Table B2). Among sampled plots, ‘Veta de la Palma’ was the area with greater proportion of records in all seasons, whereas ‘Partido’ was the plot with lower proportion of records (Appendix B2).

Table B2 - Total number of waterbird records, discriminated by functional group and season.

Functional Group	Autumn	Spring	Summer	Winter	Total
Dabbling ducks	6586	6083	1686	15696	30051
Diving birds	671	2407	664	1907	5649
Fishing birds	2660	2865	1715	3562	10802
Large wading birds	7998	11948	9493	9342	38781
Small wading birds	3290	3687	2630	4139	13746
Total	21205 (21%)	26990 (27%)	16188 (16%)	34646 (35%)	99029 (100%)

Biodiversity metrics

i) Species richness per functional trait, corresponding to the number of species (per functional trait) present in a given plot per season per year;

ii) **Density of individuals per functional trait**, corresponding to the number of individuals (per functional trait) present in a given plot (per hectare) per season per year.

ABIOTIC DATA

Databases:

DATABASE:

Land use data: MUCVA (1977, 1984, 1999, 2003, 2007); SIOSEA (2005, 2009, 2011, 2013, 2016); SIPNA 2020 (Provided by Ricardo Díaz-Delgado – site manager - in March 2022)

Hydrological and vegetation data: Inundation raster files 1974-2020 (Provided by Ricardo Díaz-Delgado - site manager - in March 2022); Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) raster files 1974-2020 (Provided by Ricardo Díaz-Delgado in March 2022).

Description:

Land use data: This database includes a set of Land Use maps (i.e. MUCVA, SIOSEA and SIPNA) for the region of Andalucía.

Hydrological and vegetation data: This data includes a set of inundation and NDVI raster files to reconstruct historical spatial and temporal patterns of marshes flooding and vegetation dynamics in the Doñana region.

Sampling strategy:

Land use data: Photointerpretation and cartography of the main land use types present in the study area. Specifically, MUCVA includes LU characterization for the years of 1977, 1984, 1999, 2003, and 2007; SIOSEA for the years of 2005, 2009, 2011, 2013, and 2016; and SIPNA for 2020 (for more details see: MUCVA products in https://portalrediam.cica.es/caracterizacion_vegetacion/mapa_usos.html; SIOSEA products in https://www.juntadeandalucia.es/medioambiente/portal/landing-page-mapa/-/asset_publisher/wO880PprC6q7/content/mapa-de-ocupaci-c3-b3n-del-suelo-en-andaluc-c3-ada.-siose-andaluc-c3-ada/20151); SIPNA products in <http://www.ideandalucia.es/catalogo/inspire/srv/api/records/1a4d79ae-7a62-42a7-9159-0721624b5784>).

Hydrological and vegetation data: Produced from Landsat TM, ETM+ and OLI images, inundation and NDVI raster files are presented every 2 weeks (16 days) before 1991, and up to 1 image every 8 days after 1991 (from L5/L7 and since 2018 L7/L8). Since cloud cover images were discarded, months without available information are more frequent during winter. For more details see Díaz-Delgado et al. (2016).

Data period:

Land Use data: 1977-2020

Hydrological and vegetation data: 1974-2020

Land Use categorization and harmonization

Land Use maps available for Doñana were harmonized in terms of coherence of land use classes among different products (i.e. MUCVA, SIOSEA and SIPNA). In order to harmonize information, MUCVA was set as the reference product. Therefore, the SIOSEA and SIPNA products were reclassified according to the MUCVA categorization (Table B3, class 1). Harmonized LU maps

among products/years were then created and reclassified into 11 aggregated LU classes (Table B3, class 2), assumed as suitable to capture modifications in waterbirds diversity and density across the study area.

Table B3 - Land use classes used to characterize the Doñana eLTER Site (class 1) and aggregated classes used for waterbird analysis (class 2).

Class1 (MUCVA/SIOSEA/SIPNA)	Class 2	Class1 (MUCVA/SIOSEA/SIPNA)	Class 2
FOR. ARBOL. DENSA: QUERCINEAS	Forestry areas	SALINAS INDUST. Y PARQUES DE CULTIVOS	Industrial salt pans and fish ponds
FOR. ARBOL. DENSA: CONIFERAS	Forestry areas	MARISMA MAREAL CON VEGETACION	Marshes
FOR. ARBOL. DENSA: EUCALIPTOS	Forestry areas	MARISMA NO MAREAL CON VEGETACION	Marshes
FOR. ARBOL. DENSA: OTRAS FRONDOSAS	Forestry areas	MARISMA RECIENTE SIN VEGETACION	Marshes
FOR. ARBOL. DENSA: QUERCINEAS+CONIFERAS	Forestry areas	SALINAS TRADICIONALES	Marshes
FOR. ARBOL. DENSA: CONIFERAS+EUCALIPTOS	Forestry areas	PASTIZAL CONTINUO	Natural grasslands
FOR. ARBOL. DENSA: OTRAS MEZCLAS	Forestry areas	PASTIZAL CON CLAROS (ROCA, SUELO)	Natural grasslands
MATORRAL DENSO ARBOLADO: QUERCINEAS DENSA	Forestry areas	MATORRAL DENSO	Natural shrublands
MATORRAL DENSO ARBOLADO: QUERCINEAS DISPERS.	Forestry areas	MATORRAL DISPERSO CON PASTIZAL	Natural shrublands
MATORRAL DENSO ARBOLADO: CONIFERAS DENSA	Forestry areas	MATORRAL DISPERSO CON PASTO Y ROCA O SUELO	Natural shrublands
MATORRAL DENSO ARBOLADO: CONIFERAS DISPERSA	Forestry areas	ARROZALES	Rice fields
MATORRAL DENSO ARBOLADO: EUCALIPTOS	Forestry areas	RIOS Y CAUCES NAT.:LAMINA DE AGUA	Rivers and riparian galleries
MATORRAL DENSO ARBOLADO: OTRAS FRONDOSAS	Forestry areas	RIOS Y CAUCES NAT.:BOSQUE GALERIA	Rivers and riparian galleries
MATORRAL DENSO ARBOLADO: QUERCINEAS+CONIFERAS	Forestry areas	RIOS Y CAUCES NAT.:OTRAS FORM. RIPARIAS	Rivers and riparian galleries
MATORRAL DENSO ARBOLADO: CONIFERAS+EUCALIPTOS	Forestry areas	LAGUNAS CONTINENTALES	Rivers and riparian galleries
MATORRAL DENSO ARBOLADO: OTRAS MEZCLAS	Forestry areas	BALSAS DE RIEGO Y GANADERAS	Rivers and riparian galleries
MATORRAL DISP. ARBOLADO: QUERCINEAS. DENSO	Forestry areas	ESTUARIOS Y CANALES DE MAREA	Rivers and riparian galleries
MATORRAL DISP. ARBOLADO: QUERCINEAS. DISPERSO	Forestry areas	CANALES ARTIFICIALES	Rivers and riparian galleries
MATORRAL DISP. ARBOLADO: CONIFERAS. DENSO	Forestry areas	EMBALSES: LAMINA DE AGUA	Rivers and riparian galleries
MATORRAL DISP. ARBOLADO: CONIFERAS. DISPERSO	Forestry areas	TEJIDO URBANO	Urban areas
MATORRAL DISP. ARBOLADO: EUCALIPTOS	Forestry areas	URBANIZACIONES RESIDENCIALES	Urban areas
MATORRAL DISP. ARBOLADO: OTRAS FRONDOSAS	Forestry areas	URBANIZACIONES AGRICOLA /RESIDENCIALES	Urban areas
MATORRAL DISP. ARBOLADO: QUERCINEAS+CONIFERAS	Forestry areas	ZONAS INDUSTRIALES Y COMERCIALES	Urban areas
MATORRAL DISP. ARBOLADO: QUERCINEAS+EUCALIPTOS	Forestry areas	AUTOVIAS, AUTOPISTAS Y ENLACES VIARIOS	Urban areas
MATORRAL DISP. ARBOLADO: CONIFERAS+EUCALIPTOS	Forestry areas	ZONAS PORTUARIAS	Urban areas
MATORRAL DISP. ARBOLADO: OTRAS MEZCLAS	Forestry areas	OTRAS INFRAESTRUCTURAS TECNICAS	Urban areas
PASTIZAL ARBOLADO: QUERCINEAS. DENSO	Forestry areas	ZONAS MINERAS	Urban areas
PASTIZAL ARBOLADO: QUERCINEAS. DISPERSO	Forestry areas	ZONAS EN CONSTRUCCION	Urban areas
PASTIZAL ARBOLADO: CONIFERAS. DENSO	Forestry areas	ZONAS VERDES URBANAS	Urban areas
PASTIZAL ARBOLADO: CONIFERAS. DISPERSO	Forestry areas	EQUIPAMIENTO DEPORTIVO Y RECREATIVO	Urban areas
PASTIZAL ARBOLADO: EUCALIPTOS	Forestry areas	AEROPUERTOS	Urban areas
PASTIZAL ARBOLADO: OTRAS FRONDOSAS	Forestry areas	ESCOMBRERAS Y VERTEDEROS	Urban areas
PASTIZAL ARBOLADO: QUERCINEAS+CONIFERAS	Forestry areas	COMPLEJOS FERROVIARIOS	Urban areas
PASTIZAL ARBOLADO: QUERCINEAS+EUCALIPTOS	Forestry areas	CULTIVOS LEÑOSOS EN SECANO: OLIVAR	Woody crops
PASTIZAL ARBOLADO: CONIFERAS+EUCALIPTOS	Forestry areas	CULTIVOS LEÑOSOS EN SECANO: VIÑEDO	Woody crops
PASTIZAL ARBOLADO: OTRAS MEZCLAS	Forestry areas	OTROS CULTIVOS LEÑOSOS EN SECANO	Woody crops
CULTIVO HERBACEO ARBOLADO: QUERCINEAS. DISPERSO	Forestry areas	CULTIVOS LEÑOSOS EN REGADIO: PARCIALMENTE REGADOS	Woody crops
TALAS Y PLANTACIONES FORESTALES RECIENTES	Forestry areas	CULTIVOS LEÑOSOS REGADOS: CITRICOS	Woody crops
FOR. ARBOL. DENSA: QUERCINEAS+EUCALIPTOS	Forestry areas	CULTIVOS LEÑOSOS REGADOS: OLIVOS	Woody crops
CULTIVO HERBACEO ARBOLADO: QUERCINEAS. DENSO	Forestry areas	OTROS CULTIVOS LEÑOSOS REGADOS	Woody crops
CULTIVOS HERBACEOS EN SECANO	Herbaceous crops	OLIVAR-VIÑEDO	Woody crops
OTROS CULTIVOS HERBACEOS REGADOS	Herbaceous crops	OTRAS ASOCIACIONES Y MOSAICOS DE CULTIVOS LEÑOSOS	Woody crops
CULTIVOS HERBACEOS EN REGADIO: REGADOS Y NO REGADOS	Herbaceous crops	MOSAICO DE LEÑOSOS EN REGADIO	Woody crops
CULTIVOS HERBACEOS EN REGADIO: NO REGADOS	Herbaceous crops	CULTIVOS LEÑOSOS Y PASTIZALES	Woody crops
CULTIVOS HERBACEOS Y LEÑOSOS EN SECANO	Herbaceous crops	CULTIVOS LEÑOSOS Y VEGETACION NATURAL LEÑOSA	Woody crops
MOSAICO DE SECANO Y REGADIO CON CULTIVOS HERBACEOS	Herbaceous crops	OLIVAR ABANDONADO	Woody crops
MOSAICO DE SECANO Y REGADIO CON CULTIVOS HERBACEOS	Herbaceous crops	OTROS CULTIVOS LEÑOSOS ABANDONADOS	Woody crops
MOSAICO DE SECANO Y REGADIO CON CULTIVOS LEÑOSOS	Herbaceous crops		
CULTIVOS HERBACEOS Y PASTIZALES	Herbaceous crops		
CULTIVOS HERBACEOS Y VEGETACION NATURAL LEÑOSA	Herbaceous crops		
OTROS MOSAICOS DE CULTIVOS Y VEGETACION NATURAL LEÑOSA	Herbaceous crops		
CULTIVOS HERBACEOS Y LEÑOSOS EN REGADIO PARCIALMENTE REGADOS	Herbaceous crops		
CULTIVOS HERBACEOS Y LEÑOSOS REGADOS	Herbaceous crops		

Due to the lack of intra- and inter-annual variation in LU products (for compatibility with seasonal waterbird data), waterbird data was characterized according to the most updated LU product available, i.e. MUCVA 1984 vs waterbird data 1984-1991; MUCVA 1999 vs waterbird data 1992-2001; MUCVA 2003 vs waterbird data 2002-2004; SIOSEA 2005 vs waterbird data 2005-2007; SIOSEA 2009 vs waterbird data 2008-2010; SIOSEA 2011 vs waterbird data 2011-2012; SIOSEA 2013 vs waterbird data 2013-2014; SIOSEA 2016 vs waterbird data 2015-2018; SIPNA 2010 vs waterbird data 2019-2020.

Hydrological and vegetation data categorization and harmonization

To reconstruct seasonal spatial and temporal patterns of marshes flooding and vegetation dynamics (from 1984 onwards for compatibility with waterbird data), the available Inundation and NDVI raster files were aggregated by season (i.e. mean value per pixel). Due to variations in the number of available raster files per season across years (due to satellite imagery availability), a minimum sampling of 3 months per season was considered suitable to encompass representativeness in variability of abiotic parameters within the season. Since this criterion (i.e. minimum sampling of 3 months per season) led us to a under representation of the years before 2000 (Appendix B3), a less conservative approach was used to overcome this bias, i.e. minimum sampling of 2 months per season, including the pool of all available raster files (Appendix B3 and Appendix B4). Values of NDVI and proportion of flooded area were then extracted per plot, based on the seasonal raster files created. The values extracted were proportion of flooded area (sum of pixels with water presence * area of pixel in ha / total area of plot in ha) and the mean, maximum, and standard deviation of NDVI. All analysis were performed using R software (R Development Core Team, 2020).

From a total of 504 raster files (for both hydrological and NDVI information) considered in the analysis (Appendix B4), 120 were used to characterize Autumn, 101 to characterize Spring, 180 to characterize Summer and 103 to characterize Winter (Table B4). On average, Autumn included 4 raster files per year (ranging from 2 to 10 raster files per year), Spring included 4 raster files per year (ranging from 2 to 11 raster files per year), Summer included 5 raster files per year (ranging from 2 to 11 raster files per year) and Winter included 4 raster files per year (ranging from 2 to 9 raster files per year) (Table B4).

Table B4 - Number of raster files used to characterize spatial-temporal abiotic conditions (hydrological and NDVI information) in the study area.

Season	Total nr of raster files	Average nr of raster files per year	Minimum nr of raster files	Maximum nr of raster files
Autumn	120	4.00	2	10
Spring	101	3.61	2	11
Summer	180	5.14	2	11
Winter	103	4.12	2	9
Total	504	4.27	2	11

Statistical analyses

To assess the effect of abiotic conditions on the waterbirds diversity and density, several variables were considered at the plot level. The model construction was preceded by a statistical procedure based on GLMs for parameter estimation, to test for seasonal cause-effect relationships between dependent and independent variables. The dependent variables correspond to the waterbird species richness and density of individuals per functional trait, whereas the independent variables are expressed by the percentage of area of each LU class considered (class 2 in Table B3), proportion of flooded area, and mean, maximum and standard deviation of NDVI, obtained at the plot level. In order to avoid high multicollinearity, the selected independent variables were tested for Spearman rho correlation coefficient and Variance Inflation Factors. Only predictors with Spearman rho correlation lower than 0.7 (Elith et al., 2006) and Generalized Variance Inflation Factor lower than

5 were considered in the analysis (Neter et al., 1996). For waterbird species richness, a Quasi-Poisson variance distribution (with log link function) was used, whereas for density of individuals, a Gamma distribution (with log link function) was fitted to assess the GLM models supporting the data. All explanatory variables were considered and the full model was selected (Burnham and Anderson, 2002). All analyses were performed using R software (R Development Core Team, 2020).

Future scenarios

In order to assess future impacts of land use changes, flooding regime and vegetation dynamics on the waterbirds communities of Doñana, two scenarios were created. For this, historical land use data was used to recreate future realistic changes in land use dynamics for each plot. Particularly, the degree of gains or losses of each LU class (in terms of proportion of area per plot) was calculated for the period between 1984 and 2020, using the formula:

$$\text{Annual } LU_i \text{ change rate/plot} = (1 + LU_i \text{ changing rate } 1984-2020)^{(1/\text{historical period})} - 1$$

$$LU_i \text{ changing rate } 1984-2020 = \text{proportion of } LU_i \text{ area in } 2020 / \text{proportion of } LU_i \text{ area in } 1984;$$

i = LU class (i.e. Forestry areas, herbaceous crops, woody crops, Industrial salt pans and fish ponds, Marshes, Natura grasslands, Natural shrublands, Rice fields or Rivers and riparian galleries); Note: losses = LU_i changing rate 1984-2020 < 1; gains = LU_i changing rate 1984-2020 > 1; in case of gains, final calculation of LU_i changing rate 1984-2020 = LU_i changing rate 1984-2020 - 1

Historical period – number of years considered in the analysis (i.e. 38 years)

In this way, future LU changes assume the historical continuity of LU trends at each plot, and were projected for 2040 assuming sequential incremental gains or losses from 2020 up to 2040, using the formula:

$$\text{proportion of } LU_i \text{ area in } t \text{ (Incremental losses)} = \text{proportion of } LU_i \text{ area in } (t-1) - \text{proportion of } LU_i \text{ area in } 2020 * \text{Annual } LU_i \text{ change rate/plot}$$

$$\text{proportion of } LU_i \text{ area in } t \text{ (Incremental gains)} = \text{proportion of } LU_i \text{ area in } (t-1) + \text{proportion of } LU_i \text{ area in } 2020 * \text{Annual } LU_i \text{ change rate/plot}$$

t = projection year (e.g. 2040)

Historical data on flooding regimes (i.e. proportion of flooded area per plot) was used in order to recreate realistic contrasting hydrological years for the future (i.e. ‘dry hydrological year’ and ‘regular hydrological year’). For this, we analysed seasonal variation in proportion of flooded area among historical years (based on the annual mean values for all 24 plots considered in the waterbird analysis), so that seasons (coming from different historical years) presenting the lower proportion of flooded area were used to characterize a ‘dry hydrological year’, whereas seasons (coming from different historical years) presenting the median proportion of flooded area were used to characterize a ‘regular hydrological year’. In this way, we were able to assign seasonal values of proportion of flooded area per plot, taking into account realistic ranges based on historical data. The ‘dry hydrological year’ aims to recreate an approximation to extreme climate events (i.e. drought events) in Doñana. Finally, we tested for seasonal cause-effect relationships between NDVI, Land Uses and proportion of flooded area (based on historical data), so that changes in land

uses and proportion of flooded area can produce automatic estimates of NDVI for the future. For this, we ran GLMs for parameter estimation, using a Gaussian variance distribution (with identity link function) to model the average and minimum NDVI, and a Gamma variance distribution (with log link function) to model the standard deviation of NDVI. All independent predictors (Land use classes and proportion of flooded area) were tested for multicollinearity, and only predictors with Spearman rho correlation lower than 0.7 (Elith et al., 2006) and Generalized Variance Inflation Factor lower than 5 were considered in the analysis (Neter et al., 1996). All explanatory variables were considered and the full model was selected (Burnham and Anderson, 2002). All analysis were performed using R software (R Development Core Team, 2020).

Spatial-temporal projections

The statistical models created were used to project spatial patterns of waterbird functional diversity and abundance for 2040, according to the future scenarios considered (i.e. ‘dry hydrological year’ and ‘regular hydrological year’). For this, seasonal waterbird estimates (i.e. species richness and density of individuals per functional trait) were obtained for each plot, and were projected taking into account all plots’ location (24 plots) across the study area. The density of individuals per hectare (model prediction) was transformed into the total abundance of individuals taking into account the area of each plot. For the purposes of comparing spatial results between the ‘dry hydrological year’ and the ‘regular hydrological year’, the colour range classes for species richness and abundance of individuals were standardized according to the maximum variation attained (i.e. between the ‘dry hydrological year’ and the ‘regular hydrological year’). While species richness was based on continuous individual classes for the number of species, abundance of individuals was based on natural breaks of the largest range attained. All analysis were performed using QGIS software (QGIS Development Team, 2020). Temporal variations (1984-2020) in waterbirds functional diversity (number of species per functional group) and abundance (number of individuals per functional group) were also plotted per season, including estimates for the future scenarios (2040) considered.

Results

Statistical outputs

Final database

Due to the availability of abiotic data to characterize waterbird records, the final dataset used in the statistical analysis comprehended a total of 7900 waterbird records, of which 25% were obtained in Autumn and Spring, 24% in Summer and 26 in Winter (Table B5). The total number of waterbird records, discriminated by functional trait, are displayed in Table B5.

Table B5 - Number of records included in the waterbird statistical analysis, discriminated by functional group and season.

Functional Group	Autumn	Spring	Summer	Winter	Total
Dabbling ducks	515	447	383	513	1858
Diving birds	219	332	226	284	1061
Fishing birds	308	319	317	355	1299
Large wading birds	500	498	582	507	2087
Small wading birds	403	365	397	430	1595
Total	1945 (25%)	1961 (25%)	1905 (24%)	2089 (26%)	7900 (100%)

Model outputs

According to the statistical outputs attained, 35 out of the 40 statistical models obtained were able to determine between 20% and 51% of the proportion of variance in the dependent variables (i.e. species richness and density of individuals) (Table B6). The models with poorer goodness of fit (less than 20% explanatory power) were: species richness of Dabbling ducks in Summer, species richness of Diving birds in Autumn, Summer and Winter, and density of Small Wading birds in Winter (Table B6). All statistical outputs (i.e. histograms, Spearman Rho correlation, Variance Inflation Factor, Regression models and partial regression coefficients) are displayed in Appendix B5.

Table B6 - Adjusted square root of the statistical models obtained to relate waterbird diversity (Species richness per functional group) and density (Density of individuals per functional group) to seasonal variation in abiotic conditions (i.e. percentage of area of each LU class considered, proportion of flooded area, and mean, maximum and standard deviation of NDVI, calculated at the plot level). Values signed as red depict low model performance (i.e. less than 20% of explained proportion of variance).

Functional Group	Autumn		Spring		Summer		Winter	
	Species richness	Density of individuals						
Dabbling ducks	0.33	0.31	0.36	0.22	0.19	0.46	0.43	0.31
Diving birds	0.16	0.46	0.28	0.47	0.13	0.46	0.13	0.27
Fishing birds	0.41	0.20	0.41	0.23	0.31	0.39	0.37	0.33
Large wading birds	0.41	0.44	0.25	0.51	0.31	0.45	0.28	0.34
Small wading birds	0.31	0.41	0.31	0.21	0.28	0.45	0.23	0.12

Future scenarios

Land use change

Comparing to LU characterization in 2020, land use changes projected for 2040 assume an increase in forestry areas, herbaceous crops, Industrial salt pans and fish ponds, natural shrublands and woody crops, and a decrease in marshes, natural grasslands, rice fields and rivers and riparian galleries (Figure B4; Appendix B6).

Figure B4 - Average changes in land use classes per plot (in terms of proportion of area) between 2020 and 2040.

Hydrological year

Taking into account the analysed historical data, the proportion of flooded area per plot in the 'Dry hydrological year' was characterized based on the Autumn of 2003, Spring of 1995, Summer of 1993 and Winter of 1999; while the 'Regular hydrological year' assumes data from Autumn of 2014; Spring of 2008; Summer of 2006 and Winter of 1989 (Table B7).

Table B7 - Average proportion of flooded area per plot, calculated by season and year. Seasons (coming from different historical years) presenting the lower proportion of flooded area (marked in red) were used to characterize a ‘Dry hydrological year’, whereas seasons (coming from different historical years) presenting the median proportion of flooded area (marked in blue) were used to characterize a ‘Regular hydrological year’.

Year	Autumn	Spring	Summer	Winter
1984	0.181		0.346	
1985			0.520	
1986			0.455	
1987	0.478		0.312	
1988	0.118		0.493	0.633
1989		0.502	0.315	0.588
1990		0.495		0.652
1991	0.427		0.275	
1992		0.441	0.315	0.299
1993	0.111		0.139	0.243
1994	0.179	0.320		0.374
1995		0.225	0.190	
1996	0.342		0.502	
1997	0.443		0.381	
1998	0.200		0.474	
1999	0.477	0.264	0.305	0.213
2000	0.235		0.398	0.434
2001		0.576		0.748
2002	0.305	0.522	0.409	0.692
2003	0.105	0.682	0.363	0.770
2004	0.230	0.610	0.503	0.534
2005	0.345	0.327	0.318	0.243
2006	0.747		0.389	0.574
2007	0.238	0.633	0.345	
2008	0.283	0.540	0.402	
2009	0.253	0.571	0.344	0.612
2010	0.342	0.737	0.518	0.850
2011	0.435	0.847	0.493	
2012	0.131	0.300		0.322
2013	0.303	0.663	0.410	
2014	0.299	0.379	0.338	0.624
2015	0.367	0.545	0.645	0.727
2016	0.616	0.457	0.395	0.738
2017	0.273	0.593	0.454	0.789
2018	0.362	0.666	0.404	0.479
2019	0.268	0.452	0.360	0.533
2020	0.260	0.546	0.346	0.509
dry year (minimum value)	0.105	0.225	0.139	0.213
regular year (median value)	0.291	0.540	0.389	0.581

NDVI estimation

In order to infer seasonal NDVI estimations from land use classes and proportion of flooded area at the plot level, a total of 30 years of data was used in Autumn, 28 years in Spring, 35 in Summer and 25 in Winter (Appendix B7).

According to the statistical outputs attained, 10 out of the 12 statistical models obtained were able to determine between 27% and 54% of the proportion of variance in the dependent variables (i.e.

average NDVI, maximum NDVI and standard deviation of NDVI) (Table B8). The models with poorer goodness of fit (less than 16% explanatory power) were concerned to maximum NDVI in Spring and Winter (Table B8). All statistical outputs (i.e. histograms, Spearman Rho correlation, Variance Inflection Factor, Regression models and partial regression coefficients) are displayed in Appendix B8.

Table B8 - Adjusted square root of the statistical models obtained to relate NDVI (mean NDVI as 'm_NDVI', maximum NDVI as 'max_NDVI' and standard deviation of NDVI as 'sd_NDVI') to seasonal variation in abiotic conditions (i.e. percentage of area of each LU class considered and proportion of flooded area, calculated at the plot level). Values signed as red depict low model performance (i.e. less than 20% of explained proportion of variance).

Season	m NDVI	max NDVI	sd NDVI
Autumn	0.45	0.27	0.44
Spring	0.42	0.16	0.34
Summer	0.46	0.30	0.42
Winter	0.54	0.09	0.37

Spatial-temporal projections

Temporal trends

Waterbirds diversity: according to the results, estimations of waterbird diversity (number of species), in both the 'Regular hydrological year' and the 'Dry hydrological year', are within the range of historical records (Table B2; Figure B5). Comparing with the 'Regular hydrological year', results indicate a decrease in diversity of Large Wading birds in the Summer of the 'Dry hydrological year' and an increase in diversity of Small Wading birds in the spring of the 'Dry hydrological year' (Figure B5).

Figure B5 - Temporal trends (1984-2020) of waterbird diversity (number of species per functional group), including predictions for 2040 according to the future scenarios considered (i.e. ‘Regular hydrological year’ and ‘Dry hydrological year’).

Waterbirds abundance: According to the results, in a few plots (Appendix B9), model predictions greatly exceeded the historical values of individuals’ abundance registered. In order not to compromise the general results of the simulations (i.e. for the remaining plots), estimates outside the historical range for these specific plots were excluded from the results. Overall, when compared with the ‘Regular hydrological year’, the results suggest a decrease in the abundance of waterbirds (from all functional groups) in all seasons of the ‘Dry hydrological year’, with the exception of Diving birds that tended to increase in the Summer of the ‘Dry hydrological year’ (Figure B6).

Figure B6 - Temporal trends (1984-2020) of waterbird abundance (number of individuals per functional group), including predictions for 2040 according to the future scenarios considered (i.e. 'Regular hydrological year' and 'Dry hydrological year').

Spatial trends

For comparison between the 'Regular hydrological year' and the 'Dry hydrological year', results of the spatial projections were qualitatively evaluated taking into account changes in species diversity and abundance of individuals in the main habitat types of the study area (i.e. Natural marshes, Veta la Palma fish farm, Rice files, Bonanza salt pans and Cereals, sunflowers and other crops, Figure B1).

Waterbirds diversity: Overall, in terms of species diversity, the most affected functional groups by drought events in the future (in terms of changes in species richness in different habitat types) were Dabbling ducks and Large Wading birds, with predicted decreases in number of species in almost all habitat types of the study area, in at least one season of the dry year (Figure B7 and Figure B10). In particular, when comparing with the 'Regular hydrological year', simulation results indicate a decrease in Dabbling ducks diversity of marshes in Winter and Spring of the 'Dry hydrological year', of Veta la Palma fish farm in Spring, of Rice fields in Winter and Autumn, and of Bonanza

salt pans in Winter and Spring (Figure B7). Predictions for the ‘Dry hydrological year’ also suggest a decrease in Large Wading birds diversity of marshes in Winter and Spring, of Veta la Palma fish farm in Spring, of Rice fields in Winter, Summer and Autumn, of Bonanza salt pans in Winter, and of areas with Cereals, sunflowers and other crops in Spring (Figure B10).

In the case of Diving birds, predictions for the ‘Dry hydrological year’ show a decrease in species richness of natural marshes in Winter and Spring and of Veta la Palma fish farm in Spring (Figure B8), whereas for Fishing birds the same occurred only for Veta la Palma fish farm in Spring (Figure B9). Projections for Small Wading birds suggest an increase in species diversity of natural marshes in Spring of the dry year, although a decrease for the same habitat was projected in Summer and for Bonanza salt pans in Autumn of the ‘Dry hydrological year’ (Figure B11).

Figure B7 - Spatial projections of seasonal variation in Dabbling ducks diversity (number of species) for the ‘Regular hydrological year’ and the ‘Dry hydrological year’.

Figure B8 - Spatial projections of seasonal variation in Diving birds diversity (number of species) for the 'Regular hydrological year' and the 'Dry hydrological year'.

Figure B9 - Spatial projections of seasonal variation in Fishing birds diversity (number of species) for the 'Regular hydrological year' and the 'Dry hydrological year'.

Figure B10 - Spatial projections of seasonal variation in Large wading birds diversity (number of species) for the 'Regular hydrological year' and the 'Dry hydrological year'.

Figure B11 - Spatial projections of seasonal variation in Small wading birds diversity (number of species) for the 'Regular hydrological year' and the 'Dry hydrological year'.

Waterbirds abundance: In terms of abundance of individuals, the most affected functional groups by drought events in the future (in terms of changes in abundance of individuals in different habitat types) were Dabbling ducks, Diving birds and Large Wading birds, with decreases in the total number of individuals predicted in three out of the five main habitat types of the study area, in at least one particular season of the year (Figure B12, Figure B13 and Figure B15). In particular, simulation results indicate:

- a decrease in abundance of Dabbling ducks in marshes in Winter, Spring and Summer of the ‘Dry hydrological year’, in Rice fields in Winter, and in areas with Cereals, sunflowers and other crops in Winter (Figure B12).
- a decrease in the abundance of Diving birds in marshes in Winter, Spring and Summer of the ‘Dry hydrological year’, in Rice fields in Summer and Autumn, and in areas with Cereals, sunflowers and other crops in Winter and Spring (Figure B13).
- a decrease in abundance of Large Wading birds in marshes in Winter and Spring of the ‘Dry hydrological year’, in Rice fields in Winter, Summer and Autumn, and in Bonanza salt pans in Winter (Figure B15).

Despite the same pattern for Fishing birds, an increase in the total number of individuals was projected for Veta la Palma fish farm in the Winter of the ‘Dry hydrological year’ (Figure B14). In the case of Small wading birds, despite an increase in abundance of individuals for Veta la Palma fish farm and Bonanza salt pans in the Spring of the ‘Dry hydrological year’, including for Rice fields in Autumn, projections suggest a decrease in the abundance of individuals using natural marshes in all seasons of the year (Figure B16).

Figure B12 - Spatial projections of seasonal variation in Dabbling ducks abundance (number of individuals) for the ‘Regular hydrological year’ and the ‘Dry hydrological year’.

Figure B13 - Spatial projections of seasonal variation in Diving birds abundance (number of individuals) for the 'Regular hydrological year' and the 'Dry hydrological year'.

Figure B14 - Spatial projections of seasonal variation in Fishing birds abundance (number of individuals) for the 'Regular hydrological year' and the 'Dry hydrological year'.

Figure B15 - Spatial projections of seasonal variation in Large Wading birds abundance (number of individuals) for the ‘Regular hydrological year’ and the ‘Dry hydrological year’.

Figure B16 - Spatial projections of seasonal variation in Small Wading birds abundance (number of individuals) for the ‘Regular hydrological year’ and the ‘Dry hydrological year’.

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Appendix B1 - Area, discriminated by square meters and hectares, of each plot considered in the waterbird analysis.

Plot	area (m2)	area (ha)
ARROZALES DE PUEBLA E ISLA MAYOR	176706108.90	17670.61
BRAZO DE LA TORRE Y CANTARITAS	39170906.24	3917.09
COLONIA DE LA ISLETA DE PUEBLA	502914.36	50.29
DE LA ALGAIDA A LOS SOTOS	13040025.87	1304.00
DEHESA DE ABAJO	1086087.54	108.61
DEL PALACIO A LA ALGAIDA	7465352.17	746.54
EL PUNTAL	10567271.68	1056.73
ENTREMUROS	22847410.27	2284.74
GUADIAMAR ENCAUZADO	5598233.72	559.82
HATO BLANCO	20965951.92	2096.60
LAGUNAS RBD	566750.31	56.68
LAS NUEVAS - MATOCHAR	87733498.49	8773.35
LOS CARACOLES	27041837.93	2704.18
LUCIO DE LA FAO	600645.83	60.06
MARISMA DE HINOJOS	86804009.39	8680.40
MARISMAS DE COTO DEL REY	27964251.18	2796.43
MARISMAS DEL ROCIO	1959057.44	195.91
MARISMILLAS	37215934.59	3721.59
MATASGORDAS	18147985.88	1814.80
OTROS CULTIVOS	104972840.00	10497.28
PARTIDO	1376595.53	137.66
RESERVA DEL GUADIAMAR	24845065.66	2484.51
SALINAS DE BONANZA	27659397.90	2765.94
VETA LA PALMA	115843472.30	11584.35
Total	860681605.09	86068.16

Appendix B2 - Total number of waterbird records, and respective percentages, discriminated by plot location and season.

Plots	nr of records					% of records				
	Autumn	Spring	Summer	Winter	Total	Autumn	Spring	Summer	Winter	Total
ARROZALES DE PUEBLA E ISLA MAYOR	1728	554	729	1532	4543	0.081	0.021	0.045	0.044	0.046
BRAZO DE LA TORRE Y CANTARITAS	1007	300	495	727	2529	0.047	0.011	0.031	0.021	0.026
COLONIA DE LA ISLETA DE PUEBLA	29	22	61	27	139	0.001	0.001	0.004	0.001	0.001
DE LA ALGAIDA A LOS SOTOS	605	1569	584	1777	4535	0.029	0.058	0.036	0.051	0.046
DEHESA DE ABAJO	329	540	418	474	1761	0.016	0.020	0.026	0.014	0.018
DEL PALACIO A LA ALGAIDA	253	728	308	878	2167	0.012	0.027	0.019	0.025	0.022
EL PUNTAL	243	888	217	1176	2524	0.011	0.033	0.013	0.034	0.025
ENTREMUIROS	1635	1718	1060	1953	6366	0.077	0.064	0.065	0.056	0.064
GUADIAMAR ENCAUZADO	1144	1185	974	1012	4315	0.054	0.044	0.060	0.029	0.044
HATO BLANCO	757	110	446	596	1909	0.036	0.004	0.028	0.017	0.019
LAGUNAS RBD	651	653	613	724	2641	0.031	0.024	0.038	0.021	0.027
LAS NUEVAS - MATOCHAR	1019	2762	988	3992	8761	0.048	0.102	0.061	0.115	0.088
LOS CARACOLES	50	437	67	575	1129	0.002	0.016	0.004	0.017	0.011
LUCIO DE LA FAO	299	460	367	484	1610	0.014	0.017	0.023	0.014	0.016
MARISMA DE HINOJOS	417	2842	870	3304	7433	0.020	0.105	0.054	0.095	0.075
MARISMAS DE COTO DEL REY	51	336	44	437	868	0.002	0.012	0.003	0.013	0.009
MARISMAS DEL ROCIO Y ROCINA	628	973	653	1128	3382	0.030	0.036	0.040	0.033	0.034
MARISMILLAS	998	1973	997	2599	6567	0.047	0.073	0.062	0.075	0.066
MATASGORDAS	42	232	59	341	674	0.002	0.009	0.004	0.010	0.007
OTROS CULTIVOS	547	32	95	296	970	0.026	0.001	0.006	0.009	0.010
PARTIDO	6	25	8	11	50	0.000	0.001	0.000	0.000	0.001
RESERVA DEL GUADIAMAR	585	1323	402	2111	4421	0.028	0.049	0.025	0.061	0.045
SALINAS DE BONANZA	2875	2465	2107	2716	10163	0.136	0.091	0.130	0.078	0.103
VETA LA PALMA	5307	4863	3626	5776	19572	0.250	0.180	0.224	0.167	0.198
Total	21205	26990	16188	34646	99029	0.214	0.273	0.163	0.350	1.000

Appendix B3 - Number of raster files (Inundation and NDVI) available per season, discriminated by month and year.

Year(month)	Autumn	Spring	Summer	Winter
1984	2		2	1
7			1	
8			1	
9	1			
10	1			
12				1
1985		1	4	1
2				1
3		1		
6			2	
8			2	
1986	1	1	3	2
1				2
5		1		
6			2	
7			1	
10	1			
1987	2	1	4	1
2				1
5		1		
6			1	
7			1	
8			2	
9	1			
11	1			
1988	3	2	2	3
1				1
2				1
4		2		
6			1	
8			1	
9	2			
10	1			
12				1
1989	1	2	3	2
1				1
2				1
3		1		
4		1		
6			1	
7			1	
8			1	
10	1			
1990		2	4	2
1				1
2				1
4		1		
5		1		
6			1	
7			1	
8			2	
1991	3	3	2	

4		1		
5		2		
6			1	
8			1	
9	1			
11	2			
1992	1	4	3	2
1				1
2				1
3		1		
4		2		
5		1		
6			1	
7			1	
8			1	
10	1			
1993	2		2	2
1				1
6			1	
7			1	
9	1			
10	1			
12				1
1994	3	2	1	2
1				1
3		1		
5		1		
7			1	
9	1			
10	1			
11	1			
12				1
1995	1	3	3	1
1				1
4		2		
5		1		
6			1	
7			1	
8			1	
9	1			
1996	2	1	4	16
2				16
5		1		
6			1	
7			1	
8			2	
9	1			
11	1			
1997	2	2	5	1
2				1
3		1		
5		1		
6			1	
7			2	
8			2	
10	1			
11	1			

1998	3	2	3	2
3		2		
6			1	
7			1	
8			1	
10	2			
11	1			
12				2
1999	4	2	2	3
1				1
2				1
4		1		
5		1		
6			1	
8			1	
9	1			
11	3			
12				1
2000	4	1	3	3
1				1
2				2
5		1		
6			1	
7			1	
8			1	
9	3			
11	1			
2001	1	2	3	2
1				1
2				1
4		1		
5		1		
6			3	
9	1			
2002	2	2	6	3
1				1
2				2
4		1		
5		1		
6			2	
7			2	
8			2	
10	1			
11	1			
2003	2	2	3	3
1				1
2				1
4		1		
5		1		
6			1	
8			2	
9	1			
10	1			
12				1
2004	4	3	5	2
1				1
3		2		

4		1		
6			1	
7			3	
8			1	
9	2			
10	1			
11	1			
12				1
2005	7	3	5	5
1				2
2				2
4		1		
5		2		
6			2	
7			2	
8			1	
9	3			
10	2			
11	2			
12				1
2006	3	1	9	6
1				2
2				2
4		1		
6			3	
7			3	
8			3	
10	1			
11	2			
12				2
2007	2	5	5	1
1				1
3		3		
5		2		
6			2	
7			2	
8			1	
10	1			
11	1			
2008	5	2	9	1
2				1
3		1		
4		1		
6			2	
7			3	
8			4	
9	2			
10	1			
11	2			
2009	4	6	5	2
2				1
3		1		
4		2		
5		3		
6			2	
7			2	
8			1	

9	1			
10	2			
11	1			
12				1
2010	4	5	6	2
1				1
2				1
4		2		
5		3		
6			3	
7			1	
8			2	
9	1			
10	1			
11	2			
2011	5	4	3	3
2				3
3		1		
4		1		
5		2		
6			1	
8			2	
9	2			
10	2			
11	1			
2012	3	4	1	4
1				2
2				2
3		1		
4		2		
5		1		
8			1	
9	1			
10	2			
2013	6	5	8	3
4		1		
5		4		
6			3	
7			2	
8			3	
9	3			
10	1			
11	2			
12				3
2014	6	7	7	4
1				1
3		2		
4		3		
5		2		
6			1	
7			2	
8			4	
9	2			
10	3			
11	1			
12				3
2015	4	3	7	9

1				3
2				3
3		1		
5		2		
6			1	
7			4	
8			2	
10	1			
11	3			
12				3
2016	6	3	11	5
2				1
3		2		
5		1		
6			4	
7			3	
8			4	
9	3			
10	2			
11	1			
12				4
2017	10	4	9	6
1				3
2				1
3		1		
4		1		
5		2		
6			2	
7			4	
8			3	
9	3			
10	4			
11	3			
12				2
2018	3	4	7	7
1				3
2				1
4		2		
5		2		
7			4	
8			3	
9	2			
11	1			
12				3
2019	7	11	9	7
1				2
2				3
3		4		
4		3		
5		4		
6			3	
7			3	
8			3	
9	3			
10	3			
11	1			
12				2

2020	7	3	9	7
1				1
2				4
3		1		
4		1		
5		1		
6			2	
7			4	
8			3	
9	2			
10	4			
11	1			
12				2

Appendix B4 - Final list of raster files used to characterize flooding regimes and vegetation dynamics in Doñana, discriminated by season and year.

Season /Year	Raster files (Dyyyyymmdd)	nr rasters
autumn 1984	D19840910;D19841012;	2
autumn 1987	D19870903;D19871122;	2
autumn 1988	D19880905;D19880921;D19881007;	3
autumn 1991	D19910914;D19911101;D19911117;	3
autumn 1993	D19930919; D19931021;	2
autumn 1994	D19940906;D19941024;D19941125;	3
autumn 1996	D19960927;D19961130;	2
autumn 1997	D19971016;D19971117;	2
autumn 1998	D19981003;D19981019;D19981120;	3
autumn 1999	D19990912;D19991107;D19991115;D19991123;	4
autumn 2000	D20000906;D20000914;D20000922;D20001101;	4
autumn 2002	D20021022;D20021107;	2
autumn 2003	D20030915;D20031009;	2
autumn 2004	D20040917;D20040925;D20041003;D20041120;	4
autumn 2005	D20050904;D20050920;D20050928;D20051006;D20051014;D20051107;D20051123;	7
autumn 2006	D20061009;D20061110;D20061126;	3
autumn 2007	D20071020;D20071105;	2
autumn 2008	D20080904;D20080912;D20081006;D20081115;D20081123;	5
autumn 2009	D20090923;D20091009;D20091017;D20091102;	4
autumn 2010	D20100910;D20101020;D20101105;D20101121;	4
autumn 2011	D20110905;D20110913;D20111015;D20111031;D20111108;	5
autumn 2012	D20120915;D20121001;D20121017;	3
autumn 2013	D20130902;D20130910;D20130926;D20131004;D20131113;D20131129;	6
autumn 2014	D20140905;D20140929;D20141007;D20141023;D20141031;D20141116;	6
autumn 2015	D20151002;D20151111;D20151119;D20151127;	4
autumn 2016	D20160902;D20160910;D20160926;D20161004;D20161028;D20161129;	6
autumn 2017	D20170905;D20170921;D20170929;D20171007;D20171015;D20171023;D20171031;D20171108;D20171116;D20171124;	10
autumn 2018	D20180916;D20180924;D20181127;	3
autumn 2019	D20190903;D20190911;D20190927;D20191005;D20191013;D20191021;D20191106;	7
autumn 2020	D20200905;D20200929;D20201007;D20201015;D20201023;D20201031;D20201108;	7
winter 1988	D19880109;D19880226;D19881210;	3
winter 1989	D19881210;D19890127;D19890212;	3
winter 1990	D19900114;D19900215;	2

winter 1992	D19920104;D19920205;	2
winter 1993	D19930106;D19931208;	2
winter 1994	D19940125;D19941211;	2
winter 1999	D19981206;D19981222;D19990107;D19990208;	4
winter 2000	D19991217;D20000118;D20000203;D20000219;	4
winter 2001	D20010120;D20010221;	2
winter 2002	D20020107;D20020208;D20020224;	3
winter 2003	D20030110;D20030211;D20031212;	3
winter 2004	D20040121;D20041230;	2
winter 2005	D20041230;D20050107;D20050131;D20050208;D20050216;	5
winter 2006	D20051217;D20060102;D20060118;D20060211;D20060227;	5
winter 2009	D20090211;D20091204;	2
winter 2010	D20091204;D20100129;D20100206;	3
winter 2012	D20120103;D20120119;D20120204;D20120220;	4
winter 2014	D20140108;D20141202;D20141210;D20141226;	4
winter 2015	D20141202;D20141210;D20141226;D20150103;D20150111;D20150127;D20150204;D20150220;D20150228;	9
winter 2016	D20160223;D20161207;D20161215;D20161223;D20161231;	5
winter 2017	D20161207;D20161215;D20161223;D20161231;D20170108;D20170116;D20170124;D20170217;	8
winter 2018	D20171202;D20171218;D20180111;D20180119;D20180127;D20180220;	6
winter 2019	D20181205;D20181221;D20181229;D20190106;D20190114;D20190207;D20190215;D20190223;	8
winter 2020	D20191208;D20191224;D20200101;D20200202;D20200210;D20200218;D20200226;	7
winter 2021	D20201202;D20201226;D20210103;D20210111;D20210212;	5
spring1 989	D19890316;D19890417;	2
spring1 990	D19900420;D19900506;	2
spring1 991	D19910407;D19910509;D19910525;	3
spring1 992	D19920324;D19920409;D19920425;D19920511;	4
spring1 994	D19940314;D19940501;	2
spring1 995	D19950402;D19950418;D19950520;	3
spring1 997	D19970306;D19970509;	2
spring1 999	D19990413;D19990531;	2
spring2 001	D20010410;D20010504;	2
spring2 002	D20020429;D20020531;	2
spring2 003	D20030416;D20030518;	2
spring2 004	D20040317;D20040325;D20040426;	3
spring2 005	D20050413;D20050515;D20050523;	3
spring2 007	D20070302;D20070310;D20070318;D20070505;D20070529;	5

spring2008	D20080328;D20080413;	2
spring2009	D20090331;D20090408;D20090424;D20090502;D20090518;D20090526;	6
spring2010	D20100403;D20100427;D20100505;D20100521;D20100529;	5
spring2011	D20110321;D20110406;D20110508;D20110524;	4
spring2012	D20120307;D20120408;D20120424;D20120510;	4
spring2013	D20130419;D20130505;D20130513;D20130521;D20130529;	5
spring2014	D20140313;D20140321;D20140406;D20140422;D20140430;D20140508;D20140516;	7
spring2015	D20150308;D20150511;D20150527;	3
spring2016	D20160302;D20160310;D20160521;	3
spring2017	D20170329;D20170406;D20170508;D20170524;	4
spring2018	D20180401;D20180417;D20180503;D20180519;	4
spring2019	D20190303;D20190311;D20190319;D20190327;D20190404;D20190412;D20190428;D20190506;D20190514;D20190522;D20190530;	11
spring2020	D20200329;D20200422;D20200524;	3
spring2021	D20210316;D20210324;D20210519;	3
summer1984	D19840708;D19840825;	2
summer1985	D19850609;D19850625;D19850812;D19850828;	4
summer1986	D19860612;D19860628;D19860730;	3
summer1987	D19870615;D19870701;D19870802;D19870818;	4
summer1988	D19880601;D19880804;	2
summer1989	D19890604;D19890722;D19890807;	3
summer1990	D19900623;D19900709;D19900810;D19900826;	4
summer1991	D19910626;D19910813;	2
summer1992	D19920628;D19920714;D19920815;	3
summer1993	D19930615;D19930717;	2
summer1995	D19950621;D19950723;D19950824;	3
summer1996	D19960623;D19960709;D19960810;D19960826;	4
summer1997	D19970626;D19970712;D19970728;D19970813;D19970829;	5
summer1998	D19980613;D19980715;D19980816;	3
summer1999	D19990616;D19990827;	2
summer2000	D20000602;D20000712;D20000813;	3
summer2002	D20020616;D20020624;D20020702;D20020718;D20020803;D20020819;	6
summer2003	D20030627;D20030814;D20030830;	3
summer2004	D20040613;D20040707;D20040715;D20040731;D20040816;	5
summer2005	D20050608;D20050616;D20050702;D20050718;D20050803;	5
summer2006	D20060603;D20060611;D20060619;D20060705;D20060713;D20060721;D20060806;D20060822;D20060830;	9
summer2007	D20070622;D20070630;D20070708;D20070724;D20070809;	5

summer2008	D20080608;D20080624;D20080710;D20080718;D20080726;D20080803;D20080811;D20080819;D20080827;	9
summer2009	D20090611;D20090627;D20090713;D20090729;D20090830;	5
summer2010	D20100606;D20100622;D20100630;D20100716;D20100801;D20100825;	6
summer2011	D20110601;D20110804;D20110828;	3
summer2013	D20130614;D20130622;D20130630;D20130708;D20130724;D20130809;D20130817;D20130825;	8
summer2014	D20140609;D20140711;D20140727;D20140804;D20140812;D20140820;D20140828;	7
summer2015	D20150628;D20150706;D20150714;D20150722;D20150730;D20150815;D20150823;	7
summer2016	D20160606;D20160614;D20160622;D20160630;D20160708;D20160716;D20160724;D20160801;D20160809;D20160817;D20160825;	11
summer2017	D20170601;D20170617;D20170703;D20170711;D20170719;D20170727;D20170804;D20170812;D20170820;	9
summer2018	D20180706;D20180714;D20180722;D20180730;D20180807;D20180823;D20180831;	7
summer2019	D20190607;D20190615;D20190623;D20190701;D20190709;D20190725;D20190802;D20190810;D20190818;	9
summer2020	D20200609;D20200617;D20200703;D20200711;D20200719;D20200727;D20200804;D20200820;D20200828;	9
summer2021	D20210604;D20210628;D20210706;D20210714;D20210722;D20210730;D20210823;D20210831;	8
	Total	504

Appendix B5 - Statistical outputs (i.e. histograms, Spearman Rho correlation, Variance Inflation Factor, Regression models and partial regression coefficients) of the statistical models obtained to relate waterbird diversity (Species richness per functional group) and density (Density of individuals per functional group) to seasonal variation in abiotic conditions (i.e. percentage of area of each LU class considered, proportion of flooded area, and mean, maximum and standard deviation of NDVI, calculated at the plot level).

HISTOGRAMS

Autumn

Spring

Summer

Winter

DABBLING_DUCKS_SPRING

	Forestry	Herbaceous.crops	Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds	Marches	Natural.grasslands	Natural.shrublands	Rice.fields	Rivers.and.riparian.galleries
Forestry	1.00000000	-0.19170274	-0.18791009	-0.193725635	0.43189878	0.69933464	-0.06614592	0.0596533304
Herbaceous.crops	-0.19170274	1.00000000	0.34559270	-0.445396116	0.04237188	-0.16234813	0.51878109	0.4371993296
Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds	-0.18791009	0.34559270	1.00000000	-0.171278539	-0.08486956	-0.17772789	0.19908213	0.0785912058
Marches	-0.19372564	-0.44539612	-0.17127854	1.00000000	-0.48207631	-0.16708506	-0.42041437	-0.4033094988
Natural.grasslands	0.43189878	0.04237188	0.08486956	-0.48207631	1.00000000	0.39394018	0.10203334	0.0289886401
Natural.shrublands	0.69933464	-0.16234813	-0.17772789	-0.16708506	0.39394018	1.00000000	-0.17615298	0.0900781067
Rice.fields	-0.06614592	0.51878109	0.19908213	-0.42041437	0.10203334	-0.17615298	1.00000000	0.1961357951
Rivers.and.riparian.galleries	0.05965333	0.43719933	0.07859121	-0.403309499	0.02898864	0.09007811	0.19613580	1.0000000000
Woody.crops	0.06345573	0.33921642	-0.11089760	-0.330796550	0.17818143	0.11411551	0.43491113	0.2219382326
sd_NDVI	-0.30765187	0.17806010	0.43528393	0.166335904	-0.16324424	-0.29559764	0.23548383	-0.0612517882
max_NDVI	0.33753590	-0.08591978	-0.11810824	-0.007759426	-0.11810824	0.39134022	0.14818132	-0.0009142403
m_NDVI	0.10467614	-0.22854658	-0.33679039	0.097795117	-0.33679039	0.25250759	0.01837310	-0.2861638964
prop_flooded_area_ha	-0.09570835	-0.14083441	-0.09258409	0.218527858	-0.17697642	-0.02808141	-0.37545068	-0.0202074845

	Woody.crops	sd_NDVI	max_NDVI	m_NDVI	prop_flooded_area_ha
Forestry	0.06345573	-0.30765187	0.3375359025	0.10467614	-0.09570835
Herbaceous.crops	0.33921642	0.17806010	-0.0859197828	-0.22854658	-0.14083441
Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds	-0.11089760	0.43528393	-0.1181082373	-0.33679039	-0.09258409
Marches	-0.33079655	0.16633590	-0.0077594264	0.09779512	0.21852786
Natural.grasslands	0.17818143	-0.16324424	0.1359092276	0.25250759	-0.17697642
Natural.shrublands	0.11411551	-0.29559764	0.3913402160	0.25054046	-0.02808141
Rice.fields	0.43491113	0.23548383	0.1481813204	0.01837310	-0.37545068
Rivers.and.riparian.galleries	0.22193823	-0.06125179	-0.0009142403	-0.28616390	-0.02020748
Woody.crops	1.00000000	0.07288424	0.1373318207	0.14038311	-0.13927516
sd_NDVI	0.07288424	1.00000000	0.1958690658	-0.04391934	0.19246235
max_NDVI	0.13733182	0.19586907	1.0000000000	0.51067806	-0.04700830
m_NDVI	0.14038311	-0.04391934	0.5106780585	1.00000000	-0.26657645
prop_flooded_area_ha	-0.13927516	0.19246235	-0.0470082990	-0.26657645	1.00000000

SPECIES RICHNESS

```

> M <- glm(No..Species ~ Forestry_F + Herbaceous.crops + Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds + Rice.fields + Natural.grasslands + Natural.shrublands + Rivers.and.riparian.galleries + Woody.crops + max_NDVI +
prop_flooded_area_ha + m_NDVI + sd_NDVI, family=quasipoisson, data= Dabbling_ducks_season)
>
> VIF(M)
              Forestry_F              Herbaceous.crops Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds              Rice.fields              Natural.grasslands              Natural.shrublands
Rivers.and.riparian.galleries              Woody.crops              max_NDVI              prop_flooded_area_ha              m_NDVI              sd_NDVI
              1.385267              1.162692              1.444805              1.486905              1.831215              1.596922
>
> summary(M)

Call:
glm(formula = No..Species ~ Forestry_F + Herbaceous.crops + Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds +
Rice.fields + Natural.grasslands + Natural.shrublands + Rivers.and.riparian.galleries +
Woody.crops + max_NDVI + prop_flooded_area_ha + m_NDVI +
sd_NDVI, family = quasipoisson, data = Dabbling_ducks_season)

Deviance Residuals:
    Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
-2.22118  -0.62027  -0.03548   0.51031   2.53943

Coefficients:
            (Intercept)              9.081e-01  4.626e-01  1.963  0.0503 .
            Forestry_F              -3.253e+00  6.733e-01  -4.831  1.88e-06 ***
            Herbaceous.crops          -6.792e-01  3.420e-01  -1.986  0.0477 *
            Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds -1.147e-01  2.019e-01  -0.568  0.5702
            Rice.fields              -1.507e+00  1.806e-01  -8.345  9.59e-16 ***
            Natural.grasslands         -1.821e-02  1.191e-01  -0.153  0.8785
            Natural.shrublands         -1.748e+00  7.315e-01  -2.390  0.0173 *
            Rivers.and.riparian.galleries -3.716e-01  1.715e-01  -2.167  0.0308 *
            Woody.crops              -1.325e+00  2.374e+00  -0.558  0.5771
            max_NDVI                 2.944e-03  2.891e-03  1.018  0.3092
            prop_flooded_area_ha      -3.275e-02  9.876e-02  -0.332  0.7403
            m_NDVI                   -8.781e-04  1.889e-03  -0.465  0.6422
            sd_NDVI                   7.863e-06  9.007e-07  8.730  < 2e-16 ***
---
Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

(Dispersion parameter for quasipoisson family taken to be 0.7812057)

Null deviance: 547.52  on 446  degrees of freedom
Residual deviance: 342.41  on 434  degrees of freedom
AIC: NA

Number of Fisher Scoring iterations: 5
>
> r2adj <- adjR2(M)
> r2adj
[1] 0.3573
    
```

DENSITY OF INDIVIDUALS

```
> M <- glm(nind_ha_adj ~ Forestry_F + Herbaceous.crops + Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds + Marches + Natural.grasslands + Natural.shrublands + Rivers.and.riparian.galleries + Woody.crops + max_NDVI + prop_flooded_area_ha + m_NDVI + sd_NDVI, Family=Gamma(link="log"), data= Dabbling_ducks_season)
```

```
> VIF(M)
```

	Forestry_F	Herbaceous.crops	Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds	Marches	Natural.grasslands	Natural.shrublands
	1.228138	1.385316	1.513789	3.851643	2.383054	1.243848
Rivers.and.riparian.galleries		Woody.crops	max_NDVI	prop_flooded_area_ha	m_NDVI	sd_NDVI
	2.184759	1.286621	1.477023	1.369641	1.862507	1.390534

```
> summary(M, dispersion=1)
```

```
Call:
glm(formula = nind_ha_adj ~ Forestry_F + Herbaceous.crops + Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds + Marches + Natural.grasslands + Natural.shrublands + Rivers.and.riparian.galleries + Woody.crops + max_NDVI + prop_flooded_area_ha + m_NDVI + sd_NDVI, family = Gamma(link = "log"), data = Dabbling_ducks_season)
```

```
Deviance Residuals:
```

Min	1Q	Median	3Q	Max
-3.7972	-1.7148	-0.9227	0.0355	5.1771

```
Coefficients:
```

	Estimate	Std. Error	z value	Pr(> z)
(Intercept)	3.734e+00	1.030e+00	3.624	0.00029 ***
Forestry_F	2.296e-02	1.049e+00	0.022	0.98253
Herbaceous.crops	1.040e+00	8.974e-01	1.158	0.24666
Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds	-2.646e+00	4.921e-01	-5.376	7.60e-08 ***
Marches	1.538e+00	2.842e-01	5.412	6.22e-08 ***
Natural.grasslands	6.212e-01	3.828e-01	1.623	0.10465
Natural.shrublands	-9.878e-01	1.407e+00	-0.702	0.48267
Rivers.and.riparian.galleries	1.633e+00	4.054e-01	4.028	5.63e-05 ***
Woody.crops	-5.023e+00	4.289e+00	-1.171	0.24152
max_NDVI	-3.309e-02	6.210e-03	-5.329	9.89e-08 ***
prop_flooded_area_ha	2.172e+00	2.037e-01	10.662	< 2e-16 ***
m_NDVI	5.150e-03	3.995e-03	1.289	0.19729
sd_NDVI	-1.627e-05	2.286e-06	-7.114	1.12e-12 ***

```
Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
```

```
(Dispersion parameter for Gamma family taken to be 1)
```

```
Null deviance: 1367.6 on 416 degrees of freedom
Residual deviance: 1032.6 on 404 degrees of freedom
(30 observations deleted due to missingness)
AIC: 1276.9
```

```
Number of Fisher Scoring iterations: 25
```

```
> r2adj <- adjR2(M)
> r2adj
[1] 0.2225
```

DABBLING_DUCKS_SUMMER

	Forestry	Herbaceous.crops	Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds	Marches	Natural.grasslands	Natural.shrublands	Rice.fields	Rivers.and.riparian.galleries	Woody.crops	sd_NDVI
Forestry	1.00000000	-0.2256601442	-0.05660218	-0.15540783	0.40219768	0.659938368	-0.17190221	-0.001041384	0.11883337	-0.27403289
Herbaceous.crops	-0.225660144	1.0000000000	0.31035041	-0.50531971	0.08240927	-0.227440576	0.42792330	0.445138695	0.22203992	0.22596726
Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds	-0.056602179	0.3103504144	1.00000000	-0.25270760	-0.01109184	-0.115456903	0.18349368	-0.036749373	-0.10516152	0.47300923
Marches	-0.155407831	-0.5053197128	-0.25270760	1.00000000	-0.44603960	-0.105076852	-0.50058631	-0.482367986	-0.29760473	-0.06507373
Natural.grasslands	0.402197680	0.0824092675	-0.01109184	-0.44603960	1.00000000	0.423015195	0.07062759	0.077724928	0.27296649	-0.14563643
Natural.shrublands	0.659938368	-0.2274405760	-0.11545690	-0.10507685	0.42301520	1.000000000	-0.24447443	-0.003340176	0.17869345	-0.36109858
Rice.fields	-0.171902205	0.4279232973	0.18349368	-0.50058631	0.07062759	-0.244474426	1.000000000	0.138272699	0.34448199	0.44594139
Rivers.and.riparian.galleries	-0.001041384	0.4451386952	-0.03674937	-0.48236799	0.07772493	-0.003340176	0.13827270	1.000000000	0.19108835	-0.06118617
Woody.crops	0.118833370	0.2220399178	-0.10516152	-0.29760473	0.27296649	0.178693448	0.34448199	0.191088351	1.000000000	-0.02547282
sd_NDVI	-0.274032889	0.2259672605	0.47300923	-0.06507373	-0.14563643	-0.361098585	0.44594139	-0.061186167	-0.02547282	1.000000000
max_NDVI	0.245696191	0.0854656851	0.15741694	-0.19855274	0.08904699	0.160054642	0.47211487	0.086227128	0.24967405	0.41163094
m_NDVI	0.027506139	-0.2415059994	-0.49979119	0.05142635	0.18891274	0.191687502	0.15525187	-0.173536774	0.18412806	-0.10835787
prop_flooded_area_ha	0.012121740	-0.0008736315	-0.03654628	-0.21494491	-0.07428418	-0.048948026	-0.10554439	0.098870513	-0.21407400	0.07091345
	max_NDVI	m_NDVI	prop_flooded_area_ha							
Forestry	0.24569619	0.02750614	0.0121217398							
Herbaceous.crops	0.08546569	-0.24150600	-0.0008736315							
Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds	0.15741694	-0.49979119	-0.0365462751							
Marches	-0.19855274	0.05142635	-0.2149449090							
Natural.grasslands	0.08904699	0.18891274	-0.0742841833							
Natural.shrublands	0.16005464	0.19168750	-0.0489480264							
Rice.fields	0.47211487	0.15525187	-0.1055443906							
Rivers.and.riparian.galleries	0.08622713	-0.17353677	0.0988705131							
Woody.crops	0.24967405	0.18412806	-0.2140739963							
sd_NDVI	0.41163094	-0.10835787	0.0709134451							
max_NDVI	1.00000000	0.34504266	-0.073535323							
m_NDVI	0.34504266	1.00000000	0.0141601763							
prop_flooded_area_ha	-0.07353533	0.01416018	1.0000000000							

SPECIES RICHNESS

```
> M <- glm(No..Species ~ Forestry_F + Herbaceous.crops + Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds + Rice.fields + Natural.grasslands + Natural.shrublands + Rivers.and.riparian.galleries + Woody.crops + max_NDVI + prop_flooded_area_ha + m_NDVI + sd_NDVI, family=quasipoisson, data= Dabbling_ducks_season)
```

```
> VIF(M)
```

	Forestry_F	Herbaceous.crops	Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds	Rice.fields	Natural.grasslands	Natural.shrublands
Forestry_F	1.219816	1.097336	2.521339	2.392207	1.205394	1.196616
Rivers.and.riparian.galleries	1.434170	Woody.crops	max_NDVI	prop_flooded_area_ha	m_NDVI	sd_NDVI
		1.173268	1.562383	1.251621	3.095480	2.408562

```
> summary(M)
```

```
Call:
glm(formula = No..Species ~ Forestry_F + Herbaceous.crops + Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds + Rice.fields + Natural.grasslands + Natural.shrublands + Rivers.and.riparian.galleries + Woody.crops + max_NDVI + prop_flooded_area_ha + m_NDVI + sd_NDVI, family = quasipoisson, data = Dabbling_ducks_season)
```

```
Deviance Residuals:
    Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
-1.4664 -0.5267 -0.2368  0.3788  2.9681
```

```
Coefficients:
            Estimate Std. Error t value Pr(>|t|)
(Intercept)  1.396e+00  6.679e-01  2.090  0.03731 *
Forestry_F    -2.444e+00  1.316e+00 -1.857  0.06414 .
Herbaceous.crops -3.598e-01  3.108e-01 -1.158  0.24768
Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds 2.279e-02  2.848e-01  0.080  0.93627
Rice.fields    1.667e-02  2.092e-01  0.080  0.93652
Natural.grasslands -1.590e-02  2.297e-01 -0.069  0.94486
Natural.shrublands -2.190e+00  1.042e+00 -2.102  0.03625 *
Rivers.and.riparian.galleries -2.038e-01  2.051e-01 -0.994  0.32104
Woody.crops    -2.999e+00  2.822e+00 -1.063  0.28868
max_NDVI       9.514e-03  3.220e-03  2.955  0.00333 **
prop_flooded_area_ha 6.107e-03  1.250e-01  0.049  0.96107
m_NDVI         -1.815e-02  4.248e-03 -4.273  2.45e-05 ***
sd_NDVI        2.612e-06  1.436e-06  1.819  0.06967 .
---
Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
```

```
(Dispersion parameter for quasipoisson family taken to be 0.5495553)
```

```
Null deviance: 227.37 on 382 degrees of freedom
Residual deviance: 178.92 on 370 degrees of freedom
AIC: NA
```

```
Number of Fisher Scoring iterations: 4
```

```
>
> r2adj <- adjR2(M)
> r2adj
[1] 0.1875
```

DENSITY OF INDIVIDUALS

```
> M <- glm(nind_ha_adj ~ Forestry_F + Herbaceous.crops + Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds + Marches + Natural.grasslands + Natural.shrublands + Rivers.and.riparian.galleries + Woody.crops + max_NDVI + prop_flooded_area_ha + m_NDVI + sd_NDVI, family=Gamma(link="log"), data= Dabbling_ducks_season)
```

```
> VIF(M)
```

	Forestry_F	Herbaceous.crops	Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds	Marches	Natural.grasslands	Natural.shrublands
Forestry_F	1.272322	1.713809	2.993234	4.457368	2.084798	1.218828
Rivers.and.riparian.galleries	2.939113	Woody.crops	max_NDVI	prop_flooded_area_ha	m_NDVI	sd_NDVI
		1.222137	1.621256	1.200320	2.528930	1.454944

```
> summary(M, dispersion=1)
```

```
Call:
glm(formula = nind_ha_adj ~ Forestry_F + Herbaceous.crops + Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds + Marches + Natural.grasslands + Natural.shrublands + Rivers.and.riparian.galleries + Woody.crops + max_NDVI + prop_flooded_area_ha + m_NDVI + sd_NDVI, family = Gamma(link = "log"), data = Dabbling_ducks_season)
```

```
Deviance Residuals:
    Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
-3.1604 -1.6639 -1.0460 -0.0782  5.3912
```

```
Coefficients:
            Estimate Std. Error z value Pr(>|z|)
(Intercept)  1.215e+01  1.356e+00  8.955 < 2e-16 ***
Forestry_F    -2.368e+00  1.825e+00 -1.298  0.194442
Herbaceous.crops 2.354e+00  6.837e-01  3.444  0.000574 ***
Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds -4.481e+00  6.938e-01 -6.459 1.06e-10 ***
Marches       -1.260e+00  3.613e-01 -3.487 0.000488 ***
Natural.grasslands -5.521e-01  5.874e-01 -0.940 0.347261
Natural.shrublands 5.330e+00  1.584e+00  3.366 0.000763 ***
Rivers.and.riparian.galleries -2.238e+00  4.940e-01 -4.531 5.88e-06 ***
Woody.crops    -1.313e+01  4.956e+00 -2.650 0.008059 ***
max_NDVI       -3.615e-02  6.405e-03 -5.643 1.67e-08 ***
prop_flooded_area_ha 3.412e+00  2.315e-01  14.741 < 2e-16 ***
m_NDVI         -4.746e-02  8.092e-03 -5.865 4.50e-09 ***
sd_NDVI        -2.131e-05  3.291e-06 -6.475 9.48e-11 ***
---
Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
```

```
(Dispersion parameter for Gamma family taken to be 1)
```

```
Null deviance: 1578.66 on 338 degrees of freedom
Residual deviance: 817.03 on 326 degrees of freedom
(44 observations deleted due to missingness)
AIC: 472.81
```

```
Number of Fisher Scoring iterations: 25
```

```
>
> r2adj <- adjR2(M)
> r2adj
[1] 0.4634
```

DABBLING_DUCKS_WINTER

```

Forestry Herbaceous.crops Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds Marches Natural.grasslands Natural.shrublands Rice.fields Rivers.and.riparian.galleries Woody.crops sd_NDVI
Forestry 1.00000000 -0.22627536 -0.1861362 -0.10997255 0.43202312 0.669874729 -0.115089622 -0.042279574 0.09383414 -0.30129878
Herbaceous.crops -0.22627536 1.00000000 0.2298944 -0.50560512 -0.075751647 -0.191492041 0.544953798 0.38376882 0.38802856 0.18977477
Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds -0.18613621 0.22989435 1.00000000 -0.10308560 -0.106474684 -0.151555051 0.138716458 0.120727542 -0.12224657 0.41905337
Marches -0.10997255 -0.50560512 0.22989435 1.00000000 -0.358497176 -0.085751708 -0.527379585 -0.307755220 -0.38462806 0.104059805
Natural.grasslands 0.43202312 -0.07575165 -0.1064747 -0.1030856 1.000000000 0.423243049 -0.005504533 -0.016287935 0.03418138 -0.25903351
Natural.shrublands 0.66987473 -0.19149204 -0.1515551 -0.08575171 0.423243049 1.000000000 -0.214622832 0.003995191 0.03800046 -0.32704905
Rice.fields -0.11508962 0.54495380 0.1387165 -0.52737959 -0.005504533 -0.214622832 1.000000000 0.162085564 0.44320870 0.32727610
Rivers.and.riparian.galleries -0.04227957 0.38376888 0.1207275 -0.30775522 -0.1207275 -0.30775522 -0.016287935 1.000000000 0.153697799 0.16427401
Woody.crops 0.09383414 0.38802856 0.1222466 -0.38462806 0.034181377 0.038000459 0.443208702 0.153697799 1.000000000 0.16427401
sd_NDVI -0.30129878 0.18977477 0.4190534 0.10459805 -0.259033508 -0.327049048 0.327276102 0.014427553 0.16427401 1.000000000
max_NDVI 0.17527113 0.19622377 0.1343178 -0.24058709 0.132919709 0.055099613 0.365941605 0.136487948 0.22706707 0.30776557
m_NDVI 0.12893596 -0.09061430 -0.1953164 -0.06518901 0.271071104 0.124803889 0.115083007 -0.244568154 0.05713275 -0.22077048
prop_flooded_area_ha -0.15494994 -0.01771305 0.0940235 0.23865043 -0.273777644 -0.115580023 -0.226392613 0.066048788 -0.03062385 0.36444359
max_NDVI m_NDVI prop_flooded_area_ha
Forestry 0.17527113 0.12893596 -0.15494994
Herbaceous.crops 0.19622377 -0.09061430 -0.01771305
Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds 0.13431780 -0.19531637 0.09402350
Marches -0.24058709 -0.06518901 0.23865043
Natural.grasslands 0.13291971 0.27107110 -0.27377764
Natural.shrublands 0.05509961 0.12480389 -0.11558002
Rice.fields 0.36594160 0.11508301 -0.22639261
Rivers.and.riparian.galleries 0.13648795 -0.24456815 0.06604879
Woody.crops 0.22706707 0.05713275 -0.03062385
sd_NDVI 0.30776557 -0.22077048 0.36444359
max_NDVI 1.00000000 0.35942413 -0.20038837
m_NDVI 0.35942413 1.00000000 -0.70002659
prop_flooded_area_ha -0.20038837 -0.70002659 1.00000000

```

SPECIES RICHNESS

```

> M <- glm(No..Species ~ Forestry_F + Herbaceous.crops + Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds + Rice.fields + Natural.grasslands + Natural.shrublands + Rivers.and.riparian.galleries + Woody.crops + max_NDVI +
prop_flooded_area_ha + m_NDVI + sd_NDVI, family=quasipoisson, data= Dabbling_ducks_season)

```

```

>
> VIF(M)

```

	Forestry_F	Herbaceous.crops	Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds	Rice.fields	Natural.grasslands	Natural.shrublands
Rivers.and.riparian.galleries	1.159910	1.122254	1.123192	1.457664	1.138001	1.092195
	1.159777	1.105511	1.343631	2.183174	2.300147	1.889518

```

> summary(M)

```

```

Call:
glm(formula = No..Species ~ Forestry_F + Herbaceous.crops + Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds +
Rice.fields + Natural.grasslands + Natural.shrublands + Rivers.and.riparian.galleries +
Woody.crops + max_NDVI + prop_flooded_area_ha + m_NDVI +
sd_NDVI, family = quasipoisson, data = Dabbling_ducks_season)

```

```

Deviance Residuals:
    Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
-2.4359  -0.6511  -0.0860   0.5801   3.8201

```

```

Coefficients:

```

	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
(Intercept)	1.228e+00	4.211e-01	2.916	0.00370 **
Forestry_F	-2.363e+00	4.170e-01	-5.667	2.46e-08 ***
Herbaceous.crops	-1.290e+00	1.632e-01	-7.906	1.72e-14 ***
Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds	-5.805e-01	1.813e-01	-3.202	0.00145 **
Rice.fields	-1.192e+00	1.174e-01	-10.159	< 2e-16 ***
Natural.grasslands	-4.640e-01	1.164e-01	-3.986	7.74e-05 ***
Natural.shrublands	-1.236e+00	5.091e-01	-2.428	0.01556 *
Rivers.and.riparian.galleries	-2.529e-01	1.540e-01	-1.642	0.10114
Woody.crops	-4.155e+00	1.971e+00	-2.108	0.03553 *
max_NDVI	4.746e-03	2.527e-03	1.878	0.06100 .
prop_flooded_area_ha	-6.710e-02	9.786e-02	-0.686	0.49327
m_NDVI	-2.058e-03	1.787e-03	-1.152	0.24993
sd_NDVI	5.305e-06	7.291e-07	7.276	1.34e-12 ***

```

---
Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

```

```

(Dispersion parameter for quasipoisson family taken to be 0.9286523)

```

```

Null deviance: 820.36 on 512 degrees of freedom
Residual deviance: 456.74 on 500 degrees of freedom
AIC: NA

```

```

Number of Fisher Scoring iterations: 5

```

```

>
> r2adj <- adjR2(M)
> r2adj
[1] 0.4299

```

DENSITY OF INDIVIDUALS

```

> M <- glm(nind_ha_adj ~ Forestry_F + Herbaceous.crops + Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds + Rice.fields + Natural.grasslands + Natural.shrublands + Rivers.and.riparian.galleries + Woody.crops + max_NDVI + prop_flooded_area_ha + m_NDVI + sd_NDVI, family=Gamma(link="log"), data= Dabbling_ducks_season)
> VIF(M)
              Forestry_F          Herbaceous.crops Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds          Rice.fields          Natural.grasslands          Natural.shrublands
Rivers.and.riparian.galleries 1.235516                1.204555                1.174035                1.647885                1.159359                1.091119
1.185764                1.155258                1.398923                2.312253                2.451240                1.857382
>
> summary(M, dispersion=1)

Call:
glm(formula = nind_ha_adj ~ Forestry_F + Herbaceous.crops + Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds + Rice.fields + Natural.grasslands + Natural.shrublands + Rivers.and.riparian.galleries + Woody.crops + max_NDVI + prop_flooded_area_ha + m_NDVI + sd_NDVI, family = Gamma(link = "log"), data = Dabbling_ducks_season)

Deviance Residuals:
    Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
-4.1375 -1.4735 -0.6945  0.1120  3.8848

Coefficients:
(Intercept)              7.406e+00  9.533e-01  7.768  7.95e-15 ***
Forestry_F              -1.647e+00  7.259e-01 -2.268  0.023305 *
Herbaceous.crops        -1.583e+00  2.546e-01 -6.220  4.96e-10 ***
Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds -3.975e+00  4.386e-01 -9.064 < 2e-16 ***
Rice.fields              -3.459e+00  2.339e-01 -14.789 < 2e-16 ***
Natural.grasslands      -1.056e+00  2.383e-01 -4.431  9.37e-06 ***
Natural.shrublands      -1.262e+00  1.110e+00 -1.136  0.255886
Rivers.and.riparian.galleries  1.179e+00  3.341e-01  3.528  0.000419 ***
Woody.crops             -3.239e+00  2.691e+00 -1.204  0.228704
max_NDVI                 -2.111e-02  5.762e-03 -3.664  0.000248 ***
prop_flooded_area_ha     4.906e-01  2.205e-01  2.225  0.026061 *
m_NDVI                   -7.947e-03  4.187e-03 -1.898  0.057696 .
sd_NDVI                  -3.522e-06  1.763e-06 -1.997  0.045793 *
---
Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

(Dispersion parameter for Gamma family taken to be 1)

Null deviance: 1566.0 on 512 degrees of freedom
Residual deviance: 1053.7 on 500 degrees of freedom
AIC: 3240.3

Number of Fisher Scoring iterations: 25
>
> r2adj <- adjR2(M)
> r2adj
[1] 0.311

```

DABBLING_DUCKS_AUTUMN

```

Forestry              1.000000000          -0.22627536          -0.18613621          -0.10997255          0.432023120          0.669874729          -0.115089622          -0.042279574          0.09383414          -0.30129878
Herbaceous.crops     -0.22627536          1.000000000          0.2298944          -0.50560512          -0.075751647          -0.191492041          0.544953798          0.383768882          0.38802856          0.18977477
Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds -0.18613621          0.22989435          1.0000000          -0.10308560          -0.106474684          -0.151555051          0.138716458          0.120727542          -0.12224657          0.41905337
Marches               -0.10997255          -0.50560512          -0.1030856          1.0000000          -0.358497176          -0.085751708          -0.527379585          -0.307755220          -0.38462806          0.10459805
Natural.grasslands   0.432023120          -0.07575165          -0.1064747          0.35849718          1.000000000          0.423243049          -0.005504533          -0.016287935          0.03418138          -0.25903351
Natural.shrublands   0.66987473          0.54495380          -0.19149204          -0.1515551          0.08575171          0.423243049          1.000000000          -0.214622832          0.003995191          0.03800046          -0.32704905
Rice.fields          -0.11508962          0.1387165          -0.52737959          0.387165          -0.52737959          -0.005504533          -0.214622832          1.000000000          0.162085564          0.44320870          0.32727610
Rivers.and.riparian.galleries -0.04227957          0.38376888          0.38802856          0.12072725          -0.30775522          -0.016287935          0.003995191          0.162085564          1.000000000          0.15369780          0.01442755
Woody.crops          0.09383414          0.38802856          0.18977477          -0.1222466          -0.38462806          0.034181377          0.038000459          0.443208700          0.153697799          1.000000000          0.16427401
sd_NDVI              -0.30129878          0.18977477          0.4190534          0.10459805          -0.259033508          -0.327049048          0.327276102          0.014427553          0.16427401          1.000000000
max_NDVI             0.17527113          0.19622377          0.1343178          -0.24058709          0.132919709          0.055099613          0.365941605          0.136487948          0.22706707          0.30776557
m_NDVI               0.12893596          -0.09061430          -0.1953164          0.06518901          0.271071104          0.124803889          0.115083007          -0.244568154          0.05713275          -0.22077048
prop_flooded_area_ha -0.15494994          -0.01771305          0.0940235          0.23865043          -0.273777644          -0.115580023          -0.226392613          0.066048788          -0.03062385          0.36444359
max_NDVI              m_NDVI prop_flooded_area_ha
Forestry              0.17527113          0.12893596          -0.15494994
Herbaceous.crops     0.19622377          -0.09061430          -0.01771305
Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds 0.13431780          0.19531637          0.09402350
Marches              -0.24058709          -0.06518901          0.23865043
Natural.grasslands   0.13291971          0.27107110          -0.27377764
Natural.shrublands   0.05509961          0.12480389          -0.11558002
Rice.fields          0.36594160          0.11508301          -0.22639261
Rivers.and.riparian.galleries 0.13648795          -0.24456815          0.06604879
Woody.crops          0.22706707          0.05713275          -0.03062385
sd_NDVI              0.30776557          -0.22077048          0.36444359
m_NDVI               1.00000000          0.35942413          -0.20038837
m_NDVI               0.35942413          1.00000000          -0.70002659
prop_flooded_area_ha -0.20038837          -0.70002659          1.00000000

```

SPECIES RICHNESS

```
> M <- glm(No.Species ~ Forestry_F + Herbaceous.crops + Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds + Rice.fields + Natural.grasslands + Natural.shrublands + Rivers.and.riparian.galleries + Woody.crops + max_NDVI + prop_flooded_area_ha + m_NDVI + sd_NDVI, family=quasipoisson, data= Dabbling_ducks_season)
>
> VIF(M)
              Forestry_F              Herbaceous.crops Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds              Rice.fields              Natural.grasslands              Natural.shrublands
Rivers.and.riparian.galleries 1.088824              1.124937              2.152214              2.663394              1.136953              1.164081
              1.230673              1.185790              1.430579              prop_flooded_area_ha              m_NDVI              sd_NDVI
              1.583883              2.489690              2.536968
>
> summary(M)

Call:
glm(formula = No.Species ~ Forestry_F + Herbaceous.crops + Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds + Rice.fields + Natural.grasslands + Natural.shrublands + Rivers.and.riparian.galleries + Woody.crops + max_NDVI + prop_flooded_area_ha + m_NDVI + sd_NDVI, family = quasipoisson, data = Dabbling_ducks_season)

Deviance Residuals:
    Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
-2.5388  -0.7923  -0.1153   0.5762   3.4397

Coefficients:
              Estimate Std. Error t value Pr(>|t|)
(Intercept)    -7.388e-01  6.222e-01  -1.187  0.23567
Forestry_F     -5.273e+00  7.960e-01  -6.624 9.04e-11 ***
Herbaceous.crops -5.553e-01  2.020e-01  -2.749  0.00620 **
Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds 5.844e-01  2.383e-01  2.453  0.01452 **
Rice.fields    -1.579e+00  1.717e-01  -9.197 < 2e-16 ***
Natural.grasslands -5.393e-01  1.735e-01  -3.109  0.00199 ***
Natural.shrublands -3.025e+00  6.666e-01  -4.538 7.11e-06 ***
Rivers.and.riparian.galleries 3.506e-01  1.623e-01  2.160  0.03126 *
Woody.crops    -2.145e+00  1.682e+00  -1.275  0.20275
max_NDVI       6.441e-03  2.600e-03  2.477  0.01359 *
prop_flooded_area_ha -3.360e-02  9.954e-02  -0.338  0.73585
m_NDVI         9.030e-03  4.046e-03  2.232  0.02608 *
sd_NDVI        7.082e-06  1.098e-06  6.448 2.66e-10 ***
---
Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

(Dispersion parameter for quasipoisson family taken to be 1.03503)

Null deviance: 805.36 on 514 degrees of freedom
Residual deviance: 525.36 on 502 degrees of freedom
AIC: NA

Number of Fisher Scoring iterations: 5
>
> r2adj <- adjR2(M)
> r2adj
[1] 0.3321
```

DENSITY OF INDIVIDUALS

```
> M <- glm(nind_ha_adj ~ Forestry_F + Herbaceous.crops + Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds + Rice.fields + Natural.grasslands + Natural.shrublands + Rivers.and.riparian.galleries + Woody.crops + max_NDVI + prop_flooded_area_ha + m_NDVI + sd_NDVI, family=Gamma(link="log"), data= Dabbling_ducks_season)
>
> VIF(M)
              Forestry_F              Herbaceous.crops Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds              Rice.fields              Natural.grasslands              Natural.shrublands
Rivers.and.riparian.galleries 1.160790              1.200100              1.819146              2.821438              1.150813              1.172125
              1.208177              1.236319              1.558643              prop_flooded_area_ha              m_NDVI              sd_NDVI
              1.543598              2.224878              2.361387
>
> summary(M, dispersion=1)

Call:
glm(formula = nind_ha_adj ~ Forestry_F + Herbaceous.crops + Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds + Rice.fields + Natural.grasslands + Natural.shrublands + Rivers.and.riparian.galleries + Woody.crops + max_NDVI + prop_flooded_area_ha + m_NDVI + sd_NDVI, family = Gamma(link = "log"), data = Dabbling_ducks_season)

Deviance Residuals:
    Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
-3.8265  -2.0361  -1.1370   0.1765   4.4182

Coefficients:
              Estimate Std. Error z value Pr(>|z|)
(Intercept)    3.136e-01  1.127e+00  0.278  0.781
Forestry_F    -4.248e+00  8.499e-01  -4.999 5.76e-07 ***
Herbaceous.crops 3.707e-01  3.333e-01  1.112  0.266
Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds 3.976e-01  5.069e-01  0.784  0.433
Rice.fields    -2.628e+00  2.840e-01  -9.253 < 2e-16 ***
Natural.grasslands -1.742e+00  2.854e-01  -6.105 1.03e-09 ***
Natural.shrublands 9.954e-01  1.105e+00  0.901  0.368
Rivers.and.riparian.galleries 1.606e+00  3.104e-01  5.173 2.30e-07 ***
Woody.crops    1.172e+00  2.236e+00  0.524  0.600
max_NDVI       -2.164e-02  5.170e-03  -4.186 2.83e-05 ***
prop_flooded_area_ha 3.060e+00  1.918e-01  15.951 < 2e-16 ***
m_NDVI         3.478e-02  7.226e-03  4.813 1.48e-06 ***
sd_NDVI        -2.170e-05  2.084e-06 -10.412 < 2e-16 ***
---
Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

(Dispersion parameter for Gamma family taken to be 1)

Null deviance: 2298.9 on 514 degrees of freedom
Residual deviance: 1548.7 on 502 degrees of freedom
AIC: 2421.8

Number of Fisher Scoring iterations: 25
>
> r2adj <- adjR2(M)
> r2adj
[1] 0.3102
```

DIVING_BIRDS_SPRING

	Forestry	Herbaceous.crops	Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds	Marches	Natural.grasslands	Natural.shrublands	Rice.fields	Rivers.and.riparian.galleries	Woody.crops	sd_NDVI
Forestry	1.00000000	-0.1647328	-0.145313604	-0.24591985	0.47321556	0.69720802	-0.07527626	0.137968074	0.11102889	-0.31504783
Herbaceous.crops	-0.16473280	1.00000000	0.344709377	-0.49691864	0.11613590	-0.15095891	0.50046766	0.406811247	0.25639715	0.15291716
Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds	-0.14531360	0.34470937	1.000000000	-0.20381948	-0.07607768	-0.17040756	0.23234153	-0.004516576	-0.10742284	0.44766883
Marches	-0.24591985	-0.49691864	-0.20381948	1.000000000	-0.50085136	-0.20973028	-0.40205928	-0.484006739	-0.28160769	0.21697244
Natural.grasslands	0.47321556	0.11613590	-0.07607768	-0.50085136	1.000000000	0.44429599	0.10212196	0.100183954	0.28297546	-0.19453416
Natural.shrublands	0.69720802	-0.15095891	-0.17040756	-0.20973028	0.44429599	1.000000000	-0.19174641	0.188947077	0.19764016	-0.35192101
Rice.fields	-0.07527626	0.50046777	0.232341529	-0.40205928	0.10212196	-0.19174641	1.000000000	0.137313674	0.37854840	0.31898779
Rivers.and.riparian.galleries	0.13796807	0.4068112	-0.004516576	-0.48400674	0.10018395	0.18894708	0.13731367	1.000000000	0.22659466	-0.16770406
Woody.crops	0.11102889	0.2563972	-0.107422837	-0.28160769	0.28297546	0.19764016	0.37854840	0.226594664	1.000000000	0.01313756
sd_NDVI	-0.31504783	0.1529172	0.447668826	0.21697244	-0.19453416	-0.35192101	0.31898779	-0.167704061	0.01313756	1.000000000
max_NDVI	0.27112074	-0.1314597	-0.106948812	0.06888007	0.10160913	0.30818341	0.15620914	0.016829247	0.12599012	0.22653099
m_NDVI	-0.01247792	-0.2329608	-0.347830169	0.20360414	0.17446500	0.16562838	0.07523686	-0.245380264	0.21107914	-0.05540181
prop_flooded_area_ha	-0.10632899	-0.2028313	-0.220123481	0.27463455	-0.20459652	-0.07247025	-0.43561919	-0.106806745	-0.19156021	0.06247871
	max_NDVI	m_NDVI	prop_flooded_area_ha							
Forestry	0.27112074	-0.01247792	-0.10632899							
Herbaceous.crops	-0.13145966	-0.23296081	-0.20283132							
Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds	-0.10694881	-0.34783017	-0.22012348							
Marches	0.06888007	0.20360414	0.27463455							
Natural.grasslands	0.10160913	0.17446500	-0.20459652							
Natural.shrublands	0.30818341	0.16562838	-0.07247025							
Rice.fields	0.15620914	0.07523686	-0.43561919							
Rivers.and.riparian.galleries	0.01682925	0.24538026	-0.10680675							
Woody.crops	0.12599012	0.21107914	-0.19156021							
sd_NDVI	0.22653099	-0.05540181	0.06247871							
max_NDVI	1.00000000	0.44817260	-0.05836507							
m_NDVI	0.44817260	1.00000000	-0.25440900							
prop_flooded_area_ha	-0.05836507	-0.25440900	1.00000000							

SPECIES RICHNESS

```

> M <- glm(No..Species ~ Forestry_F + Herbaceous.crops + Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds + Rice.fields + Natural.grasslands + Natural.shrublands + Rivers.and.riparian.galleries + Woody.crops + max_NDVI + prop_flooded_area_ha + m_NDVI + sd_NDVI, family=quasipoisson, data= Diving_birds_season)
>
> VIF(M)
              Forestry_F              Herbaceous.crops  Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds              Rice.fields              Natural.grasslands              Natural.shrublands
Rivers.and.riparian.galleries              Woody.crops              max_NDVI              prop_flooded_area_ha              m_NDVI              sd_NDVI
              1.254250              1.58355              1.574099              1.305695              1.394989              1.192698
              1.508626              1.391592              1.326289              1.515181              1.939043              1.605552
>
> summary(M)

Call:
glm(formula = No..Species ~ Forestry_F + Herbaceous.crops + Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds + Rice.fields + Natural.grasslands + Natural.shrublands + Rivers.and.riparian.galleries + Woody.crops + max_NDVI + prop_flooded_area_ha + m_NDVI + sd_NDVI, family = quasipoisson, data = Diving_birds_season)

Deviance Residuals:
    Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
-1.2130  -0.3907   0.1149   0.2670   1.1611

Coefficients:
              Estimate Std. Error t value Pr(>|t|)
(Intercept)  2.584e-01  3.610e-01  0.716 0.474758
Forestry_F   -7.186e-02  4.520e-01 -0.159 0.873801
Herbaceous.crops  1.133e-01  2.719e-01  0.417 0.677260
Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds  1.097e+00  1.345e-01  8.155 0.07e-15 ***
Rice.fields   -3.163e-01  1.269e-01 -2.493 0.013181 *
Natural.grasslands  1.505e-01  1.241e-01  1.213 0.226216
Natural.shrublands  9.708e-01  6.509e-01  1.491 0.136831
Rivers.and.riparian.galleries  4.388e-02  1.133e-01  0.387 0.698895
Woody.crops   -1.838e+00  2.097e+00 -0.876 0.381548
max_NDVI     -3.505e-04  2.139e-03 -0.164 0.869961
prop_flooded_area_ha  3.010e-01  8.628e-02  3.488 0.000554 ***
m_NDVI       1.581e-04  1.423e-03  0.111 0.911580
sd_NDVI      2.526e-06  6.995e-07  3.612 0.000353 ***
---
Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

(Dispersion parameter for quasipoisson family taken to be 0.1627708)

Null deviance: 76.674  on 331  degrees of freedom
Residual deviance: 53.439  on 319  degrees of freedom
AIC: NA

Number of Fisher Scoring iterations: 4

>
> teste <- adjR2(M)
> teste
[1] 0.2768
    
```

DENSITY OF INDIVIDUALS

```
> M <- glm(nind_ha_adj ~ Forestry_F + Herbaceous.crops + Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds + Marches + Natural.grasslands + Natural.shrublands + Rivers.and.riparian.galleries + Woody.crops + max_NDVI + prop_flooded_area_ha + m_NDVI + sd_NDVI, family=Gamma(link="log"), data= Diving_birds_season)
>
> VIF(M)
              Forestry_F              Herbaceous.crops Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds              Marches              Natural.grasslands              Natural.shrublands
Rivers.and.riparian.galleries 1.295586              1.346617              1.776777              4.050348              2.438701              1.198872
                2.524965              Woody.crops              max_NDVI              prop_flooded_area_ha              m_NDVI              sd_NDVI
                1.455458              1.366557              1.413424              1.905952              1.405913
>
> summary(M, dispersion=1)

Call:
glm(formula = nind_ha_adj ~ Forestry_F + Herbaceous.crops + Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds + Marches + Natural.grasslands + Natural.shrublands + Rivers.and.riparian.galleries + Woody.crops + max_NDVI + prop_flooded_area_ha + m_NDVI + sd_NDVI, family = Gamma(link = "log"), data = Diving_birds_season)

Deviance Residuals:
    Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
-3.3264 -1.2527 -0.6338  0.2242  3.3571

Coefficients:
(Intercept)              6.121e+00  1.194e+00  5.125  2.97e-07 ***
Forestry_F                3.211e+00  1.400e+00  2.294  0.0218 *
Herbaceous.crops          8.498e-01  1.030e+00  0.825  0.4094
Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds -9.464e-01  5.434e-01 -1.742  0.0816 .
Marches                   -6.084e-01  3.392e-01 -1.793  0.0729 .
Natural.grasslands        -8.071e-01  5.193e-01 -1.554  0.1201
Natural.shrublands         1.153e+00  2.163e+00  0.533  0.5941
Rivers.and.riparian.galleries -1.031e+00  4.658e-01 -2.213  0.0269 *
Woody.crops               -1.047e+01  6.170e+00 -1.696  0.0898 .
max_NDVI                  -4.362e-02  7.009e-03 -6.224  4.86e-10 ***
prop_flooded_area_ha      3.797e+00  2.629e-01 14.440 < 2e-16 ***
m_NDVI                    -8.627e-03  4.601e-03 -1.875  0.0608 .
sd_NDVI                   -2.319e-05  2.330e-06 -9.952 < 2e-16 ***
---
Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

(Dispersion parameter for Gamma family taken to be 1)

Null deviance: 996.01 on 323 degrees of freedom
Residual deviance: 511.72 on 311 degrees of freedom
(8 observations deleted due to missingness)
AIC: -184.3

Number of Fisher Scoring iterations: 12
>
> teste <- adjR2(M)
> teste
[1] 0.4664
```

DIVING_BIRDS_SUMMER

	Forestry	Herbaceous.crops	Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds	Marches	Natural.grasslands	Natural.shrublands	Rice.fields	Rivers.and.riparian.galleries	Woody.crops	sd_NDVI
Forestry	1.00000000	-0.09012231	0.06600754	-0.27092137	0.423402470	0.63093204	-0.210000167	0.123894032	0.12554524	-0.29739211
Herbaceous.crops	-0.09012231	1.00000000	0.26330638	-0.38722287	0.134149971	-0.12693938	0.295891813	0.272974290	0.15762775	0.12672936
Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds	0.06600754	0.26330638	1.00000000	-0.18854019	-0.035824002	-0.04602749	0.114024095	-0.151976636	-0.11820826	0.45726051
Marches	-0.27092137	-0.38722287	-0.18854019	1.00000000	-0.522168859	-0.16675227	-0.367791370	-0.396494170	-0.25481462	0.10004073
Natural.grasslands	0.423402470	0.134149971	-0.035824002	-0.522168859	1.000000000	0.420459904	-0.007927114	0.140959905	0.22548895	-0.20189065
Natural.shrublands	0.63093204	-0.12693938	-0.04602749	-0.16675227	0.420459904	1.000000000	-0.305767994	0.140959905	0.14831650	-0.38263460
Rice.fields	-0.210000167	0.295891813	0.11402410	-0.36779137	-0.007927114	-0.30576799	1.000000000	-0.033287524	0.29942303	0.45336263
Rivers.and.riparian.galleries	0.123894032	0.27297429	-0.15197664	-0.39649417	0.090314327	0.14095991	-0.033287524	1.000000000	0.15284041	-0.23893356
Woody.crops	0.12554524	0.15762775	-0.11820826	-0.25481462	0.225488948	0.14831650	0.299423028	0.152840413	1.000000000	-0.04502122
sd_NDVI	-0.29739211	0.12672936	0.45726051	0.10004073	-0.201890645	-0.38263460	0.453362633	-0.238933556	-0.04502122	1.000000000
max_NDVI	0.19544842	0.03305367	0.21113205	-0.11753440	0.016529650	0.10440536	0.470404624	0.007394293	0.21190260	0.40947623
m_NDVI	-0.06470345	-0.30471944	-0.65145846	0.13362991	-0.116977928	0.05403085	0.134281972	-0.126381413	0.21339257	-0.23483067
prop_flooded_area_ha	0.19251790	-0.18670589	-0.24744568	-0.08793995	0.044945443	0.20755128	-0.342883750	0.150624483	-0.20750487	-0.21292425
	max_NDVI	m_NDVI	prop_flooded_area_ha							
Forestry	0.195448420	-0.06470345	0.19251790							
Herbaceous.crops	0.033053669	-0.30471944	-0.18670589							
Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds	0.211132055	-0.65145846	-0.24744568							
Marches	-0.117534404	0.13362991	-0.08793995							
Natural.grasslands	0.016529650	0.11697793	0.04494544							
Natural.shrublands	0.104405362	0.05403085	0.20755128							
Rice.fields	0.470404624	0.13428197	-0.34288375							
Rivers.and.riparian.galleries	0.007394293	-0.12638141	0.15062448							
Woody.crops	0.211902597	0.21339257	-0.20750487							
sd_NDVI	0.409476234	-0.23483067	-0.21292425							
max_NDVI	1.000000000	0.18335972	-0.14285046							
m_NDVI	0.183359718	1.000000000	0.04209012							
prop_flooded_area_ha	-0.142850460	0.04209012	1.000000000							

SPECIES RICHNESS

```
> M <- glm(No.Species ~ Forestry_F + Herbaceous.crops + Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds + Rice.fields + Natural.grasslands + Natural.shrublands + Rivers.and.riparian.galleries + Woody.crops + max_NDVI + prop_flooded_area_ha + m_NDVI + sd_NDVI, family=quasipoisson, data= Diving_birds_season)
>
> VIF(M)
              Forestry_F          Herbaceous.crops Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds          Rice.fields          Natural.grasslands          Natural.shrublands
Rivers.and.riparian.galleries 1.365490          1.118932          2.946079          1.778638          1.245842          1.251353
              1.723932          1.156334          1.549766          1.338249          3.136771          1.878068
>
> summary(M)

Call:
glm(formula = No.Species ~ Forestry_F + Herbaceous.crops + Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds + Rice.fields + Natural.grasslands + Natural.shrublands + Rivers.and.riparian.galleries + Woody.crops + max_NDVI + prop_flooded_area_ha + m_NDVI + sd_NDVI, family = quasipoisson, data = Diving_birds_season)

Deviance Residuals:
    Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
-0.7986 -0.3926 -0.1313  0.3294  1.0233

Coefficients:
              Estimate Std. Error t value Pr(>|t|)
(Intercept)  1.583e+00  6.238e-01  2.538  0.0119 *
Forestry_F   1.120e+00  7.979e-01  1.404  0.1618
Herbaceous.crops 1.605e-01  2.507e-01  0.640  0.5227
Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds 9.401e-02  2.419e-01  0.389  0.6979
Rice.fields  -3.465e-01  1.906e-01 -1.818  0.0705 .
Natural.grasslands -1.341e-02  2.116e-01 -0.063  0.9495
Natural.shrublands -4.861e-01  1.025e+00 -0.474  0.6360
Rivers.and.riparian.galleries -4.120e-01  1.738e-01 -2.371  0.0186 *
Woody.crops  -1.687e+00  2.480e+00 -0.680  0.4972
max_NDVI     -1.078e-04  2.857e-03 -0.038  0.9699
prop_flooded_area_ha 1.161e-01  1.266e-01  0.917  0.3600
m_NDVI      -9.359e-03  3.989e-03 -2.346  0.0199 *
sd_NDVI     2.579e-06  1.291e-06  1.997  0.0471 *
---
Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

(Dispersion parameter for quasipoisson family taken to be 0.2081062)

Null deviance: 52.848  on 225  degrees of freedom
Residual deviance: 43.426  on 213  degrees of freedom
AIC: NA

Number of Fisher Scoring iterations: 4

>
> teste <- adjR2(M)
> teste
[1] 0.132
```

DENSITY OF INDIVIDUALS

```
> M <- glm(nind_ha_adj ~ Forestry_F + Herbaceous.crops + Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds + Rice.fields + Natural.grasslands + Natural.shrublands + Rivers.and.riparian.galleries + Woody.crops + max_NDVI + prop_flooded_area_ha + m_NDVI + sd_NDVI, family=Gamma(link="log"), data= Diving_birds_season)
>
> VIF(M)
              Forestry_F          Herbaceous.crops Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds          Rice.fields          Natural.grasslands          Natural.shrublands
Rivers.and.riparian.galleries 1.355762          1.129227          2.720057          1.832199          1.272746          1.258457
              1.705815          1.189804          1.599970          1.362215          3.029157          1.854714
>
> summary(M, dispersion=1)

Call:
glm(formula = nind_ha_adj ~ Forestry_F + Herbaceous.crops + Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds + Rice.fields + Natural.grasslands + Natural.shrublands + Rivers.and.riparian.galleries + Woody.crops + max_NDVI + prop_flooded_area_ha + m_NDVI + sd_NDVI, family = Gamma(link = "log"), data = Diving_birds_season)

Deviance Residuals:
    Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
-3.080 -1.479 -0.848  0.052  4.730

Coefficients:
              Estimate Std. Error z value Pr(>|z|)
(Intercept) -5.441e+00  1.628e+00 -3.342  0.000831 ***
Forestry_F   1.396e+01  2.289e+00  6.099  1.06e-09 ***
Herbaceous.crops 3.961e+00  6.533e-01  6.064  1.33e-09 ***
Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds -7.595e-01  6.716e-01 -1.131  0.258133
Rice.Fields  -2.268e+00  4.734e-01 -4.791  1.66e-06 ***
Natural.grasslands -1.251e+00  5.369e-01 -2.330  0.019800 *
Natural.shrublands 1.024e+01  2.623e+00  3.903  9.49e-05 ***
Rivers.and.riparian.galleries -6.174e-01  4.407e-01 -1.401  0.161190
Woody.crops  -1.779e+01  5.486e+00 -3.242  0.001185 **
max_NDVI     4.182e-03  7.700e-03  0.543  0.587087
prop_flooded_area_ha 3.084e+00  3.339e-01  9.237  < 2e-16 ***
m_NDVI      1.333e-02  1.051e-02  1.267  0.204988
sd_NDVI     -2.364e-05  3.397e-06 -6.961  3.39e-12 ***
---
Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

(Dispersion parameter for Gamma family taken to be 1)

Null deviance: 896.13  on 225  degrees of freedom
Residual deviance: 454.40  on 213  degrees of freedom
AIC: -407.25

Number of Fisher Scoring iterations: 25

>
> teste <- adjR2(M)
> teste
[1] 0.4644
```

DIVING_BIRDS_WINTER

```

Forestry Herbaceous.crops Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds Marches Natural.grasslands Natural.shrublands Rice.fields Rivers.and.riparian.galleries Woody.crops sd_NDVI
Forestry 1.00000000 -0.122254513 -0.122659360 -0.27998825 0.46255832 0.700500392 -0.09176852 0.148870041 0.13883628 -0.35927142
Herbaceous.crops -0.12225451 1.000000000 0.271569244 -0.49093527 0.11295495 -0.098036471 0.45885182 0.445978877 0.27306532 0.15748162
Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds -0.12265936 0.271569244 1.000000000 -0.21164386 -0.09478937 -0.160648784 0.19334190 0.007121193 -0.12027268 0.42422997
Marches -0.27998825 -0.490935267 -0.211643857 1.000000000 -0.51946483 -0.257440042 -0.41724161 -0.429282172 -0.31445980 0.20945691
Natural.grasslands 0.46255832 0.112954946 -0.094789371 -0.51946483 1.000000000 0.451238385 0.08892660 0.081446865 0.29048648 -0.25399228
Natural.shrublands 0.70050039 -0.098036471 -0.160648784 -0.25744004 0.45123838 1.000000000 -0.13881955 0.204255985 0.23601534 -0.39528008
Rice.fields -0.09176852 0.458851823 0.193341901 -0.41724161 0.08892660 -0.138819554 1.000000000 0.126886324 0.37046074 0.35640943
Rivers.and.riparian.galleries 0.14887004 0.445978877 0.007121193 -0.42928217 0.08144687 0.204255985 0.12688632 1.000000000 0.22453057 -0.12275259
Woody.crops 0.13883628 0.273065316 -0.120272682 -0.31445980 0.29048648 0.236015342 0.37046074 0.224530569 1.00000000 0.03452884
sd_NDVI -0.35927142 0.157481616 0.424229968 0.20945691 -0.25399228 -0.395280076 0.35640943 -0.122752594 0.03452884 1.000000000
max_NDVI 0.10779174 0.184788151 0.219746834 -0.15002040 0.06583899 0.072200625 0.37114062 0.208612144 0.18304316 0.37615858
m_NDVI -0.07198019 -0.087259469 -0.089373494 0.03942076 0.12040875 -0.004615486 0.22715934 -0.156538341 0.14560167 -0.10712974
prop_flooded_area_ha -0.08213556 0.004584944 -0.083644775 0.17146251 -0.19043727 -0.068650852 -0.26570521 -0.084294619 -0.03423276 0.20379498
max_NDVI m_NDVI prop_flooded_area_ha
Forestry 0.10779174 -0.071980187 -0.082135561
Herbaceous.crops 0.18478815 -0.087259469 0.004584944
Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds 0.21974683 -0.089373494 -0.083644775
Marches -0.15002040 0.039420762 0.171462511
Natural.grasslands 0.06583899 0.120408750 -0.190437265
Natural.shrublands 0.07220062 -0.004615486 -0.068650852
Rice.fields 0.37114062 0.227159342 -0.265705208
Rivers.and.riparian.galleries 0.20861214 -0.156538341 -0.084294619
Woody.crops 0.18304316 0.145601667 -0.034232763
sd_NDVI 0.37615858 -0.107129741 0.203794985
max_NDVI 1.00000000 0.243753400 -0.146138928
m_NDVI 0.24375340 1.000000000 -0.656637687
prop_flooded_area_ha -0.14613893 -0.656637687 1.000000000

```

SPECIES RICHNESS

```

> M <- glm(No..Species ~ Forestry_F + Herbaceous.crops + Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds + Rice.fields + Natural.grasslands + Natural.shrublands + Rivers.and.riparian.galleries + Woody.crops + max_NDVI +
prop_flooded_area_ha + m_NDVI + sd_NDVI, family=quasipoisson, data= Diving_birds_season)

```

```

>
> VIF(M)

```

	Forestry_F	Herbaceous.crops	Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds	Rice.fields	Natural.grasslands	Natural.shrublands
Forestry_F	1.244302					
Herbaceous.crops		1.171605				
Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds			1.187223			
Rice.fields				1.297771		
Natural.grasslands					1.471266	
Natural.shrublands						1.179844
Rivers.and.riparian.galleries		Woody.crops	max_NDVI	prop_flooded_area_ha	m_NDVI	sd_NDVI
	1.371937	1.467794	1.334389	2.022153	2.122188	1.844345

```

> summary(M)

```

```

Call:
glm(formula = No..Species ~ Forestry_F + Herbaceous.crops + Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds +
Rice.fields + Natural.grasslands + Natural.shrublands + Rivers.and.riparian.galleries +
Woody.crops + max_NDVI + prop_flooded_area_ha + m_NDVI +
sd_NDVI, family = quasipoisson, data = Diving_birds_season)

```

```

Deviance Residuals:
    Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
-0.7484 -0.3527 -0.1341  0.3790  1.0053

```

```

Coefficients:
(Intercept)                2.869e-01  4.884e-01  0.587  0.55736
Forestry_F                 -1.076e-01  7.022e-01 -0.153  0.87834
Herbaceous.crops          -9.176e-02  2.803e-01 -0.327  0.74359
Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds  3.944e-01  1.545e-01  2.552  0.01126 *
Rice.fields                -5.691e-01  1.749e-01 -3.254  0.00128 **
Natural.grasslands        -2.809e-01  1.632e-01 -1.722  0.08624 .
Natural.shrublands        -5.976e-01  9.552e-01 -0.626  0.53212
Rivers.and.riparian.galleries  1.041e-01  1.534e-01  0.679  0.49801
Woody.crops                2.723e+00  2.544e+00  1.070  0.28553
max_NDVI                   9.830e-04  2.731e-03  0.360  0.71919
prop_flooded_area_ha      -3.877e-02  1.238e-01 -0.313  0.75439
m_NDVI                     -9.586e-04  2.056e-03 -0.466  0.64146
sd_NDVI                    3.648e-06  8.250e-07  4.422  1.41e-05 ***
---
Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

```

```

(Dispersion parameter for quasipoisson family taken to be 0.1966126)

```

```

Null deviance: 62.711 on 283 degrees of freedom
Residual deviance: 51.969 on 271 degrees of freedom
AIC: NA

```

```

Number of Fisher Scoring iterations: 4

```

```

>
> teste <- adjR2(M)
> teste
[1] 0.1346

```

DENSITY OF INDIVIDUALS

```

> M <- glm(nind_ha_adj ~ Forestry_F + Herbaceous.crops + Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds + Rice.fields + Natural.grasslands + Natural.shrublands + Rivers.and.riparian.galleries + Woody.crops + max_NDVI +
prop_flooded_area_ha + m_NDVI, family=Gamma(link="log"), data= Diving_birds_season)
>
> VIF(M)
              Forestry_F              Herbaceous.crops Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds              Rice.fields              Natural.grasslands              Natural.shrublands
              1.236671              1.166771              1.178798              1.335521              1.390988              1.174561
Rivers.and.riparian.galleries              Woody.crops              max_NDVI              prop_flooded_area_ha              m_NDVI              sd_NDVI
              1.360612              1.394559              1.321625              2.020506              2.115767              1.786359
>
> summary(M, dispersion=1)

Call:
glm(formula = nind_ha_adj ~ Forestry_F + Herbaceous.crops + Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds +
Rice.fields + Natural.grasslands + Natural.shrublands + Rivers.and.riparian.galleries +
Woody.crops + max_NDVI + prop_flooded_area_ha + m_NDVI +
sd_NDVI, family = Gamma(link = "log"), data = Diving_birds_season)

Deviance Residuals:
    Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
-3.4633 -1.4810 -0.7212  0.2146  4.6023

Coefficients:
              Estimate Std. Error z value Pr(>|z|)
(Intercept)  1.671e+00  1.344e+00  1.244  0.2136
Forestry_F   9.480e+00  1.807e+00  5.247 1.54e-07 ***
Herbaceous.crops  1.639e-01  7.712e-01  0.212  0.8317
Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds -1.032e+00  4.578e-01 -2.254  0.0242 *
Rice.fields  -2.287e+00  4.408e-01 -5.188 2.12e-07 ***
Natural.grasslands  3.812e-01  3.972e-01  0.960  0.3372
Natural.shrublands -1.787e+00  2.466e+00 -0.724  0.4688
Rivers.and.riparian.galleries -3.710e-01  4.162e-01 -0.891  0.3728
Woody.crops  -1.400e+01  6.764e+00 -2.070  0.0384 *
max_NDVI     -1.874e-02  7.422e-03 -2.525  0.0116 *
prop_flooded_area_ha  2.135e+00  3.354e-01  6.366 1.94e-10 ***
m_NDVI       2.063e-03  5.621e-03  0.367  0.7137
sd_NDVI     -1.450e-05  2.365e-06 -6.131 8.73e-10 ***
---
Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

(Dispersion parameter for Gamma family taken to be 1)

Null deviance: 833.14 on 283 degrees of freedom
Residual deviance: 581.57 on 271 degrees of freedom
AIC: 310.98

Number of Fisher Scoring iterations: 18

>
> teste <- adjR2(M)
> teste
[1] 0.271

```

DIVING_BIRDS_AUTUMN

	Forestry	Herbaceous.crops	Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds	Marches	Natural.grasslands	Natural.shrublands	Rice.fields	Rivers.and.riparian.galleries	Woody.crops
Forestry	1.000000000	-0.04143818	0.001225711	-0.25232368	0.4301981648	0.64941799	-0.16237435	0.1861475224	0.1768846
Herbaceous.crops	-0.041438179	1.000000000	0.265439154	-0.47449693	0.2627203925	-0.01896846	0.37057921	0.2907993418	0.1886738
Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds	0.001225711	0.26543915	1.000000000	-0.13774438	-0.0295882456	-0.06173868	0.10325444	-0.1869847895	-0.1645444
Marches	-0.252323683	-0.47449693	-0.137744384	1.000000000	-0.5749641407	-0.23834930	-0.46833447	-0.4623167059	-0.3298402
Natural.grasslands	0.430198165	0.26272039	-0.029588246	-0.57496414	1.0000000000	0.46084126	0.11625342	0.2476541150	0.4028266
Natural.shrublands	0.649417989	-0.01896846	-0.061738681	-0.23834930	0.4608412556	1.000000000	-0.23014434	0.2815827732	0.2999234
Rice.fields	-0.162374351	0.37057921	0.103254437	-0.46833447	0.1162534200	-0.23014434	1.000000000	0.0477268118	0.3304097
Rivers.and.riparian.galleries	0.186147522	0.29079934	-0.186984790	-0.46231671	0.2476541150	0.28158277	0.04772681	1.0000000000	0.2539917
Woody.crops	0.176884591	0.18867383	-0.164544450	-0.32984016	0.4028265572	0.29992340	0.33040968	0.2539917194	1.00000000
sd_NDVI	-0.130137343	0.30857184	0.573492108	-0.20501150	0.0002979613	-0.27677097	0.51668352	-0.0887309469	-0.0269649
max_NDVI	0.295966173	0.03903362	0.304198031	-0.08820978	-0.0094606617	0.15464015	0.27511036	0.0171620508	0.1214198
m_NDVI	-0.008828083	-0.20885133	-0.611325615	0.03254152	0.0352614639	0.04295604	0.18709306	-0.0009893662	0.2623156
prop_flooded_area_ha	0.157760321	-0.07387171	0.207694966	-0.11285387	0.0286680548	0.12665657	-0.16925317	-0.0794928477	-0.2184488
	sd_NDVI	max_NDVI	m_NDVI	prop_flooded_area_ha					
Forestry	-0.1301373426	0.295966173	-0.0088280830	0.15776032					
Herbaceous.crops	0.3085718360	0.039033615	-0.2088513273	-0.07387171					
Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds	0.5734921079	0.304198031	-0.6113256148	0.20769497					
Marches	-0.2050114963	-0.088209784	0.0325415164	-0.11285387					
Natural.grasslands	0.0002979613	-0.009460662	0.0325415164	0.02866805					
Natural.shrublands	-0.2767709728	0.154640150	0.0429560354	0.12665657					
Rice.fields	0.5166835231	0.275110357	0.1870930622	-0.16925317					
Rivers.and.riparian.galleries	-0.0887309469	0.017162051	-0.0009893662	-0.07949285					
Woody.crops	-0.0269649000	0.121419799	0.2623156361	-0.21844883					
sd_NDVI	1.0000000000	0.359774643	-0.3634535629	0.29294732					
max_NDVI	0.3597746434	1.0000000000	0.0699470085	-0.09051922					
m_NDVI	-0.3634535629	0.069947009	1.0000000000	-0.29837307					
prop_flooded_area_ha	0.2929473191	-0.090519221	-0.2983730735	1.000000000					

SPECIES RICHNESS

```
> M <- glm(No..Species ~ Forestry_F + Herbaceous.crops + Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds + Marches + Natural.grasslands + Natural.shrublands + Rivers.and.riparian.galleries + Woody.crops + max_NDVI + prop_flooded_area_ha + m_NDVI + sd_NDVI, family=quasipoisson, data= Diving_birds_season)
>
> VIF(M)
              Forestry_F          Herbaceous.crops Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds          Marches          Natural.grasslands          Natural.shrublands
Rivers.and.riparian.galleries  1.759643                1.468014                3.818728                4.498021                2.280147                1.294434
                                3.622545                1.480234                max_NDVI                prop_flooded_area_ha                m_NDVI                sd_NDVI
                                1.480234                1.441762                1.642456                2.825261                2.044432
>
> summary(M)

Call:
glm(formula = No..Species ~ Forestry_F + Herbaceous.crops + Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds + Marches + Natural.grasslands + Natural.shrublands + Rivers.and.riparian.galleries + Woody.crops + max_NDVI + prop_flooded_area_ha + m_NDVI + sd_NDVI, family = quasipoisson, data = Diving_birds_season)

Deviance Residuals:
    Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
-0.7269 -0.3028 -0.1336  0.2631  1.5226

Coefficients:
            (Intercept)          -1.418e-01  6.773e-01  -0.209  0.834369
          Forestry_F              8.010e-01  1.890e+00  0.424  0.672144
        Herbaceous.crops          4.328e-01  2.738e-01  1.581  0.115428
    Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds  9.322e-01  2.646e-01  3.523  0.000526 ***
          Marches                  4.620e-01  1.547e-01  2.986  0.003171 **
        Natural.grasslands          3.751e-01  2.444e-01  1.535  0.126361
        Natural.shrublands          -1.221e+00  1.049e+00  -1.163  0.246142
    Rivers.and.riparian.galleries      4.196e-01  2.314e-01  1.813  0.071233 .
          Woody.crops               -2.704e+00  2.659e+00  -1.017  0.310463
          max_NDVI                   2.085e-05  2.443e-03  0.009  0.993199
    prop_flooded_area_ha              -2.287e-01  1.111e-01  -2.060  0.040681 *
          m_NDVI                     2.480e-04  4.855e-03  0.061  0.951296
          sd_NDVI                     3.537e-06  1.085e-06  3.260  0.001305 **
---
Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

(Dispersion parameter for quasipoisson family taken to be 0.1599784)

Null deviance: 38.946  on 218  degrees of freedom
Residual deviance: 30.818  on 206  degrees of freedom
AIC: NA

Number of Fisher Scoring iterations: 4

>
> teste <- adjR2(M)
> teste
[1] 0.1626
```

DENSITY OF INDIVIDUALS

```
> M <- glm(nind_ha_adj ~ Forestry_F + Herbaceous.crops + Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds + Rice.fields + Natural.grasslands + Natural.shrublands + Rivers.and.riparian.galleries + Woody.crops + max_NDVI + prop_flooded_area_ha + m_NDVI + sd_NDVI, family=Gamma(link="log"), data= Diving_birds_season)
>
> VIF(M)
              Forestry_F          Herbaceous.crops Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds          Rice.fields          Natural.grasslands          Natural.shrublands
Rivers.and.riparian.galleries  1.799675                1.083697                2.296397                2.281656                1.559700                1.335988
                                1.987552                1.558146                max_NDVI                prop_flooded_area_ha                m_NDVI                sd_NDVI
                                1.524939                1.578663                2.759922                2.291482
>
> summary(M, dispersion=1)

Call:
glm(formula = nind_ha_adj ~ Forestry_F + Herbaceous.crops + Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds + Rice.fields + Natural.grasslands + Natural.shrublands + Rivers.and.riparian.galleries + Woody.crops + max_NDVI + prop_flooded_area_ha + m_NDVI + sd_NDVI, family = Gamma(link = "log"), data = Diving_birds_season)

Deviance Residuals:
    Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
-3.3451 -1.5451 -0.7901 -0.0403  5.6829

Coefficients:
            (Intercept)          1.677e+00  1.739e+00  0.965  0.334762
          Forestry_F              4.124e+01  5.247e+00  7.861  3.81e-15 ***
        Herbaceous.crops          2.537e+00  6.732e-01  3.768  0.000164 ***
    Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds  -2.269e+00  6.322e-01  -3.589  0.000332 ***
          Rice.fields              -3.022e+00  4.968e-01  -6.083  1.18e-09 ***
        Natural.grasslands          -2.767e+00  5.411e-01  -5.114  3.16e-07 ***
        Natural.shrublands          -1.283e+00  2.779e+00  -0.462  0.644237
    Rivers.and.riparian.galleries      -1.708e+00  4.836e-01  -3.532  0.000412 ***
          Woody.crops               1.894e+00  6.766e+00  0.280  0.779542
          max_NDVI                   -3.192e-02  7.266e-03  -4.393  1.12e-05 ***
    prop_flooded_area_ha              2.407e+00  3.143e-01  7.659  1.87e-14 ***
          m_NDVI                     1.456e-02  1.134e-02  1.285  0.198909
          sd_NDVI                     -1.150e-05  3.436e-06  -3.346  0.000818 ***
---
Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

(Dispersion parameter for Gamma family taken to be 1)

Null deviance: 878.91  on 218  degrees of freedom
Residual deviance: 444.66  on 206  degrees of freedom
AIC: -191.91

Number of Fisher Scoring iterations: 19

>
> teste <- adjR2(M)
> teste
[1] 0.4646
```

FISHING_BIRDS_SPRING

	Forestry	Herbaceous.crops	Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds	Marches	Natural.grasslands	Natural.shrublands	Rice.fields	Rivers.and.riparian.galleries	Woody.crops
Forestry	1.0000000000	-0.04883452	-0.125826140	-0.19687812	0.36936082	0.64609360	-0.03358247	0.099884876	0.13597691
Herbaceous.crops	-0.0488345194	1.000000000	0.249567848	-0.55221428	0.08030691	-0.09528118	0.56215469	0.368344047	0.41562437
Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds	-0.1258261398	0.24956785	1.000000000	-0.06730538	-0.09506365	-0.16578261	0.07297130	-0.007462464	-0.17478783
Marches	-0.1968781221	-0.55221428	-0.067305379	1.000000000	-0.41867470	-0.10910841	-0.54749247	-0.389579802	-0.44737109
Natural.grasslands	0.3693608236	0.08030691	-0.095063652	-0.41867470	1.000000000	0.45380885	0.01682464	0.041650650	0.11610744
Natural.shrublands	0.6460935983	-0.09528118	-0.165782609	-0.10910841	0.45380885	1.000000000	-0.19736620	0.137158655	0.09403536
Rice.fields	-0.0335824699	0.56215469	0.072971303	-0.54749247	0.01682464	-0.19736620	1.000000000	0.124364901	0.49965500
Rivers.and.riparian.galleries	0.0998848755	0.36834405	-0.007462464	-0.38957980	0.04165065	0.13715865	0.12436490	1.000000000	0.21212813
Woody.crops	0.1359769063	0.41562437	-0.174787830	-0.44737109	0.11610744	0.09403536	0.49965500	0.212128130	1.000000000
sd_NDVI	-0.3777195002	0.06714643	0.402132492	0.24496775	-0.29146040	-0.40040908	0.16379772	-0.245080109	0.03241100
max_NDVI	0.2575184773	-0.04163362	-0.162465049	0.02820916	0.04633534	0.27857322	0.17157473	-0.001575879	0.13382327
m_NDVI	0.0001786674	-0.19594164	-0.370317777	0.09720696	0.20324707	0.18612752	0.01684011	-0.210503892	0.14068665
prop_flooded_area_ha	-0.0226903819	-0.30138801	-0.140282804	0.37257504	-0.13476964	0.04118826	-0.47482255	-0.088446563	-0.18102817
	sd_NDVI	max_NDVI	m_NDVI	prop_flooded_area_ha					
Forestry	-0.37771950	0.257518477	0.0001786674	-0.02269038					
Herbaceous.crops	0.06714643	-0.041633622	-0.1959416449	-0.30138801					
Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds	0.40213249	-0.162465049	-0.3703177768	-0.14028280					
Marches	0.24496775	0.028209161	0.0972069606	0.37257504					
Natural.grasslands	-0.29146040	0.046335340	0.2032470747	-0.13476964					
Natural.shrublands	-0.40040908	0.278573220	0.1861275164	0.04118826					
Rice.fields	0.16379772	0.171574728	0.0168401065	-0.47482255					
Rivers.and.riparian.galleries	-0.24508011	-0.001575879	-0.2105038921	-0.08844656					
Woody.crops	0.03241100	0.133823274	0.1406866527	-0.18102817					
sd_NDVI	1.000000000	0.084197360	-0.1350679452	0.23134648					
max_NDVI	0.08419736	1.000000000	0.4549507358	-0.04480897					
m_NDVI	-0.13506795	0.454950736	1.0000000000	-0.27368472					
prop_flooded_area_ha	0.23134648	-0.044808967	-0.2736847164	1.00000000					

SPECIES RICHNESS

```

> M <- glm(No. Species ~ Forestry_F + Herbaceous.crops + Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds + Marches + Natural.grasslands + Natural.shrublands + Rivers.and.riparian.galleries + Woody.crops + max_NDVI + prop_flooded_area_ha + m_NDVI + sd_NDVI, family=quasipoisson, data= Fishing_birds_season)
>
> VIF(M)
              Forestry_F              Herbaceous.crops Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds              Marches              Natural.grasslands              Natural.shrublands
Rivers.and.riparian.galleries              Woody.crops              max_NDVI              prop_flooded_area_ha              m_NDVI
              2.021577              1.234002              1.289000              1.87224              2.003661              1.920224
>
> summary(M)

Call:
glm(formula = No. Species ~ Forestry_F + Herbaceous.crops + Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds + Marches + Natural.grasslands + Natural.shrublands + Rivers.and.riparian.galleries + Woody.crops + max_NDVI + prop_flooded_area_ha + m_NDVI + sd_NDVI, family = quasipoisson, data = Fishing_birds_season)

Deviance Residuals:
    Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
-1.81440 -0.56668 -0.05184  0.38078  1.79328

Coefficients:
            Estimate Std. Error t value Pr(>|t|)
(Intercept)  1.293e-01  5.496e-01  0.235  0.814216
Forestry_F   -9.075e-01  8.144e-01 -1.114  0.265996
Herbaceous.crops  9.953e-01  2.927e-01  3.401  0.000762 ***
Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds  1.580e+00  1.921e-01  8.223  5.74e-15 ***
Marches       5.443e-01  1.306e-01  4.168  4.00e-05 ***
Natural.grasslands  3.820e-01  1.935e-01  1.974  0.049274 *
Natural.shrublands -3.122e+00  1.367e+00 -2.284  0.023077 *
Rivers.and.riparian.galleries  4.029e-01  2.080e-01  1.937  0.053613 .
Woody.crops    -2.354e+00  1.738e+00 -1.355  0.176525
max_NDVI       4.963e-03  3.198e-03  1.552  0.121730
prop_flooded_area_ha -6.204e-02  1.299e-01 -0.478  0.633322
m_NDVI        -6.175e-03  2.261e-03 -2.731  0.006679 **
sd_NDVI       5.424e-06  8.932e-07  6.073  3.72e-09 ***

Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

(Dispersion parameter for quasipoisson family taken to be 0.4324299)

Null deviance: 224.87 on 318 degrees of freedom
Residual deviance: 128.58 on 306 degrees of freedom
AIC: NA

Number of Fisher Scoring iterations: 4
>
> teste <- adjR2(M)
> teste
[1] 0.4058

```

DENSITY OF INDIVIDUALS

```

--
> M <- glm(nind_ha_adj ~ Forestry_F + Herbaceous.crops + Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds + Marches + Natural.grasslands + Natural.shrublands + Rivers.and.riparian.galleries + Woody.crops + max_NDVI +
prop_flooded_area_ha + m_NDVI + sd_NDVI, family=Gamma(link="log"), data= Fishing_birds_season)
>
> VIF(M)
              Forestry_F          Herbaceous.crops Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds          Marches          Natural.grasslands          Natural.shrublands
Rivers.and.riparian.galleries 1.140532          1.626980          1.383638          3.437124          2.053340          1.241186
              1.961483          1.308351          1.367479          1.845780          2.038612          1.641543
>
> summary(M, dispersion=1)

Call:
glm(formula = nind_ha_adj ~ Forestry_F + Herbaceous.crops + Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds +
Marches + Natural.grasslands + Natural.shrublands + Rivers.and.riparian.galleries +
Woody.crops + max_NDVI + prop_flooded_area_ha + m_NDVI +
sd_NDVI, family = Gamma(link = "log"), data = Fishing_birds_season)

Deviance Residuals:
    Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
-3.3332  -1.2862  -0.6056   0.2375   4.6415

Coefficients:
              Estimate Std. Error z value Pr(>|z|)
(Intercept)  -5.347e-01  1.221e+00  -0.438  0.661442
Forestry_F    1.856e+00  1.366e+00  1.358  0.174322
Herbaceous.crops  1.197e+00  6.726e-01  1.780  0.075051 .
Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds  2.786e+00  4.855e-01  5.739  9.53e-09 ***
Marches       8.341e-01  2.834e-01  2.943  0.003247 **
Natural.grasslands  -3.478e-02  3.886e-01  -0.090  0.928667
Natural.shrublands  2.458e+00  2.303e+00  1.067  0.285796
Rivers.and.riparian.galleries  1.579e+00  4.258e-01  3.708  0.000209 ***
Woody.crops   -4.783e+00  3.089e+00  -1.548  0.121526
max_NDVI     -4.315e-03  7.257e-03  -0.595  0.552076
prop_flooded_area_ha  1.672e+00  2.765e-01  6.047  1.47e-09 ***
m_NDVI       -1.381e-02  4.976e-03  -2.776  0.005504 **
sd_NDVI      -1.140e-05  2.101e-06  -5.424  5.83e-08 ***
---
Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

(Dispersion parameter for Gamma family taken to be 1)

Null deviance: 730.31 on 318 degrees of freedom
Residual deviance: 543.57 on 306 degrees of freedom
AIC: -357.75

Number of Fisher Scoring iterations: 16

>
> teste <- adjR2(M)
> teste
[1] 0.2265

```

FISHING_BIRDS_SUMMER

```

Forestry Herbaceous.crops Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds Marches Natural.grasslands Natural.shrublands Rice.fields Rivers.and.riparian.galleries Woody.crops sd_NDVI
Forestry 1.00000000 -0.08225640 -0.01679825 -0.08085892 0.33109317 0.58530709 -0.20772497 0.03161155 0.12568134 -0.37480106
Herbaceous.crops -0.08225640 1.00000000 0.17463883 -0.53050066 0.13930791 -0.07580009 0.44000052 0.19223272 0.32002019 0.15082143
Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds -0.01679825 0.17463883 1.00000000 -0.02028065 -0.07326510 -0.042193829 -0.05966441 -0.09988614 -0.19183881 0.35728670
Marches -0.08085892 -0.53050066 -0.02028065 1.00000000 -0.35946198 -0.050282070 -0.62271289 -0.33483313 -0.43162772 -0.08455371
Natural.grasslands 0.33109317 0.13930791 -0.07326510 -0.35946198 1.00000000 0.49021138 -0.04054378 0.11122694 0.07455213 -0.43036001
Natural.shrublands 0.58530709 -0.07580001 -0.04219383 -0.05028207 -0.49021138 1.00000000 0.26755729 0.11122694 0.07455213 -0.43036001
Rice.fields -0.20772497 0.44000052 -0.05966441 -0.62271289 -0.04054378 -0.267557289 1.00000000 -0.01000699 0.40529814 0.48549185
Rivers.and.riparian.galleries 0.03161155 0.19223272 -0.09988614 -0.33483313 0.07267052 0.111226943 -0.01000699 1.00000000 0.10804602 -0.24362795
Woody.crops 0.12568134 0.32002019 -0.19183881 -0.43162772 0.05622518 -0.074552128 0.40529814 0.10804602 1.00000000 0.10256211
sd_NDVI -0.37480106 0.15082143 0.35728670 -0.08455371 -0.39018932 -0.430360005 0.48549185 -0.24362795 0.10256211 1.00000000
max_NDVI 0.06581318 0.29196867 0.01884274 -0.40349123 -0.01884274 -0.047836267 0.62614377 0.07842759 0.32768518 0.41306889
m_NDVI -0.13760896 0.07437302 -0.56289475 -0.28439352 0.03774574 -0.053234836 0.45721308 -0.02698558 0.34356987 0.05880904
prop_flooded_area_ha 0.02637748 -0.04301015 -0.08291074 -0.24202705 -0.09144008 -0.002809272 0.12684704 0.11477095 0.01712536 0.27202984

max_NDVI m_NDVI prop_flooded_area_ha
Forestry 0.06581318 -0.13760896 0.026377482
Herbaceous.crops 0.29196867 0.07437302 -0.043010150
Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds 0.01884274 -0.56289475 -0.082910741
Marches -0.40349123 -0.28439352 -0.242027046
Natural.grasslands -0.05838993 0.03774574 -0.091440081
Natural.shrublands -0.04783627 -0.05323484 -0.002809272
Rice.fields 0.62614377 0.45721308 0.126847042
Rivers.and.riparian.galleries 0.07842759 -0.02698558 0.114770955
Woody.crops 0.32768518 0.34356987 0.017125363
sd_NDVI 0.41306889 0.05880904 0.272029845
max_NDVI 1.00000000 0.45850292 0.157238992
m_NDVI 0.45850292 1.00000000 0.286964185
prop_flooded_area_ha 0.15723899 0.28696418 1.000000000

```

SPECIES RICHNESS

```
> M <- glm(No.Species ~ Forestry_F + Herbaceous.crops + Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds + Rice.fields + Natural.grasslands + Natural.shrublands + Rivers.and.riparian.galleries + Woody.crops + max_NDVI + prop_flooded_area_ha + m_NDVI + sd_NDVI, family=quasipoisson, data= Fishing_birds_season)
>
> VIF(M)
              Forestry_F              Herbaceous.crops Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds              Rice.fields              Natural.grasslands              Natural.shrublands
Rivers.and.riparian.galleries 1.285562              1.280255              2.768733              3.475494              1.162199              1.140832
              1.490846              Woody.crops              max_NDVI              prop_flooded_area_ha              m_NDVI              sd_NDVI
              1.203036              1.746823              1.797588              5.214737              3.200719
>
> summary(M)

Call:
glm(formula = No.Species ~ Forestry_F + Herbaceous.crops + Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds + Rice.fields + Natural.grasslands + Natural.shrublands + Rivers.and.riparian.galleries + Woody.crops + max_NDVI + prop_flooded_area_ha + m_NDVI + sd_NDVI, family = quasipoisson, data = Fishing_birds_season)

Deviance Residuals:
    Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
-1.1924  -0.4855  -0.1347   0.3900   1.7150

Coefficients:
            (Intercept)      1.175e+00  6.108e-01  1.923  0.055407 .
      Forestry_F          -3.735e-01  9.906e-01 -0.377  0.706359
Herbaceous.crops        6.458e-02  1.762e-01  0.367  0.714241
Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds  1.953e-01  2.321e-01  0.841  0.400797
      Rice.fields         1.926e-01  1.346e-01  1.431  0.153537
Natural.grasslands     -4.282e-01  2.412e-01 -1.775  0.076825 .
Natural.shrublands     -3.058e+00  1.403e+00 -2.179  0.030101 *
Rivers.and.riparian.galleries -3.850e-01  1.910e-01 -2.016  0.044724 *
      Woody.crops         2.868e-01  1.218e+00  0.236  0.813947
      max_NDVI            1.093e-02  2.970e-03  3.682  0.000274 ***
prop_flooded_area_ha    1.422e-01  1.332e-01  1.068  0.286346
      m_NDVI              -1.845e-02  3.616e-03 -5.102  5.94e-07 ***
      sd_NDVI             2.043e-06  8.795e-07  2.323  0.020831 *
---
Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

(Dispersion parameter for quasipoisson family taken to be 0.3728798)

Null deviance: 165.51 on 316 degrees of freedom
Residual deviance: 109.80 on 304 degrees of freedom
AIC: NA

Number of Fisher Scoring iterations: 4

>
> teste <- adjR2(M)
> teste
[1] 0.3104
```

DENSITY OF INDIVIDUALS

```
> M <- glm(nind_ha_adj ~ Forestry_F + Herbaceous.crops + Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds + Rice.fields + Natural.grasslands + Natural.shrublands + Rivers.and.riparian.galleries + Woody.crops + max_NDVI + prop_flooded_area_ha + m_NDVI + sd_NDVI, family=Gamma(link="log"), data= Fishing_birds_season)
>
> VIF(M)
              Forestry_F              Herbaceous.crops Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds              Rice.fields              Natural.grasslands              Natural.shrublands
Rivers.and.riparian.galleries 1.294209              1.321507              2.515827              2.993827              1.177372              1.194788
              1.538511              Woody.crops              max_NDVI              prop_flooded_area_ha              m_NDVI              sd_NDVI
              1.204819              1.823195              1.594749              4.239965              2.558329
>
> summary(M, dispersion=1)

Call:
glm(formula = nind_ha_adj ~ Forestry_F + Herbaceous.crops + Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds + Rice.fields + Natural.grasslands + Natural.shrublands + Rivers.and.riparian.galleries + Woody.crops + max_NDVI + prop_flooded_area_ha + m_NDVI + sd_NDVI, family = Gamma(link = "log"), data = Fishing_birds_season)

Deviance Residuals:
    Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
-3.0937  -1.3093  -0.5942   0.1022   3.7928

Coefficients:
            (Intercept)      2.481e+00  1.426e+00  1.740  0.081821 .
      Forestry_F          3.171e+00  1.931e+00  1.642  0.100576
Herbaceous.crops        4.427e+00  4.468e-01  9.909 < 2e-16 ***
Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds  1.509e+00  6.063e-01  2.489  0.012802 *
      Rice.fields         -1.388e+00  3.433e-01 -4.044  5.25e-05 ***
Natural.grasslands     1.743e-02  5.013e-01  0.035  0.972260
Natural.shrublands     9.658e+00  3.257e+00  2.965  0.003023 **
Rivers.and.riparian.galleries  5.220e-02  3.990e-01  0.131  0.896118
      Woody.crops         -1.043e+01  2.887e+00 -3.612  0.000304 ***
      max_NDVI            -2.048e-02  6.960e-03 -2.942  0.003258 **
prop_flooded_area_ha    2.868e+00  3.108e-01  9.227 < 2e-16 ***
      m_NDVI              -9.631e-03  8.850e-03 -1.088  0.276528
      sd_NDVI             -8.240e-06  2.269e-06 -3.632  0.000281 ***
---
Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

(Dispersion parameter for Gamma family taken to be 1)

Null deviance: 762.85 on 286 degrees of freedom
Residual deviance: 448.84 on 274 degrees of freedom
(30 observations deleted due to missingness)
AIC: 82.789

Number of Fisher Scoring iterations: 24

>
> teste <- adjR2(M)
> teste
[1] 0.3859
```

FISHING_BIRDS_WINTER

	Forestry	Herbaceous.crops	Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds	Marches	Natural.grasslands	Natural.shrublands	Rice.fields	Rivers.and.riparian.galleries	Woody.crops
Forestry	1.000000000	-0.10938957	-0.16239543	-0.11944996	3.398928e-01	0.5533947553	-0.10822250	-0.05587433	0.163709881
Herbaceous.crops	-0.109389567	1.000000000	0.22297648	-0.61859037	3.522462e-02	-0.1099127716	0.54968104	0.36641527	0.442485341
Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds	-0.162395429	0.22297648	1.000000000	-0.12898878	-9.712061e-02	-0.1514053333	0.06780782	0.05282678	-0.185801964
Marches	-0.119449963	-0.61859037	-0.12898878	1.000000000	-2.875771e-01	-0.0789686134	-0.65055311	-0.36945074	-0.480425769
Natural.grasslands	0.339892774	0.03522462	-0.09712061	-0.28757711	1.0000000e+00	0.4498223905	-0.04149105	0.02091461	0.007600858
Natural.shrublands	0.553394755	-0.10991277	-0.15140533	-0.07896861	4.498224e-01	1.0000000000	-0.23197166	0.04008375	0.056609407
Rice.fields	-0.108222502	0.54968104	0.06780782	-0.65055311	-4.149105e-02	-0.2319716599	1.000000000	0.12660695	0.464110482
Rivers.and.riparian.galleries	-0.055874330	0.36641527	0.05282678	-0.36945074	2.091461e-02	0.0400837471	0.12660695	1.000000000	0.137787034
Woody.crops	0.163709881	0.44248534	-0.18580196	-0.48042577	7.600858e-03	0.0566094067	0.46411048	0.13778703	1.000000000
sd_NDVI	-0.374710952	0.18339898	0.36594495	0.01188398	-3.534792e-01	-0.4619301082	0.35037411	-0.12370868	0.144921660
max_NDVI	0.102665808	0.27359189	0.12846509	-0.27715792	-6.286381e-05	-0.0312610894	0.41361368	0.12129687	0.276487883
m_NDVI	-0.024490551	0.02551598	-0.17377615	-0.04832783	1.469952e-01	0.0254966395	0.21487723	-0.14196191	0.149757674
prop_flooded_area_ha	0.006015869	-0.09999654	0.03833697	0.18903128	-1.414488e-01	-0.0007698003	-0.29637268	-0.03349289	-0.076789930
	sd_NDVI	max_NDVI	m_NDVI	prop_flooded_area_ha					
Forestry	-0.37471095	1.026658e-01	-0.02449055	0.0060158693					
Herbaceous.crops	0.18339898	2.735919e-01	0.02551598	-0.0999965351					
Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds	0.36594495	1.284657e-01	-0.17377615	0.0383369660					
Marches	0.01188398	-2.771579e-01	-0.04832783	0.1890312752					
Natural.grasslands	-0.35347921	-6.286381e-05	0.14699524	-0.1414488244					
Natural.shrublands	-0.46193011	-3.126109e-02	0.02549664	-0.0007698003					
Rice.fields	0.35037411	4.136137e-01	0.21487723	-0.2963726813					
Rivers.and.riparian.galleries	-0.12370868	1.212969e-01	-0.14196191	0.0334928851					
Woody.crops	0.14492166	2.764879e-01	0.14975767	-0.0767899206					
sd_NDVI	1.000000000	3.007682e-01	-0.20924438	0.3091459440					
max_NDVI	0.30676818	1.0000000e+00	0.33295536	-0.1531783504					
m_NDVI	-0.20924438	3.329554e-01	1.000000000	-0.6783096982					
prop_flooded_area_ha	0.30914594	-1.531784e-01	-0.67830970	1.0000000000					

SPECIES RICHNESS

```

> M <- glm(No..Species ~ Forestry_F + Herbaceous.crops + Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds + Marches + Natural.grasslands + Natural.shrublands + Rivers.and.riparian.galleries + Woody.crops + max_NDVI + prop_flooded_area_ha + m_NDVI + sd_NDVI, family=quasipoisson, data= Fishing_birds_season)
>
> VIF(M)
      Forestry_F      Herbaceous.crops Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds      Marches      Natural.grasslands      Natural.shrublands
Rivers.and.riparian.galleries      Woody.crops      max_NDVI      prop_flooded_area_ha      m_NDVI      sd_NDVI
      1.136534      1.932986      1.277540      2.665690      1.385514      1.142525
      1.510407      1.305970      1.429550      2.240536      2.362330      2.045204
>
> summary(M)

Call:
glm(formula = No..Species ~ Forestry_F + Herbaceous.crops + Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds + Marches + Natural.grasslands + Natural.shrublands + Rivers.and.riparian.galleries + Woody.crops + max_NDVI + prop_flooded_area_ha + m_NDVI + sd_NDVI, family = quasipoisson, data = Fishing_birds_season)

Deviance Residuals:
    Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
-1.40956 -0.44192 -0.04004  0.33600  1.42169

Coefficients:
            Estimate Std. Error t value Pr(>|t|)
(Intercept)  4.284e-01  4.240e-01  1.010  0.31304
Forestry_F   -3.118e+00  9.578e-01  -3.255  0.00125 **
Herbaceous.crops  4.599e-01  1.447e-01  3.179  0.00161 **
Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds  1.220e+00  1.382e-01  8.826 < 2e-16 ***
Marches       -8.689e-02  8.188e-02  -1.061  0.28934
Natural.grasslands -2.340e-01  1.573e-01  -1.487  0.13783
Natural.shrublands -2.196e-01  7.449e-01  -0.295  0.76829
Rivers.and.riparian.galleries  5.054e-01  1.537e-01  3.289  0.00111 **
Woody.crops    2.312e+00  1.030e+00  2.244  0.02549 *
max_NDVI       4.699e-03  2.560e-03  1.835  0.06733 .
prop_flooded_area_ha -1.239e-01  1.043e-01  -1.188  0.23575
m_NDVI        -4.992e-03  1.969e-03  -2.536  0.01166 *
sd_NDVI       2.623e-06  6.116e-07  4.288  2.35e-05 ***
---
Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

(Dispersion parameter for quasipoisson family taken to be 0.2561746)

Null deviance: 145.222  on 354  degrees of freedom
Residual deviance: 87.713  on 342  degrees of freedom
AIC: NA

Number of Fisher Scoring iterations: 4
>
> teste <- adjR2(M)
> teste
[1] 0.3748

```

DENSITY OF INDIVIDUALS

```
> M <- glm(nind_ha_adj ~ Forestry_F + Herbaceous.crops + Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds + Marches + Natural.grasslands + Natural.shrublands + Rivers.and.riparian.galleries + Woody.crops + max_NDVI + prop_flooded_area_ha + m_NDVI + sd_NDVI, Family=Gamma(link="log"), data= Fishing_birds_season)
> VIF(M)
              Forestry_F              Herbaceous.crops Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds              Marches              Natural.grasslands              Natural.shrublands
Rivers.and.riparian.galleries              Woody.crops              max_NDVI              prop_flooded_area_ha              m_NDVI              sd_NDVI
              1.157398              1.875712              1.196394              2.782221              1.513468              1.142307
              1.475212              1.263236              1.406033              2.104645              2.241149              1.874244
> summary(M, dispersion=1)

Call:
glm(formula = nind_ha_adj ~ Forestry_F + Herbaceous.crops + Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds + Marches + Natural.grasslands + Natural.shrublands + Rivers.and.riparian.galleries + Woody.crops + max_NDVI + prop_flooded_area_ha + m_NDVI + sd_NDVI, family = Gamma(link = "log"), data = Fishing_birds_season)

Deviance Residuals:
    Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
-3.6372 -1.5012 -0.6069  0.1455  4.6135

Coefficients:
            Estimate Std. Error z value Pr(>|z|)
(Intercept)  7.760e+00  1.164e+00  6.664 2.66e-11 ***
Forestry_F   2.948e-01  1.933e+00  0.153 0.878782
Herbaceous.crops  2.162e+00  4.452e-01  4.856 1.20e-06 ***
Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds  3.555e-01  4.528e-01  0.785 0.432344
Marches      -1.195e+00  2.338e-01 -5.111 3.20e-07 ***
Natural.grasslands -1.467e+00  4.079e-01 -3.596 0.000323 ***
Natural.shrublands  9.279e-01  1.900e+00  0.488 0.625350
Rivers.and.riparian.galleries  6.602e-01  4.405e-01  1.499 0.133903
Woody.crops  -6.591e+00  3.218e+00 -2.048 0.040553 *
max_NDVI     -3.123e-02  6.997e-03 -4.464 8.04e-06 ***
prop_flooded_area_ha  7.989e-01  2.827e-01  2.826 0.004710 ***
m_NDVI       -2.179e-02  5.298e-03 -4.112 3.93e-05 ***
sd_NDVI      -1.134e-05  1.819e-06 -6.231 4.63e-10 ***
---
Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

(Dispersion parameter for Gamma family taken to be 1)

Null deviance: 1083.30 on 354 degrees of freedom
Residual deviance: 704.85 on 342 degrees of freedom
AIC: 59.804

Number of Fisher Scoring iterations: 25

>
> teste <- adjR2(M)
> teste
[1] 0.3265
```

FISHING_BIRDS_AUTUMN

```
Forestry Herbaceous.crops Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds Marches Natural.grasslands Natural.shrublands Rice.fields Rivers.and.riparian.galleries Woody.crops sd_NDVI
Forestry 1.00000000 -0.0867001617 -0.10059152 -0.03627876 0.280306588 0.4090037064 -0.26725419 -0.029854736 0.179980039 -0.2815616
Herbaceous.crops -0.08670016 1.0000000000 0.10263056 -0.54893763 0.053440954 0.0008285935 0.47588889 -0.008470876 0.436784737 0.2913915
Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds -0.10059152 0.1026305559 1.000000000 0.14763739 -0.067197879 -0.1131449775 -0.11435825 -0.162807987 -0.285383285 0.4678244
Marches -0.03627876 -0.5489376321 0.14763739 1.000000000 -0.213684145 -0.0599013516 -0.63802737 -0.211670141 -0.526942433 -0.2532684
Natural.grasslands 0.28030659 0.0534409544 0.000000000 -0.06719788 -0.21368415 1.000000000 0.495859183 -0.16801815 0.134213459 -0.003290341 -0.2475560
Natural.shrublands 0.40900371 0.0008285935 -0.11314498 -0.05990135 0.49585918 1.000000000 -0.29515552 0.103004810 0.105396276 -0.3434669
Rice.fields -0.26725419 0.4758888901 0.14763739 -0.63802737 -0.11435825 -0.63802737 -1.000000000 -0.112644226 0.437701177 0.5493286
Rivers.and.riparian.galleries -0.02985474 -0.0084708756 -0.16280799 -0.21167014 0.134213459 0.1030048103 -0.11264423 1.000000000 -0.002788044 -0.1880104
Woody.crops 0.17998004 0.4367847365 -0.28538329 -0.52694243 -0.003290341 0.1053962756 0.43770118 -0.002788044 1.000000000 0.1357985
sd_NDVI -0.28156160 0.2913915422 0.46782436 -0.25326840 -0.247556019 -0.3434669386 0.54932857 -0.188010446 0.135798506 1.0000000
max_NDVI 0.10548237 0.2317957344 0.09417298 -0.16530412 -0.193175364 0.0158793458 0.38243810 -0.140828689 0.231806716 0.2766805
m_NDVI -0.07030972 0.1183763236 -0.49583634 -0.25462925 -0.038272770 -0.0218450956 0.43709008 -0.017995927 0.302516331 -0.1350790
prop_flooded_area_ha 0.08115728 -0.0667198756 0.27837954 -0.16794900 -0.062497079 0.015390718 0.06031345 -0.030733412 -0.082008225 0.4951181
max_NDVI m_NDVI prop_flooded_area_ha
Forestry 0.10548237 -0.07030972 0.08115728
Herbaceous.crops 0.23179573 0.11837632 -0.06671988
Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds 0.09417298 -0.49583634 0.27837954
Marches -0.16530412 -0.25462925 -0.16794900
Natural.grasslands -0.19317536 -0.03827277 -0.06249708
Natural.shrublands 0.01587935 -0.02184510 0.01539072
Rice.fields 0.38243810 0.43709008 0.06031345
Rivers.and.riparian.galleries -0.14082869 -0.01799593 -0.03073341
Woody.crops 0.23180672 0.30251633 -0.08200822
sd_NDVI 0.27668048 -0.13507897 0.49511806
max_NDVI 1.00000000 0.20937680 -0.11279353
m_NDVI 0.20937680 1.00000000 -0.10916407
prop_flooded_area_ha -0.11279353 -0.10916407 1.00000000
```

SPECIES RICHNESS

```
> M <- glm(No.Species ~ Forestry_F + Herbaceous.crops + Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds + Marches + Natural.grasslands + Natural.shrublands + Rivers.and.riparian.galleries + Woody.crops + max_NDVI + prop_flooded_area_ha + m_NDVI + sd_NDVI, family=quasipoisson, data= Fishing_birds_season)
>
> VIF(M)
              Forestry_F              Herbaceous.crops Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds              Marches              Natural.grasslands              Natural.shrublands
Rivers.and.riparian.galleries 1.430110                2.651579                2.946784                3.324874                1.398174                1.286258
                                Woody.crops                max_NDVI                prop_flooded_area_ha                m_NDVI                sd_NDVI
                                2.586443                1.345560                1.685214                1.865547                2.756233                2.480456
>
> summary(M)

Call:
glm(formula = No..Species ~ Forestry_F + Herbaceous.crops + Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds + Marches + Natural.grasslands + Natural.shrublands + Rivers.and.riparian.galleries + Woody.crops + max_NDVI + prop_flooded_area_ha + m_NDVI + sd_NDVI, family = quasipoisson, data = Fishing_birds_season)

Deviance Residuals:
    Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
-1.48336  -0.37643  -0.06262   0.32914   1.15561

Coefficients:
            (Intercept)      2.549e-01  5.446e-01   0.468  0.64001
      Forestry_F          -4.061e+00  1.338e+00  -3.036  0.00261 **
      Herbaceous.crops    2.151e-01  1.436e-01   1.496  0.13585
      Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds  1.518e+00  1.899e-01   7.992  3.02e-14 ***
      Marches              -3.170e-01  1.039e-01  -3.055  0.00246 **
      Natural.grasslands    1.041e-01  1.691e-01   0.616  0.53852
      Natural.shrublands   -3.147e+00  9.584e-01  -3.284  0.00115 **
      Rivers.and.riparian.galleries  1.658e-01  1.688e-01   0.982  0.32673
      Woody.crops          7.525e-01  7.360e-01   1.022  0.30743
      max_NDVI              1.282e-03  2.403e-03   0.534  0.59408
      prop_flooded_area_ha  1.430e-03  9.498e-02   0.015  0.98800
      m_NDVI                1.872e-03  2.842e-03   0.659  0.51065
      sd_NDVI               1.076e-06  6.807e-07   1.581  0.11503
---
Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

(Dispersion parameter for quasipoisson family taken to be 0.2317368)

Null deviance: 120.707 on 307 degrees of freedom
Residual deviance: 68.016 on 295 degrees of freedom
AIC: NA

Number of Fisher Scoring iterations: 4

>
> teste <- adjR2(M)
> teste
[1] 0.4136
```

DENSITY OF INDIVIDUALS

```
> M <- glm(nind_ha_adj ~ Forestry_F + Herbaceous.crops + Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds + Marches + Natural.grasslands + Natural.shrublands + Rivers.and.riparian.galleries + Woody.crops + max_NDVI + prop_flooded_area_ha + m_NDVI + sd_NDVI, family=Gamma(link="log"), data= Fishing_birds_season)
>
> VIF(M)
              Forestry_F              Herbaceous.crops Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds              Marches              Natural.grasslands              Natural.shrublands
Rivers.and.riparian.galleries 1.363264                2.679317                2.271942                3.665632                1.394881                1.276050
                                Woody.crops                max_NDVI                prop_flooded_area_ha                m_NDVI                sd_NDVI
                                2.652763                1.313086                1.638423                1.682065                2.312910                2.344925
>
> summary(M, dispersion=1)

Call:
glm(formula = nind_ha_adj ~ Forestry_F + Herbaceous.crops + Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds + Marches + Natural.grasslands + Natural.shrublands + Rivers.and.riparian.galleries + Woody.crops + max_NDVI + prop_flooded_area_ha + m_NDVI + sd_NDVI, family = Gamma(link = "log"), data = Fishing_birds_season)

Deviance Residuals:
    Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
-3.6962  -1.5640  -0.7754   0.1461   4.9542

Coefficients:
            (Intercept)      -1.423e+00  1.595e+00  -0.893  0.372115
      Forestry_F          3.841e+00  2.779e+00   1.382  0.166953
      Herbaceous.crops    6.642e-01  4.371e-01   1.520  0.128592
      Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds  2.763e-01  5.899e-01   0.468  0.639508 ***
      Marches              -1.349e+00  3.024e-01  -4.461  8.16e-06 ***
      Natural.grasslands   -1.924e+00  5.001e-01  -3.847  0.000120 ***
      Natural.shrublands   -1.229e+01  2.439e+00  -5.037  4.73e-07 ***
      Rivers.and.riparian.galleries  5.120e-01  4.782e-01   1.071  0.284304
      Woody.crops          -8.074e+00  2.342e+00  -3.447  0.000567 ***
      max_NDVI              -1.645e-02  6.849e-03  -2.402  0.016291 *
      prop_flooded_area_ha  2.333e+00  2.692e-01   8.665 < 2e-16 ***
      m_NDVI                3.063e-02  8.397e-03   3.647  0.000265 ***
      sd_NDVI               -1.379e-05  2.115e-06  -6.519  7.06e-11 ***
---
Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

(Dispersion parameter for Gamma family taken to be 1)

Null deviance: 932.43 on 307 degrees of freedom
Residual deviance: 712.90 on 295 degrees of freedom
AIC: 368.73

Number of Fisher Scoring iterations: 22

>
> teste <- adjR2(M)
> teste
[1] 0.2043
```

LARGE_WADING_BIRDS_SPRING

	Forestry	Herbaceous.crops	Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds	Marches	Natural.grasslands	Natural.shrublands	Rice.fields	Rivers.and.riparian.galleries	Woody.crops	sd_NDVI
Forestry	1.00000000	-0.176526874	-0.20525990	-0.15650131	0.44704585	0.65386146	-0.09878730	0.03349017	0.05997915	-0.32244096
Herbaceous.crops	-0.17652687	1.000000000	0.28580206	-0.51484389	-0.03290169	-0.13764873	0.61814044	0.39022270	0.46748190	0.20806664
Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds	-0.20525990	0.285802060	1.00000000	-0.08881140	-0.09227047	-0.17741000	0.13749947	0.08348591	-0.14940580	0.39278500
Marches	-0.15650131	-0.514843891	-0.08881140	1.00000000	-0.38111046	-0.12192726	-0.52588464	-0.37785885	-0.44467528	0.12463565
Natural.grasslands	0.44704585	-0.032901688	-0.09227047	-0.38111046	1.00000000	0.42345391	-0.01460692	0.04276480	0.01521265	-0.20319826
Natural.shrublands	0.65386146	-0.137648729	-0.17741000	-0.12192726	0.42345391	1.00000000	-0.18030566	0.07372325	0.04467031	-0.29154611
Rice.fields	-0.09878730	0.618140437	0.13749947	-0.52588464	-0.01460692	-0.18030566	1.00000000	0.19474662	0.53652662	0.26510470
Rivers.and.riparian.galleries	0.03349017	0.390222701	0.08348591	-0.37785885	0.04276480	0.07372325	0.04467031	1.00000000	0.16799726	-0.06380341
Woody.crops	0.05997915	0.467481896	-0.14940580	-0.44467528	0.01521265	0.04467031	0.53652662	-0.16799726	1.00000000	0.15367652
sd_NDVI	-0.32244096	0.208066637	0.39278500	0.12463565	-0.20319826	-0.29154611	0.26510470	0.06380341	0.15367652	1.00000000
max_NDVI	0.34872326	0.006020966	-0.14108159	-0.05191321	0.11540920	0.39326000	0.18501145	-0.01840036	0.17809985	0.15069852
m_NDVI	0.16778344	-0.209547434	-0.33176564	0.09401340	0.28692883	0.29439437	-0.04282332	-0.28992058	0.06749617	-0.10351221
prop_flooded_area_ha	-0.12196287	-0.188850681	-0.07073639	0.29744432	-0.19541017	-0.06991809	-0.36863979	-0.02609887	-0.16138901	0.22541961
	max_NDVI	m_NDVI	prop_flooded_area_ha							
Forestry	0.348723257	0.16778344	-0.12196287							
Herbaceous.crops	0.006020966	-0.20954743	-0.18885068							
Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds	-0.141081586	-0.33176564	-0.07073639							
Marches	-0.051913215	0.09401340	0.29744432							
Natural.grasslands	0.115409200	0.28692883	-0.19541017							
Natural.shrublands	0.393259996	0.29439437	-0.06991809							
Rice.fields	0.185011453	-0.04282332	-0.36863979							
Rivers.and.riparian.galleries	-0.014800356	-0.28992058	-0.02609887							
Woody.crops	0.178099848	0.06749617	-0.16138901							
sd_NDVI	0.150698518	-0.10351221	0.22541961							
max_NDVI	1.000000000	0.50936432	-0.12151885							
m_NDVI	0.509364319	1.00000000	-0.30958941							
prop_flooded_area_ha	-0.121518847	-0.30958941	1.00000000							

SPECIES RICHNESS

```
> M <- glm(No..Species ~ Forestry_F + Herbaceous.crops + Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds + Rice.fields + Natural.grasslands + Natural.shrublands + Rivers.and.riparian.galleries + Woody.crops + max_NDVI + prop_flooded_area_ha + m_NDVI + sd_NDVI, family=quasipoisson, data= Large_wading_birds_season)
>
> VIF(M)
      Forestry_F      Herbaceous.crops      Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds      Rice.fields      Natural.grasslands      Natural.shrublands      Rivers.and.riparian.galleries      Woody.crops      max_NDVI      prop_flooded_area_ha      m_NDVI
1.197953      1.220034      1.353779      1.574701      1.208590      1.166337      1.319676      1.186029      1.471410      1.684526      2.060499      1.599891
>
> summary(M)
```

```
Call:
glm(formula = No..Species ~ Forestry_F + Herbaceous.crops + Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds + Rice.fields + Natural.grasslands + Natural.shrublands + Rivers.and.riparian.galleries + Woody.crops + max_NDVI + prop_flooded_area_ha + m_NDVI + sd_NDVI, family = quasipoisson, data = Large_wading_birds_season)
```

```
Deviance Residuals:
    Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
-2.13875  -0.57108  0.03469  0.53286  2.14242
```

```
Coefficients:
(Intercept)      -5.224e-01  3.713e-01  -1.407  0.160112
Forestry_F       -1.496e+00  3.386e-01  -4.419  1.23e-05 ***
Herbaceous.crops -7.173e-01  1.586e-01  -4.524  7.65e-06 ***
Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds  6.217e-01  1.602e-01  3.881  0.000119 ***
Rice.fields      -4.259e-01  9.755e-02  -4.366  1.55e-05 ***
Natural.grasslands  2.823e-02  9.035e-02  0.312  0.754817
Natural.shrublands -6.418e-01  4.822e-01  -1.331  0.183783
Rivers.and.riparian.galleries  3.961e-01  1.128e-01  3.511  0.000488 ***
Woody.crops      -1.695e-01  1.170e+00  -0.145  0.884859
max_NDVI         6.280e-03  2.306e-03  2.724  0.006682 **
prop_flooded_area_ha  2.647e-01  7.783e-02  3.401  0.000727 ***
m_NDVI           5.679e-03  1.456e-03  3.899  0.000110 ***
sd_NDVI          2.147e-06  6.710e-07  3.200  0.001464 **
```

```
---
Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
```

```
(Dispersion parameter for quasipoisson family taken to be 0.6256678)
```

```
Null deviance: 441.78 on 497 degrees of freedom
Residual deviance: 324.56 on 485 degrees of freedom
AIC: NA
```

```
Number of Fisher Scoring iterations: 4
```

```
>
> teste <- adjR2(M)
> teste
[1] 0.2471
```

DENSITY OF INDIVIDUALS

```
> M <- glm(nind_ha_adj ~ Forestry_F + Herbaceous.crops + Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds + Rice.fields + Natural.grasslands + Natural.shrublands + Rivers.and.riparian.galleries + Woody.crops + max_NDVI + prop_flooded_area_ha + m_NDVI + sd_NDVI, family=Gamma(link="log"), data= Large_wading_birds_season)
>
> VIF(M)
              Forestry_F              Herbaceous.crops Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds              Rice.fields              Natural.grasslands              Natural.shrublands
Rivers.and.riparian.galleries              Woody.crops              max_NDVI              prop_flooded_area_ha              m_NDVI              sd_NDVI
              1.242823              1.257079              1.307650              1.699630              1.195233              1.169038
              1.334047              1.184488              1.477589              1.796684              2.070356              1.570037
>
> summary(M, dispersion=1)

Call:
glm(formula = nind_ha_adj ~ Forestry_F + Herbaceous.crops + Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds + Rice.fields + Natural.grasslands + Natural.shrublands + Rivers.and.riparian.galleries + Woody.crops + max_NDVI + prop_flooded_area_ha + m_NDVI + sd_NDVI, family = Gamma(link = "log"), data = Large_wading_birds_season)

Deviance Residuals:
    Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
-3.548  -1.532  -0.760   0.032   5.501

Coefficients:
            Estimate Std. Error z value Pr(>|z|)
(Intercept)  4.777e+00  9.482e-01  5.038 4.70e-07 ***
Forestry_F   -5.332e-01  7.745e-01  -0.688 0.49119
Herbaceous.crops -1.756e+00  3.403e-01  -5.159 2.48e-07 ***
Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds 3.586e+00  4.527e-01  7.920 2.37e-15 ***
Rice.fields   -2.102e+00  2.311e-01  -9.095 < 2e-16 ***
Natural.grasslands -7.714e-01  2.428e-01  -3.177 0.00149 **
Natural.shrublands  3.761e+00  1.267e+00  2.968 0.00300 **
Rivers.and.riparian.galleries  3.438e-01  3.090e-01  1.113 0.26591
Woody.crops   -2.166e+00  2.740e+00  -0.791 0.42918
max_NDVI      -2.970e-02  5.866e-03  -5.064 4.11e-07 ***
prop_flooded_area_ha  4.113e+00  2.019e-01  20.374 < 2e-16 ***
m_NDVI        -4.337e-03  3.866e-03  -1.122 0.26190
sd_NDVI       -2.451e-05  1.802e-06  -13.604 < 2e-16 ***
---
Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

(Dispersion parameter for Gamma family taken to be 1)

Null deviance: 2128.2 on 497 degrees of freedom
Residual deviance: 1025.4 on 485 degrees of freedom
AIC: 1430.3

Number of Fisher Scoring iterations: 18

>
> teste <- adjR2(M)
> teste
[1] 0.5063
```

LARGE_WADING_BIRDS_SUMMER

```

              Forestry Herbaceous.crops Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds Marches Natural.grasslands Natural.shrublands Rice.fields Rivers.and.riparian.galleries Woody.crops sd_NDVI
Forestry      1.000000000              -0.23138847              -0.13818992 -0.03661018              0.37046496              0.58985305 -0.19007331 -0.10366423 0.08305901 -0.33543577
Herbaceous.crops -0.23138847              1.000000000              -0.13818992 -0.03661018              0.37046496              0.58985305 -0.19007331 -0.10366423 0.08305901 -0.33543577
Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds -0.13818992              -0.13818992              1.000000000              -0.08456211 -0.07562344 -0.15084315 0.07588907 0.05155828 -0.14404430 0.41984965
Marches        -0.03661018              -0.03661018              -0.08456211 1.000000000              -0.34153389 -0.04728033 -0.58252112 -0.34998298 -0.43267987 -0.10981811
Natural.grasslands 0.37046496              0.37046496              -0.07562344 -0.34153389 1.000000000              0.41892951 -0.01493173 0.03076999 0.01984397 -0.29302485
Natural.shrublands 0.58985305              0.58985305              -0.15084315 -0.04728033 0.41892951 1.000000000              -0.23588890 -0.08558834 0.04449018 -0.38087231
Rice.fields     -0.19007331              0.55617068              0.07588907 -0.58252112 -0.01493173 -0.23588890 1.000000000              0.13613044 0.46899492 0.49904618
Rivers.and.riparian.galleries -0.10366423              0.36215670              0.05155828 -0.34998298 0.03076999 -0.08558834 0.13613044 1.000000000              0.09885427 0.02713336
Woody.crops     0.08305901              0.40543661              -0.14404430 -0.43267987 0.01984397 0.04449018 0.46899492 0.09885427 1.000000000              0.20772855
sd_NDVI        -0.33543577              0.30598494              0.41984965 -0.10981811 -0.29302485 -0.38087231 0.49904618 0.02713336 0.20772855 1.000000000
max_NDVI       0.21525813              0.25817794              0.05620809 -0.32995829 0.04716619 0.15513960 0.52972793 0.06392869 0.34004714 0.36050417
m_NDVI        0.06399937              -0.01061495              -0.40113800 -0.20732685 0.15448605 0.18418643 0.29519189 -0.12661373 0.25181620 -0.01643406
prop_flooded_area_ha -0.16327615              0.08030688              0.06331978 -0.14169924 -0.25120274 -0.21330534 0.11055101 0.15948341 0.01689481 0.41067092
              max_NDVI              m_NDVI prop_flooded_area_ha
Forestry      0.215258126 0.06399937 -0.163276152
Herbaceous.crops 0.258177941 -0.01061495 0.080306879
Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds 0.056208095 -0.40113800 0.063319700
Marches        -0.329958289 -0.20732685 -0.141699239
Natural.grasslands 0.047166186 0.15448605 -0.251202739
Natural.shrublands 0.155139597 0.18418643 -0.213305339
Rice.fields     0.529727925 0.29519189 0.110551012
Rivers.and.riparian.galleries 0.063928686 -0.12661373 0.159483412
Woody.crops     0.340047140 0.25181620 0.016894809
sd_NDVI        0.360504174 -0.01643406 0.410670923
max_NDVI       1.000000000 0.48748993 0.006608637
m_NDVI        0.487489929 1.000000000 0.097539177
prop_flooded_area_ha 0.006608637 0.09753918 1.000000000

```

SPECIES RICHNESS

```
> M <- glm(No..Species ~ Forestry_F + Herbaceous.crops + Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds + Rice.fields + Natural.grasslands + Natural.shrublands + Rivers.and.riparian.galleries + Woody.crops + max_NDVI + prop_flooded_area_ha + m_NDVI + sd_NDVI, family=quasipoisson, data= Large_wading_birds_season)
>
> VIF(M)
              Forestry_F              Herbaceous.crops Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds              Rice.fields              Natural.grasslands              Natural.shrublands
Rivers.and.riparian.galleries 1.136954                1.216305                2.085708                3.501358                1.221658                1.193161
              1.344064                1.242911                1.925845                1.513352                3.505255                3.080821
>
> summary(M)

Call:
glm(formula = No..Species ~ Forestry_F + Herbaceous.crops + Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds + Rice.fields + Natural.grasslands + Natural.shrublands + Rivers.and.riparian.galleries + Woody.crops + max_NDVI + prop_flooded_area_ha + m_NDVI + sd_NDVI, family = quasipoisson, data = Large_wading_birds_season)

Deviance Residuals:
    Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
-2.29949  -0.47303  -0.01435   0.45274   2.05812

Coefficients:
              Estimate Std. Error t value Pr(<|t|)
(Intercept)   -4.816e-01  3.303e-01  -1.458 0.145423
Forestry_F    -2.179e+00  3.450e-01  -6.316 5.41e-10 ***
Herbaceous.crops -5.600e-01  9.874e-02  -5.671 2.26e-08 ***
Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds  5.052e-01  1.618e-01  3.123 0.001884 **
Rice.fields    -7.200e-01  9.999e-02  -7.201 1.91e-12 ***
Natural.grasslands  4.801e-02  9.866e-02  0.487 0.626699
Natural.shrublands -1.645e+00  3.941e-01  -4.173 3.47e-05 ***
Rivers.and.riparian.galleries  5.769e-01  9.425e-02  6.121 1.73e-09 ***
Woody.crops     2.638e+00  7.792e-01  3.386 0.000758 ***
max_NDVI        7.025e-03  1.760e-03  3.991 7.45e-05 ***
prop_flooded_area_ha  4.316e-01  6.328e-02  6.822 2.31e-11 ***
m_NDVI          4.427e-03  2.101e-03  2.107 0.035569 *
sd_NDVI         1.629e-06  6.203e-07  2.626 0.008870 **
---
Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

(Dispersion parameter for quasipoisson family taken to be 0.5057687)

Null deviance: 456.42 on 581 degrees of freedom
Residual deviance: 306.79 on 569 degrees of freedom
AIC: NA

Number of Fisher Scoring iterations: 4

>
> teste <- adjR2(M)
> teste
[1] 0.3136
```

DENSITY OF INDIVIDUALS

```
> M <- glm(nind_ha_adj ~ Forestry_F + Herbaceous.crops + Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds + Rice.fields + Natural.grasslands + Natural.shrublands + Rivers.and.riparian.galleries + Woody.crops + max_NDVI + prop_flooded_area_ha + m_NDVI + sd_NDVI, family=Gamma(link="log"), data= Large_wading_birds_season)
>
> VIF(M)
              Forestry_F              Herbaceous.crops Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds              Rice.fields              Natural.grasslands              Natural.shrublands
Rivers.and.riparian.galleries 1.137955                1.308903                2.187658                2.943212                1.203359                1.255052
              1.354927                1.229097                1.899318                1.386197                3.379349                2.434888
>
> summary(M, dispersion=1)

Call:
glm(formula = nind_ha_adj ~ Forestry_F + Herbaceous.crops + Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds + Rice.fields + Natural.grasslands + Natural.shrublands + Rivers.and.riparian.galleries + Woody.crops + max_NDVI + prop_flooded_area_ha + m_NDVI + sd_NDVI, family = Gamma(link = "log"), data = Large_wading_birds_season)

Deviance Residuals:
    Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
-2.8282  -1.2607  -0.6474   0.0765   6.5002

Coefficients:
              Estimate Std. Error z value Pr(<|z|)
(Intercept)   1.389e+00  1.050e+00  1.322 0.186219
Forestry_F    9.816e-02  1.196e+00  0.082 0.934574
Herbaceous.crops  3.855e+00  3.737e-01  10.317 < 2e-16 ***
Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds  9.153e-01  5.408e-01  1.692 0.090564 .
Rice.fields    -3.337e+00  3.115e-01  -10.712 < 2e-16 ***
Natural.grasslands  -4.825e-01  3.277e-01  -1.472 0.140912
Natural.shrublands  4.637e+00  1.132e+00  4.095 4.23e-05 ***
Rivers.and.riparian.galleries  6.461e-01  3.196e-01  2.022 0.043211 *
Woody.crops    -7.969e+00  2.567e+00  -3.105 0.001903 **
max_NDVI       -2.475e-02  5.620e-03  -4.404 1.06e-05 ***
prop_flooded_area_ha  3.138e+00  2.104e-01  14.914 < 2e-16 ***
m_NDVI         2.170e-02  6.868e-03  3.159 0.001583 **
sd_NDVI        -7.727e-06  2.076e-06  -3.721 0.000198 ***
---
Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

(Dispersion parameter for Gamma family taken to be 1)

Null deviance: 1346.30 on 459 degrees of freedom
Residual deviance: 718.32 on 447 degrees of freedom
(122 observations deleted due to missingness)
AIC: 2175.5

Number of Fisher Scoring iterations: 20

>
> teste <- adjR2(M)
> teste
[1] 0.4521
```

LARGE_WADING_BIRDS_WINTER

	Forestry	Herbaceous.crops	Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds	Marches	Natural.grasslands	Natural.shrublands	Rice.fields	Rivers.and.riparian.galleries	Woody.crops
Forestry	1.000000000	-0.18502144	-0.18424645	-0.12464252	0.406773057	0.64844771	-0.10973791	-0.0003115474	0.091920254
Herbaceous.crops	-0.1850214382	1.000000000	0.22706625	-0.49938074	-0.063488326	-0.15411950	0.57432620	0.3632954071	0.425352436
Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds	-0.1842464505	0.22706625	1.000000000	-0.08959773	-0.106501690	-0.15793685	0.11785494	0.1106516285	-0.133431340
Marches	-0.1246425203	-0.49938074	-0.08959773	1.000000000	-0.363156218	-0.11584102	-0.55133319	-0.3156011667	-0.417597503
Natural.grasslands	0.4067730569	-0.06348833	-0.10650169	-0.36315622	1.000000000	0.42643620	-0.01823897	-0.0077461166	0.003318186
Natural.shrublands	0.6484477055	-0.15411950	-0.15793685	-0.11584102	0.426436205	1.000000000	-0.19330069	0.0324884022	0.041994120
Rice.fields	-0.1097379077	0.57432620	0.11785494	-0.55133319	-0.018238968	-0.19330069	1.000000000	0.1673437720	0.466220861
Rivers.and.riparian.galleries	-0.0003115474	0.36329541	0.11065163	-0.31560117	-0.007746117	0.03248840	0.16734377	1.0000000000	0.148259381
Woody.crops	0.0919202540	0.42535244	-0.13343134	-0.41759750	0.003318186	0.04199412	0.46622086	0.1482593809	1.0000000000
sd_NDVI	-0.3155777166	0.24074302	0.40431215	0.06607201	-0.278595474	-0.35711000	0.36895692	0.0025962230	0.185797658
max_NDVI	0.1454916675	0.25041535	0.11740715	-0.26167317	0.121322113	0.04693252	0.39877575	0.1510505007	0.232656143
m_NDVI	0.0862454308	-0.05449872	-0.19388431	0.06603765	0.260370157	0.11910450	0.12431333	-0.2200777570	0.066907180
prop_flooded_area_ha	-0.1271991687	-0.03724666	0.08785383	0.23216361	-0.263142514	-0.12037789	-0.22457609	0.0401928893	-0.037506646
	sd_NDVI	max_NDVI	m_NDVI	prop_flooded_area_ha					
Forestry	-0.315577717	0.14549167	0.08624543	-0.12719917					
Herbaceous.crops	0.240743015	0.25041535	-0.05449872	-0.03724666					
Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds	0.404312153	0.11740715	-0.19388431	0.08785383					
Marches	0.066072011	-0.26167317	0.06603765	0.23216361					
Natural.grasslands	-0.278595474	0.12132211	0.26037016	-0.26314251					
Natural.shrublands	-0.357109998	0.04693252	0.11910450	-0.12037789					
Rice.fields	0.368956924	0.39877575	0.12431333	-0.22457609					
Rivers.and.riparian.galleries	0.002596223	0.15105050	-0.22007776	0.04019289					
Woody.crops	0.185797658	0.23265614	0.06690718	-0.03750665					
sd_NDVI	1.000000000	0.32120909	-0.19598665	0.33497998					
max_NDVI	0.321209093	1.00000000	0.38218816	-0.21864581					
m_NDVI	-0.195986653	0.38218816	1.00000000	-0.69489870					
prop_flooded_area_ha	0.334979985	-0.21864581	-0.69489870	1.00000000					

SPECIES RICHNESS

```

> M <- glm(No.Species ~ Forestry_F + Herbaceous.crops + Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds + Rice.fields + Natural.grasslands + Natural.shrublands + Rivers.and.riparian.galleries + Woody.crops + max_NDVI + prop_flooded_area_ha + m_NDVI + sd_NDVI, family=quasipoisson, data= Large_wading_birds_season)
>
> VIF(M)
              Forestry_F              Herbaceous.crops Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds              Rice.fields              Natural.grasslands              Natural.shrublands              Rivers.and.riparian.galleries              Woody.crops              max_NDVI              prop_flooded_area_ha              m_NDVI              sd_NDVI
1.137798              1.254004              1.234304              1.928857              1.182362              1.099803              1.215118              1.213794              1.408860              2.247099              2.467880              1.182362              1.198943
>
> summary(M)

Call:
glm(formula = No.Species ~ Forestry_F + Herbaceous.crops + Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds + Rice.fields + Natural.grasslands + Natural.shrublands + Rivers.and.riparian.galleries + Woody.crops + max_NDVI + prop_flooded_area_ha + m_NDVI + sd_NDVI, family = quasipoisson, data = Large_wading_birds_season)

Deviance Residuals:
    Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
-2.17796 -0.63305  0.03764  0.54846  1.95957

Coefficients:
(Intercept)          -5.299e-01  3.971e-01  -1.334  0.182727
Forestry_F           -1.705e+00  4.040e-01  -4.221  2.90e-05 ***
Herbaceous.crops     -2.567e-01  1.192e-01  -2.153  0.031828 *
Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds  9.083e-01  1.531e-01  5.931  5.65e-09 ***
Rice.fields          -3.277e-02  8.826e-02  -0.371  0.710600
Natural.grasslands    6.848e-02  9.184e-02  0.746  0.456265
Natural.shrublands    5.220e-01  4.811e-01  1.085  0.278460
Rivers.and.riparian.galleries  7.483e-01  1.203e-01  6.222  1.05e-09 ***
Woody.crops          4.049e+00  9.282e-01  4.362  1.57e-05 ***
max_NDVI             3.841e-03  2.374e-03  1.618  0.106278
prop_flooded_area_ha  4.522e-01  9.380e-02  4.821  1.91e-06 ***
m_NDVI              6.538e-03  1.731e-03  3.776  0.000179 ***
sd_NDVI             3.777e-06  6.247e-07  6.046  2.93e-09 ***
---
Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

(Dispersion parameter for quasipoisson family taken to be 0.6347382)

Null deviance: 481.81  on 506  degrees of freedom
Residual deviance: 337.66  on 494  degrees of freedom
AIC: NA

Number of Fisher Scoring iterations: 4
>
> teste <- adjR2(M)
> teste
[1] 0.2822

```

DENSITY OF INDIVIDUALS

```
> M <- glm(nind_ha_adj ~ Forestry_F + Herbaceous.crops + Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds + Rice.fields + Natural.grasslands + Natural.shrublands + Rivers.and.riparian.galleries + Woody.crops + max_NDVI + prop_flooded_area_ha + m_NDVI + sd_NDVI, family=Gamma(link="log"), data= Large_wading_birds_season)
>
> VIF(M)
              Forestry_F              Herbaceous.crops Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds              Rice.fields              Natural.grasslands              Natural.shrublands
Rivers.and.riparian.galleries 1.188308                1.253547                1.173849                1.699297                1.176824                1.088254
1.193783                1.160571                1.417965                2.270139                2.445486                sd_NDVI
1.892211
> summary(M, dispersion=1)

Call:
glm(formula = nind_ha_adj ~ Forestry_F + Herbaceous.crops + Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds + Rice.fields + Natural.grasslands + Natural.shrublands + Rivers.and.riparian.galleries + Woody.crops + max_NDVI + prop_flooded_area_ha + m_NDVI + sd_NDVI, family = Gamma(link = "log"), data = Large_wading_birds_season)

Deviance Residuals:
    Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
-3.5895 -1.3746 -0.7065  0.3661  4.1703

Coefficients:
(Intercept)                Estimate Std. Error z value Pr(>|z|)
Forestry_F                 -3.133e-01  8.098e-01  -0.387  0.698813
Herbaceous.crops           -1.047e+00  2.699e-01  -3.877  0.000106 ***
Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds  4.831e+00  4.388e-01  11.009 < 2e-16 ***
Rice.fields                 -4.829e-01  2.261e-01  -2.136  0.032698 *
Natural.grasslands          2.598e-01  2.318e-01  1.121  0.262218
Natural.shrublands          3.267e+00  1.202e+00  2.717  0.006579 **
Rivers.and.riparian.galleries  2.196e+00  3.272e-01  6.711  1.93e-11 ***
Woody.crops                 3.315e+00  2.679e+00  1.237  0.215905
max_NDVI                   -3.461e-02  5.768e-03  -6.001  1.96e-09 ***
prop_flooded_area_ha        2.841e+00  2.250e-01  12.629 < 2e-16 ***
m_NDVI                     -6.268e-03  4.235e-03  -1.480  0.138801
sd_NDVI                    -7.230e-06  1.712e-06  -4.223  2.42e-05 ***
---
Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

(Dispersion parameter for Gamma family taken to be 1)

Null deviance: 1513.0 on 506 degrees of freedom
Residual deviance: 972.1 on 494 degrees of freedom
AIC: 1123.7

Number of Fisher Scoring iterations: 14

>
> teste <- adjR2(M)
> teste
[1] 0.3419
```

LARGE_WADING_BIRDS_AUTUMN

	Forestry	Herbaceous.crops	Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds	Marches	Natural.grasslands	Natural.shrublands	Rice.fields	Rivers.and.riparian.galleries	Woody.crops	sd_NDVI
Forestry	1.00000000	-0.220698465	-0.14435771	-0.02918528	0.325285979	0.562251724	-0.18447552	-0.056157122	0.08406292	-0.2922485
Herbaceous.crops	-0.22069847	1.000000000	0.22248378	-0.58057853	-0.009826148	-0.143773214	0.58288719	0.300142624	0.43996389	0.4260550
Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds	-0.14435771	0.222483782	1.000000000	-0.08646060	-0.056835271	-0.137304854	0.08167230	0.060402234	-0.16677716	0.4877189
Marches	-0.02918528	-0.580578531	-0.08646060	1.000000000	-0.304029714	-0.047497872	-0.62132511	-0.383744407	-0.46889406	-0.2979085
Natural.grasslands	0.32528598	-0.009826148	-0.05683627	-0.30402971	1.000000000	0.373198468	-0.02635869	-0.007100642	0.01626777	-0.1719739
Natural.shrublands	0.56225172	-0.143773214	-0.13730485	-0.04749787	0.373198468	1.000000000	-0.22458053	-0.007258698	0.07976511	-0.3097950
Rice.fields	-0.18447552	0.582887194	0.08167230	-0.62132511	-0.026358693	-0.224580530	1.000000000	0.126512817	0.48831772	0.5555776
Rivers.and.riparian.galleries	-0.05615712	0.300142624	0.06040223	-0.30374441	-0.007100642	-0.007258698	0.12651282	1.000000000	0.12204448	0.1867896
Woody.crops	0.08406292	0.439963895	-0.16677716	-0.46889406	0.016267771	0.079765107	0.48831772	0.122044481	1.000000000	0.2617519
sd_NDVI	-0.29224852	0.426055018	0.48771892	-0.29790849	-0.171973868	-0.309795025	0.55557761	0.186789572	0.26175191	1.000000000
max_NDVI	0.23139017	0.204988294	0.14495800	-0.15905935	-0.093156628	0.174973486	0.35284247	0.085788182	0.24170584	0.2761351
m_NDVI	0.09879173	-0.071967637	-0.39337871	-0.10779337	0.100786730	0.166489157	0.21164249	-0.101678373	0.19184345	-0.2153608
prop_flooded_area_ha	-0.08234726	0.139239592	0.30741248	-0.23485452	-0.116457075	-0.119704395	0.14648346	0.218073902	0.05685350	0.5760771
	max_NDVI	m_NDVI	prop_flooded_area_ha							
Forestry	0.23139017	0.09879173	-0.08234726							
Herbaceous.crops	0.20498829	-0.07196764	0.13923959							
Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds	0.14495800	-0.39337871	0.30741248							
Marches	-0.15905935	-0.10779337	-0.23485452							
Natural.grasslands	-0.09315663	0.10078673	-0.11645707							
Natural.shrublands	0.17497349	0.16648916	-0.11970439							
Rice.fields	0.35284247	0.21164249	0.14648346							
Rivers.and.riparian.galleries	0.08578818	-0.10167837	0.21807390							
Woody.crops	0.24170584	0.19184345	0.05685350							
sd_NDVI	0.27613509	-0.21536078	0.57607708							
max_NDVI	1.00000000	0.24561362	-0.09251935							
m_NDVI	0.24561362	1.000000000	-0.16464362							
prop_flooded_area_ha	-0.09251935	-0.16464362	1.000000000							

SPECIES RICHNESS

```
> M <- glm(No..Species ~ Forestry_F + Herbaceous.crops + Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds + Rice.fields + Natural.grasslands + Natural.shrublands + Rivers.and.riparian.galleries + Woody.crops + max_NDVI + prop_flooded_area_ha + m_NDVI + sd_NDVI, family=quasipoisson, data= Large_wading_birds_season)
>
> VIF(M)
              Forestry_F              Herbaceous.crops Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds              Rice.fields              Natural.grasslands              Natural.shrublands
Rivers.and.riparian.galleries 1.223971              1.186424              2.363257              3.467545              1.155425              1.170863
              1.524939              1.217824              1.735524              1.686909              2.541260              2.766309
>
> summary(M)

Call:
glm(formula = No..Species ~ Forestry_F + Herbaceous.crops + Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds + Rice.fields + Natural.grasslands + Natural.shrublands + Rivers.and.riparian.galleries + Woody.crops + max_NDVI + prop_flooded_area_ha + m_NDVI + sd_NDVI, family = quasipoisson, data = Large_wading_birds_season)

Deviance Residuals:
    Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
-2.1411 -0.7397 -0.0832  0.5082  2.5117

Coefficients:
              Estimate Std. Error t value Pr(>|t|)
(Intercept) -2.147e+00  5.041e-01  -4.259 2.46e-05 ***
Forestry_F   -5.234e+00  9.623e-01  -5.439 8.48e-08 ***
Herbaceous.crops  3.238e-01  1.030e-01  3.145  0.00177 **
Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds  1.816e+00  2.114e-01  8.593 < 2e-16 ***
Rice.fields   1.433e-01  1.198e-01  1.196  0.23240
Natural.grasslands  2.424e-01  1.282e-01  1.891  0.05921 .
Natural.shrublands -1.287e+00  6.773e-01  -1.900  0.05804 .
Rivers.and.riparian.galleries  1.439e+00  1.301e-01  11.057 < 2e-16 ***
Woody.crops   2.608e+00  8.225e-01  3.171  0.00161 **
max_NDVI      8.099e-03  2.431e-03  3.331  0.00093 ***
prop_flooded_area_ha  4.058e-01  9.177e-02  4.421 1.21e-05 ***
m_NDVI        1.270e-02  3.113e-03  4.081 5.25e-05 ***
sd_NDVI       1.652e-06  8.094e-07  2.041  0.04178 *
---
Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

(Dispersion parameter for quasipoisson family taken to be 0.7549248)

Null deviance: 639.11 on 499 degrees of freedom
Residual deviance: 366.17 on 487 degrees of freedom
AIC: NA

Number of Fisher Scoring iterations: 5

>
> teste <- adjR2(M)
> teste
[1] 0.4129
```

DENSITY OF INDIVIDUALS

```
> M <- glm(nind_ha_adj ~ Forestry_F + Herbaceous.crops + Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds + Rice.fields + Natural.grasslands + Natural.shrublands + Rivers.and.riparian.galleries + Woody.crops + max_NDVI + prop_flooded_area_ha + m_NDVI + sd_NDVI, family=Gamma(link="log"), data= Large_wading_birds_season)
>
> VIF(M)
              Forestry_F              Herbaceous.crops Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds              Rice.fields              Natural.grasslands              Natural.shrublands
Rivers.and.riparian.galleries 1.121265              1.178072              1.927882              2.902432              1.144367              1.166752
              1.288843              1.191057              1.602925              1.509377              2.123955              2.449929
>
> summary(M, dispersion=1)

Call:
glm(formula = nind_ha_adj ~ Forestry_F + Herbaceous.crops + Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds + Rice.fields + Natural.grasslands + Natural.shrublands + Rivers.and.riparian.galleries + Woody.crops + max_NDVI + prop_flooded_area_ha + m_NDVI + sd_NDVI, family = Gamma(link = "log"), data = Large_wading_birds_season)

Deviance Residuals:
    Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
-3.0045 -1.5873 -0.8304  0.1528  5.9963

Coefficients:
              Estimate Std. Error z value Pr(>|z|)
(Intercept) -1.920e+00  1.166e+00  -1.646  0.0997 .
Forestry_F   -1.812e+00  1.528e+00  -1.185  0.2359
Herbaceous.crops  1.852e+00  2.592e-01  7.143 9.14e-13 ***
Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds  5.593e+00  5.273e-01  10.607 < 2e-16 ***
Rice.fields   -2.458e-01  2.802e-01  -0.877  0.3804
Natural.grasslands  1.551e+00  2.992e-01  5.183 2.19e-07 ***
Natural.shrublands -2.837e+00  1.282e+00  -2.214  0.0269 *
Rivers.and.riparian.galleries  3.956e+00  3.171e-01  12.477 < 2e-16 ***
Woody.crops   -2.262e+00  2.203e+00  -1.027  0.3046
max_NDVI      -3.072e-02  5.549e-03  -5.536 3.09e-08 ***
prop_flooded_area_ha  2.927e+00  2.073e-01  14.120 < 2e-16 ***
m_NDVI        4.486e-02  7.346e-03  6.107 1.01e-09 ***
sd_NDVI       -1.199e-05  2.060e-06  -5.822 5.82e-09 ***
---
Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

(Dispersion parameter for Gamma family taken to be 1)

Null deviance: 1722.04 on 436 degrees of freedom
Residual deviance: 932.19 on 424 degrees of freedom
(63 observations deleted due to missingness)
AIC: 1189.8

Number of Fisher Scoring iterations: 20

>
> teste <- adjR2(M)
> teste
[1] 0.4433
```

SMALL_WADING_BIRDS_SPRING

	Forestry	Herbaceous.crops	Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds	Marches	Natural.grasslands	Natural.shrublands	Rice.fields	Rivers.and.riparian.galleries	Woody.crops	sd_NDVI
Forestry	1.00000000	-0.08391800	-0.13574438	-0.21560092	0.37590845	0.69536040	-0.02394399	0.14644967	0.14565124	-0.29326547
Herbaceous.crops	-0.08391800	1.00000000	0.33368540	-0.50219964	0.13035425	-0.13521937	0.51067382	0.43134679	0.31529478	0.13086863
Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds	-0.13574438	0.33368540	1.00000000	-0.19400819	-0.04476057	-0.14478765	0.18133787	0.04319654	-0.11324429	0.46032771
Marches	-0.21560092	-0.50219964	-0.19400819	1.00000000	-0.47224291	-0.15244250	-0.45695190	-0.42263419	-0.31328567	0.17446957
Natural.grasslands	0.37590845	0.13035425	-0.04476057	-0.47224291	1.00000000	0.40677888	0.11634153	0.07351832	0.19030452	-0.12868829
Natural.shrublands	0.69536040	-0.13521937	-0.14478765	-0.15244250	0.40677888	1.00000000	-0.18194284	0.11909833	0.11894335	-0.31174682
Rice.fields	-0.02394399	0.51067382	0.18133787	-0.45695190	0.11634153	-0.18194284	1.00000000	0.18315581	0.39827945	0.23173919
Rivers.and.riparian.galleries	0.14644967	0.43134679	0.04319654	-0.42263420	0.07351832	0.11909833	0.18315582	1.00000000	0.20602857	-0.13208019
Woody.crops	0.14565124	0.31529478	-0.11324429	-0.31328567	0.19030452	0.11894335	0.39827945	0.20602856	1.00000000	0.04215068
sd_NDVI	-0.29326547	0.13086863	0.46032771	0.17446957	-0.12868829	-0.31174682	0.23173919	-0.13208018	0.04215068	1.00000000
max_NDVI	0.28703510	-0.07991706	-0.11689989	0.02393389	0.09239458	0.32422927	0.18642843	-0.01995844	0.12421854	0.18958341
m_NDVI	0.01636015	-0.23600549	-0.37373774	0.15731680	0.22634173	0.21278764	0.02909481	-0.30723520	0.14566772	-0.07678439
prop_flooded_area_ha	-0.09897187	-0.15415265	-0.10222981	0.24060617	-0.19122660	-0.02107878	-0.38574729	-0.00321504	-0.11876985	0.18821933
	max_NDVI	m_NDVI	prop_flooded_area_ha							
Forestry	0.28703510	0.01636015	-0.09897187							
Herbaceous.crops	-0.07991706	-0.23600549	-0.15415264							
Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds	-0.11689989	-0.37373774	-0.10222981							
Marches	0.02393389	0.15731680	0.24060616							
Natural.grasslands	0.09239458	0.22634173	-0.19122660							
Natural.shrublands	0.32422927	0.21278764	-0.02107878							
Rice.fields	0.18642843	0.02909481	-0.38574728							
Rivers.and.riparian.galleries	-0.01995844	-0.30723520	-0.00321504							
Woody.crops	0.12421854	0.14566772	-0.11876985							
sd_NDVI	0.18958341	-0.07678439	0.18821932							
max_NDVI	1.00000000	0.43831046	-0.02393245							
m_NDVI	0.43831046	1.00000000	-0.25027182							
prop_flooded_area_ha	-0.02393246	-0.25027183	1.00000000							

SPECIES RICHNESS

```
> M <- glm(No.Species ~ Forestry_F + Herbaceous.crops + Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds + Marches + Natural.grasslands + Natural.shrublands + Rivers.and.riparian.galleries + Woody.crops + max_NDVI + prop_flooded_area_ha + m_NDVI + sd_NDVI, family=quasipoisson, data= Small_wading_birds_season)
```

```
>
> VIF(M)
              Forestry_F              Herbaceous.crops Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds              Marches              Natural.grasslands              Natural.shrublands
Rivers.and.riparian.galleries 1.167031              1.429501              1.887457              3.762936              2.188125              1.175646
Woody.crops                    2.176299              1.129665              1.279934              1.490119              1.997006              1.549409
sd_NDVI
m_NDVI
prop_flooded_area_ha
```

```
> summary(M)
```

```
Call:
glm(formula = No.Species ~ Forestry_F + Herbaceous.crops + Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds + Marches + Natural.grasslands + Natural.shrublands + Rivers.and.riparian.galleries + Woody.crops + max_NDVI + prop_flooded_area_ha + m_NDVI + sd_NDVI, family = quasipoisson, data = Small_wading_birds_season)
```

```
Deviance Residuals:
    Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
-1.8188 -0.6858 -0.1513  0.4902  2.4372
```

```
Coefficients:
(Intercept)              7.799e-01  5.534e-01  1.409  0.15962
Forestry_F              -1.480e+00  9.792e-01 -1.511  0.13163
Herbaceous.crops        -2.297e-02  3.803e-01 -0.060  0.95188
Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds  1.520e+00  2.206e-01  6.890  2.57e-11 ***
Marches                  5.619e-01  1.531e-01  3.670  0.00028 ***
Natural.grasslands       3.613e-01  2.110e-01  1.712  0.08778 .
Natural.shrublands       -1.304e+00  9.244e-01 -1.411  0.15909
Rivers.and.riparian.galleries  2.876e-01  2.400e-01  1.198  0.23164
Woody.crops              -5.126e+00  2.955e+00 -1.735  0.08368 .
max_NDVI                 4.567e-03  3.191e-03  1.431  0.15330
prop_flooded_area_ha     -6.196e-01  1.163e-01 -5.330  1.76e-07 ***
m_NDVI                   -6.119e-03  2.349e-03 -2.605  0.00958 **
sd_NDVI                  5.296e-06  1.020e-06  5.194  3.49e-07 ***
```

```
---
Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
```

```
(Dispersion parameter for quasipoisson family taken to be 0.6722745)
```

```
Null deviance: 343.02 on 364 degrees of freedom
Residual deviance: 228.74 on 352 degrees of freedom
AIC: NA
```

```
Number of Fisher Scoring iterations: 5
```

```
>
> teste <- adjR2(M)
> teste
[1] 0.3104
```

DENSITY OF INDIVIDUALS

```
> M <- glm(nind_ha_adj ~ Forestry_F + Herbaceous.crops + Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds + Marches + Natural.grasslands + Natural.shrublands + Rivers.and.riparian.galleries + Woody.crops + max_NDVI + prop_flooded_area_ha + m_NDVI + sd_NDVI, family=Gamma(link="log"), data= Small_wading_birds_season)
>
> VIF(M)
      Forestry_F      Herbaceous.crops  Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds      Marches      Natural.grasslands      Natural.shrublands
Rivers.and.riparian.galleries 1.164088      1.542898      1.496217      3.919817      2.291518      1.190675
      2.239119      1.213157      1.349932      1.431137      1.972024      1.428991
>
> summary(M, dispersion=1)

Call:
glm(formula = nind_ha_adj ~ Forestry_F + Herbaceous.crops + Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds + Marches + Natural.grasslands + Natural.shrublands + Rivers.and.riparian.galleries + Woody.crops + max_NDVI + prop_flooded_area_ha + m_NDVI + sd_NDVI, family = Gamma(link = "log"), data = Small_wading_birds_season)

Deviance Residuals:
    Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
-3.3939 -1.7480 -0.7726  0.1489  3.6380

Coefficients:
            Estimate Std. Error z value Pr(>|z|)
(Intercept)  1.832e+00  1.121e+00  1.635  0.10210
Forestry_F    7.556e-01  1.555e+00  0.486  0.62694
Herbaceous.crops  2.925e+00  7.404e-01  3.950  7.80e-05 ***
Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds  4.581e+00  4.939e-01  9.113 < 2e-16 ***
Marches       1.899e+00  2.974e-01  6.385  1.71e-10 ***
Natural.grasslands  1.159e+00  3.927e-01  2.950  0.00318 **
Natural.shrublands -7.897e-01  1.571e+00 -0.503  0.61529
Rivers.and.riparian.galleries  2.658e+00  4.303e-01  6.176  6.57e-10 ***
Woody.crops   -7.196e+00  4.064e+00 -1.771  0.07661 .
max_NDVI     -3.384e-02  6.593e-03 -5.132  2.86e-07 ***
prop_flooded_area_ha  1.491e+00  2.303e-01  6.476  9.43e-11 ***
m_NDVI       1.172e-02  4.574e-03  2.563  0.01036 *
sd_NDVI     -1.952e-05  2.143e-06 -9.109 < 2e-16 ***
---
Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

(Dispersion parameter for Gamma family taken to be 1)

Null deviance: 1139.81 on 364 degrees of freedom
Residual deviance: 875.74 on 352 degrees of freedom
AIC: 463.19

Number of Fisher Scoring iterations: 17

>
> teste <- adjR2(M)
> teste
[1] 0.2055
```

SMALL_WADING_BIRDS_SUMMER

```
Forestry_Herbaceous.crops_Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds_Marches_Natural.grasslands_Natural.shrublands_Rice.fields_Rivers.and.riparian.galleries_Woody.crops
Forestry      1.00000000      -0.16662184      -0.04383470      -0.11228360      0.353092275      0.59650641      -1.628709e-01      3.128844e-02      0.16066748
Herbaceous.crops -0.16662184      1.00000000      0.22580970      0.22580970      -0.04383470      -0.11228360      0.353092275      0.59650641      -1.628709e-01
Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds -0.04383470      0.22580970      1.00000000      -0.14525895      -0.039646724      -0.05210371      0.05939985      -5.758453e-02      -3.779226e-01
Marches         -0.11228360      0.22580970      -0.14525895      1.00000000      -0.398356926      -0.05939985      -5.758453e-02      -3.779226e-01      -0.34476864
Natural.grasslands  0.353092275      0.04537123      0.039646724      -0.398356926      1.000000000      0.46068648      2.436124e-02      2.806785e-02      0.06975188
Natural.shrublands  0.59650641      -0.18272191      -0.05210371      0.05939985      0.46068648      1.000000000      -2.325240e-01      9.461197e-05      0.01923778
Rice.fields      -0.16287094      0.46335847      0.06118611      -0.57584533      -0.23252402      0.024361244      1.0000000e+00      6.759765e-02      0.01923778
Rivers.and.riparian.galleries  0.03128844      0.27399729      -0.04316836      0.37792258      -0.028067851      0.06759765      9.461197e-05      1.000000e+00      0.08375413
Woody.crops      0.16066748      0.28867059      -0.12876708      -0.34476864      0.069751881      0.01923778      3.563247e-01      8.375413e-02      1.00000000
sd_NDVI         -0.30957727      0.20732328      0.44630785      -0.09227998      -0.243981951      -0.34708677      4.767819e-01      -1.421208e-01      0.06116242
max_NDVI        0.12806436      0.25641513      0.10843518      -0.31364107      0.008608322      0.04486165      5.763754e-01      7.349091e-02      0.26502689
m_NDVI          -0.05028990      -0.02040257      -0.48982795      0.13539756      0.124404677      0.06977454      3.495182e-01      -1.195459e-01      0.27008484
prop_flooded_area_ha  0.02706812      0.01159183      -0.03382069      -0.22890987      -0.069597095      0.01854156      4.436622e-02      1.801885e-01      -0.03415074
sd_NDVI         0.02706812      0.128064355      -0.05028990      0.02706812
max_NDVI        0.20732328      0.256415130      -0.02040257      0.01159183
m_NDVI          0.44630785      0.108435181      -0.48982795      -0.03382069
prop_flooded_area_ha  -0.09227998      -0.313641074      0.13539756      -0.22890987
Natural.grasslands  -0.24398195      0.008608322      0.12440468      -0.06959709
Natural.shrublands  -0.34708677      0.044861646      0.06977454      -0.01854156
Rice.fields      0.47678189      0.576375444      0.34951817      0.04436622
Rivers.and.riparian.galleries  -0.14212076      0.073490913      -0.11954594      0.18018852
Woody.crops      0.06116242      0.265026887      0.27008484      -0.03415074
sd_NDVI         1.00000000      0.439557450      -0.01245196      0.16414356
max_NDVI        0.43955745      1.000000000      0.41379450      0.05658192
m_NDVI          -0.01245196      0.413794502      1.00000000      0.15988192
prop_flooded_area_ha  0.16414356      0.056581920      0.15988192      1.00000000
```

SPECIES RICHNESS

```
> M <- glm(No..Species ~ Forestry_F + Herbaceous.crops + Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds + Marches + Natural.grasslands + Natural.shrublands + Rivers.and.riparian.galleries + Woody.crops + max_NDVI + prop_flooded_area_ha + m_NDVI + sd_NDVI, family=quasipoisson, data= Small_wading_birds_season)
>
> VIF(M)
              Forestry_F              Herbaceous.crops Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds              Marches              Natural.grasslands              Natural.shrublands
Rivers.and.riparian.galleries 1.350310                2.005090                3.803843                4.391817                1.747371                1.181284
                2.641485                1.223509                1.659448                prop_flooded_area_ha                m_NDVI                sd_NDVI
                2.641485                1.223509                1.659448                1.346935                3.718924                2.180191
>
> summary(M)

Call:
glm(Formula = No..Species ~ Forestry_F + Herbaceous.crops + Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds + Marches + Natural.grasslands + Natural.shrublands + Rivers.and.riparian.galleries + Woody.crops + max_NDVI + prop_flooded_area_ha + m_NDVI + sd_NDVI, family = quasipoisson, data = Small_wading_birds_season)

Deviance Residuals:
    Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
-1.4716 -0.7630 -0.1043  0.4904  1.8886

Coefficients:
            Estimate Std. Error t value Pr(>|t|)
(Intercept)  1.359e+00  6.508e-01  2.087  0.0375 *
Forestry_F   -8.980e-01  1.017e+00  -0.883  0.3778
Herbaceous.crops -3.084e-01  2.547e-01  -1.211  0.2266
Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds 4.922e-01  2.763e-01  1.782  0.0756 .
Marches      1.920e-01  1.481e-01  1.297  0.1954
Natural.grasslands 9.538e-02  2.415e-01  0.395  0.6931
Natural.shrublands -5.369e-01  1.017e+00  -0.528  0.5979
Rivers.and.riparian.galleries 4.212e-02  2.276e-01  0.185  0.8533
Woody.crops  1.378e-01  1.493e+00  0.092  0.9265
max_NDVI     1.112e-02  2.772e-03  4.011  7.28e-05 ***
prop_flooded_area_ha 1.094e-01  1.134e-01  0.965  0.3354
m_NDVI      -1.894e-02  3.627e-03  -5.224  2.88e-07 ***
sd_NDVI     1.703e-06  1.047e-06  1.627  0.1045
---
Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

(Dispersion parameter for quasipoisson family taken to be 0.591436)

Null deviance: 315.02  on 396  degrees of freedom
Residual deviance: 221.35  on 384  degrees of freedom
AIC: NA

Number of Fisher Scoring iterations: 4

>
> teste <- adjR2(M)
> teste
[1] 0.2754
```

DENSITY OF INDIVIDUALS

```
> M <- glm(nind_ha_adj ~ Forestry_F + Herbaceous.crops + Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds + Marches + Natural.grasslands + Natural.shrublands + Rivers.and.riparian.galleries + Woody.crops + max_NDVI + prop_flooded_area_ha + m_NDVI + sd_NDVI, family=Gamma(link="log"), data= Small_wading_birds_season)
>
> VIF(M)
              Forestry_F              Herbaceous.crops Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds              Marches              Natural.grasslands              Natural.shrublands
Rivers.and.riparian.galleries 1.367259                2.103278                3.179087                4.131894                1.759449                1.219263
                2.821779                1.259615                1.755177                prop_flooded_area_ha                m_NDVI                sd_NDVI
                2.821779                1.259615                1.755177                1.240634                3.103890                1.602805
>
> summary(M, dispersion=1)

Call:
glm(formula = nind_ha_adj ~ Forestry_F + Herbaceous.crops + Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds + Marches + Natural.grasslands + Natural.shrublands + Rivers.and.riparian.galleries + Woody.crops + max_NDVI + prop_flooded_area_ha + m_NDVI + sd_NDVI, family = Gamma(link = "log"), data = Small_wading_birds_season)

Deviance Residuals:
    Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
-2.9616 -1.2097 -0.6483  0.1709  3.2050

Coefficients:
            Estimate Std. Error z value Pr(>|z|)
(Intercept) -2.849e+00  1.440e+00  -1.978  0.047947 *
Forestry_F   5.693e+00  1.900e+00  2.997  0.002728 **
Herbaceous.crops 4.385e+00  5.689e-01  7.708  1.27e-14 ***
Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds 2.578e+00  6.655e-01  3.874  0.000107 ***
Marches      5.756e-01  3.321e-01  1.733  0.083025 .
Natural.grasslands 8.197e-01  5.358e-01  1.530  0.126019
Natural.shrublands 2.278e+00  2.010e+00  1.133  0.257126
Rivers.and.riparian.galleries 2.337e+00  4.860e-01  4.809  1.52e-06 ***
Woody.crops  -1.390e+01  3.046e+00  -4.562  5.06e-06 ***
max_NDVI     3.304e-03  6.435e-03  0.513  0.607678
prop_flooded_area_ha 3.419e+00  2.634e-01  12.978  < 2e-16 ***
m_NDVI      3.251e-03  8.385e-03  0.388  0.698226
sd_NDVI     -1.979e-05  2.730e-06  -7.248  4.22e-13 ***
---
Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

(Dispersion parameter for Gamma family taken to be 1)

Null deviance: 915.20  on 327  degrees of freedom
Residual deviance: 485.43  on 315  degrees of freedom
(69 observations deleted due to missingness)
AIC: 1032.2

Number of Fisher Scoring iterations: 20

>
> teste <- adjR2(M)
> teste
[1] 0.4494
```

SMALL_WADING_BIRDS_WINTER

```

Forestry Herbaceous.crops Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds Marches Natural.grasslands Natural.shrublands Rice.fields Rivers.and.riparian.galleries Woody.crops
1.00000000 -0.123102501 -0.17725658 -0.141680708 0.376736677 0.669463757 -0.122375257 0.024827882 0.12396150
Herbaceous.crops -0.12310250 1.000000000 0.27408461 -0.511445249 0.002059631 -0.140611646 0.532321402 0.372505496 0.42569348
Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds -0.17725658 0.274084606 1.00000000 -0.134618082 -0.079334627 -0.140264293 0.131950844 0.109666711 -0.13978814
Marches -0.14168071 -0.511445249 -0.13461808 1.00000000 -0.363709435 -0.089246009 -0.564989386 -0.365015013 -0.41067097
Natural.grasslands 0.37673668 0.002059631 -0.07933463 -0.363709435 1.00000000 0.417200781 -0.001717582 0.029820994 0.02775295
Natural.shrublands 0.66946376 -0.140611646 -0.14026429 -0.089246009 0.417200781 1.000000000 -0.232488456 0.034934051 0.04172935
Rice.fields -0.12237526 0.532321402 0.13195084 -0.564989386 -0.001717582 -0.232488456 1.000000000 0.209372028 0.45228344
Rivers.and.riparian.galleries 0.02482788 0.372505496 0.10966671 -0.365015013 0.029820994 0.034934051 0.209372028 1.000000000 0.15598036
Woody.crops 0.12396150 0.425693482 -0.13978814 -0.410670972 0.027752953 0.041729353 0.452283439 0.155980358 1.00000000
sd_NDVI -0.31497474 0.238767354 0.41615961 0.040349877 -0.241234510 -0.356771732 0.384814666 -0.021013179 0.16023907
max_NDVI 0.10864372 0.236617209 0.13038796 -0.233220358 0.096487368 0.005988001 0.385089361 0.181617237 0.22800788
m_NDVI 0.01725514 -0.089030325 -0.20426482 -0.009803994 0.222806317 0.052320728 0.134980499 -0.221713256 0.07933463
prop_flooded_area_ha 0.05160890 -0.020596691 0.08407944 0.202446316 -0.215083401 -0.035775477 -0.227065494 0.007159795 -0.03748336
sd_NDVI max_NDVI m_NDVI prop_flooded_area_ha
Forestry -0.31497474 0.108643722 0.017255136 -0.051608903
Herbaceous.crops 0.23876735 0.236617209 -0.089030325 -0.020596691
Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds 0.41615961 0.130387956 -0.204264825 0.084079441
Marches 0.04034988 -0.233220358 -0.009803994 0.202446316
Natural.grasslands -0.24123451 0.096487368 0.222806317 -0.215083401
Natural.shrublands -0.35677173 0.005988001 0.052320728 -0.035775477
Rice.fields 0.38481467 0.385089361 0.134980499 -0.227065494
Rivers.and.riparian.galleries -0.02101318 0.181617237 -0.221713256 0.007159795
Woody.crops 0.16023907 0.22800788 0.079334628 -0.037483362
sd_NDVI 1.00000000 0.344004204 -0.166938889 0.294625183
max_NDVI 0.34400420 1.000000000 0.330889731 -0.137538914
m_NDVI -0.16693889 0.330889731 1.000000000 -0.665959404
prop_flooded_area_ha 0.29462518 -0.137538914 -0.665959404 1.000000000

```

SPECIES RICHNESS

```

> M <- glm(No.Species ~ Forestry_F + Herbaceous.crops + Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds + Marches + Natural.grasslands + Natural.shrublands + Rivers.and.riparian.galleries + Woody.crops + max_NDVI +
prop_flooded_area_ha + m_NDVI + sd_NDVI, family=quasipoisson, data= Small_wading_birds_season)
>
> VIF(M)
              Forestry_F              Herbaceous.crops Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds              Marches              Natural.grasslands              Natural.shrublands
Rivers.and.riparian.galleries 1.118273              1.700460              1.366643              2.899826              1.631850              1.118227
1.543544              1.190488              1.357013              2.080542              2.320354              1.741410
>
> summary(M)
Call:
glm(formula = No.Species ~ Forestry_F + Herbaceous.crops + Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds +
Marches + Natural.grasslands + Natural.shrublands + Rivers.and.riparian.galleries +
Woody.crops + max_NDVI + prop_flooded_area_ha + m_NDVI +
sd_NDVI, family = quasipoisson, data = Small_wading_birds_season)

Deviance Residuals:
    Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
-1.5254 -0.7004 -0.1134  0.4301  2.6885

Coefficients:
(Intercept)              3.320e-01  5.538e-01  0.599  0.54919
Forestry_F              -1.375e+00  6.439e-01  -2.136  0.03326 *
Herbaceous.crops         1.181e-01  2.185e-01  0.541  0.58905
Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds 1.671e+00  1.912e-01  8.742 < 2e-16 ***
Marches                  3.451e-01  1.182e-01  2.920  0.00369 ***
Natural.grasslands       -1.429e-01  1.897e-01  -0.753  0.45174
Natural.shrublands       -2.929e-01  6.828e-01  -0.429  0.66816
Rivers.and.riparian.galleries 2.856e-01  2.176e-01  1.312  0.19014
Woody.crops              -2.024e+00  1.992e+00  -1.016  0.31034
max_NDVI                 4.478e-03  3.326e-03  1.346  0.17890
prop_flooded_area_ha     -3.911e-01  1.308e-01  -2.991  0.00295 **
m_NDVI                   -1.650e-03  2.520e-03  -0.655  0.51311
sd_NDVI                  2.805e-06  8.827e-07  3.178  0.00159 **
---
Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

(Dispersion parameter for quasipoisson family taken to be 0.7340524)

Null deviance: 396.95  on 429  degrees of freedom
Residual deviance: 295.31  on 417  degrees of freedom
AIC: NA

Number of Fisher Scoring iterations: 5
>
> teste <- adjR2(M)
> teste
[1] 0.2346

```

DENSITY OF INDIVIDUALS

```
> M <- glm(mind_ha_adj ~ Forestry_F + Herbaceous.crops + Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds + Rice.fields + Natural.grasslands + Natural.shrublands + Rivers.and.riparian.galleries + Woody.crops + max_NDVI + prop_flooded_area_ha + m_NDVI + sd_NDVI, family=Gamma(link="log"), data= Small_wading_birds_season)
> VIF(M)
              Forestry_F              Herbaceous.crops Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds              Rice.fields              Natural.grasslands              Natural.shrublands
Rivers.and.riparian.galleries 1.120440                1.220508                1.243791                1.491463                1.116271                1.121479
              1.243091                1.209071                1.400708                prop_flooded_area_ha                m_NDVI                sd_NDVI
              1.243091                1.209071                1.400708                1.930096                2.055680                1.539262
>
> summary(M, dispersion=1)

Call:
glm(formula = mind_ha_adj ~ Forestry_F + Herbaceous.crops + Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds + Rice.fields + Natural.grasslands + Natural.shrublands + Rivers.and.riparian.galleries + Woody.crops + max_NDVI + prop_flooded_area_ha + m_NDVI + sd_NDVI, family = Gamma(link = "log"), data = Small_wading_birds_season)

Deviance Residuals:
    Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
-3.2545 -1.6961 -0.9535  0.0947  6.3393

Coefficients:
              Estimate Std. Error z value Pr(>|z|)
(Intercept)  1.351e+00  1.133e+00  1.192  0.23320
Forestry_F   -2.673e+00  1.252e+00 -2.135  0.03273 *
Herbaceous.crops  1.074e+00  4.125e-01  2.604  0.00922 **
Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds -1.017e-01  4.624e-01 -0.220  0.82589
Rice.fields   -6.850e-01  2.858e-01 -2.397  0.01653 **
Natural.grasslands  2.299e+00  3.355e-01  6.855  7.15e-12 ***
Natural.shrublands -4.015e+00  1.264e+00 -3.176  0.00149 ***
Rivers.and.riparian.galleries  3.311e-01  3.635e-01  0.911  0.36231
Woody.crops   -2.185e+01  4.375e+00 -4.994  5.93e-07 ***
max_NDVI      -6.243e-03  6.888e-03 -0.906  0.36475
prop_flooded_area_ha  1.312e+00  2.917e-01  4.500  6.81e-06 ***
m_NDVI        3.156e-03  5.297e-03  0.596  0.55126
sd_NDVI       -1.194e-05  2.265e-06 -5.274  1.34e-07 ***
---
Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

(Dispersion parameter for Gamma family taken to be 1)

Null deviance: 950.84  on 346  degrees of freedom
Residual deviance: 807.56  on 334  degrees of freedom
(83 observations deleted due to missingness)
AIC: 1436.2

Number of Fisher Scoring iterations: 25

>
> teste <- adjR2(M)
> teste
[1] 0.1202
```

SMALL_WADING_BIRDS_AUTUMN

	Forestry	Herbaceous.crops	Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds	Marches	Natural.grasslands	Natural.shrublands	Rice.fields	Rivers.and.riparian.galleries	Woody.crops	sd_NDVI
Forestry	1.00000000	-0.20890824	-0.16946282	-0.03902990	0.31912838	0.57431569	-0.23960108	-0.09120395	0.106421475	-0.3461832
Herbaceous.crops	-0.20890824	1.00000000	0.28302083	-0.57198387	0.04640145	-0.18977167	0.55233029	0.33393571	0.401380255	0.4291714
Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds	-0.16946282	0.28302083	1.00000000	-0.13937846	-0.03976010	-0.15202608	0.09269128	0.05222943	-0.172443909	0.5204148
Marches	-0.03902990	-0.57198387	-0.13937846	1.00000000	-0.32641610	-0.02360508	-0.63553497	-0.36285667	-0.443274089	-0.2857197
Natural.grasslands	0.31912838	0.04640145	-0.03976010	-0.32641610	1.00000000	0.40371251	-0.01892278	0.04805626	0.072640589	-0.1606151
Natural.shrublands	0.57431569	-0.18977167	-0.15202608	-0.02360508	0.40371251	1.00000000	-0.28059919	-0.06518009	0.039792506	0.4061281
Rice.fields	-0.23960108	0.55233029	0.09269128	-0.63553497	-0.01892278	-0.28059919	1.00000000	0.15410476	0.445324750	0.5613768
Rivers.and.riparian.galleries	-0.09120395	0.33393571	0.05222943	-0.36285667	0.04805626	-0.06518009	0.15410476	1.00000000	0.155622351	0.1926484
Woody.crops	0.10642147	0.40138025	-0.17244391	-0.44327409	0.07264059	0.03979251	0.44532475	0.15562235	1.000000000	0.1706143
sd_NDVI	-0.34618324	0.42917140	0.52041481	-0.28571966	-0.16061511	-0.40612814	0.56137682	0.19264845	0.170614272	1.00000000
max_NDVI	0.22203948	0.18588369	0.15139762	-0.16010262	-0.10756095	0.13749501	0.32873569	0.05997385	0.194620930	0.2304511
m_NDVI	0.08503512	-0.03182240	-0.44875911	-0.15228217	0.09670851	0.17193340	0.25140669	-0.12654479	0.200203834	-0.2785570
prop_flooded_area_ha	-0.09784698	0.17697312	0.31045947	-0.26039816	-0.05714999	-0.14666377	0.14849955	0.21497057	0.001360784	0.5694851
	max_NDVI	m_NDVI	prop_flooded_area_ha							
Forestry	0.22203948	0.08503512	-0.097846980							
Herbaceous.crops	0.18588369	-0.03182240	0.176973122							
Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds	0.15139762	-0.44875911	0.310459470							
Marches	-0.16010262	-0.15228217	-0.260398163							
Natural.grasslands	-0.10756095	0.09670851	-0.057149992							
Natural.shrublands	0.13749501	0.17193340	-0.146663769							
Rice.fields	0.32873569	0.25140669	0.148499553							
Rivers.and.riparian.galleries	0.05997385	-0.12654479	0.214970573							
Woody.crops	0.19462093	0.20020383	0.001360784							
sd_NDVI	0.23045112	-0.27855699	0.569485079							
max_NDVI	1.00000000	0.21680709	-0.118965954							
m_NDVI	0.21680709	1.00000000	-0.240126692							
prop_flooded_area_ha	-0.11896595	-0.24012669	1.000000000							

SPECIES RICHNESS

```
> M <- glm(No..Species ~ Forestry_F + Herbaceous.crops + Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds + Rice.fields + Natural.grasslands + Natural.shrublands + Rivers.and.riparian.galleries + Woody.crops + max_NDVI + prop_flooded_area_ha + m_NDVI + sd_NDVI, family=quasipoisson, data= Small_wading_birds_season)
>
> VIF(M)
              Forestry_F              Herbaceous.crops Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds              Rice.fields              Natural.grasslands              Natural.shrublands
Rivers.and.riparian.galleries 1.183979              1.149383              2.798745              2.663022              1.154006              1.181624
                                Woody.crops              max_NDVI              prop_flooded_area_ha              m_NDVI              sd_NDVI
                                1.416560              1.188619              1.609192              1.580666              2.914849              2.170606
>
> summary(M)

Call:
glm(formula = No..Species ~ Forestry_F + Herbaceous.crops + Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds + Rice.fields + Natural.grasslands + Natural.shrublands + Rivers.and.riparian.galleries + Woody.crops + max_NDVI + prop_flooded_area_ha + m_NDVI + sd_NDVI, family = quasipoisson, data = Small_wading_birds_season)

Deviance Residuals:
    Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
-1.4968 -0.7297 -0.1627  0.4833  2.4036

Coefficients:
            (Intercept)  -1.031e+00  6.788e-01  -1.519  0.12966
Forestry_F             -3.928e+00  1.313e+00  -2.991  0.00296 **
Herbaceous.crops      -7.653e-02  1.860e-01  -0.411  0.68094
Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds  1.948e+00  2.499e-01  7.794  5.94e-14 ***
Rice.fields           -1.583e-02  1.508e-01  -0.105  0.91644
Natural.grasslands    2.367e-02  1.898e-01  0.125  0.90083
Natural.shrublands    -1.074e-00  7.818e-01  -1.374  0.17017
Rivers.and.riparian.galleries  8.651e-01  1.712e-01  5.054  6.66e-07 ***
Woody.crops           -1.761e+00  1.359e+00  -1.295  0.19600
max_NDVI              7.311e-03  3.057e-03  2.392  0.01725 *
prop_flooded_area_ha  7.508e-02  1.151e-01  0.653  0.51445
m_NDVI                4.581e-03  4.270e-03  1.073  0.28396
sd_NDVI               1.113e-06  1.113e-06  1.000  0.31771
---
Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

(Dispersion parameter for quasipoisson family taken to be 0.69988)

Null deviance: 385.32 on 402 degrees of freedom
Residual deviance: 258.63 on 390 degrees of freedom
AIC: NA

Number of Fisher Scoring iterations: 4

>
> teste <- adjR2(M)
> teste
[1] 0.3081
```

DENSITY OF INDIVIDUALS

```
> M <- glm(nind_ha_adj ~ Forestry_F + Herbaceous.crops + Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds + Rice.fields + Natural.grasslands + Natural.shrublands + Rivers.and.riparian.galleries + Woody.crops + max_NDVI + prop_flooded_area_ha + m_NDVI + sd_NDVI, family=Gamma(link="log"), data= Small_wading_birds_season)
>
> VIF(M)
              Forestry_F              Herbaceous.crops Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds              Rice.fields              Natural.grasslands              Natural.shrublands
Rivers.and.riparian.galleries 1.126569              1.171195              2.581730              2.303215              1.176741              1.237482
                                Woody.crops              max_NDVI              prop_flooded_area_ha              m_NDVI              sd_NDVI
                                1.294017              1.197152              1.714315              1.355616              2.712797              1.898781
>
> summary(M, dispersion=1)

Call:
glm(formula = nind_ha_adj ~ Forestry_F + Herbaceous.crops + Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds + Rice.fields + Natural.grasslands + Natural.shrublands + Rivers.and.riparian.galleries + Woody.crops + max_NDVI + prop_flooded_area_ha + m_NDVI + sd_NDVI, family = Gamma(link = "log"), data = Small_wading_birds_season)

Deviance Residuals:
    Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
-2.8031 -1.5249 -0.7708  0.1726  3.5397

Coefficients:
            (Intercept)  4.310e+00  1.482e+00  2.908  0.003636 **
Forestry_F             -4.167e-01  1.770e+00  -0.235  0.813847
Herbaceous.crops      2.640e+00  4.517e-01  5.845  5.08e-09 ***
Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds  3.012e+00  6.307e-01  4.776  1.79e-06 ***
Rice.fields           3.508e-01  3.640e-01  0.964  0.335199
Natural.grasslands    1.480e+00  4.021e-01  3.680  0.000233 ***
Natural.shrublands    4.436e-01  1.546e+00  0.287  0.774191
Rivers.and.riparian.galleries  2.278e+00  3.534e-01  6.445  1.15e-10 ***
Woody.crops           -1.621e+01  3.021e+00  -5.365  8.10e-08 ***
max_NDVI              -3.431e-02  6.905e-03  -4.968  6.75e-07 ***
prop_flooded_area_ha  2.445e+00  2.442e-01  10.014  < 2e-16 ***
m_NDVI                6.897e-03  9.940e-03  0.694  0.487799
sd_NDVI               -1.971e-05  2.908e-06  -6.778  1.22e-11 ***
---
Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

(Dispersion parameter for Gamma family taken to be 1)

Null deviance: 982.65 on 298 degrees of freedom
Residual deviance: 560.40 on 286 degrees of freedom
(104 observations deleted due to missingness)
AIC: 1045.9

Number of Fisher Scoring iterations: 25

>
> teste <- adjR2(M)
> teste
[1] 0.4058
```

Appendix B6 - Changes in land use classes per plot (in terms of proportion of area) between 2020 and 2040.

	Forestry		Herbaceous crops		Industrial salt pans and fish ponds		Marches		Natural grasslands		Natural shrublands		Rice fields		Rivers and riparian galleries		Woody crops		
	2020	2040	2020	2040	2020	2040	2020	2040	2020	2040	2020	2040	2020	2040	2020	2040	2020	2040	
ARROZALES DE PUEBLA E ISLA MAYOR	0.00	0.00	0.03	0.02	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.96	0.97	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.00
BRAZO DE LA TORRE Y CANTARITAS	0.00	0.00	0.40	0.47	0.00	0.00	0.06	0.06	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.50	0.43	0.04	0.04	0.00	0.00	
COLONIA DE LA ISLETA DE PUEBLA	0.00	0.00	0.92	0.95	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.08	0.05	0.00	0.00	
DE LA ALGAIDA A LOS SOTOS	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.95	0.95	0.04	0.05	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	
DEHESA DE ABAJO	0.31	0.60	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.06	0.05	0.19	0.15	0.02	0.02	0.00	0.00	0.42	0.19	0.00	0.00	
DEL PALACIO A LA ALGAIDA	0.05	0.11	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.89	0.82	0.02	0.04	0.04	0.03	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	
EL PUNTAL	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.98	0.99	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	
ENTREMUROS	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.12	0.06	0.58	0.52	0.03	0.04	0.00	0.00	0.21	0.17	0.05	0.21	
GUADAMAR ENCAUZADO	0.00	0.00	0.02	0.02	0.00	0.00	0.36	0.22	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.62	0.76	0.00	0.00	
HATO BLANCO	0.02	0.04	0.40	0.59	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.53	0.34	0.00	0.00	0.05	0.03	
LAGUNAS RBD	0.01	0.02	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.86	0.88	0.13	0.09	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	
LAS NUEVAS - MATOCHAR	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.99	0.99	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.00	
LOS CARACOLES	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.03	0.28	0.97	0.72	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	
LUCIO DE LA FAO	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	1.00	1.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	
MARISMA DE HINOJOS	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	1.00	1.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	
MARISMAS DE COTO DEL REY	0.02	0.02	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.91	0.85	0.06	0.12	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.00	
MARISMAS DEL ROCIO	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.72	0.33	0.00	0.00	0.12	0.50	0.00	0.00	0.15	0.17	0.00	0.00	
MARISMILLAS	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.99	0.88	0.01	0.11	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	
MATASGORDAS	0.26	0.20	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.39	0.29	0.30	0.46	0.03	0.03	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.03	0.00	0.00	
OTROS CULTIVOS	0.00	0.00	0.83	0.68	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.02	0.06	0.21	0.07	0.08	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.02	
PARTIDO	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.69	0.49	0.26	0.49	0.00	0.00	0.05	0.02	0.00	0.00	
RESERVA DEL GUADAMAR	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	1.00	1.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	
SALINAS DE BONANZA	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.46	0.52	0.51	0.35	0.02	0.11	0.01	0.02	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	
VETA LA PALMA	0.00	0.00	0.22	0.26	0.27	0.38	0.45	0.31	0.02	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.05	0.04	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	

Appendix B7 - Number of years used to infer NDVI estimations from Land use classes and proportion of flooded area at the plot level.

Plots	Autumn	Spring	Summer	Winter
ARROZALES DE PUEBLA E ISLA MAYOR	30	28	35	25
BRAZO DE LA TORRE Y CANTARITAS	30	28	35	25
COLONIA DE LA ISLETA DE PUEBLA	30	28	35	25
DE LA ALGAIDA A LOS SOTOS	30	28	35	25
DEHESA DE ABAJO	30	28	35	25
DEL PALACIO A LA ALGAIDA	30	28	35	25
EL PUNTAL	30	28	35	25
ENTREMUROS	30	28	35	25
GUADAMAR ENCAUZADO	30	28	35	25
HATO BLANCO	30	28	35	25
LAGUNAS RBD	30	28	35	25
LAS NUEVAS - MATOCHAR	30	28	35	25
LOS CARACOLES	30	28	35	25
LUCIO DE LA FAO	30	28	35	25
MARISMA DE HINOJOS	30	28	35	25
MARISMAS DE COTO DEL REY	30	28	35	25
MARISMAS DEL ROCIO Y ROCINA	30	28	35	25
MARISMILLAS	30	28	35	25
MATASGORDAS	30	28	35	25
OTROS CULTIVOS	30	28	35	25
PARTIDO	30	28	35	25
RESERVA DEL GUADAMAR	30	28	35	25
SALINAS DE BONANZA	30	28	35	25
VETA LA PALMA	30	28	35	25

Appendix B8 - Statistical outputs (i.e. histograms, Spearman Rho correlation, Variance Inflection Factor, Regression models and partial regression coefficients) of the statistical models obtained to relate NDVI (mean NDVI as 'm_NDVI', maximum NDVI as 'max_NDVI' and standard deviation of NDVI as 'sd_NDVI') to seasonal variation in abiotic conditions (i.e. percentage of area of each LU class considered and proportion of flooded area, calculated at the plot level).

HISTOGRAMS

M_NDVI_SPRING

```
> M <- lm(m_NDVI ~ prop_flooded_area_ha + Forestry_F + Herbaceous.crops + Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds + Marches + Natural.grasslands + Natural.shrublands + Rivers.and.riparian.galleries + Woody.crops, data=
spring)
>
> VIF(M)
      prop_flooded_area_ha      Forestry_F      Herbaceous.crops      Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds      Marches      Natural.grasslands
      1.556226      1.126247      2.447025      1.137832      2.992033      1.821889
      Natural.shrublands      Rivers.and.riparian.galleries      Woody.crops
      1.048049      1.327588      1.112246
>
> summary(M)

Call:
lm(formula = m_NDVI ~ prop_flooded_area_ha + Forestry_F + Herbaceous.crops +
  Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds + Marches + Natural.grasslands +
  Natural.shrublands + Rivers.and.riparian.galleries + Woody.crops,
  data = spring)

Residuals:
    Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
-50.538  -7.502  -0.196   7.239  34.244

Coefficients:
            Estimate Std. Error t value Pr(>|t|)
(Intercept)    130.411     2.041   63.903 < 2e-16 ***
prop_flooded_area_ha -12.371     1.858  -6.657 5.88e-11 ***
Forestry_F      34.920     8.194   4.262 2.32e-05 ***
Herbaceous.crops   8.906     2.797   3.184 0.00152 ***
Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds -33.911     5.127  -6.614 7.73e-11 ***
Marches          11.566     2.144   5.394 9.62e-08 ***
Natural.grasslands 22.487     2.877   7.816 2.15e-14 ***
Natural.shrublands 89.949    11.069   8.127 2.17e-15 ***
Rivers.and.riparian.galleries -23.465     3.817  -6.147 1.37e-09 ***
Woody.crops       75.756    27.539   2.751 0.00611 **
---
Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

Residual standard error: 12.68 on 662 degrees of freedom
Multiple R-squared:  0.4305, Adjusted R-squared:  0.4228
F-statistic: 55.61 on 9 and 662 DF, p-value: < 2.2e-16
```

M_NDVI_SUMMER

```
> M <- lm(m_NDVI ~ prop_flooded_area_ha + Forestry_F + Herbaceous.crops + Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds + Marches + Natural.grasslands + Natural.shrublands + Rivers.and.riparian.galleries + Woody.crops, data=
summer)
>
> VIF(M)
      prop_flooded_area_ha      Forestry_F      Herbaceous.crops      Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds      Marches      Natural.grasslands
      1.686126      1.175067      3.222195      1.132769      3.561132      2.295909
      Natural.shrublands      Rivers.and.riparian.galleries      Woody.crops
      1.052164      1.215251      1.089064
>
> summary(M)

Call:
lm(formula = m_NDVI ~ prop_flooded_area_ha + Forestry_F + Herbaceous.crops +
  Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds + Marches + Natural.grasslands +
  Natural.shrublands + Rivers.and.riparian.galleries + Woody.crops,
  data = summer)

Residuals:
    Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
-25.865  -5.259  -0.684   4.966  34.881

Coefficients:
            Estimate Std. Error t value Pr(>|t|)
(Intercept)    150.940     1.574   95.875 < 2e-16 ***
prop_flooded_area_ha   5.050     1.327   3.807 0.000151 ***
Forestry_F      -1.829     5.140  -0.356 0.721997
Herbaceous.crops -11.526     1.962  -5.875 6.13e-09 ***
Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds -65.307     3.246 -20.119 < 2e-16 ***
Marches         -19.765     1.471 -13.434 < 2e-16 ***
Natural.grasslands -16.008     2.084  -7.682 4.40e-14 ***
Natural.shrublands 30.734     6.653   4.620 4.46e-06 ***
Rivers.and.riparian.galleries -31.024     2.474 -12.540 < 2e-16 ***
Woody.crops      -16.749    19.183  -0.873 0.382855
---
Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

Residual standard error: 8.813 on 830 degrees of freedom
Multiple R-squared:  0.4617, Adjusted R-squared:  0.4559
F-statistic: 79.11 on 9 and 830 DF, p-value: < 2.2e-16
```

M_NDVI_WINTER

```
--
> M <- lm(m_NDVI ~ prop_flooded_area_ha + Forestry_F + Herbaceous.crops + Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds + Marches + Natural.grasslands + Natural.shrublands + Rivers.and.riparian.galleries + Woody.crops, data=
winter)
>
> VIF(M)
prop_flooded_area_ha      Forestry_F      Herbaceous.crops      Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds      Marches      Natural.grasslands
1.513341      1.137619      2.537432      1.136811      2.796440      1.835080
Natural.shrublands      Rivers.and.riparian.galleries      Woody.crops
1.053214      1.231770      1.097587
>
> summary(M)

Call:
lm(formula = m_NDVI ~ prop_flooded_area_ha + Forestry_F + Herbaceous.crops +
  Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds + Marches + Natural.grasslands +
  Natural.shrublands + Rivers.and.riparian.galleries + Woody.crops,
  data = winter)

Residuals:
    Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
-48.575  -6.965   0.917   8.423  36.093

Coefficients:
            Estimate Std. Error t value Pr(>|t|)
(Intercept)      141.648      2.099   67.486 < 2e-16 ***
prop_flooded_area_ha    -31.146      1.770  -17.597 < 2e-16 ***
Forestry_F          20.967      8.028    2.612  0.00923 **
Herbaceous.crops     -1.549      2.737   -0.566  0.57158
Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds -13.652      4.980   -2.741  0.00630 **
Marches             4.502      2.028    2.220  0.02680 *
Natural.grasslands    14.089      2.862    4.923 1.11e-06 ***
Natural.shrublands    41.763     10.443    3.999 7.17e-05 ***
Rivers.and.riparian.galleries -20.975      3.815   -5.499 5.71e-08 ***
Woody.crops          61.170     30.149    2.029  0.04292 *
---
Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

Residual standard error: 11.62 on 590 degrees of freedom
Multiple R-squared:  0.547,    Adjusted R-squared:  0.5401
F-statistic: 79.16 on 9 and 590 DF,  p-value: < 2.2e-16
```

M_NDVI_AUTUMN

```
--
> M <- lm(m_NDVI ~ prop_flooded_area_ha + Forestry_F + Herbaceous.crops + Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds + Marches + Natural.grasslands + Natural.shrublands + Rivers.and.riparian.galleries + Woody.crops, data=
autumn)
>
> VIF(M)
prop_flooded_area_ha      Forestry_F      Herbaceous.crops      Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds      Marches      Natural.grasslands
1.490580      1.138462      2.788640      1.170715      3.398984      2.100232
Natural.shrublands      Rivers.and.riparian.galleries      Woody.crops
1.048618      1.260276      1.108171
>
> summary(M)

Call:
lm(formula = m_NDVI ~ prop_flooded_area_ha + Forestry_F + Herbaceous.crops +
  Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds + Marches + Natural.grasslands +
  Natural.shrublands + Rivers.and.riparian.galleries + Woody.crops,
  data = autumn)

Residuals:
    Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
-32.218  -4.321  -0.379   3.839  24.975

Coefficients:
            Estimate Std. Error t value Pr(>|t|)
(Intercept)      144.631      1.190  121.551 < 2e-16 ***
prop_flooded_area_ha    -4.701      1.086   -4.331 1.70e-05 ***
Forestry_F          12.872      4.214    3.054 0.002341 **
Herbaceous.crops     -12.857      1.510   -8.512 < 2e-16 ***
Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds -44.307      2.657  -16.678 < 2e-16 ***
Marches            -12.606      1.167  -10.806 < 2e-16 ***
Natural.grasslands    -5.954      1.586   -3.754 0.000189 ***
Natural.shrublands    32.514      5.659    5.745 1.36e-08 ***
Rivers.and.riparian.galleries -19.715      1.905  -10.348 < 2e-16 ***
Woody.crops          -1.527     14.012   -0.109 0.913232
---
Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

Residual standard error: 6.671 on 710 degrees of freedom
Multiple R-squared:  0.4557,    Adjusted R-squared:  0.4488
F-statistic: 66.05 on 9 and 710 DF,  p-value: < 2.2e-16
```

MAX_NDVI_SPRING

```
> M <- lm(max_NDVI ~ prop_flooded_area_ha + Forestry_F + Herbaceous.crops + Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds + Marches + Natural.grasslands + Natural.shrublands + Rivers.and.riparian.galleries + Woody.crops, data=spring)
>
> VIF(M)
      prop_flooded_area_ha      Forestry_F      Herbaceous.crops      Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds      Marches      Natural.grasslands
      1.556226                1.126247                2.447025                1.137832                2.992033                1.821889
      Natural.shrublands      Rivers.and.riparian.galleries      Woody.crops
      1.048049                1.327588                1.112246

> summary(M)

Call:
lm(formula = max_NDVI ~ prop_flooded_area_ha + Forestry_F + Herbaceous.crops + Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds + Marches + Natural.grasslands + Natural.shrublands + Rivers.and.riparian.galleries + Woody.crops, data = spring)

Residuals:
    Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
-30.819  -5.311   1.105   6.669  18.591

Coefficients:
            Estimate Std. Error t value Pr(>|t|)
(Intercept)      176.537      1.511  116.806 < 2e-16 ***
prop_flooded_area_ha      3.988      1.376   2.898  0.00388 **
Forestry_F         29.674      6.068   4.890  1.27e-06 ***
Herbaceous.crops     -4.644      2.071  -2.242  0.02528 *
Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds -6.620      3.797  -1.743  0.08175 .
Marches            -5.695      1.588  -3.586  0.00036 ***
Natural.grasslands   -6.347      2.131  -2.979  0.00300 **
Natural.shrublands    54.822      8.197   6.688  4.82e-11 ***
Rivers.and.riparian.galleries -18.427      2.827  -6.518  1.41e-10 ***
Woody.crops         67.332     20.396   3.301  0.00101 **
---
Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

Residual standard error: 9.387 on 662 degrees of freedom
Multiple R-squared:  0.1731, Adjusted R-squared:  0.1619
F-statistic: 15.4 on 9 and 662 DF, p-value: < 2.2e-16
```

MAX_NDVI_SUMMER

```
> M <- lm(max_NDVI ~ prop_flooded_area_ha + Forestry_F + Herbaceous.crops + Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds + Marches + Natural.grasslands + Natural.shrublands + Rivers.and.riparian.galleries + Woody.crops, data=summer)
>
> VIF(M)
      prop_flooded_area_ha      Forestry_F      Herbaceous.crops      Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds      Marches      Natural.grasslands
      1.686126                1.175067                3.222195                1.132769                3.561132                2.295909
      Natural.shrublands      Rivers.and.riparian.galleries      Woody.crops
      1.052164                1.215251                1.089064

> summary(M)

Call:
lm(formula = max_NDVI ~ prop_flooded_area_ha + Forestry_F + Herbaceous.crops + Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds + Marches + Natural.grasslands + Natural.shrublands + Rivers.and.riparian.galleries + Woody.crops, data = summer)

Residuals:
    Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
-39.781  -6.610   1.613   7.547  25.588

Coefficients:
            Estimate Std. Error t value Pr(>|t|)
(Intercept)      185.575      1.919  96.713 < 2e-16 ***
prop_flooded_area_ha      1.741      1.617   1.077  0.28201
Forestry_F         18.094      6.265   2.888  0.00397 **
Herbaceous.crops    -16.220      2.391  -6.783  2.24e-11 ***
Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds -3.070      3.956  -0.776  0.43803
Marches            -20.074      1.793 -11.195 < 2e-16 ***
Natural.grasslands  -31.915      2.540 -12.567 < 2e-16 ***
Natural.shrublands   50.876      8.109   6.274  5.65e-10 ***
Rivers.and.riparian.galleries -30.288      3.015 -10.045 < 2e-16 ***
Woody.crops         62.233     23.380   2.662  0.00792 **
---
Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

Residual standard error: 10.74 on 830 degrees of freedom
Multiple R-squared:  0.312, Adjusted R-squared:  0.3045
F-statistic: 41.82 on 9 and 830 DF, p-value: < 2.2e-16
```

MAX_NDVI_WINTER

```
> M <- lm(max_NDVI ~ prop_flooded_area_ha + Forestry_F + Herbaceous.crops + Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds + Marches + Natural.grasslands + Natural.shrublands + Rivers.and.riparian.galleries + Woody.crops, data=winter)
>
> VIF(M)
      prop_flooded_area_ha      Forestry_F      Herbaceous.crops      Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds      Marches      Natural.grasslands
      1.513341                1.137619                2.537432                1.136811                2.796440                1.835080
      Natural.shrublands      Rivers.and.riparian.galleries      Woody.crops
      1.053214                1.231770                1.097587
>
> summary(M)

Call:
lm(formula = max_NDVI ~ prop_flooded_area_ha + Forestry_F + Herbaceous.crops + Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds + Marches + Natural.grasslands + Natural.shrublands + Rivers.and.riparian.galleries + Woody.crops, data = winter)

Residuals:
    Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
-35.616  -4.302   1.578   5.916  17.783

Coefficients:
            Estimate Std. Error t value Pr(>|t|)
(Intercept)    179.2770     1.6063  111.611 < 2e-16 ***
prop_flooded_area_ha -0.6992     1.3545   -0.516  0.605882
Forestry_F      21.6768     6.1434   3.528  0.000450 ***
Herbaceous.crops -3.9120     2.0945  -1.868  0.062296 .
Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds  6.2361     3.8112   1.636  0.102319
Marches         -6.0022     1.5520  -3.867  0.000122 ***
Natural.grasslands -3.4286     2.1900  -1.566  0.117987
Natural.shrublands -2.3249     7.9921  -0.291  0.771232
Rivers.and.riparian.galleries -12.6322     2.9193  -4.327  1.77e-05 ***
Woody.crops      67.4090     23.0725   2.922  0.003615 **
---
Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

Residual standard error: 8.894 on 590 degrees of freedom
Multiple R-squared:  0.1041, Adjusted R-squared:  0.09043
F-statistic: 7.617 on 9 and 590 DF, p-value: 1.298e-10
```

MAX_NDVI_AUTUMN

```
> M <- lm(max_NDVI ~ prop_flooded_area_ha + Forestry_F + Herbaceous.crops + Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds + Marches + Natural.grasslands + Natural.shrublands + Rivers.and.riparian.galleries + Woody.crops, data=autumn)
>
> VIF(M)
      prop_flooded_area_ha      Forestry_F      Herbaceous.crops      Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds      Marches      Natural.grasslands
      1.490580                1.138462                2.788640                1.170715                3.398984                2.100232
      Natural.shrublands      Rivers.and.riparian.galleries      Woody.crops
      1.048618                1.260276                1.108171
>
> summary(M)

Call:
lm(formula = max_NDVI ~ prop_flooded_area_ha + Forestry_F + Herbaceous.crops + Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds + Marches + Natural.grasslands + Natural.shrublands + Rivers.and.riparian.galleries + Woody.crops, data = autumn)

Residuals:
    Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
-32.289  -5.288   0.956   6.553  22.606

Coefficients:
            Estimate Std. Error t value Pr(>|t|)
(Intercept)    179.842     1.738  103.500 < 2e-16 ***
prop_flooded_area_ha -4.882     1.585  -3.079  0.00215 ***
Forestry_F      24.562     6.154   3.991  7.26e-05 ***
Herbaceous.crops -15.120     2.206  -6.855  1.55e-11 ***
Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds  9.456     3.879   2.438  0.01503 *
Marches         -14.550     1.704  -8.541 < 2e-16 ***
Natural.grasslands -23.676     2.316 -10.222 < 2e-16 ***
Natural.shrublands  43.979     8.264   5.322  1.38e-07 ***
Rivers.and.riparian.galleries -29.981     2.782 -10.776 < 2e-16 ***
Woody.crops      54.905     20.462   2.683  0.00746 **
---
Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

Residual standard error: 9.741 on 710 degrees of freedom
Multiple R-squared:  0.2802, Adjusted R-squared:  0.271
F-statistic: 30.7 on 9 and 710 DF, p-value: < 2.2e-16
```

SD_NDVI_SPRING

```

> M <- glm(sd_NDVI ~ prop_flooded_area_ha + Forestry_F + Herbaceous.crops + Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds + Marches + Natural.grasslands + Natural.shrublands + Rivers.and.riparian.galleries + Woody.crops,
family=Gamma(link="log"), data= spring)
>
> VIF(M)
      prop_flooded_area_ha      Forestry_F      Herbaceous.crops      Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds      Marches      Natural.grasslands
      1.519395                1.151143                2.428459                1.135738                2.907274                1.626367
      Natural.shrublands      Rivers.and.riparian.galleries      Woody.crops
      1.027761                1.325894                1.114679
>
> summary(M)

Call:
glm(formula = sd_NDVI ~ prop_flooded_area_ha + Forestry_F + Herbaceous.crops +
  Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds + Marches + Natural.grasslands +
  Natural.shrublands + Rivers.and.riparian.galleries + Woody.crops,
     family = Gamma(link = "log"), data = spring)

Deviance Residuals:
    Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
-3.7397 -1.3972 -0.4495  0.5017  2.1726

Coefficients:
            Estimate Std. Error t value Pr(>|t|)
(Intercept)      9.1744     0.1693   54.183 < 2e-16 ***
prop_flooded_area_ha  2.8180     0.1557   18.101 < 2e-16 ***
Forestry_F       -3.7350     0.6866   -5.440 7.58e-08 ***
Herbaceous.crops  -0.5103     0.2329   -2.191 0.02882 *
Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds  1.5998     0.4246    3.768 0.00018 ***
Marches          -1.1404     0.1778   -6.413 2.75e-10 ***
Natural.grasslands -1.5915     0.2505   -6.353 3.99e-10 ***
Natural.shrublands -8.6897     0.9674   -8.983 < 2e-16 ***
Rivers.and.riparian.galleries -4.4759     0.3162  -14.156 < 2e-16 ***
Woody.crops       1.6122     2.2839    0.706 0.48049
---
Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

(Dispersion parameter for Gamma family taken to be 1.101466)

Null deviance: 2123.1 on 655 degrees of freedom
Residual deviance: 1376.1 on 646 degrees of freedom
(16 observations deleted due to missingness)
AIC: 13262

Number of Fisher Scoring iterations: 17
>
> teste <- adjR2(M)
> teste
[1] 0.3428

```

SD_NDVI_SUMMER

```

> M <- glm(sd_NDVI ~ prop_flooded_area_ha + Forestry_F + Herbaceous.crops + Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds + Marches + Natural.grasslands + Natural.shrublands + Rivers.and.riparian.galleries + Woody.crops,
family=Gamma(link="log"), data= summer)
>
> VIF(M)
      prop_flooded_area_ha      Forestry_F      Herbaceous.crops      Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds      Marches      Natural.grasslands
      1.627896                1.192499                3.090399                1.129651                3.372491                1.874994
      Natural.shrublands      Rivers.and.riparian.galleries      Woody.crops
      1.032889                1.212261                1.093074
>
> summary(M)

Call:
glm(formula = sd_NDVI ~ prop_flooded_area_ha + Forestry_F + Herbaceous.crops +
  Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds + Marches + Natural.grasslands +
  Natural.shrublands + Rivers.and.riparian.galleries + Woody.crops,
     family = Gamma(link = "log"), data = summer)

Deviance Residuals:
    Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
-4.7471 -1.8681 -0.5891  0.3630  2.6474

Coefficients:
            Estimate Std. Error t value Pr(>|t|)
(Intercept)      9.0793     0.2196   41.349 < 2e-16 ***
prop_flooded_area_ha  3.0694     0.1862   16.487 < 2e-16 ***
Forestry_F       -9.1075     0.7508  -12.130 < 2e-16 ***
Herbaceous.crops  -0.8104     0.2772   -2.923 0.00356 **
Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds  1.8939     0.4508    4.201 2.96e-05 ***
Marches          -1.1968     0.2051   -5.834 7.90e-09 ***
Natural.grasslands -2.4405     0.3083   -7.916 8.32e-15 ***
Natural.shrublands -9.4467     0.9921   -9.522 < 2e-16 ***
Rivers.and.riparian.galleries -4.1591     0.3439  -12.093 < 2e-16 ***
Woody.crops       5.1078     2.6689    1.914 0.05601 .
---
Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

(Dispersion parameter for Gamma family taken to be 1.495597)

Null deviance: 3781.4 on 797 degrees of freedom
Residual deviance: 2148.1 on 788 degrees of freedom
(42 observations deleted due to missingness)
AIC: 14952

Number of Fisher Scoring iterations: 24
>
> teste <- adjR2(M)
> teste
[1] 0.4254

```

SD_NDVI_WINTER

```
> M <- glm(sd_NDVI ~ prop_flooded_area_ha + Forestry_F + Herbaceous.crops + Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds + Marches + Natural.grasslands + Natural.shrublands + Rivers.and.riparian.galleries + Woody.crops,
family=Gamma(link="log"), data= winter)
>
> VIF(M)
      prop_flooded_area_ha      Forestry_F      Herbaceous.crops      Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds      Marches      Natural.grasslands
      1.476465      1.168001      2.543045      1.135280      2.723733      1.629342
      Natural.shrublands      Rivers.and.riparian.galleries      Woody.crops
      1.027241      1.231150      1.099582
>
> summary(M)

Call:
glm(formula = sd_NDVI ~ prop_flooded_area_ha + Forestry_F + Herbaceous.crops +
  Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds + Marches + Natural.grasslands +
  Natural.shrublands + Rivers.and.riparian.galleries + Woody.crops,
     family = Gamma(link = "log"), data = winter)

Deviance Residuals:
    Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
-3.7041 -1.2507 -0.4380  0.5304  2.0635

Coefficients:
            Estimate Std. Error t value Pr(>|t|)
(Intercept)      9.5941      0.1867   51.380 < 2e-16 ***
prop_flooded_area_ha  2.5206      0.1591   15.842 < 2e-16 ***
Forestry_F       -3.8762      0.7214   -5.373 1.12e-07 ***
Herbaceous.crops  -0.9639      0.2433   -3.961 8.39e-05 ***
Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds  0.8846      0.4413    2.004 0.0455 *
Marches          -1.3432      0.1801   -7.458 3.25e-13 ***
Natural.grasslands -2.1081      0.2638   -7.991 7.33e-15 ***
Natural.shrublands -9.2251      0.9930   -9.290 < 2e-16 ***
Rivers.and.riparian.galleries -4.7004      0.3380  -13.904 < 2e-16 ***
Woody.crops       1.4177      2.6746    0.530 0.5963
---
Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

(Dispersion parameter for Gamma family taken to be 1.060179)

Null deviance: 1836.2 on 586 degrees of freedom
Residual deviance: 1129.7 on 577 degrees of freedom
(13 observations deleted due to missingness)
AIC: 12115

Number of Fisher Scoring iterations: 18

>
> teste <- adjR2(M)
> teste
[1] 0.3752
```

SD_NDVI

```
> M <- glm(sd_NDVI ~ prop_flooded_area_ha + Forestry_F + Herbaceous.crops + Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds + Marches + Natural.grasslands + Natural.shrublands + Rivers.and.riparian.galleries + Woody.crops,
family=Gamma(link="log"), data= autumn)
>
> VIF(M)
      prop_flooded_area_ha      Forestry_F      Herbaceous.crops      Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds      Marches      Natural.grasslands
      1.453169      1.140777      2.733043      1.167016      3.255398      1.799808
      Natural.shrublands      Rivers.and.riparian.galleries      Woody.crops
      1.031375      1.253762      1.110894
>
> summary(M)

Call:
glm(formula = sd_NDVI ~ prop_flooded_area_ha + Forestry_F + Herbaceous.crops +
  Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds + Marches + Natural.grasslands +
  Natural.shrublands + Rivers.and.riparian.galleries + Woody.crops,
     family = Gamma(link = "log"), data = autumn)

Deviance Residuals:
    Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
-4.9154 -1.8768 -0.6287  0.4281  2.8504

Coefficients:
            Estimate Std. Error t value Pr(>|t|)
(Intercept)      8.9599      0.2276   39.368 < 2e-16 ***
prop_flooded_area_ha  3.6168      0.2088   17.325 < 2e-16 ***
Forestry_F       -5.2411      0.8662   -6.050 2.39e-09 ***
Herbaceous.crops  -0.4641      0.2904   -1.598 0.110474
Industrial.salt.pans.and.fish.ponds  1.7324      0.5070    3.417 0.000671 ***
Marches          -1.4828      0.2233   -6.641 6.38e-11 ***
Natural.grasslands -2.1823      0.3215   -6.789 2.47e-11 ***
Natural.shrublands -11.5694      1.1265  -10.270 < 2e-16 ***
Rivers.and.riparian.galleries -4.1705      0.3650  -11.426 < 2e-16 ***
Woody.crops       2.7748      2.6788    1.036 0.300655
---
Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

(Dispersion parameter for Gamma family taken to be 1.61981)

Null deviance: 3375.2 on 688 degrees of freedom
Residual deviance: 1851.0 on 679 degrees of freedom
(31 observations deleted due to missingness)
AIC: 12652

Number of Fisher Scoring iterations: 19

>
> teste <- adjR2(M)
> teste
[1] 0.4443
```

Appendix B9 - Identification of plots in which model predictions greatly exceeded the historical values of individuals' abundance registered, discriminated by waterbird functional group and season.

Season	Functional group	nr plots with pred abundance > max abundance recorded		Plot identification
		Regular year	Dry year	
Autumn	Dabbling ducks	0	0	
	Diving birds	2	2	Dehesa de bajo; matasgordas
	Fishing birds	0	0	
	Large wading birds	0	0	
	Small wading birds	0	0	
Spring	Dabbling ducks	0	0	
	Diving birds	0	0	
	Fishing birds	0	0	
	Large wading birds	0	0	
	Small wading birds	0	0	
Summer	Dabbling ducks	2	1	Regular year - brazo de la torre y cantaritas; otros cultivos / Dry year - Otros cultivos
	Diving birds	3	2	Regular year - dehesa de bajo; Marismila del rocío; otros cultivos / Dry year - dehesa de bajo; otros cultivos
	Fishing birds	1	1	Regular year - otros cultivos / Dry year - otros cultivos
	Large wading birds	1	1	Regular year - otros cultivos / Dry year - otros cultivos
	Small wading birds	0	0	
Winter	Dabbling ducks	0	0	
	Diving birds	0	0	
	Fishing birds	0	0	
	Large wading birds	0	0	
	Small wading birds	0	0	

6.3. Appendix C

Appendix C - Detailed description of the methods and results of Case study 3 – Moor House eLTER Site - ‘Identify stressors of biodiversity change by addressing biodiversity responses to environmental variation based on accompanying abiotic data (i.e. in situ measurements)’.

Methodology

BIODIVERSITY DATA

Database: UK Environmental Change Network; dataset available on B2DROP)

Description: This indicator is characterised by data from ground-based surveys recording the presence of all species of vascular plants rooted in the cell, and bryophytes and lichens, except those growing on rock or wood (for more details see ‘V protocol’ in <https://ecn.ac.uk/measurements/terrestrial>).

Sampling strategy: At least two 10m x 10m plots are randomly selected within each National Vegetation Classification type present on the site. Species presence is recorded in 40cm x 40cm cells within these plots. Each cell is used for recording the presence of all species of vascular plants rooted in the cell, and bryophytes and lichens, except those growing on rock or wood (for more details see ‘V protocol’ in <https://ecn.ac.uk/measurements/terrestrial>).

Site code: 04

Data period: 1996-2015

Data measurements:

- 45 plots sampled at three-years interval (1996, 1999, 2002, 2005, 2008, 2011, 2014)
- 8 plots sampled annually (1996 – 2015)

Note: Plots in which disturbance effects were recorded during sampling were removed from the database (for more details see ‘quality codes’ in ‘supporting documentation’ at <https://catalogue.ceh.ac.uk/documents/b98efec8-6de0-4e0c-85dc-fe4cdf01f086>)

ABIOTIC DATA – in situ measurements of soil chemistry and weather data

Database: ECN (downloaded from http://data.ecn.ac.uk/request_form.asp in June 2022; dataset available on B2DROP)

Description:

SCD - Soil chemistry data: This data is characterized by a set of chemical composition variables of soil solution using suction lysimeters (for more details see ‘SS protocol’ in <https://ecn.ac.uk/measurements/terrestrial>).

MD - Meteorological data: This data is characterized by a set of meteorological variables collected by an Automatic Weather Station (AWS) (for more details see ‘MA protocol’ in <https://ecn.ac.uk/measurements/terrestrial>).

Sampling strategy:

SCD - Soil chemistry data: Suction samplers are used to measure the soil solution chemistry. The samples are collected fortnightly (for more details see ‘SS protocol’ in <https://ecn.ac.uk/measurements/terrestrial>).

MD - Meteorological data: The data are hourly summaries from 5-second samplings collected by an Automatic Weather Station (AWS) (for more details see ‘MA protocol’ in <https://ecn.ac.uk/measurements/terrestrial>).

Site code: 04

Data period:

SCD - Soil chemistry data: 1996-2015

MD - Meteorological data: 1996-2015

Note: Samples in which the quality of the data have been affected during sampling were removed from the database (for more details see 'quality codes' in 'supporting documentation' at <https://catalogue.ceh.ac.uk/documents/b330d395-68f2-47f1-8d59-3291dc02923b> and <https://catalogue.ceh.ac.uk/documents/fc9bcd1c-e3fc-4c5a-b569-2fe62d40f2f5>).

Data Analyses

Metrics selection

In order to assess changes in plant diversity at the Moor House eLTER Site, we accounted for species richness (the number of species in the community) and species composition (the identity of the species present in a community and its relative abundance). We also used abiotic metrics discriminated by soil properties and weather conditions in order to investigate potential relationships between plant diversity and environmental parameters.

Biodiversity metrics

i) Species abundance per plot per year: this metric is an estimate of species frequency per plot per year: i.e. number of cells in a given plot where the species is present. Note: 10 cells were surveyed in each plot therefore response values range between 0 when the species is absent and 10 when the species is present in all cells of the plot.

ii) Species presence/absence per plot per year: in this metric a value of 1 is considered when the species is sampled in at least one cell of a given plot, and absence is considered when the species is not occurring in any cell of the plot.

iii) Species richness per year: corresponding to the number of species present in a given plot, habitat and/or at the site level per year.

Abiotic metrics

The abiotic variables considered in the analysis are displayed in Table C1. These variables represent the pool of all available abiotic parameters for Moor House, which were used in order to identify the most influential predictors shaping plant diversity in this eLTER Site. Overall, from a total pool of 25 metrics, 15 correspond to soil properties and 10 to weather conditions (Table C1). It is important to note that, from the overall pool of soil/weather variables available (31), 6 were removed à priori due to data gaps in relation to the vegetation database (i.e. 3 complete years without sampling: soil: ALKY - Alkalinity in mg per litre; weather: DRYMP_RH - Dry bulb temperature within the relative humidity sensor in °C, RH - Relative humidity in %, SOLAR - Solar Radiation in w per m², SWATER - Soil moisture – gypsum block in bars, WETTEMP - Wet bulb temperature in °C).

Table C1 - Description of abiotic variables used for vegetation analysis on the Moor House eLTER Site.

Class	Variable	Description
Soil	ALUMINIUM	Concentration of aluminium (mg per litre)
	CALCIUM	Concentration of calcium (mg per litre)
	CHLORIDE	Concentration of chloride (mg per litre)
	CONDY	Conductivity (micro Siemens per centimetre)
	DOC	Dissolved organic carbon (mg per litre)
	IRON	Concentration of iron (mg per litre)
	MAGNESIUM	Concentration of magnesium (mg per litre)
	NH4N	Concentration of ammonium (mg per litre)
	NO3N	Concentration of nitrate nitrogen (mg per litre)
	PO4P	Concentration of phosphate phosphorus (mg per litre)
	POTASSIUM	Concentration of potassium (mg per litre)
	SO4S	Concentration of sulphate sulphur (mg per litre)
	SODIUM	Concentration of sodium (mg per litre)
	TOTALN	Concentration of total nitrogen (mg per litre)
TOTALP	Concentration of dissolved phosphorus (mg per litre)	
Weather	ALBGRD	Albedo Ground (average) (w per m2)
	ALBSKY	Albedo sky (average) (w per m2)
	DRYTMP	Dry bulb temperature (°C)
	NETRAD	Net Radiation (average) (w per m2)
	RAIN	Rainfall (total) (mm)
	STMP10	Soil temperature at 10 cm (average) (°C)
	STMP30	Soil temperature at 30 cm (average) (°C)
	SURWET	Surface wetness (number of minutes in the hour that surface is wet) (minutes)
	WDIR	Wind direction (average) (degrees)
	WSPEED	Wind speed (average) (m per second)

Since available data on soil and weather correspond to measurements at one location within the site, abiotic variables were considered as annual values for all vegetation plots sampled by year. For this, the annual average of abiotic variables was calculated based on the average of their trimestral values. All abiotic variables include measurements in the 4 trimesters of each year.

Data limitations:

- In 1999 only 3 trimesters were sampled for all soil variables.
- In 2010 only 2 trimesters were sampled for potassium and sodium.
- In 2011 only 2 trimesters were sampled for aluminium, calcium, magnesium, potassium and sodium.
- In 1996 only 3 trimesters were sampled for SURWET and in 2012 only 2 trimesters were sampled for SURWET.
- In 2006 only 3 trimesters were sampled for DRRYTMP and in 2007 only 2 trimesters were sampled for DRRYTMP.
- In 1996 only 3 trimesters were sampled for SURWET and in 2012 only 2 trimesters were sampled for SURWET.
- In 2011 only 1 trimesters was sampled for ALBSKY and in 2010 no samples were available for this variable.

Statistical analyses

We aimed to investigate the temporal variability of species richness at the site and habitat levels (multiple comparisons and anomaly detection), and assess gradients underlying variations in the floristic composition, including the potential impact of environmental data on targeted plant communities (multivariate analysis).

Multiple comparisons and anomaly detection

To investigate potential variations in vegetation patterns at Moor House, two statistical methods were implemented: 1) a Kruskal-Wallis to test whether species richness diverged among years and 2) a STL decomposition to investigate potential anomalies in species richness throughout time. STL stands for Seasonal-Trend Decomposition procedure based on Loess (Cleveland et al., 1990). This technique enables to split the time series signal into three parts: seasonal, trend, and residuals. The anomaly detection algorithm analyses the deviation of the residual data from the decomposition and introduces a threshold to detect potential anomalies in the data (Dancho and Vaughan, 2022).

Analyses were performed at two spatial scales (i.e. site level and habitat level), discriminated by data sampled at three-years interval (45 plots) and data sampled annually (8 plots). In order to identify temporal changes in vegetation communities within habitats, the available classification of plots in terms of Land use/Land cover (LU/LC) type was used, and only LU/LC with more than 1 sampled plot were further considered in the analyses (i.e. Data sampled at three-years interval: Semi-natural grasslands = 15 plots ; fen, moor or bog = 22 plots; permanent or long-term grassland = 5 plots; deciduous forest = 1; mixed forest = 1; montane vegetation = 1; Data sampled annually: Semi-natural grasslands = 4 plots ; fen, moor or bog = 4 plots). Variation of species richness were plotted across years at both site and habitat levels. All analysis were performed using R software (R Development Core Team, 2020).

Multivariate Analysis

Multivariate analysis was performed in order to: (i) disclose gradients underlying variations in the floristic composition; (ii) understand patterns of structure and composition across vegetation types through years; and, (iii) to assess the potential impact of environmental data on targeted plant communities.

Analysis of species composition at the site level

A DCA (Detrended Correspondence Analysis), based on species abundance, of the whole vegetation dataset was performed using the default setting of CANOCO 4.5 (four re-scaling cycles and 26 segments to re-scaling, according to Hill's method; ter Braak and Smilauer, 2002). This analysis aimed at disclosing the main gradients underlying variations in the floristic composition and to determine the length of the gradient of the dataset (Legendre and Legendre, 1998; ter Braak and Smilauer, 2002).

Analysis of species composition and environmental data at the site level

In order to avoid multicollinearity, the selected 25 environmental predictors (Table C1) were tested for pair-wise correlation using Spearman's rho correlation coefficient and only predictors with $p > 0.01$ were considered in the analyses (Elith et al., 2006; Wisz and Guisan, 2009).

A PCA (Principal Component Analysis) was performed to visualise variation of abiotic variables in the ordination space. Overall, PCA extracts information from the values matrix of the abiotic variables, converting it into linearly uncorrelated, orthogonal, variables called principal components. Through this method the distance between objects (abiotic variables values) is projected in a reduced space, by simplifying the abiotic information, thereby expressing the maximum variance captured in the database.. All statistical procedures were conducted using CANOCO 4.5 (ter Braak and Smilauer, 2002).

Results

Multiple comparisons and anomaly detection

Results suggest the absence of significant differences in plant species richness among the years, both at the site and habitat levels (Table C2). In terms of anomaly detection, the results indicate the occurrence of anomalies in plant species richness in 1996 and 1999, at the site level, and in 1999, 2004, 2006 and 2014 at the habitat level (Table C2). Particularly, at the habitat level, the results show the occurrence of anomalies in plant species richness of semi-natural grasslands, fen, moor or bog and permanent or long-term grasslands in 2014 (45 plots sampled at 3 yr interval, Table C2); the occurrence of anomalies in plant species richness of semi-natural grasslands and fen, moor or bog in 1999, and of semi-natural grasslands also in 2004 and 2006 (8 plots sampled annually, table C2). Variations of species richness among years, both at the site and habitat levels, are shown in Appendix C1.

Table C2 - Summary results of multiple comparisons and anomaly detection to investigate potential variations in vegetation patterns at the Moor House eLTER Site.

Spatial scale	Sampling strategy	Habitat type	Differences in plant species richness among years (multiple comparisons)	Anomalies in plant species richness throughout time (anomaly detection)
Site level	45 plots sampled at 3 yr interval	-	n.s	1996*
	8 plots sampled annually	-	n.s	1999
Habitat level	45 plots sampled at 3 yr interval	Semi-natural grasslands	n.s	2014*
		fen, moor or bog	n.s	2014*
		Permanent or long-term grasslands	n.s	2014*
	8 plots sampled annually	Semi-natural grasslands	n.s	1999, 2004, 2006
		fen, moor or bog	n.s	1999

absence of significant differences in plant species richness among years (n.s)

anomaly detection in plant species richness (year)

Lack of confidence interval in the response ()*

Multivariate analysis

Analysis of species composition at the site level

Overall, DCA results showed turnover values along the first axis above 4.0 (DCA1: 6.16 SD; SD, Standard Deviation) that, according to ter Braak and Smilauer (2002), point to the use of unimodal models for constrained ordination methods (Table C3).

Table C3 - Detrended Correspondence Analysis (DCA) results (Total variation: 10.65512).

Statistic	Axis 1	Axis 2	Axis 3	Axis 4
Eigenvalues	0.7250	0.4745	0.3333	0.1848
Explained variation (cumulative)	6.80	11.26	14.39	16.12
Gradient length	6.16	4.15	3.82	2.87

Figure C1 shows the ordination plot resulting from the DCA analysis. Overall, patterns reflect differences among contrasting land uses (semi-natural grasslands, montane vegetation, fen, moor or bog, permanent or long-term grassland, deciduous forest, and mixed) integrated in the dataset, which tend, as expected, to cluster (see also Figure C2), due to similarity in terms of species composition. The same pattern is observed for plots of the same land use for different years. When analysing the pattern of plots across the ordination space in relation to species richness (Figure C2), permanent or long-term grasslands, mixed and semi-natural grasslands appear as those exhibiting higher values of species richness, though some variation is observed between plots of the same land use. Overall, considering all plots from the targeted land uses in the same analysis, it was not possible to clearly identify an underlying gradient

Figure C1 - Detrended Correspondence Analysis (DCA) of plots across years at the site level. Distance between symbols approximates the dissimilarity of species composition measured as turnover distance in

standard deviation (SD) units. Designation of plots reflect the plot number and survey year. Symbols depict surveyed years.

Figure C2 - Ordination plot (DCA) showing the distribution of the total number of species per plot through isolines summarising a fitted regression model (the positions of original data points used to fit the regression model correspond to plot scores in the ordination space). Distance between symbols approximates the dissimilarity of species composition measured as turnover distance in standard deviation (SD) units. Land use types are discriminated through contrasting symbols.

Analysis of species composition and environmental data at the site level

The abiotic variables selected were (Table C4): Aluminium, Calcium, Chloride, Dissolved Organic Carbon, Iron, Magnesium, Ammonium, Nitrate Nitrogen, Phosphate Phosphorus, Potassium, Sulphate Sulphur, Sodium, Total Nitrogen, Dissolved Phosphorus, Albedo Sky, Dry Bulb Temperature, Rainfall, Surface Wetness and Wind Direction. Changes in temporal variability of abiotic data are displayed in Appendix C9.

Table C4 - Pair-wise correlation using Spearman’s rho correlation coefficient with p-value > 0.01 (*) (i.e. Spearman pairwise correlation lower than 0.86). Pair-wise correlated variables (p-value <0.01; **, ***) are signed in red.

	ALUMINIUM	CALCIUM	CHLORIDE	CONDY	DOC	IRON	MAGNESIUM	NH4N	NO3N	PO4P	POTASSIUM	SO4S	SODIUM	TOTALN	TOTALP	ALBGRD	ALBSKY	DRYTMP	NETRAD	RAIN	STMP10	STMP30	SURWET	WDIR	
ALUMINIUM																									
CALCIUM	0.54																								
CHLORIDE	0.43	0.39																							
CONDY	0.89**	0.68	0.71																						
DOC	0.32	0.11	0.21	0.32																					
IRON	0.75	0.71	0.68	0.81**	0.54																				
MAGNESIUM	0.32	0.86*	0.32	0.54	-0.04	0.64																			
NH4N	0.43	-0.25	0.39	0.43	-0.14	0.18	-0.32																		
NO3N	-0.57	0.04	0.07	-0.39	-0.75	-0.46	0.11	-0.21																	
PO4P	-0.86*	-0.29	-0.57	-0.86*	-0.25	-0.68	-0.07	-0.79*	0.5																
POTASSIUM	0.54	0.29	-0.25	0.25	-0.43	-0.04	0.07	0.25	-0.04	-0.36															
SO4S	0	0.29	0.64	0.25	-0.36	0.21	0.5	0	0.57	0.04	-0.18														
SODIUM	0.86*	0.5	0.36	0.68	0.36	0.57	0.29	0.07	-0.43	-0.54	0.46	0.14													
TOTALN	-0.07	-0.75	0.04	-0.14	0.36	-0.18	-0.82*	0.57	-0.43	-0.29	-0.32	-0.43	-0.21												
TOTALP	-0.61	-0.64	-0.64	-0.79*	-0.29	-0.86*	-0.79*	-0.04	0.25	0.43	0.07	-0.57	-0.57	0.39											
ALBGRD	0.61	0.14	0	0.5	0.68	0.54	-0.07	0.32	0.89**	-0.64	0.14	-0.68	0.32	0.39	-0.14										
ALBSKY	0	-0.46	0.46	0.04	0.5	0.04	-0.61	0.36	-0.21	-0.25	-0.5	0	0.07	0.79*	0.11	0.14									
DRYTMP	-0.32	-0.36	-0.29	-0.5	0.46	-0.39	-0.57	-0.46	-0.11	0.43	-0.29	-0.39	0.04	0.32	0.5	0	0.5								
NETRAD	0.61	0.93**	0.54	0.79*	0.39	0.86*	0.71	-0.11	-0.18	-0.46	0.11	0.14	0.5	-0.46	-0.64	0.39	-0.18	-0.57							
RAIN	0.25	0.07	0.46	0.46	0.21	0.57	0.43	0.29	-0.32	-0.32	-0.39	0.43	0.07	0.07	-0.75	0.14	0.07	-0.57	0.14						
STMP10	-0.18	-0.36	0	-0.29	0.57	-0.21	-0.64	-0.18	-0.18	0.14	-0.36	-0.36	0.07	0.54	0.43	0.14	0.75	0.93**	-0.14	-0.46					
STMP30	-0.21	-0.29	-0.07	-0.32	0.64	-0.18	-0.5	-0.39	-0.21	0.29	-0.43	-0.32	0.11	0.39	0.32	0.11	0.64	0.96***	-0.11	-0.39	0.36***				
SURWET	-0.39	0.25	0.14	-0.29	-0.36	-0.29	0.18	-0.54	0.82*	0.54	-0.07	0.54	-0.04	-0.54	0.11	-0.79*	-0.07	0.29	0.07	-0.46	0.18	0.21			
WDIR	-0.29	-0.61	-0.71	-0.54	-0.07	-0.61	-0.75	0.18	-0.21	0.11	0.21	-0.86*	-0.43	0.54	0.86*	0.32	0.04	0.32	-0.54	-0.54	0.29	0.18	-0.39		
WSPEED	0.36	-0.21	0.04	0.36	0.32	0.36	-0.14	0.64	-0.71	-0.61	-0.04	-0.43	-0.07	0.57	-0.14	0.75	0.14	-0.39	0	0.54	-0.21	-0.29	0.96***	0.32	

The projection of the abiotic variables in the PCA biplot is shown in Figure C3.

Figure C3 - Principal Component Analysis (PCA) of environmental data of the plots across years at the site level. Each arrow points in the direction of the steepest increase of the values for the corresponding environmental parameter. The angle between arrows indicates the sign of the correlation between environmental parameters: the approximated correlation is positive when the angle is sharp, and negative when the angle is larger than 90 degrees. Designation of sites reflect plot number and survey year.

Considering the length of gradient determined by DCA, a Canonical Correspondence Analysis (CCA) was implemented as direct analysis of gradient. However, results reflect data limitations, namely the lack of environmental variation across plots belonging to the same land use (semi-natural grasslands, montane vegetation, fen, moor or bog, permanent or long-term grassland, deciduous forest, and mixed). Figure C4 (and below individual ordination plots) show results from CCA analysis, i.e. ordination diagrams (plots and biplots).

Figure C4 - Canonical Correspondence Analysis (CCA) of species data and environmental data of the plots across years at the site level. Designation of sites reflect plot number and survey year (individual plots from the CCA analysis below; left - plots, right - environmental variables).

Overall, CCA results seem to reflect the lack of environmental variation across plots of different land uses (resulting from the fact that one value per environmental variable is available per site), as the plots cluster per year (and do not segregate per land use type). Similar patterns were obtained when a similar analysis was implemented to the habitat level (Figure C5), e.g. Semi-natural grasslands.

Figure C5 - Canonical Correspondence Analysis (CCA) of species data and environmental data of semi-natural grassland plots across years. Designation of sites reflect plot number and survey year.

References

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Appendix C1- Variation in plant species richness, discriminated by spatial scale (site versus habitat level) and sampling strategy (45 plots sampled at 3 yr interval versus 8 plots samples annually).

ANALYSIS OF SPECIES RICHNESS AT THE SITE LEVEL

45 PLOTS SAMPLED AT THREE-YEARS INTERVAL

Variation of species richness (site level) across years.

Variation of species richness (plot level) across years.

8 PLOTS SAMPLED ANNUALLY

Variation of species richness (site level) across years.

Variation of species richness (plot level) across years.

ANALYSIS OF SPECIES RICHNESS AT THE HABITAT LEVEL

45 PLOTS SAMPLED AT THREE-YEARS INTERVAL

◇ Semi-natural grasslands

Variation of species richness (habitat level) across years.

Variation of species richness of semi-natural grasslands (plot level) across years.

◇ fen, moor or bog

Variation of species richness (habitat level) across years.

Variation of species richness of fen, moor or bogs (plot level) across years.

◇ Permanent or long-term grasslands

Variation of species richness (habitat level) across years.

Variation of species richness of permanent or long-term grasslands (plot level) across years.

8 PLOTS SAMPLED ANNUALLY

◇ Semi-natural grasslands (4 plots)

Variation of species richness (habitat level) across years.

Variation of species richness (plot level) across years.

◇ fen, moor or bog (4 plots)

Variation of species richness (habitat level) across years.

Variation of species richness (plot level) across years.

Appendix C2 - Statistical outputs (i.e. histograms, multiple comparisons and anomaly detection) to investigate potential variations in vegetation patterns at the Moor House eLTER Site using 45 plots sampled at 3 yr interval.


```
> shapiro.test(Dataset$sp_rich)
```

Shapiro-Wilk normality test

data: Dataset\$sp_rich
W = 0.93109, p-value = 6.682e-11

```
> ks.test(Dataset$sp_rich, 'pnorm')
```

One-sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov test

data: Dataset\$sp_rich
D = 1, p-value < 2.2e-16
alternative hypothesis: two-sided

```
> teste <- kruskal.test(sp_rich ~ year, data= Dataset)
> teste
```

Kruskal-Wallis rank sum test

data: sp_rich by year
Kruskal-Wallis chi-squared = 11.233, df = 6, p-value = 0.08145

Above: descriptive data analysis of plant species richness (site level): Histogram; Q-Q Plot; Normality Test: Shapiro-Wilk and Kolmogorov-Smirnov; Multiple comparisons Test: Kruskal-Wallis. Below: Variation of plant species richness between years. The lower and upper limits of each box represent the first and third quartiles, respectively, and the line inside each box represents the median. The bottom and top bars represent

the minimum and maximum number of species, respectively. Circles outside the first and third quartiles range are plotted as outliers.

Detection of anomalies in time series of plant species richness (48 plots) at the site level.

Appendix C3 - Statistical outputs (i.e. histograms, multiple comparisons and anomaly detection) to investigate potential variations in vegetation patterns at the Moor House eLTER Site using 8 plots sampled annually.

Histogram of Dataset\$sp_rich

Normal Q-Q Plot


```
> shapiro.test(Dataset$sp_rich)

Shapiro-Wilk normality test
```

data: Dataset\$sp_rich
W = 0.77864, p-value = 7.028e-14

```
> ks.test(Dataset$sp_rich, 'pnorm')

One-sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov test
```

data: Dataset\$sp_rich
D = 1, p-value < 2.2e-16
alternative hypothesis: two.sided

```
> teste <- kruskal.test(sp_rich ~ year, data= Dataset)
> teste
```

Kruskal-Wallis rank sum test

data: sp_rich by year
Kruskal-Wallis chi-squared = 21.89, df = 18, p-value = 0.2369

total species richness

Above: descriptive data analysis of plant species richness (site level): Histogram; Q-Q Plot; Normality Test: Shapiro-Wilk and Kolmogorov-Smirnov; Multiple comparisons Test: Kruskal-Wallis. Below: Variation of plant species richness between years. The lower and upper limits of each box represent the first and third quartiles, respectively, and the line inside each box represents the median. The bottom and top bars represent the minimum and maximum number of species, respectively. Circles outside the first and third quartiles range are plotted as outliers.

Detection of anomalies in time series of plant species richness (8 plots) at the site level.

Appendix C4 - Statistical outputs (i.e. histograms, multiple comparisons and anomaly detection) to investigate potential variations in vegetation patterns of semi-natural grasslands at the Moor House eLTER Site, using 45 plots sampled at 3 yr interval.


```
> shapiro.test(semi_grass$sp_rich)
```

Shapiro-Wilk normality test

```
data: semi_grass$sp_rich
W = 0.94824, p-value = 0.0004481
```

```
> ks.test(semi_grass$sp_rich, 'pnorm')
```

One-sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov test

```
data: semi_grass$sp_rich
D = 1, p-value < 2.2e-16
alternative hypothesis: two-sided
```

```
> teste_grass <- kruskal.test(sp_rich ~ year, data= semi_grass)
```

```
> teste_grass
```

Kruskal-Wallis rank sum test

```
data: sp_rich by year
```

```
Kruskal-Wallis chi-squared = 3.735, df = 6, p-value = 0.7125
```

species richness: Semi-natural grassland

Above: descriptive data analysis of plant species richness (habitat level): Histogram; Q-Q Plot; Normality Test: Shapiro-Wilk and Kolmogorov-Smirnov; Multiple comparisons Test: Kruskal-Wallis. Below:

Variation of plant species richness between years. The lower and upper limits of each box represent the first and third quartiles, respectively, and the line inside each box represents the median. The bottom and top bars represent the minimum and maximum number of species, respectively. Circles outside the first and third quartiles range are plotted as outliers.

Detection of anomalies in time series of plant species richness (15 plots) at the habitat level (semi-natural grasslands).

Appendix C5 - Statistical outputs (i.e. histograms, multiple comparisons and anomaly detection) to investigate potential variations in vegetation patterns of fen, moor or bog at the Moor House eLTER Site, using 45 plots sampled at 3 yr interval.


```
> teste_fen <- kruskal.test(sp_rich ~ year, data= fen)
> teste_fen

Kruskal-Wallis rank sum test

data:  sp_rich by year
Kruskal-Wallis chi-squared = 12.942, df = 6, p-value = 0.04397

> DunnTest(x = fen$sp_rich, g = fen$year)

Dunn's test of multiple comparisons using rank sums : holm

      mean.rank.diff  pval
1999-1996  0.2727273 1.0000
2002-1996  2.7954545 1.0000
2005-1996 11.1363636 1.0000
2008-1996 -2.6590909 1.0000
2011-1996 30.4545455 0.4444
2014-1996 28.4772727 0.5784
2002-1999  2.5227273 1.0000
2005-1999 10.8636364 1.0000
2008-1999 -2.9318182 1.0000
2011-1999 30.1818182 0.4444
2014-1999 28.2045455 0.5784
2005-2002  8.3409091 1.0000
2008-2002 -5.4545455 1.0000
2011-2002 27.6590909 0.5926
2014-2002 25.6818182 0.7828
2008-2005 -13.7954545 1.0000
2011-2005 19.3181818 1.0000
2014-2005 17.3409091 1.0000
2011-2008 33.1136364 0.2878
2014-2008 31.1363636 0.4093
2014-2011 -1.9772727 1.0000
---
```

Signif. codes: 0 '****' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

Above: descriptive data analysis of plant species richness (habitat level): Histogram; Q-Q Plot; Normality Test: Shapiro-Wilk and Kolmogorov-Smirnov; Multiple comparisons Test: Kruskal-Wallis and Dunn’s Test. Below: Variation of plant species richness between years. The lower and upper limits of each box represent the first and third quartiles, respectively, and the line inside each box represents the median. The bottom and top bars represent the minimum and maximum number of species, respectively. Circles outside the first and third quartiles range are plotted as outliers.

Detection of anomalies in time series of plant species richness (22 plots) at the habitat level (fen, moor or bog).

Appendix C6 - Statistical outputs (i.e. histograms, multiple comparisons and anomaly detection) to investigate potential variations in vegetation patterns of permanent or long-term grasslands at the Moor House eLTER Site, using 45 plots sampled at 3 yr interval.

Above: descriptive data analysis of plant species richness (habitat level): Histogram; Q-Q Plot; Normality Test: Shapiro-Wilk and Kolmogorov-Smirnov; Multiple comparisons Test: Kruskal-Wallis. Below: Variation of plant species richness between years. The lower and upper limits of each box represent the first and third quartiles, respectively, and the line inside each box represents the median. The bottom and top bars represent the minimum and maximum number of species, respectively. Circles outside the first and third quartiles range are plotted as outliers.

Detection of anomalies in time series of plant species richness (5 plots) at the habitat level (permanent or long-term grasslands).

Appendix C7 - Statistical outputs (i.e. histograms, multiple comparisons and anomaly detection) to investigate potential variations in vegetation patterns of semi-natural grasslands at the Moor House eLTER Site, using 8 plots sampled annually.


```
> shapiro.test(semi_grass$sp_rich)
```

Shapiro-Wilk normality test

```
data: semi_grass$sp_rich
W = 0.78379, p-value = 3.289e-09
```

```
> ks.test(semi_grass$sp_rich, 'pnorm')
```

One-sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov test

```
data: semi_grass$sp_rich
D = 1, p-value < 2.2
alternative hypotheses
```

Normal Q-Q Plot

Theoretical Quantiles

```
> teste_grass <- kruskal.test(sp_rich ~ year, data= semi_grass)
> teste_grass
```

Kruskal-Wallis rank sum test

```
data: sp_rich by year
Kruskal-Wallis chi-squared = 9.7586, df = 18, p-value = 0.9395
```

```
>
```

species richness: Semi-natural grassland

Above: descriptive data analysis of plant species richness (habitat level): Histogram; Q-Q Plot; Normality Test: Shapiro-Wilk and Kolmogorov-Smirnov; Multiple comparisons Test: Kruskal-Wallis. Below: Variation of plant species richness between years. The lower and upper limits of each box represent the first and third quartiles, respectively, and the line inside each box represents the median. The bottom and top bars

represent the minimum and maximum number of species, respectively. Circles outside the first and third quartiles range are plotted as outliers.

Detection of anomalies in time series of plant species richness (4 plots) at the habitat level (semi-natural grasslands).

Appendix C8 - Statistical outputs (i.e. histograms, multiple comparisons and anomaly detection) to investigate potential variations in vegetation patterns of fen, moor or bog at the Moor House eLTER Site, using 8 plots sampled annually.

Histogram of fen\$sp_rich

Normal Q-Q Plot


```
> shapiro.test(fen $sp_rich)
```

Shapiro-Wilk normality test

```
data: fen$sp_rich
W = 0.76531, p-value = 1.112e-09
```

```
> ks.test(fen $sp_rich, 'pnorm')
```

One-sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov test

```
data: fen$sp_rich
D = 1, p-value < 2.2e-16
alternative hypothesis: two-sided
```

```
> teste_fen <- kruskal.test(sp_rich ~ year, data= fen)
> teste_fen
```

Kruskal-Wallis rank sum test

```
data: sp_rich by year
Kruskal-Wallis chi-squared = 18.817, df = 18, p-value = 0.4032
```

species richness: fen, moor or bog

Above: descriptive data analysis of plant species richness (habitat level): Histogram; Q-Q Plot; Normality Test: Shapiro-Wilk and Kolmogorov-Smirnov; Multiple comparisons Test: Kruskal-Wallis. Below:

Variation of plant species richness between years. The lower and upper limits of each box represent the first and third quartiles, respectively, and the line inside each box represents the median. The bottom and top bars represent the minimum and maximum number of species, respectively. Circles outside the first and third quartiles range are plotted as outliers.

Detection of anomalies in time series of plant species richness (4 plots) at the habitat level (fen, moor or bog).

Appendix C9 - Variation in soil chemistry (SCD) and weather-related variables (MD) across years. To facilitate the visualisation of the data, the selection of variables included in the graphs present the same order of magnitude of variation within the set of SCD or MD variables.

SCD - SOIL CHEMISTRY

Temporal variation of Aluminium, Nitrate Nitrogen, Phosphate Phosphorus and Dissolved Phosphorus

Temporal variation of Calcium, Iron, Magnesium, Ammonium, Potassium, Sulphate Sulphur and Total Nitrogen

Temporal variation of Chloride and Sodium

Temporal variation of Dissolved Organic Carbon

MD - METEOROLOGY

Temporal variation of Albedo Sky, Surface Wetness and Wind Direction

Temporal variation of Dry bulb temperature and Rainfall

6.4. Appendix D

Appendix D - Data documentation, including provenance, of the workflow of data analysis for the case study 'Biodiversity trend analysis at the site scale - Moor House UK' (as a direct output to WP10).

A - Data retrieval

- Biodiversity Raw database: plant species list and relative abundance, obtained from Pilloto et al. – Database provided by Martin Musche in June 2022 (dataset 'v02_spABR.csv')
- Abiotic Raw datasets: *In-situ* abiotic measurements of soil chemistry and meteorological data obtained from ECN (downloaded from http://data.ecn.ac.uk/request_form.asp in June 2022) (dataset 'soil.csv' and 'ecn_ma_YEAR[1996;2015].csv' in folder weather)

B - Data cleaning and variables harmonization

- **BIODIVERSITY**

- Cleaning of original plant species names ('v02_spABR.csv'): DESC_LATIN -> DESC_LATIN_F (Manual removal of text associated to species names, such as growth forms (e.g. Acer campestre (e), Acer campestre (g), Acer campestre (s)) and species names in forms other than genus + specific epithet, i.e. of sub-species, hybrids, varieties, vegetation cover, grid reference, etc..).
- Abbreviation of plant species names ('v02_spABR_F.xlsx'): DESC_LATIN_F -> abbrev_F (Via R code: criteria of 5 letters (genus) + 5 letters (specific epithet))

R code

```
library('fuzzySim')
library('terra')
library("xlsx")
```

```
Dataset_veg <- read.table("v02_spABR.csv", header = TRUE, sep = ",", quote = "\"\"", dec = ".")
names(Dataset_veg)
```

```
Dataset_veg$abbrev_F <- spCodes( Dataset_veg$DESC_LATIN_F, nchar.gen = 5, nchar.sp = 5, nchar.ssp = 3,
sep.species = " ", sep.spcode = " ", verbosity = 2)
```

```
write.csv(Dataset_veg, "v02_spABR_F.csv")
```

Note: The automatic abbreviation of species names via R code was followed by a manual abbreviation of species names in the form of sub-species, hybrids and varieties (Table D1). Classifications in the form of vegetation cover, grid reference, etc.. were removed from the database (Table D1). In addition, specific abbreviations were assumed to different species which, due to similarity in Latin names, cannot be

distinguished according to the criteria of 5 letters (genus) + 5 letters (specific epithet), e.g. *Carex panicea* vs *Carex paniculata* (assumed as *Carex panicea* vs *Carex panicul*) (Table D1).

- Site selection and quality control ('v02_spABR_F_T04_VEG.xlsx'): Selection of the eLTER Site of Moor House (SITE_CODE_NERC = T04) and removal of samples in which the quality of the data has been affected during sampling (i.e. FIELDNAME = Q1, Q2 and Q3).

- **ABIOTIC**

- ◇ Soil - Site selection and quality control ('soil.xlsx'):

- Sheet 'Soil_data' – original soil dataset
 - Sheet 'soil_data_T04' - Selection of the eLTER Site of Moor House (SITECODE= T04 in Sheet 'Soil_data')
 - Sheet 'sT04_QC' - Removal of samples in which the quality of the data has been affected during sampling (i.e. FIELDNAME = Q1, Q2, Q3, Q4, Q5 in Sheet 'soil_data_T04').

- ◇ Weather - Site selection and data merging:

- Selection of the eLTER Site of Moor House (SITECODE= T04 via R code) ('ecn_ma_YEAR[1996;2015]_T04.csv' in Folder 'weather_T04')

```
library('fuzzySim')
```

```
library('terra')
```

```
library("xlsx")
```

```
Dataset <- read.table("ecn_ma_1996.csv", header = TRUE, sep = ",", quote = "\"", dec = ".")
Dataset <- read.table("ecn_ma_1997.csv", header = TRUE, sep = ",", quote = "\"", dec = ".")
Dataset <- read.table("ecn_ma_1998.csv", header = TRUE, sep = ",", quote = "\"", dec = ".")
Dataset <- read.table("ecn_ma_1999.csv", header = TRUE, sep = ",", quote = "\"", dec = ".")
Dataset <- read.table("ecn_ma_2000.csv", header = TRUE, sep = ",", quote = "\"", dec = ".")
Dataset <- read.table("ecn_ma_2001.csv", header = TRUE, sep = ",", quote = "\"", dec = ".")
Dataset <- read.table("ecn_ma_2002.csv", header = TRUE, sep = ",", quote = "\"", dec = ".")
Dataset <- read.table("ecn_ma_2003.csv", header = TRUE, sep = ",", quote = "\"", dec = ".")
Dataset <- read.table("ecn_ma_2004.csv", header = TRUE, sep = ",", quote = "\"", dec = ".")
Dataset <- read.table("ecn_ma_2005.csv", header = TRUE, sep = ",", quote = "\"", dec = ".")
Dataset <- read.table("ecn_ma_2006.csv", header = TRUE, sep = ",", quote = "\"", dec = ".")
Dataset <- read.table("ecn_ma_2007.csv", header = TRUE, sep = ",", quote = "\"", dec = ".")
Dataset <- read.table("ecn_ma_2008.csv", header = TRUE, sep = ",", quote = "\"", dec = ".")
Dataset <- read.table("ecn_ma_2009.csv", header = TRUE, sep = ",", quote = "\"", dec = ".")
Dataset <- read.table("ecn_ma_2010.csv", header = TRUE, sep = ",", quote = "\"", dec = ".")
Dataset <- read.table("ecn_ma_2011.csv", header = TRUE, sep = ",", quote = "\"", dec = ".")
Dataset <- read.table("ecn_ma_2012.csv", header = TRUE, sep = ",", quote = "\"", dec = ".")
Dataset <- read.table("ecn_ma_2013.csv", header = TRUE, sep = ",", quote = "\"", dec = ".")
Dataset <- read.table("ecn_ma_2014.csv", header = TRUE, sep = ",", quote = "\"", dec = ".")
```

```
Dataset <- read.table("ecn_ma_2015.csv", header = TRUE, sep = ",", quote = "\"", dec = ".")
```

```
Dataset_T04 <- subset (Dataset, Dataset$SITECODE == 'T04')
```

- `write.csv(Dataset_T04, "ecn_ma_xxxx_T04.csv")`
- Merging of T04 weather datasets ('weather.xlsx'): years 1996-2005 in Sheet 'weather96_05' and years 2006-2015 in Sheet 'weather06_15'

C - Data transformation (spatial-temporal aggregation)

- **BIODIVERSITY** ('v02_spABR_F_T04_VEG_sp_abund_pres_abs.xlsx'):
 - Sheet 'Sp abundance' – Manual calculation of species abundance per plot per year (via sheet 'abund_calc): this metric is an estimate of species frequency per plot per year: i.e. number of cells in a given plot where the species is present. Note: 10 cells were surveyed in each plot therefore response values range between 0 when the species is absent and 10 when the species is present in all cells of the plot.
 - Sheet 'Sp pres abs' – Manual calculation of species presence/absence per plot per year (via Sheet 'Sp abundance' in which cells > 0 = 1): in this metric a value of 1 is considered when the species is sampled in at least one cell of a given plot, and absence is considered when the species is not occurring in any cell of the plot.
 - - **ABIOTIC**
 - ◊ Soil variables ('soil.xlsx')
 - Sheet 'sT04_QC_avr_qtr_YEAR' – Manual calculation of soil chemistry variables; i.e. mean annual values based on the average of trimestral values (via Sheet 'sT04_QC_qtr').
 - Sheet 'sT04_QC_samples_qtr' – Inspection of measurements per trimester per sampling year.
 - ◊ Weather-related variables (weather.xlsx)
 - Sheet 'w96_05_avr_qtr_YEAR' and 'w06_15_avr_qtr_YEAR' - Manual calculation of weather-related variables; i.e. mean annual values based on the average of trimestral values (via Sheets 'weather96_05' and 'weather06_15').
 - Sheet 'w96_05_samples' – Inspection of measurements per trimester per sampling year (via sheet 'w96_05_samples_qtr').

D - Data Analysis (Statistical procedure and data visualization)

- **BIODIVERSITY:**

- Identification of plots sampled at three-years interval and plots sampled annually ('v02_spABR_F_T04_VEG_PLOTS.xlsx'): Manual identification of plots in which plant sampling was performed in 3-years interval or annually (Sheet 'PLOTS_sampling' via v02_spABR')
- LU characterization of sampling plots, discriminated by 45 plots sampled at three-years interval and 8 plots sampled annually ('LU_LC_plots_charact.xlsx')
- Calculation of temporal trends in total species richness at the site and habitat level, discriminated by 45 plots sampled at three-years interval and 8 plots sampled annually ('biod_sprich_SITE_HABITAY_LEVEL.xlsx').
- Calculation of temporal trends in species richness at the plot level for 8 plots sampled annually ('biod_sprich_Site_habitat_Plots_yearlyPoints.xlsx').
- Implementation of the Kruskal-Wallis Test, including all pairwise *pos-hoc* multiple comparisons at site and habitat level, discriminated by 45 plots sampled at three-years interval ('sp_rich_time_LU.csv') and 8 plots sampled annually ('v02_yearlyPoints.csv') (via R code):

```
library('lme4')
```

```
library('ggResidpanel')
```

```
library('sjPlot')
```

```
library(DescTools)
```

```
library('stats')
```

```
#### 45 PLOTS SAMPLED AT THREE-YEARS INTERVAL
```

```
par(mfrow=c(1,2))
```

```
##### Site level
```

```
Dataset <- read.table("sp_rich_time_LU.csv", header = TRUE, sep = ",", quote = "\"", dec = ".")
```

```
### Descriptive analysis
```

```
hist(Dataset$sp_rich)
```

```
qqnorm(Dataset$sp_rich)
```

```
qqline(Dataset$sp_rich)
```

```
shapiro.test(Dataset$sp_rich)
```

```
ks.test(Dataset$sp_rich, 'pnorm')
```

```
### p > 0.05 data is normally distributed
```

```
### multiple comparisons
```

```
teste <- kruskal.test(sp_rich ~ year, data= Dataset)
teste

par(mfrow=c(1,1))

boxplot(sp_rich ~ year, data= Dataset, main = 'total species richness')

DunnTest(x = Dataset$sp_rich,
         g = Dataset$year)

##### Habitat-level

#Semi-natural grassland

semi_grass <- subset(Dataset, Dataset$LU_Final == 'Semi-natural grassland')

par(mfrow=c(1,2))
hist(semi_grass$sp_rich)
qqnorm(semi_grass $sp_rich)
qqline(semi_grass $sp_rich)

shapiro.test(semi_grass$sp_rich)
ks.test(semi_grass$sp_rich, 'pnorm')

### multiple comparisons

teste_grass <- kruskal.test(sp_rich ~ year, data= semi_grass)
teste_grass

par(mfrow=c(1,1))

boxplot(sp_rich ~ year, data= semi_grass, main = 'species richness: Semi-natural grassland')

#fen, moor or bog

fen <- subset(Dataset, Dataset$LU_Final == 'fen, moor or bog')

par(mfrow=c(1,2))

hist(fen $sp_rich)
qqnorm(fen $sp_rich)
qqline(fen $sp_rich)

shapiro.test(fen $sp_rich)
ks.test(fen $sp_rich, 'pnorm')
```

```
### multicomparisons

teste_fen <- kruskal.test(sp_rich ~ year, data= fen)
teste_fen

par(mfrow=c(1,1))

boxplot(sp_rich ~ year, data= fen, main = 'species richness: fen, moor or bog')

DunnTest(x = fen$sp_rich, g = fen$year)

#permanent or long-term grassland

perm <- subset(Dataset, Dataset$LU_Final == 'permanent or long-term grassland')

par(mfrow=c(1,2))
hist(perm $sp_rich)
qqnorm(perm $sp_rich)
qqline(perm $sp_rich)

shapiro.test(perm$sp_rich)
ks.test(perm$sp_rich, 'pnorm')

### multiple comparisons

teste_perm <- kruskal.test(sp_rich ~ year, data= perm)
teste_perm

par(mfrow=c(1,1))

boxplot(sp_rich ~ year, data= perm, main = 'permanent or long-term grassland')

#### 8 PLOTS SAMPLED ANNUALLY

par(mfrow=c(1,2))

##### Site level

Dataset <- read.table("v02_yearlyPoints.csv", header = TRUE, sep = ",", quote = "\"", dec = ".")
names(Dataset)

###Descriptive analysis

hist(Dataset$sp_rich)

qqnorm(Dataset$sp_rich)
```

```
qqline(Dataset$sp_rich)

shapiro.test(Dataset$sp_rich)
ks.test(Dataset$sp_rich, 'pnorm')

### p > 0.05 data is normally distributed

### multiple comparisons

teste <- kruskal.test(sp_rich ~ year, data= Dataset)
teste

par(mfrow=c(1,1))

boxplot(sp_rich ~ year, data= Dataset, main = 'total species richness')

DunnTest(x = Dataset$sp_rich,
         g = Dataset$year)

##### habitat level

#Semi-natural grassland

semi_grass <- subset(Dataset, Dataset$LU == 'Semi-natural grassland')

par(mfrow=c(1,2))
hist(semi_grass$sp_rich)
qqnorm(semi_grass $sp_rich)
qqline(semi_grass $sp_rich)

shapiro.test(semi_grass$sp_rich)
ks.test(semi_grass$sp_rich, 'pnorm')

### multiple comparisons

teste_grass <- kruskal.test(sp_rich ~ year, data= semi_grass)
teste_grass

par(mfrow=c(1,1))

boxplot(sp_rich ~ year, data= semi_grass, main = 'species richness: Semi-natural grassland')

#fen, moor or bog

fen <- subset(Dataset, Dataset$LU == 'fen, moor or bog')

par(mfrow=c(1,2))
```

```

hist(fen $sp_rich)
qqnorm(fen $sp_rich)
qqline(fen $sp_rich)

shapiro.test(fen $sp_rich)
ks.test(fen $sp_rich, 'pnorm')

### multiple comparisons

teste_fen <- kruskal.test(sp_rich ~ year, data= fen)
teste_fen

par(mfrow=c(1,1))

boxplot(sp_rich ~ year, data= fen, main = 'species richness: fen, moor or bog')

DunnTest(x = fen$sp_rich, g = fen$year)

#permanent or long-term grassland

perm <- subset(Dataset, Dataset$LU_Final == 'permanent or long-term grassland')

par(mfrow=c(1,2))
hist(perm $sp_rich)
qqnorm(perm $sp_rich)
qqline(perm $sp_rich)

shapiro.test(perm$sp_rich)
ks.test(perm$sp_rich, 'pnorm')

### multicomparisons

teste_perm <- kruskal.test(sp_rich ~ year, data= perm)
teste_perm

par(mfrow=c(1,1))

boxplot(sp_rich ~ year, data= perm, main = 'permanent or long-term grassland')

```

- Implementation of STL decomposition at site and habitat level, discriminated by 45 plots sampled at three-years interval ('tri_annualPoints_totalrich_2.csv'; 'tri_annualPoints_totalrich_LU_2.csv') and 8 plots sampled annually ('v02_yearlyPoints_totalrich_2.csv'; 'v02_yearlyPoints_totalrich_LU_2.csv') (via R code):

```

#ANOMALY DETECTION - OUTLIERS IN TIME SERIES/TEMPORAL TREND#

```

```

library(anomalize) #tidy anomaly detection
library(tidyverse) #tidyverse packages like dplyr, ggplot, tidyr
library(tibbletime)
library(tidyquant)
## 45 PLOTS SAMPLED AT THREE-YEARS INTERVAL

##Site level

data <- read.table("tri_annualPoints_totalrich_2.csv", header = TRUE, sep = ",", quote = "\"", dec = ".")

tbl <- data %>%
  transmute(date = as.POSIXct(strptime(year, "%d/%m/%Y"), # %H:%M")),
  sp_rich = sp_rich)

tbl_t <- tbl_time(tbl, index = date)
  names(tbl_t)
  class( tbl_t)

tbl_t %>%
  time_decompose(sp_rich, method = "stl", frequency = "auto", trend = "auto") %>%
  anomalize(remainder, method = "gesd", alpha = 0.05, max_anoms = 0.2) %>%
  plot_anomaly_decomposition()

tbl_t %>%
  time_decompose(sp_rich, method = "stl", frequency = "auto", trend = "auto") %>%
  anomalize(remainder, method = "gesd", alpha = 0.05, max_anoms = 0.2) %>%
  time_recompose() %>%
  plot_anomalies(time_recomposed = TRUE, ncol = 3, alpha_dots = 0.5)

tbl_t %>%
  time_decompose(sp_rich) %>%
  anomalize(remainder) %>%
  time_recompose() %>%
  filter(anomaly == 'Yes')

####Habitat level

data <- read.table("tri_annualPoints_totalrich_LU_2.csv", header = TRUE, sep = ",", quote = "\"", dec =
  ".")
names(data)

##### fen, moor or bog / mixed / Montane vegetation / permanent or long-term grassland / Semi-natural
grassland

```

```
data <- subset(data, data$LU == 'Montane vegetation')
```

```
tbl <- data %>%
  transmute(date = as.POSIXct(strptime(year, "%d/%m/%Y"), # %H:%M"),
  sp_rich = sp_rich)
```

```
tbl_t <- tbl_time(tbl, index = date)
names(tbl_t)
class(tbl_t)
```

```
tbl_t %>%
  time_decompose(sp_rich, method = "stl", frequency = "auto", trend = "auto") %>%
  anomalise(remainder, method = "gesd", alpha = 0.05, max_anoms = 0.2) %>%
  plot_anomaly_decomposition()
```

```
tbl_t %>%
  time_decompose(sp_rich, method = "stl", frequency = "auto", trend = "auto") %>%
  anomalise(remainder, method = "gesd", alpha = 0.05, max_anoms = 0.2) %>%
  time_recompose() %>%
  plot_anomalies(time_recomposed = TRUE, ncol = 3, alpha_dots = 0.5)
```

```
tbl_t %>%
  time_decompose(sp_rich) %>%
  anomalise(remainder) %>%
  time_recompose() %>%
  filter(anomaly == 'Yes')
```

```
#### 8 PLOTS SAMPLED ANNUALY
```

```
##Site level
```

```
data <- read.table("v02_yearlyPoints_totalrich_2.csv", header = TRUE, sep = ",", quote = "\"", dec = ".")
names(data)
```

```
tbl <- data %>%
  transmute(year = as.POSIXct(strptime(year, "%d/%m/%Y"), # %H:%M"),
  sp_rich = sp_rich)
```

```
tbl_t <- tbl_time(tbl, index = year)
names(tbl_t)
```

```

class( tbl_t)

#par(mfrow=c(1,2))

tbl_t %>%
  time_decompose(sp_rich, method = "stl", frequency = "auto", trend = "auto") %>%
  anomalise(remainder, method = "gesd", alpha = 0.05, max_anoms = 0.2) %>%
  plot_anomaly_decomposition()

tbl_t %>%
  time_decompose(sp_rich, method = "stl", frequency = "auto", trend = "auto") %>%
  anomalise(remainder, method = "gesd", alpha = 0.05, max_anoms = 0.2) %>%
  time_recompose() %>%
  plot_anomalies(time_recomposed = TRUE, ncol = 3, alpha_dots = 0.5)

##### Habitat level

data <- read.table("v02_yearlyPoints_totalrich_LU_2.csv", header = TRUE, sep = ",", quote = "\"", dec =
".")
names(data)

##### fen, moor or bog

data <- subset(data, data$LU == 'fen, moor or bog')

tbl <- data %>%
  transmute(year = as.POSIXct(strptime(year, "%d/%m/%Y")), # %H:%M"),
  sp_rich = sp_rich)

tbl_t <- tbl_time(tbl, index = year)
  names(tbl_t)
  class( tbl_t)

#par(mfrow=c(1,2))

tbl_t %>%
  time_decompose(sp_rich, method = "stl", frequency = "auto", trend = "auto") %>%
  anomalise(remainder, method = "gesd", alpha = 0.05, max_anoms = 0.2) %>%
  plot_anomaly_decomposition()

tbl_t %>%
  time_decompose(sp_rich, method = "stl", frequency = "auto", trend = "auto") %>%
  anomalise(remainder, method = "gesd", alpha = 0.05, max_anoms = 0.2) %>%
  time_recompose() %>%
  plot_anomalies(time_recomposed = TRUE, ncol = 3, alpha_dots = 0.5)

```

```
#####Semi-natural grasslands

data <- subset(data, data$LU == 'Semi-natural grassland')

tbl <- data %>%
  transmute(year = as.POSIXct(strptime(year, "%d/%m/%Y")), # %H:%M"),
  sp_rich = sp_rich)

tbl_t <- tbl_time(tbl, index = year)
names(tbl_t)
class(tbl_t)

#par(mfrow=c(1,2))

tbl_t %>%
  time_decompose(sp_rich, method = "stl", frequency = "auto", trend = "auto") %>%
  anomalize(remainder, method = "gesd", alpha = 0.05, max_anoms = 0.2) %>%
  plot_anomaly_decomposition()

tbl_t %>%
  time_decompose(sp_rich, method = "stl", frequency = "auto", trend = "auto") %>%
  anomalize(remainder, method = "gesd", alpha = 0.05, max_anoms = 0.2) %>%
  time_recompose() %>%
  plot_anomalies(time_recomposed = TRUE, ncol = 3, alpha_dots = 0.5)
```

- **ABIOTIC:**

- Implementation of pair-wise correlation using Spearman's rho correlation coefficient ('abiotic_avrQrtYear_F.csv'; 'abiotic_avrQrtYear_F_CORREL') (via R code):

```
vars<-read.table("abiotic_avrQrtYear_F.csv", header = TRUE, sep = ",", quote = "\"", dec = ".")
```

```
library(Hmisc)
```

```
corstarsl <- function(x){
  require(Hmisc)
  x <- as.matrix(x)
  R <- rcorr(x, type="spearman")$r
  p <- rcorr(x, type="spearman")$P
```

```
## define notions for significance levels; spacing is important.
```

```
mystars <- ifelse(p < .001, "****", ifelse(p < .01, "*** ", ifelse(p < .05, "** ", " ")))
```

```

## truncate the matrix that holds the correlations to two decimal
R <- format(round(cbind(rep(-1.11, ncol(x)), R), 2))[, -1]

## build a new matrix that includes the correlations with their appropriate significance values (as stars)
Rnew <- matrix(paste(R, mystars, sep=""), ncol=ncol(x))
diag(Rnew) <- paste(diag(R), " ", sep="")
rownames(Rnew) <- colnames(x)
colnames(Rnew) <- paste(colnames(x), "", sep="")

## remove upper triangle
Rnew <- as.matrix(Rnew)
Rnew[upper.tri(Rnew, diag = TRUE)] <- ""
Rnew <- as.data.frame(Rnew)

## remove last column and return the matrix (which is now a data frame)
Rnew <- cbind(Rnew[1:length(Rnew)-1])
return(Rnew)
}

corrfinal <- corstarsl(vars)

write.table(corrfinal, "abiotic_avrQrtYear_F_CORREL2.csv", sep = ",")

```

- Graphs of the variation in soil chemistry and weather-related variables across years ('abiotic_graphs 2.xlsx').

- **BIODIVERSITY VS ABIOTIC:**

Multivariate Analysis used to (i) disclose gradients underlying variations in the floristic composition; (ii) understand patterns of structure and composition across vegetation types through years; and, (iii) to assess the potential impact of environmental data on targeted plant communities were performed using the default setting of CANOCO Software (version 4.5).

Table D1 - Manual abbreviation (DESC_LATIN_F) of species names in the form of sub-species, hybrids and varieties (DESC_LATIN). Classifications in the form of vegetation cover, grid reference, etc.. were removed from the database (DESC_LATIN_F = Removed).

DESC_LATIN	DESC_LATIN_F
Acer seedling/sp	acer sp
Algal mat	Removed
Alisma plantago-aquatica	alism pla_aqu
Arctium minus ssp pubens	arcti minus pub
Arctostaphylos uva-ursi	arcto uva_ursi
Asplenium ruta-muraria	asple ruta_mur
Athyrium filix-femina	athyr filix_fem
Bare rock (talus)	Removed
Bare soil (including sand)	Removed
Betula seedling/sp	betul sp
Callitriche seedling/sp	calli sp
Calypogeia cf. muelleriana	calyp cf muell
Campylopus atrovirens ssp.sulcatus	campy atrov sul
Capsella bursa-pastoris	capse bursa_pas
Carex panicea	carex panicea
Carex paniculata	carex panicul
Carex seedling/sp	carex sp
Carex viridula ssp scottica	carex virid sco
Cephalozia bicuspidata	cepha bicus
Cephalozia bicuspidata var. lammersiana	cepha bicus lam
Cephalozia connivens	cepha conni
Cephalozia sp	cephalozia sp
Cephaloziella sp	cephaloziella sp
Cladonia cervicornis var verticillata	clado cervi ver
Cladonia ciliata var tenuis	clado cilia ten
Cladonia crispata var cetrariaeformis	clado crisp cet
Cladonia rangiferina	clado rangife
Cladonia rangiformis	clado rangifo
Cochlearia seedling/sp	cochl sp
Dryopteris filix-mas	dryop filix_mas
Equisetum arvense x palustre	equis arv_pal
Euphrasia officinalis agg	euphr offic agg
Eurhynchium praelongum var. stokesii	eurhy prael sto
Festuca ovina/rubra (vegetative)	festuc ovi_rub
Grid reference 100km square	Removed
Grid reference easting	Removed
Hieracium peleteranum (pil)	hiera pelet

Hieracium pilosella ss	hiera pilos
Hypnum cupressiforme ssp resupinatum	hypnu cupre res
Hypnum cupressiforme var cupressiforme	hypnu cupre cup
Hypnum cupressiforme var lacunosum	hypnu cupre lac
Jungermannia exertifolia var cordifolia	junge exert cor
Larix sp.(g)	larix sp
Lathyrus seedling/sp	lathy sp
Limonium binervosum ss	limon biner
Lophocolea sp	lophoc sp
Lophozia cf. ventricosa	lophoz ventri
Lophozia sp	lophoz sp
Luzula campestris/multiflora	luzul cam_mul
Lychnis flos-cuculi	lychn flos_cuc
Moss cover (%)	Removed
Moss height	Removed
Myosotis seedling/sp	myoso sp
Open water (%)	Removed
Peltigera cf. rufescens	pelti cf rufes
Pilosella officinarum agg	pilos offic agg
Pinus seedling/sp	pinus sp
Plagiomnium sp	plagiom sp
Plagiomnium undulatum	plagiom undul
Plagiothecium sp	plagioth sp
Plagiothecium undulatum	plagioth undul
Poa trivialis/nemoralis	poa tri_nem
Polygala sp	polyga sp
Polygonum sp	polygo sp
Ptilium crista-castrensis	ptili cista_cas
Quercus seedling/sp	querc sp
Ranunculus seedling/sp	ranun sp
Ribes uva-crispa	ribes uva_cris
Riccardia/Aneura sp	ric_ane sp
Rosa canina agg.	rosa canin agg
Rosa seedling/sp	rosa sp
Rubus fruticosus agg (g)	rubus fruti agg
Rubus fruticosus agg.	rubus fruti agg
Rubus fruticosus sect. triviales	robus fruti tri
Rumex acetosa	rumex acetosa
Rumex acetosella	rumex acetose
Rumex conglomeratus/sanguineus	rumex com_san
Rumex seedling/sp	rumex sp
Salix atrocinerea x aurita (s)	salix atr_aur

Salix cinerea ssp oleifolia(c)	salix ciner ole
Salix lapponum x atrocinerea (s)	salix lap_atr
Salix repens agg.	salix repen agg
Salix seedling/sp	salix sp
Sample no (thousands)	Removed
Scandix pecten-veneris	scand pecte_ven
Silene alba x dioica	silen alb_dio
Sphagnum auriculatum var auriculatum	sphag auric aur
Sphagnum auriculatum var inundatum	sphag auric inu
Stellaria seedling/sp	stell sp
Taraxacum anglicum (pal)	tarax angli
Taraxacum euryphyllum (spe)	tarax euryp
Taraxacum fulvum (ery)	tarax fulvu
Taraxacum officinale agg.	tarax offic agg
Taraxacum sect. erythrosperma	tarax eryth
Taraxacum simile (ery)	tarax simil
Thuidium abietinum ssp hystricosum	thuid abiet hys
Unidentified broadleaf seedling	Removed
Unidentified conifer seedling	Removed
Unidentified dicot seedling	Removed
Unidentified fern gametophyte	Removed
Unidentified grass seedling	Removed
Unidentified seedling	Removed
Vaccinium vitis-idaea	vacci vitis_ida
Veronica seedling/sp	veron sp
Vicia seedling/sp	vicia sp
Viola riviniana x rupestris	viola riv_rup
Viola riviniana/reichenbachiana	viola riv_rei
Viola seedling/sp	viola sp

6.5. Appendix E

Appendix E - Detailed description of the results from ‘Identification of suitable datasets to integrate biodiversity analysis in WAILS’.

Among 170 eLTER Sites available on B2DROP, 83 presented biodiversity data (Figure E1). Of these, 57 included biodiversity data with timespan longer than 15 years, of which 50 had more than 10 measurements within the monitoring period considered (Figure E1). Only 31 of these sites presented supplementary abiotic data (Figure E1). In none of these sites, environmental data belong simultaneously to all the spheres covered by WAILS (i.e. biodiversity, biogeochemistry, hydrology and socio-ecology) (Figure E1).

Figure E1 - Number of sites available on B2DROP (last update 1st of April 2022) presenting biodiversity (BD) data, timespan longer than 15 years, more than 10 measurements within the monitoring period and availability of supplementary abiotic data.

In both sets of sites (i.e. sites with timespan > 15 years AND > 10 measurements; sites with timespan > 15 years AND > 10 measurements AND supplementary abiotic data), the most sampled taxonomic groups were terrestrial macroinvertebrates, Flora/Vascular plants, Mammals and Birds (Figure E2). These sites were mostly located in the UK, Italy, Sweden and Germany (Figure E2).

Figure E2 - Biodiversity data available on B2DROP (last update 1st of April 2022) in 2 sets of sites (i.e. in blue: sites with timespan > 15 years AND > 10 measurements; in green: sites with timespan > 15 years, > 10 measurements and abiotic data), discriminated by taxa and country.

The list of eLTER Sites, discriminated by country, presence/absence of biodiversity data, timespan longer than 15 years, more than 10 sampled years and availability of supplementary abiotic data are displayed in Appendix E1. The list of eLTER Sites with biodiversity data presenting timespan longer than 15 years and more than 10 sampled years, discriminated by Biodiversity Indicator, timespan, number of sampled years, and presence/absence of supplementary abiotic data are displayed in Appendix E2.

Appendix E1 - Set of sites available on B2DROP (last update 1st April 2022) discriminated by: country and presence (Y) / absence (N) of biodiversity data (BD data), timespan longer than 15 years (time span > 15 years), more than 10 measurements within the monitoring period considered (samples > 10) and availability of supplementary abiotic data (Abiotic data).

	Country	Site	BD data	time span > 15 years	samples > 10	Abiotic data	Abiotic data from all spheres
1	Antartica	Mooring A	Y	N			
2	Antartica	Mooring B	Y	N			
3	Austria	Gesause NP	Y	Y	Y	N	
4	Austria	Gossenköllesee	N				
5	Austria	HOAL Petzenkirchen	N				
6	Austria	Hochschwab	Y	Y	N		
7	Austria	Jamtalferner	Y	N			
8	Austria	Kalkalpen NP	N				
9	Austria	Mondsee	N				
10	Austria	Obergurgl	Y	Y	Y	N	
11	Austria	Piburger See	N				
12	Austria	Rosalia	N				
13	Austria	Schrankogel	Y	Y	N		
14	Austria	Stubai	N				
15	Austria	Zöbelboden	Y	Y	N		
16	Belgium	Beverbeek	N				
17	Belgium	Brasschaat	N				
18	Belgium	Doode Bemde	N				
19	Belgium	Forest of Meerdaal	N				
20	Belgium	Gontrode	N				
21	Belgium	Ichtegem	N				
22	Belgium	Lonzée	N				
23	Belgium	NP Hoge Kempen	N				
24	Belgium	Ravels Forest	N				
25	Belgium	Rode Forest and Laan Valley	N				
26	Belgium	Scheldt Estuary	N				
27	Belgium	Sonian Forest	N				
28	Belgium	Valley of the Zwarte Beek	N				
29	Bulgaria	Black Sea	Y	Y	Y	N	
30	Bulgaria	Mesta River	N				
31	Bulgaria	Petrohan-Ponor	N				
32	Bulgaria	Sozopol - Black Sea	N				
33	Bulgaria	Srebana	Y	Y	Y	Y	N
34	Switzerland	Alptal	N				
35	Switzerland	Alptal, Beatenberg, Bettlachstock, Celerina, Chironico, Davos Seehornwald, Isonne, Jussy, Lausanne, Lens, Nationalpark, Neunkirch, Novaggio, Othmarsingen, Schaenis, Visp, Vordemwald	Y	-	-	N	
36	Switzerland	Davos Seehornwald	N				
37	Switzerland	Laegeren	N				
38	Switzerland	Pfynwald	N				
39	Switzerland	Stillberg	N				
40	Switzerland	Swiss Canopy Crane II	N				
41	Czechia	Bily Kriz	N				
42	Czechia	Lysina & Pluhuv Bor	N				
43	Germany	AgroScapeLab Quillow	Y	Y	Y	Y	N
44	Germany	Augustendorf	Y	Y	Y	N	
45	Germany	Bornhoeved	Y	Y	Y	Y	N
46	Germany	Coastal Deciduous Forests North-Eastern Germany	N				
47	Germany	Darss-Zingst Bodden	Y	N			
48	Germany	Ehrhorn	Y	Y	Y	Y	N
49	Germany	Göttinger Wald	Y	Y	Y	Y	N
50	Germany	Helgoland Roads	N				
51	Germany	Hohes Holz	N				
52	Germany	Krofdorf	Y	N			
53	Germany	Lake Stechlin	N				
54	Germany	Lange Bramke	Y	Y	Y	Y	N
55	Germany	Luess	Y	Y	Y	Y	N

56	Germany	Müggelsee	N				
57	Germany	NP Berchtesgaden	N				
58	Germany	NP Hunsrück	Y	Y	Y	Y	N
59	Germany	NP Kellerwald-Edersee	Y	N			
60	Germany	Rhine-Main-Observatory	Y	Y	Y	Y	N
61	Germany	Solling	Y	Y	Y	Y	N
62	Germany	TERENO - Bad Lauchstaedt	N				
63	Germany	TERENO - Bode catchment	N				
64	Germany	TERENO – Friedeburg Greifenhagen Harsleben Schafstaedt Siptenfelde Wanzleben	Y	N			
65	Germany	TERENO - Gimritz	N				
66	Germany	TERENO - Rollesbroich - Selhausen - Wüstebach	N				
67	Spain	Donana	Y	N			
68	Finland	Hyttiälä	N				
69	Finland	Lammi	Y	Y	Y	Y	N
70	Finland	Värriö	N				
71	Finland	Western Gulf of Finland	Y	Y	Y	N	
72	France	Agricultural site Network of organic farms	N				
73	France	Atelier Alpes	N				
74	France	Atelier Armorique	Y	Y	Y	N	
75	France	Atelier Bassin du Rhône	Y	Y	Y	N	
76	France	Atelier Loire	N				
77	France	Atelier Loire - Downstream Allier River	N				
78	France	Atelier Loire - Louroux Watershed	N				
79	France	Atelier Loire - Mareau-aux-Prés Islands	Y	N			
80	France	Atelier Plaine et Val de Sevre	N				
81	France	NATURA2000 River floodplain	N				
82	France	OZCAR-RI PEATLAND Landemarais	N				
83	France	OZCAR-RI SNO KARST Baget Karstic Catchment	N				
84	Greece	Koiliaris	N				
85	Hungary	Bugac	N				
86	Hungary	Kiskun	N				
87	Hungary	KISKUN - Fulophaza Site	N				
88	Hungary	KISKUN - Orgovany Site	N				
89	Hungary	KISKUN - Restoration Experiments	Y	Y	Y	N	
90	Hungary	Sikfokut	N				
91	Israel	Avdat	N				
92	Israel	Gilat	N				
93	Israel	Karei Deshe	N				
94	Israel	Kdoshim	N				
95	Israel	Matta	N				
96	Israel	Morris Khan	Y	N			
97	Israel	Park Shaked	N				
98	Israel	Ramat Hanadiv	N				
99	Israel	Ramon	N				
100	Israel	Shagririm	N				
101	Israel	Shita Wadi	Y	N			
102	Israel	Yatir	N				
103	Italy	Acquatina	Y	N			
104	Italy	Alimini	Y	N			
105	Italy	Angelo Mosso	Y	N			
106	Italy	Appennino centrale: Gran Sasso d'Italia	Y	Y	Y	N	
107	Italy	Appennino centrale: Velino-Duchessa	N				
108	Italy	Appennino centro	Y	N			
109	Italy	Appennino settentrionale	Y	N			
110	Italy	Bosco Fontana	Y	N			
111	Italy	Central Italy coastal dunes	Y	Y	Y	N	
112	Italy	Collelongo-Selva Piana	N				
113	Italy	Delta del Po e Costa Romagnola	N				
114	Italy	Eastern Ligurian Sea	Y	Y	Y	N	
115	Italy	Foce Saccione	N				
116	Italy	Foce Trigno	N				
117	Italy	Golfo di Trieste	N				
118	Italy	Golfo di Venezia	Y	Y	Y	Y	N
119	Italy	Lago Anterselva	Y	Y	Y	N	
120	Italy	Lago Bidighinzu	Y	Y	Y	Y	N
121	Italy	Lago Braies	Y	Y	Y	N	
122	Italy	Lago Maggiore	Y	Y	Y	Y	N
123	Italy	Lago Piccolo di Monticolo	Y	Y	Y	N	
124	Italy	Lagoon of Venice	N				
125	Italy	Lake Trasimeno	Y	Y	N		

126	Italy	Mar Piccolo of Taranto	Y	Y	Y	N	
127	Italy	Montagna di Torricchio	Y	N			
128	Italy	Renon	N				
129	Italy	Torgnon grassland Tellinod	Y	N			
130	Italy	Torgnon Larch Forest	Y	N			
131	Italy	Torre Flavia	N				
132	Italy	Transetto Senigallia-Susak	N				
133	Italy	Val Mazia - Matschertal	Y	N			
134	Lithuania	Aukstaitija	Y	Y	Y	Y	N
135	Lithuania	Zemaitija	N				
136	Latvia	Engure	N				
137	Latvia	Randu meadows	Y	Y	Y	N	
138	Latvia	Riga Reservoir	Y	Y	Y	N	
139	Latvia	River Salaca	Y	Y	Y	N	
140	Poland	Brenna	Y	Y	N		
141	Poland	Slowinski NP	Y	Y	N		
142	Poland	Tatranski NP	Y	Y	N		
143	Portugal	Baixo Sabor	Y	N			
144	Portugal	Companhia das Lezírias	N				
145	Portugal	Herdade da Ribeira Abaixo	N				
146	Portugal	Montado	N				
147	Portugal	Ria de Aveiro	Y	N			
148	Romania	Braila Islands	Y	N			
149	Romania	Retezat Bioshere Reserve	N				
150	Sweden	Aneboda	Y	Y	Y	Y	N
151	Sweden	Asko Laboratory	N				
152	Sweden	Gammtratten	Y	Y	Y	Y	N
153	Sweden	Gardsjön	Y	Y	Y	Y	N
154	Sweden	Kindla	Y	Y	Y	Y	N
155	Sweden	Ore estuary	N				
156	Sweden	Svartberget Fields	N				
157	Slovenia	Postojna-Planina Cave System	Y	N			
158	Turkey	Lake Eymir and Lake Mogan	Y	Y	Y	N	
159	UK	Alice Holt	Y	Y	Y	Y	N
160	UK	Cairngorms	Y	Y	Y	Y	N
161	UK	Drayton	Y	Y	Y	Y	N
162	UK	Glensaugh	Y	Y	Y	Y	N
163	UK	Hillsborough	Y	Y	Y	Y	N
164	UK	Moor House - Upper Teesdale	Y	Y	Y	Y	N
165	UK	North Wyke	Y	Y	Y	Y	N
166	UK	Porton	Y	Y	Y	Y	N
167	UK	Rothamsted	Y	Y	Y	Y	N
168	UK	Sourhope	Y	Y	Y	Y	N
169	UK	Wytham	Y	Y	Y	Y	N
170	UK	Yr Wyddfa / Snowdon	Y	Y	Y	Y	N

Appendix E2 - Set of sites available on B2DROP (last update 1st of April 2022) with biodiversity data presenting timespan longer than 15 years and more than 10 measurements within the monitoring period considered, and respective BD Indicator, timespan, number of samples years, and presence (Y) / absence (N) of supplementary abiotic data.

Abiotic data	Site (sites with BD timespan > 15 years AND > 10 measurements)	Indicator (timespan)	no. sampled years
N	Gesause NP (Austria)	Actitis hypoleucos 2004-2020	17
N		Aquila chrysaetos 2004-2020	17
N		birds 2000-2019	15
N		Mammals 2004-2019	16
N	Obergurgl (Austria)	Flora 2000-2018	12
N	Black Sea (Bulgaria)	aquatic macroinv 2000-2019	18
Y	Srebana (Bulgaria)	Pelicanus crispus 1955-2020	66
Y	AgroScapeLab Quillow (Germany)	crop plant species 2000-2019	20
N	Augustendorf (Germany)	bryophyte and lichen 1994-2019	26
Y	Bornhoeved (Germany)	bryophyte and lichen 2004-2019	16
Y	Ehrhorn (Germany)	bryophyte and lichen 1995-2019	25
Y	Göttinger Wald (Germany)	bryophyte and lichen 1994-2019	26
Y	Lange Bramke (Germany)	bryophyte and lichen 1994-2019	26
Y	Luess (Germany)	bryophyte and lichen 1994-2019	26
Y	NP Hunsrück (Germany)	aquatic macroinv 1985 - 2019	21
Y	Rhine-Main-Observatory (Germany)	Insecta 2001-2016	16
Y	Solling (Germany)	bryophyte and lichen 1994-2019	26
Y	Lammi (Finland)	Moths 1993-2020	28
Y		Mammals 1986-2020	35
N	Western Gulf of Finland (Finland)	aquatic macroinv 1966-2017	52
N	Atelier Armorique (France)	Predators (birds) 1999-2018	20
N		Prey (mammals) 1989-2018	30
N	Atelier Bassin du Rhône (France)	Fish 1985-2020	36
N	KISKUN - Restoration Experiments (Hungary)	Flora 1995-2019	5-11
N	Appennino centrale: Gran Sasso d'Italia (Italy)	Florea 1993-2020	16
N	Central Italy coastal dunes (Italy)	migratory birds 1999-2020	22
N		sedentary birds 1999-2019	21
N		nesting birds 1999-2020	22
N	Eastern Ligurian Sea (Italy)	seagrass Posidonia oceanica 1991-2006	16
Y	Golfo di Venezia (Italy)	phyto and zooplankton 1965-2015	51
N	Lago Anterselva (Italy)	zooplankton 1979-2014	36
Y	Lago Bidighinzu (Italy)	phytoplankton 1988-2015	16
N	Lago Braies (Italy)	zooplankton 2000-2018	19
Y	Lago Maggiore (Italy)	phytoplankton 1984-2018	35
N	Lago Piccolo di Monticolo (Italy)	zooplankton 1979-2014	36
N	Mar Piccolo of Taranto (Italy)	phytobenthos 1989-2019	12
Y	Aukstaitija (Lithuania)	Vascular plants 2000-2019	20
N	Randu meadows (Latvia)	Insects 1996-2012	17
N	Riga Reservoir (Latvia)	zoobenthos 1976-2017	42
N	River Salaca (Latvia)	zoobenthos 1968-2015	48
Y	Aneboda (Sweden)	flora 1989-2019	31
Y	Gammtratten (Sweden)	flora 1999-2019	21
Y	Gardsjön (Sweden)	flora and vascular plants 1995-2019	25
Y	Kindla (Sweden)	flora 1996-2019	24
N	Lake Eymir and Lake Mogan (Turkey)	phyto and zooplankton 1997-2013	17
Y	Alice Holt (T09) (UK)	bats 1994-2015	20
Y		birds 1998-2015	28
Y		butterflies 1994-2015	22
Y		carabid beetle 1994-2014	21
Y		flora 1996-2014	12
Y		moths 1992-2015	24
Y	Cairngorms (T12) (UK)	carabid beetle 1999-2015	17
Y		moths 2001-2015	14
Y		spittle bug 1999-2014	26
Y	Drayton (T01) (UK)	birds 1995-2010	14
Y		butterflies 1993-2011	19
Y		carabid beetle 1993-2009	16
Y		flora 1994-2012	16
Y		frogs 1994-2012	19
Y		moths 1993-2013	20
Y		rabbit and deer 1993-2006	14
Y		spittle bug 1993-2006	21

Y	Glensaugh (T02) (UK)	bats 1994-2014	20
Y		butterflies 1994-2014	20
Y		carabid beetle 1994-2012	19
Y		flora 1996-2014	16
Y		frogs 1994-2014	21
Y		moths 1994-2015	22
Y		spittle bug 1994-2014	40
Y	Hillsborough (T03) (UK)	butterflies 1993-2015	22
Y		carabid beetle 1993-2015	23
Y		flora 1996-2015	17
Y		frogs 1994-2011	18
Y		moths 1993-2015	23
Y		rabbit and deer 1995-2014	20
Y		spittle bug 1993-2014	31
Y	Moor House - Upper Teesdale (T04) (UK)	bats 1993-2015	23
Y		birds 1996-2015	19
Y		butterflies 1993-2015	23
Y		carabid beetle 1993-2015	23
Y		flora 1996-2015	19
Y		frogs 1994-2015	22
Y		moths 1993-2015	23
Y	North Wyke (T05) (UK)	rabbit and deer 1993-2015	23
Y		spittle bug 1993-2015	46
Y		bats 1993-2015	22
Y		birds 1997-2015	17
Y		butterflies 1993-2011	22
Y		carabid beetle 1993-2015	23
Y		flora 1994-2014	17
Y	Porton (T10) (UK)	frogs 1994-2015	22
Y		moths 1992-2015	24
Y		rabbit and deer 1993-2015	22
Y		spittle bug 1993-2015	45
Y		birds 1995-2010	16
Y		butterflies 1994-2013	21
Y		carabid beetle 1994-2013	20
Y	Rothamsted (T06) (UK)	flora 1996-2011	11
Y		moths 1994-2015	21
Y		rabbit and deer 1994-2015	22
Y		spittle bug 1994-2015	36
Y		butterflies 1993-2010	18
Y		carabid beetle 1992-2011	18
Y		frogs 1994-2010	13
Y	Sourhope (T07) (UK)	moths 1992-2015	24
Y		rabbit and deer 1994-2010	17
Y		spittle bug 1993-2011	30
Y		bats 1994-2014	21
Y		butterflies 1993-2010	18
Y		carabid beetle 1994-2012	19
Y		flora 1996-2014	18
Y	Wytham (T08) (UK)	moths 1993-2015	23
Y		spittle bug 1994-2012	37
Y		bats 1993-2012	20
Y		butterflies 1993-2013	22
Y		carabid beetle 1993-2014	22
Y		common birds 1971-2003	33
Y		flora 1994-2012	19
Y	Yr Wyddfa / Snowdon (T11) (UK)	moths 1992-2015	24
Y		rabbit and deer 1993-2015	23
Y		spittle bug 1993-2015	44
Y		bats 1996-2011	16
Y		birds 1996-2012	17
Y		butterflies 1996-2012	17
Y		frogs 1995-2012	18

6.6. Appendix F

Appendix F - List of standard observations proposed by eLTER PLUS (last update January 2024).

Standard Observation	Compared to Variables in use of variables		Wetlands (Inters, Intra, Nests)		Grasslands and heathlands (Inters, Intra, Nests)		Grasslands and heathlands (Inters, Intra, Nests)		Heathlands, shrub and tundra		Heathlands, shrub and tundra		Forests and other wooded land		Forests and other wooded land		Vegetated non-wooded habitats (terrestrial)		Vegetated non-wooded habitats (terrestrial)		Inland surface standing waters		Coastal (transitional) waters including coastal littoral zones, coastal littoral zones		Coastal (transitional) waters including coastal littoral zones, coastal littoral zones		Sparsely vegetated habitats and deserts		Sparsely vegetated habitats and deserts		eLTER Platform										
	min + Cat2	Intensive Cat1	min + Cat2	Intensive Cat1	min + Cat2	Intensive Cat1	min + Cat2	Intensive Cat1	min + Cat2	Intensive Cat1	min + Cat2	Intensive Cat1	min + Cat2	Intensive Cat1	min + Cat2	Intensive Cat1	min + Cat2	Intensive Cat1	min + Cat2	Intensive Cat1	min + Cat2	Intensive Cat1	min + Cat2	Intensive Cat1	min + Cat2	Intensive Cat1	min + Cat2	Intensive Cat1	min + Cat2	Intensive Cat1	min + Cat2	Intensive Cat1	min + Cat2	Intensive Cat1	min + Cat2	Intensive Cat1	min + Cat2	Intensive Cat1			
Filter																																									
SOE02_001	Soil inventory - pedological/biopedological	Soil texture (for region categories, based on soil pH, SOC, base saturation, organic matter, soil characteristics, amongst other characteristics)	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	X		
SOE02_003	Soil chemical and physical characteristics	Hydrogen Concentration, 03 Hydrogen, 04 Hydrogen, 05 Hydrogen, 06 Hydrogen, 07 Hydrogen, 08 Hydrogen, 09 Hydrogen, 10 Hydrogen, 11 Hydrogen, 12 Hydrogen, 13 Hydrogen, 14 Hydrogen, 15 Hydrogen, 16 Hydrogen, 17 Hydrogen, 18 Hydrogen, 19 Hydrogen, 20 Hydrogen, 21 Hydrogen, 22 Hydrogen, 23 Hydrogen, 24 Hydrogen, 25 Hydrogen, 26 Hydrogen, 27 Hydrogen, 28 Hydrogen, 29 Hydrogen, 30 Hydrogen, 31 Hydrogen, 32 Hydrogen, 33 Hydrogen, 34 Hydrogen, 35 Hydrogen, 36 Hydrogen, 37 Hydrogen, 38 Hydrogen, 39 Hydrogen, 40 Hydrogen, 41 Hydrogen, 42 Hydrogen, 43 Hydrogen, 44 Hydrogen, 45 Hydrogen, 46 Hydrogen, 47 Hydrogen, 48 Hydrogen, 49 Hydrogen, 50 Hydrogen, 51 Hydrogen, 52 Hydrogen, 53 Hydrogen, 54 Hydrogen, 55 Hydrogen, 56 Hydrogen, 57 Hydrogen, 58 Hydrogen, 59 Hydrogen, 60 Hydrogen, 61 Hydrogen, 62 Hydrogen, 63 Hydrogen, 64 Hydrogen, 65 Hydrogen, 66 Hydrogen, 67 Hydrogen, 68 Hydrogen, 69 Hydrogen, 70 Hydrogen, 71 Hydrogen, 72 Hydrogen, 73 Hydrogen, 74 Hydrogen, 75 Hydrogen, 76 Hydrogen, 77 Hydrogen, 78 Hydrogen, 79 Hydrogen, 80 Hydrogen, 81 Hydrogen, 82 Hydrogen, 83 Hydrogen, 84 Hydrogen, 85 Hydrogen, 86 Hydrogen, 87 Hydrogen, 88 Hydrogen, 89 Hydrogen, 90 Hydrogen, 91 Hydrogen, 92 Hydrogen, 93 Hydrogen, 94 Hydrogen, 95 Hydrogen, 96 Hydrogen, 97 Hydrogen, 98 Hydrogen, 99 Hydrogen, 100 Hydrogen	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
SOE02_007	Soil water chemical characteristics	Soil water pH, soil water conductivity (per hectare), soil water NH ₄ , NO ₃ -N, DON, DOC, Cation, Anion	X	P	X	P	X	P	X	P	X	P	X	P	X	P	X	P	X	P	X	P	X	P	X	P	X	P	X	P	X	P	X	P	X	P	X	P	X	P	X
SOE02_048	penetration/filtration - soil	infiltration rate - soil	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	
SOE02_105	Sediment (aquatic and marine) inventory	Physical and chemical characteristics (particle size distribution, composition, pH, carbon, sulfur)	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	
SOHW0_004	Profiles of physical and chemical of waters characteristics - surface water (standing)	Water temperature, water temperature, pH, EC, turbidity, oxygen, water depth	B	P	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	
SOHW0_005	Physical and chemical water characteristics (surface water (running water))	Water temperature, pH, EC, turbidity, oxygen, NO ₃ , DOC, water level	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	
SOHW0_006	Physical and chemical water characteristics (groundwater)	Water temperature, hydraulic head, electrical conductivity	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	
SOHW0_168	Nutrient concentration: NO ₂ , NH ₄ , DOC, DOC - running waters	NO ₂ , NH ₄ , DOC, DOC	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	
SOHW0_170	Profiles of nutrient concentration: NO ₂ , NH ₄ , DOC, DOC - standing waters	NO ₂ , NH ₄ , DOC, DOC	B	P	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	
SOHW0_171	Nutrient concentration: Cl, SO ₄ , B, Na, K, Mg, Ca, B, Silica - Inland (running/standing waters, transitional waters)	Cl, SO ₄ , B, Na, K, Mg, Ca, B, Silica	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	
SOHW0_202	Water level - surface water (running water)	Water level (in order to derive the excess discharge)	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	
SOHW0_011	Ice cover/thickness (standing and transitional water)	Ice cover/thickness (standing and transitional water)	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	
SOHW0_012	Snow cover and depth	Snow cover depth	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	
SOHW0_168	Soil water content/soil temperature	Soil water content, soil temperature	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	
SOHW0_058	Stable isotopes (δ ¹³ C, δ ¹⁵ N) - standing, running waters	Stable isotopes (δ ¹³ C, δ ¹⁵ N) - standing, running waters	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	
SOHW0_209	Stable isotopes (δ ¹³ C, δ ¹⁵ N) - groundwater	Stable isotopes (δ ¹³ C, δ ¹⁵ N) - groundwater	X	P	X	P	X	P	X	P	X	P	X	P	X	P	X	P	X	P	X	P	X	P	X	P	X	P	X	P	X	P	X	P	X	P	X	P	X	P	
SOHW0_062	Nutrient concentration: Cl, SO ₄ , B, Na, K, Mg, Ca, B - groundwater	Nutrient concentration: Cl, SO ₄ , B, Na, K, Mg, Ca, B - groundwater	X	P	X	P	X	P	X	P	X	P	X	P	X	P	X	P	X	P	X	P	X	P	X	P	X	P	X	P	X	P	X	P	X	P	X	P	X	P	
SOHW0_064	Nutrient concentration: TP, SRP, TDN, NO ₂ , NH ₄ , DOC, DOC - groundwater	Nutrient concentration: TP, SRP, TDN, NO ₂ , NH ₄ , DOC, DOC - groundwater	X	P	X	P	X	P	X	P	X	P	X	P	X	P	X	P	X	P	X	P	X	P	X	P	X	P	X	P	X	P	X	P	X	P	X	P	X	P	
SOHW0_065	DOM composition - groundwater	DOM composition - groundwater	X	P	X	P	X	P	X	P	X	P	X	P	X	P	X	P	X	P	X	P	X	P	X	P	X	P	X	P	X	P	X	P	X	P	X	P	X	P	
SOHW0_067	Microplastics: non-target screening (≥200 micrometers) - running water	Microplastics: non-target screening (≥200 micrometers) - running water	X	P	X	P	X	P	X	P	X	P	X	P	X	P	X	P	X	P	X	P	X	P	X	P	X	P	X	P	X	P	X	P	X	P	X	P	X	P	
SOHW0_164	glacier front variation	glacier front variation	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	
SOHW0_165	glacier mass balance	glacier mass balance	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	
SOHW0_166	glacier area	glacier area	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	
SOHW0_174	Stream Depth: standing waters and transitional waters	Stream Depth: standing waters and transitional waters	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	
SOHW0_014	Flying insects	Flying insects	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	
SOHW0_017	Vegetation composition (shrub species (shrub/bushes))	Shrub vegetation	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	
SOHW0_018	Birds, bats, frogs, moths using acoustic monitoring	Birds, bats, frogs, moths using acoustic monitoring	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	
SOHW0_019	Fishes and species	Fishes and species	X	P	X	P	X	P	X	P	X	P	X	P	X	P	X	P	X	P	X	P	X	P	X	P	X	P	X	P	X	P	X	P	X	P	X	P	X	P	
SOHW0_021	OTN Water	OTN Water	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	
SOHW0_023	OTN soil	OTN soil	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	
SOHW0_024	OTN water	OTN water	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	
SOHW0_172	Nutrient concentration: TP, SRP, TDN, NO ₂ , NH ₄ , DOC, DOC - running waters	Nutrient concentration: TP, SRP, TDN, NO ₂ , NH ₄ , DOC, DOC - running waters	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	
SOHW0_173	Profiles of nutrient concentration: TP, SRP, TDN, NO ₂ , NH ₄ , DOC, DOC - standing waters	Profiles of nutrient concentration: TP, SRP, TDN, NO ₂ , NH ₄ , DOC, DOC - standing waters	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	
SOHW0_027	Meteorological data	Weather or boundary conditions, or temperature, wind speed/direction, surface atmospheric pressure	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	
SOHW0_028	Evaporation	Evaporation	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	
SOHW0_029	Ground heat flux	Ground heat flux	X	P	X	P	X	P	X	P	X	P	X	P	X	P	X	P	X	P	X	P	X	P	X	P	X	P	X	P	X	P	X	P	X	P	X	P	X	P	
SOHW0_105	Atmospheric deposition in precipitation	Atmospheric deposition in precipitation	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	
SOHW0_106	Dry deposition of N compounds	Dry deposition of N compounds	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	
SOHW0_176	CO ₂ flux and concentrations, latent heat flux, sensible heat flux - Eddy Covariance	CO ₂ flux and concentrations, latent heat flux, sensible heat flux - Eddy Covariance	X	P	X	P	X	P	X	P	X	P	X	P	X	P	X	P	X	P	X	P	X	P	X	P	X	P	X	P	X	P	X	P	X	P	X	P	X	P	
SOHW0_033	Vegetation aboveground biomass - forest	Forest aboveground vegetation biomass	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
SOHW0_177	Tree growth	Tree growth	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
SOHW0_034	Vegetation aboveground biomass - non-forested sites	Aboveground biomass - non-forested sites	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	B	P	
SOHW0_080	GPP calculated from Eddy Covariance measure	GPP calculated from Eddy Covariance measure	X	P	X	P</																																			

The eLTER pre-screening survey again received extensive feedback, particularly with respect to the proposed methods and protocols for certain Standard Observations. These criticisms related, for example, to the lack of eLTER-wide coordinated protocols for some Standard Observations as well as to the effort required both in terms of installation costs and the expertise required for certain measurements. Each of these criticisms was evaluated on a case-by-case basis and, as a result, some Standard Observations were removed from the current list. These Standard Observations will be re-considered within the relevant expert groups in light of the criticisms raised and may be resubmitted at a later date.

The Standard Observations for the Sociosphere are still under discussion by the respective Expert Group and will be provided until mid of July 2023.

Currently, it is envisaged that the Sociosphere SOs for all Cat1/Ca2 sites will be provided via a central service.

How to use the SO-Habitat-Tables?

1. Select the habitat of interest (row 1, cells E1-V1)!	X	This SO was not proposed for or is not applicable in this habitat.
2. Select the eLTER site category of interest (row 2)!	B	Basic METHOD (see SOs_METHOD table for details). Color corresponds to the respective sphere assign
3. Filter all SOs proposed for the selected habitat and category (row 4)! In the filter dropdown menu select either "B" or "P".	P	Prime METHOD (see SOs_METHOD table for details). Color corresponds to the respective sphere assign

For Category 1-sites only: In terms of the criteria for a Cat1 site, only two of the four spheres (geosphere, biosphere, hydrosphere, atmosphere) need to be covered with Prime METHODS. The mandatory monitoring program for the other two remaining spheres meets the requirements for a Cat 2 site. Prime METHODS for the Sociosphere apply for Platforms only.

General Remarks

Large areas and **extended sites may include several types of habitats**. Main habitats should be selected, in terms of a nested approach the relevant SOs are considered.

Customizable characteristics: If a **SO is not relevant or not measurable** from technical or scientific point of view (e.g. groundwater level in high alpine altitudes; ice cover on mediterranean surface water bodies), we do not measure it and it can be excluded from the habitat-specific SOs selection for that special site.

Considering the selection of habitat-specific SOs it was supposed to keep the consistency within terrestrial / aquatic habitats and to meet the demands in terms of **the WAILS approach**. In the spirit of WAILS it would be very desirable to measure also variables in the surrounding habitats. We must not forget, that one of the unique selling points of eLTER RI will be the provision of pan-European data sets for some important environmental variables.

The focus for the **monitoring of water habitats** (rivers, lakes, transitional waters) should be on the description of the water body. Except for a few basic SOs, which are indispensable in the sense of WAILS and for the general description of the habitat (e.g., meteorological data), the majority of geosphere and atmosphere SOs are therefore not reasonable in water habitats. If a water habitat site wants to focus on either geosphere or atmosphere for labelling as Cat 1, the SO selection for the corresponding terrestrial habitat would apply.

The group of **"Sociosphere"** SOs consists of 4 bundles of Standard Observations. For all Cat1 and Cat2 sites there will be recommendations on Basic SOs. It is envisioned that these will be provided in their entirety through a centralized service so that no additional site-specific "Sociosphere" surveys will be required for the Cat1 or Cat2 sites. In addition to the 9 habitat groups, the category "Platform" has been added to the habitat table. Unlike "sites", it is envisioned that "platforms" will collect additional Sociosphere SOs, which are identified as prime methods. The composition of the SOs will be decided shortly.